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Investigation of the correlations among biological parameters of mass reared peach
fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* (Diptera: Tephritidae)

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Abstract:

The peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) (Diptera: Tephritidae) is one of the most important species of family Tephritidae. It is a polyphagous species attacking more than 50 species of fruit and vegetables and It causes serious economic losses, either by direct damage to fruits or indirectly by warranting quarantine and phytosanitary measures. To perform required studies on biology, attractants, various biological control agents, sterile insect technique (SIT), and postharvest treatment also, to obtain an accurate result that guarantee success of the applied control methods, it is required a regular supply of good quality insects. This study is aimed to minimize quality control test used to evaluate the quality of laboratory mass produced peach fruit fly *B. zonata*. through finding the correlations among these biological parameters and choose some of these tests as a representative for the rest traditional tests, thus minimize time, costs and labors. Results revealed that six parameter out of the eight studied parameters (survival ability, number, size weight, emergence percentage and flight ability [of pupae per each pupation depth]) have the same trend, while only two parameters follow random trend (percent pupal deformity and sex ratio). results revealed that pupae collected 2 cm under sand surface have the best quality since have the largest size, highest weight, survive longer, have highest emergence percentage, highest percent of fliers and highest percent of pupae (with means of 0.0346 ml, 11.98 mg, 67.8 hrs. 98.67 %, 97.33 % and 39.71 % respectively) , followed by pupae from 3 cm depth then first cm and finally the forth cm depth. Also, correlation tests results revealed that there was a strong direct correlation among the five parameters (with correlation coefficient r ranging from 0.997 to 0.877). Pupal weight correlates well with other quality parameters and can be a predictor for tests performed late, its weight gives a robust measure of fly quality. So, use it to compare overall quality of pupae from different facilities is highly recommended. thus, minimized labor, time and costs consumed by other tests.

Introduction

Fruit flies are believed to be the most serious threat to horticultural products all over the world (Allwood and Drew, 1997; Barnes, 2004 and Ekesi and Billah, 2007). As, they are

highly polyphagous, attacking more than 350 species of host plants belonging to about 67 families (Aluja and Mangan, 2008). One of them the peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) (Diptera: Tephritidae) is one of the most important species of fruit

flies infested more than 50 species of fruit and vegetables and It causes direct damage to fruits or indirectly by warranting quarantine and phytosanitary measures (OEPP/EPPO, 2005). One Of the greater aspects is the fact that fruit flies represent a great risk as key and potential quarantine pests since they are easily translocated due to the global trade and passenger trafficking. This leading to even in fruit fly controlled countries, European markets rejection increase day after day. (Ole-MoiYoi and Lux, 2004). Myers *et al.* (1998) defined pest eradication as the getting rid of all individuals of a pest species from a distinct geographic area without any possibility of reinvasion. Eradication procedures include pesticide spraying (Full or partial), use of attractants (sexual, olfactory or food) for catch and kill (Steiner *et al.*, 1961), in addition to, baiting and male annihilation techniques, biological control (pathogens, parasitoids and predators), and agricultural control means (Orchard sanitation, fruit bagging, and early harvesting) (Klassen, 1989; Allwood, 1997; Barnes, 2004; Mau *et al.*, 2007 and Ekesi, and Billah, 2007). More than hundred years has elapsed since Runner (1916) demonstrated that X-rays induced sterility in cigarette beetles, *Lasioderma serricorne* (F.) (Coleoptera: Anobiidae) . Lindquist (1955) mentioned that the control of the screwworm *Cochliomyia hominivorax* Coquerel, through a technique of sterilizing the males by somehow. These sterilized males released in large numbers into the field to mate with wild females, thus compete with wild males, copulate with wild females leading to population decline. Released individuals for sterile insect technique (SIT) must be in good condition. based on classical Mendelian genetics, Busch-Petersen and Kafu 1989 demonstrated that X-rays induced sterility has

disadvantage that 50% reduction in the productivity of the mass-reared colony. many innovations have been made to improve production efficiency (Robinson, 2002), male competitiveness (Shelly, 2001), and thereby increase induced sterility in wild populations (Rendon *et al.*, 2004). sterile males only releasing will increase the biological efficiency of SIT process but increase the costs dramatically (Hendrichs *et al.*, 1995) . Hendrichs, 2000 and Chakroun *et al.*, 2017 studied doses and method of insect sterilization. And in 2002, Hendrichs *et al.* insured that the SIT has been proven to be very effective for the suppression, or eradication of populations of the Mediterranean fruit fly. A successful series of experiments have been developed by many scientists all over the world to compare tephritid fruit flies that produced based on different rearing protocols. These attempts resulted in the production of many fruit fly quality control manuals (e.g. Orozco *et al.*, 1983; Boller and Chamber, 1977 and Brazzel *et al.*, 1986). Calkins *et al.* (1996), strongly recommended to construct a separate product quality control unit for SIT program. each program that incorporates the SIT component requires an efficient monitoring system to assess over-flooding ratios, spatial distribution of the released sterile males, etc. (Vreysen *et al.*, 2005). To execute required studies on biology, response to attractants, efficacy of the various biological control agents, SIT, and postharvest treatment also, obtain an accurate result that guarantee success of the applied control methods, it is required a regular supply of good quality insects. quality control parameters must be established and closely monitored in mass rearing procedures (Ekesi and Mohamed, 2011).

This study is aimed minimized labor, time and costs consumed by quality control tests through finding the correlations among biological parameters used to evaluate the quality of laboratory mass produced peach fruit fly and consequently, choose one or two tests as a representatives to each correlated quality control tests. Thus, minimized labor, time and costs.

Materials and methods

1. Peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* strain:

Peach fruit fly lab strain (horticultural yields department laboratories - plant protection research institute) that reared upon an artificial larval diet composed of Sugar (as a source for carbohydrate) 8 %, dried sterile yeast (as a source for protein) 10.5 %, wheat bran (as a bulking agent) 26.7 %, sodium benzoate 0.53 %, citric acid 0.53 % and water 53.4 %. The adult flies feed normally upon water, sugar and hydrolyzed protein (4:1).

2. Experiments:

2.1. Experiments sequences:

To correlate biological parameters, a group of tests executed sequentially, begin with determination of pupation depth of medfly popped larvae then isolate pupae of different depths and weight them, then measure their sizes. Emerged flies checked out to recorded emergence ratio and deformity ratio, upon fly emergence, sex ratio calculated finally, Flight ability and Survival under Stress tests executed and according to the statistically analyzed results, the correlation is estimated.

2.2. Experiments details:(IAEA 2014):

2.2.1. Pupation depth:

Using a wooden box that each of the four sides is composed of 6 strips (1 cm x 15 cm) to give a 6 cm depth, this box is filled with a fine sand as a pupation media, putting the trays that containing the larval artificial media (In which eggs were seeded) on the top of

the sand till larvae reach pupation and pop out to pupate inside the sand in different depths, remove the first (top) strip of the four side and collect the sand, sieve and collect the pupae found. Repeat with the rest of the strips and collect the pupae of each depth sequentially, classify pupae into categories according to weight, record and save for the next test

2.2.2. Pupal weight:

For each group of pupae resulted from the pupation depth record the average weight for 5 lots of 100 pupae two days before emergence (since age at sampling is critical because pupae lose water and, therefore, weight). Record the weight for each group and save for the next test.

2.2.3. Pupal size:

For each pupal weight category , count (Five lots) the number of pupae per one ml using graduated cylinder and record the average size per pupa, record and save the pupae.

2.2.4. Emergence ratio:

For each pupal weight category, calculate number of successfully emerged flies for each 100 pupae (Using five lots) to calculate the percentage of emergence.

2.2.5. Deformity ratio:

For each pupal weight category, calculate number of flies that failed to emerge , or emerge with deformation for each 100 pupae (Using five lots) to calculate the percentage of deformity.

2.2.6. Sex ratio:

For each pupal weight category, a group of 100 pupae separated in a petri dish, Once it has been determined that no further emergence will occur, The numbers of emerged males and females are counted and recorded.

2.2.7. Flight ability:

PVC tubes are used to investigate flight ability of the newly emerged flies (Outside diameter 8.9 cm with 3 mm thick walls; painted black so that light enters only at the top; 10 cm high).

Avoid using an abrasive cleaner. Petri dish lids, 90-100 mm in diameter, should be painted black or the bottom overlaid with black paper. Strip of porous paper, 1 cm wide, and formed into a ring 6 cm in diameter. Two days before emergence, For each pupal weight category, 100 pupae are placed within the ring of paper, in the bottom of the Petri dish. the inside of the tube is lightly coated with unscented talcum powder to prevent the flies walking out. Tubes are tapped on a firm surface to remove excess talc, and the talc should be wiped off the bottom. The PVC tube with talc is placed in the darkened Petri dish lid. Five replicates (Five tubes with 100 pupae each) are set up for each lot to be tested.

2.2.8. Survival under stress:

For each pupal weight category, five lots each of 100 flies are transferred separately to cup (Covered top with a fiber mish to supply aeration) using an aspirator, or preferably a suction pump, Leave flies without any feeding material or water, recording date and time for emergence and death to calculate how long the fly can persist alive without any food.

3. Statistical analysis:

Table (1): Percent of peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* pupae collected from different pupation depths.

No.	Pupation depth	% pupae
1	1cm	14.2 ± 0.0447 c
2	2	39.71 ± 0.0049 a
3	3	33.24 ± 0.0035 b
4	4	11.88± 0.0038 d

1.2.Pupal weight :

Relating pupal weight to depth of pupation, calculating the mean pupal weight for pupae collected from each depth level revealed that the mean pupal weight for the first pupation depth (1 cm) was 11.75 mg, 11.98 mg for the second level,

Table (2) : Pupal weight of peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* collected from different pupation depths.

No.	Pupation depth	Pupal weight
1	1	11.75 ± 0.0017 c
2	2	11.98 ± 0.0027 a
3	3	11.90 ± 0.0170 b
4	4	11.65± 0.0064 d

Results subjected to statistical analysis using IBM SPSS statistics version 23 one-way ANOVA test and correlation coefficient test (IBM Corp, 2020).

Results and discussion:

1. Estimating biological parameters of the mass reared flies:

1.1. Pupation depth:

Results revealed that peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* larvae penetrate the sand pupation medium not deeper than 5 cm, but a few pupae descended to 5 cm, so they are eliminated from calculations. Percent of pupae found within the first cm of the sand 14.2 % of the total pupae, while it is 39.71 % within the second cm depth, and 33.24 % within 3 cm in the third rand and the deepest pupation level (4 cm) came with the least pupation percentage of 11.88 % . There was a significant difference among the four levels. 2 cm depth pupae came as the superior percentage of pupal number followed by the 3 cm depth pupae then the first cm depth pupae while larvae those pupate within the 5th cm depth was few pupae, so all records of the 5th cm pupation depth (If found) are eliminated (Table 1) .

11.90 mg for the third level and finally, 11.65 mg for the last level (4 cm depth), with a significant differences among the four levels 2cm pupae was the weightiest followed by 3 cm then one cm while pupae within 4 cm deep was the lighter (Table 2).

1.3. Pupal size:

Measurements of the pupal size revealed that, the mean pupal size for the first pupation depth (0.0197 ml), 0.0236 ml for the second depth, 0.0227 ml for the third cm depth and finally, 0.0205 ml for the last pupation depth (4 cm), also revealed that there were

significant differences among the four size groups, [pupae of the second cm pupation depth came as the largest pupae followed by 3 cm depth and then the pupae in the first cm depth and the 4cm depth of the pupation medium contain the smaller pupae (Table 3).

Table (3): Pupal size of peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* collected from different pupation depths.

No.	Pupation depth	Pupal Size
1	1cm	0.0197 ±0.0012 D
2	2	0.0236 ±0.0019 A
3	3	0.0227 ±0.0007 B
4	4	0.205±0.0007 C

1.4. Emergence percentage:

Regarding to emergence percentage tests, the mean emergence percentage for the first pupal weight was 93.67 %, 98.67 % , 96.67 % and 92.67 % for the successive depth

categories with a significant differences among the four levels, where 2 cm depth came with the highest percentage of emergence, followed by 3 cm, then one cm and finally the fourth cm depth (Table 4).

Table (4) : Percent emergence of peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* adult collected from different pupation depths.

No.	Pupation depth	% emergence
1	1	93.67 ± 0.0016 C
2	2	98.67 ± 0.002 A
3	3	96.67 ± 0.0017 B
4	4	92.67 ± 0.0018 D

1.5. Deformity percentage:

Calculating the percentage of the deformed flies, revealed that the mean of the deformed flies for the first pupal cm pupation depth was 2.3 %, 0.9

% for the second cm, 1.6 % for the third cm and finally, 3.5 % of the pupae for the last pupation depth was deformed, with a significant differences among the four levels (Table 5) .

Table (5): Percent deformed pupae of peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* collected from different pupation depths.

No.	Pupation depth	% deformed Pupae
1	1	2.3 ± 0.0224 B
2	2	0.9 ± 0.0079 D
3	3	1.6 ± 0.0114 C
4	4	3.5 ± 0.0170 A

1.6. Sex ratio:

Results revealed that there was no relation between pupation depth and male to female ratio. For first pupation cm, the sex ratio was 50.21 ♂ : 48.79 ♀, 49.24 ♂ : 50.76 ♀ for 2 cm pupae, 49.3

♂ : 50.7 ♀ for 3 cm pupae and for 4 cm pupae sex ratio was 49.64 ♂ : 50.36 ♀ these results with a significant differences among these ratios (Table 6) .

Table (6) : Sex ratios of peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* collected as pupae from different pupation depths.

	Pupation depth	Males	Females
1	1	50.21 ± 0.332 A	48.79 ± 0.0332 III
2	2	49.24 ± 0.068 C	50.76 ± 0.067 I
3	3	49.30 ± 0.447 C	50.70 ± 0.044 I
4	4	49.64 ± 0.075 B	50.36 ± 0.075 II

1.7. Flight ability:

Results of the flight ability tests revealed that the highest percentage of flies those have the ability to pass flight ability test (97.33 %) was resulted from 2 cm pupation depth, followed by 3 cm

depth with 96.33 % , then 95.67 % for flies resulted from one cm depth and those resulted from 4 cm pupation depth have the least percentage of fliers with significant differences among the four categories (Table 7).

Table (7) : Percent fliers of peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* collected as pupae from different pupation depths.

No.	Pupation depth	% fliers
1	1	95.67 ± 0.0035 C
2	2	97.33 ± 0.0070 A
3	3	96.33 ± 0.0017 B
4	4	93.67± 0.0018 D

1.8. Survival under stress:

Survival test revealed that flies differ significantly in there with standing survival without food or water. Pupae of 2 cm pupation depth have the greatest persistence with a mean of 67.8 hrs. 3 cm pupae came in the second

level with a mean of 64.7 hrs. For the first pupation cm, the resulted flies can persist starved for mean of 61.4 hrs. as the third rank. While the least survival persistence was recorded for the flies resulted from 4 cm pupation depth with mean age of 58.7 hrs. (Table 8).

Table (8) : Longevity (Per hours) of survival adults of peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* collected from different pupation depths.

No.	Pupation depth	Adult longevity
1	1	61.4 ± 0.0101 C
2	2	67.8 ± 0.0152 A
3	3	64.7 ± 0.0174 B
4	4	58.7 ± 0.0171 D

2. Estimating the correlations among the biological parameters:

Correlation tests revealed that there were a strong direct correlation among the five parameters [Survival, no of pupae, weight of pupae, emergence percentage and number of flies those have flight ability (of pupae per each pupation depth)] with r range values of 0.877 : 0.997, and the correlations are significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

While these parameters (Survival, no of pupae, weight of pupae, emergence percentage and number of flies those have flight ability [of pupae per each pupation depth]) have a strong reversed correlation with the no of the deformed flies resulted from different pupation depth with r range values of – 0.920 : - 0.994) also, these correlations are significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) (Table 9).

Table (9): Correlation relationships among different biological parameters of laboratory reared peach fruit fly.

	Pupal size	Pupal No. per Depth	Weight per Depth	Age	Emergence percentage	Percent fliers	Percent deformity	Male Ratio	Female Ratio
Depth	.292	-.126	-.328	-.300-	-.234-	-.585**	.500*	-.459-*	.642**
Pupal size		.527*	.432	.455*	.487*	.282	-.345-	-.583-**	.603**
Pupal No. per Depth			.967**	.979**	.991**	.877**	-.920-**	-.773-**	.656**
Weight per Depth				.984**	.979**	.949**	-.969-**	-.634-**	.481*
Age					.997**	.940**	-.967-**	-.664-**	.524*
Emergence percentage						.918**	-.952-**	-.710-**	.579**
Percent fliers							-.994-**	-.406-	.220
Percent deformity								.493*	-.317-
Male Ratio									-.967-**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Results revealed that six parameter out of the eight studied parameters [Survival ability, number, size weight, emergence percentage and flight ability (Of pupae per each pupation depth)] have the same trend, while only two parameters follow random trend (Percent pupal deformity and sex ratio). Also, pupae collected 2 cm under sand surface have the best quality since have the largest size, highest weight, survive longer, have highest emergence percentage, highest percent of fliers and highest percent of pupae, followed by pupae from 3 cm depth then first cm and finally the forth cm depth. Correlation tests results revealed that there was a strong direct correlation among the five parameters [Survival, number, weight, emergence percentage and number of flies those have flight ability (For pupae collected from each pupation depth)]. Obtained results revealed also that, pupal size, adult deformity percentage, adult flight ability and starvation ability tests are related to pupal weight. pupal weight correlates well with other quality

parameters and can be a predictor for tests performed late and gives a robust measure of fly quality. So, use it to compare overall quality of pupae from different facilities is highly recommended, thus minimized labor, time and costs consumed by other tests.

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A faunistic study on Braconidae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonoidea) from Ardebil and East Azarbayjan provinces, Northwestern Iran

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Abstract:

This paper deals with the fauna of braconid wasps (Hymenoptera: Braconidae) in Ardebil and East Azarbayjan provinces (Northwestern Iran). In total, 29 species spread over in 12 subfamilies viz., Agathidinae (Two species and two genera), Alysiinae (Three species and three genera), Aphidiinae (One species), Brachistinae (One species), Braconinae (One species), Doryctinae (One species), Ichneutinae (Two species and two genera), Macrocentrinae (One species), Microgasterinae (12 species and six genera), Rogadinae (Four species and one genus), and Opiinae (One species) were collected and identified. Thirteen species are newly recorded from the fauna of Iran. Data of reared species with host records are also provided.

Introduction

Braconid wasps (Hymenoptera, Braconidae) is a diverse group of parasitoids with a worldwide distribution (Wahl and Sharkey, 1993) which have an important role in biological control programs of many crop pests (Matthews, 1974 and Shaw, 1995). Most of the species are primary parasites, especially of larval instars of Coleoptera, Diptera and Lepidoptera. Other hosts include nymphs and adults of Hemiptera, Orthoptera, Psocoptera, adults of aculeate Hymenoptera, and

larvae of Symphyta (Tobias, 1967; Shaw and Huddleston, 1991; Wharton, 1993 and Whitfield and Wharton, 1997). Braconids are speciose with 21,223 described species belonging to 1071 genera, which represent nearly 20% of the total hymenopteran diversity worldwide (Yu *et al.*, 2016).

Faunistic knowledge of the family Braconidae in of Iran is largely incomplete due to the lack of regional studies and taxonomic complexity of this group in comparison with well-studied other western Palearctic

countries. Despite this lack, the fauna of Iranian Braconidae has been studied rather well (e.g., Gadallah and Ghahari, 2013a, 2013b, 2015, 2016, 2017; Barahoei *et al.*, 2014; Gadallah *et al.*, 2015a, 2015b, 2016a, 2016b; Farahani *et al.* 2016; Ghahari 2016; Beyarslan *et al.*, 2017; Samin *et al.* 2018a, b; Gadallah and Ghahari, 2019 and Gadallah *et al.*, 2019), but since Iran is a large country comprises with various agro-ecosystems, several new species are likely to be discovered in future. More than eight hundred species spread over to 151 genera of 28 subfamilies of Braconidae are recognized in Iran (Samin *et al.*, 2018a, b and Yu *et al.*, 2016).

The purpose of this paper is to record the species of Braconidae of the Ardebil and East Azarbayjan provinces as part of ongoing faunistic studies of

Braconidae in Iran. In the present study, totally 29 braconid species were collected, of which 13 species are recorded for the first time from Iran.

Materials and methods

The materials of the present study were collected during 2011-2017 by Malaise traps and sweeping net from different regions of Ardebil and East Azarbayjan provinces (Northwestern Iran) (Figure, 1). Some specimens were reared in optimum conditions at laboratory condition or incubator (26 ± 3 °C; 60 ± 10 RH and 14: 10 L: D). Here we follow Yu *et al.* (2016) for nomenclature, classification and distributional data. For the following subfamilies, Microgastrinae and Rogadinae we followed the classification of Fernandez-Triana *et al.* (2020) and van Achterberg and Shaw (2016) respectively.

Figure (1): Map of Iran with boundaries of provinces.

Results and discussion

Totally, 29 species within 12 subfamilies Agathidinae, Alysiinae, Aphidiinae, Brachistinae, Braconinae,

Doryctinae, Ichneutinae, Macrocentrinae, Microgasterinae, Rogadinae and Opiinae were collected and identified from some regions of

Ardebil and East Azarbaijan provinces. Thirteen species are new records for Iran: *Aleiodes cruentus* (Nees, 1834), *Aleiodes praetor* (Reinhard, 1863), *Atanycolus initiator* (Fabricius, 1793), *Dolichogenidea gagates* (Nees, 1834), *Dolichogenidea ultor* (Reinhard, 1880), *Glyptapanteles inclusus* Ratzeburg, 1844, *Microgaster hospes* Marshall, 1885, *Microplitis tuberculatus* (Bouché, 1834), *Pachysema discolor* (Förster, 1863), *Phaenolexis senilis* (Nees, 1812), *Praon longicorne* Marshall, 1896, *Proterops nigripennis* Wesmael, 1835, and *Psytalia carinata* (Thomson, 1895). The list of species is given below alphabetically under each subfamily.

1. Subfamily Agathidinae Haliday, 1833

1.1. *Cremonops dessertor* Linnaeus, 1758

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Azarshahr, 3♀♀, ex *Cydia pomonella* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera Tortricidae), 8.viii.2014.

General distribution: Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, China, Croatia, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, India, Indonesia, Iran, Italy, Japan, Korea, Latvia, Lithuania, Malaysia, Moldova, Myanmar, Nepal, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Thailand, Turkey, United States of America, Ukraine, United Kingdom, Vietnam, and former Yugoslavia.

1.2. *Earinus elator* (Fabricius, 1804)

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Horand, 3♀♀, ex *Caloptilia rufipennella* (Hübner, 1796) (Lepidoptera: Gracillariidae), 24.viii.2016.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Croatia, former

Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Korea, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom, and former Yugoslavia.

2. Subfamily Alysiinae Leach, 1815

2.1. *Dacnusa adducta* (Haliday, 1839)

Material examined: Ardebil province, Namin, 1♀, 17.vi.2015.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Korea, Poland, Russia, Serbia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, United Kingdom, and former Yugoslavia.

2.2. *Pachysema discolor* (Förster, 1863)

Material examined: Ardebil province, Aslanduz, 3♀♀, 2♂♂, ex *Phytomyza plantaginis* Goureau, 1851 (Diptera: Agromyzidae), 14.vi.2015.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Norway, Poland, Russia, Serbia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom, and former Yugoslavia.

Notes: This species is newly reported from Iran.

2.3. *Phaenolexis senilis* (Nees, 1812)

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Absh-Ahmad, 2♂♂, 21.v.2016.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Faeroe Islands, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Russia, Serbia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, United Kingdom, and former Yugoslavia.

Notes: This species is newly reported from Iran.

3. Subfamily Aphidiinae Haliday, 1833

3.1. *Praon longicorne* Marshall, 1896

Material examined: Ardebil province, Meshginshahr, 3♀♀, ex *Macrosiphum euphorbiae* (Thomas) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) on *Euphorbia pulcherrima* (Euphorbiaceae), 17.vii.2013.

General distribution: Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, India, Italy, Moldova, Montenegro, Netherlands, Poland, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Tajikistan, Turkey, and United Kingdom.

Notes: This species is newly reported from Iran.

4. Subfamily Brachistinae Förster, 1863

4.1. *Blacus (Ganychorus) tripudians* Haliday, 1835

Material examined: Ardebil province, Germe, 1♀, 1♂, 18.vi.2015.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Sweden, Switzerland, Tunisia, United Kingdom, and former Yugoslavia.

5. Subfamily Braconinae Nees, 1811

5.1. *Atanycolus initiator* (Fabricius, 1793)

Material examined: Ardebil province, Germe, 3♀♀, 1♂, ex *Chrysobothris affinis* (Fabricius, 1794) (Coleoptera: Buprestidae), 18.vi.2015.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Lithuania, Mongolia, Norway, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, and United Kingdom.

Notes: This species is newly reported from Iran.

6. Subfamily Doryctinae Foerster, 1863

6.1. *Spathius exarator* Chao, 1978

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Kaleybar, 4♀♀, ex *Ips typographus* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae), 11.viii.2014.

General distribution: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, China, Croatia, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Greenland, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Korea, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine, United Kingdom, and former Yugoslavia.

7. Subfamily Ichneutinae Förster, 1863

7.1. *Ichneutes brevis* Wesmael, 1835

Material examined: Ardebil province, Germe, 2♀♀, ex *Nematus fagi* Zaddach, 1876 (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae), 19.vi.2015.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kazakhstan, Korea, Mongolia, Poland, Russia, Switzerland, and United Kingdom.

7.2. *Proterops nigripennis* Wesmael, 1835

Material examined: Semnan province, Shahrud (Jangal-e Abr), 3♀♀, July 2011, ex *Arge ochropus* (Gmelin in Linnaeus, 1790) (Hymenoptera: Argidae).

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, China, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway,

Poland, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, and United Kingdom.

Notes: This species is newly reported from Iran.

8. Subfamily Macrocentrinae Förster, 1863

8.1. *Macrocentrus infirmus* (Nees, 1834)

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Absh-Ahmad, 3♀♀, ex. *Zeuzera pyrina* (Linnaeus, 1761) (Lepidoptera: Cossidae), 21.v.2016.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, former Czechoslovakia, Faeroe Islands, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kazakhstan, Korea, Lithuania, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom, and former Yugoslavia.

9. Subfamily Microgastrinae Foerster, 1862

9.1. *Cotesia affinis* (Nees, 1834)

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Azarshahr, 1♀, 8.viii.2014.

General distribution: Armenia, Austria, Cape Verde Islands, China, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Latvia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, and United Kingdom.

9.2. *Dolichogenidea ensiformis* (Ratzeburg, 1844)

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Azarshahr, 2♀♀, ex *Plutella xylostella* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae), 8.viii.2014.

General distribution: Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Mongolia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, and Tunisia.

9.3. *Dolichogenidea gagates* (Nees, 1834)

Material examined: Guilan province, Talesh, 2♀♀, August 2014, ex *Pandemis corylana* (Fabricius, 1794) (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae).

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and United Kingdom.

Notes: This species is newly reported from Iran.

9.4. *Dolichogenidea praetor* (Marshall, 1885)

Material examined: Ardebil province, Aslanduz, 2♂♂, 13.vi.2015.

General distribution: Armenia, Finland, France, Hungary, Mongolia, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, and United Kingdom.

9.5. *Dolichogenidea ultor* (Reinhard, 1880)

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Kaleybar, 2♀♀, 11.viii.2014, ex. *Malacosoma neustria* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Lasiocampidae).

General distribution: Azerbaijan, Czech Republic, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland, Ukraine, and United Kingdom.

Notes: This species is newly reported from Iran.

9.6. *Glyptapanteles inclusus* Ratzeburg, 1844

Material examined: Ardebil province, Meshginshahr, 3♀♀, ex *Euproctis Euproctis chrysorrhoea* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Erebiidae), 17.vii.2013.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Cape Verde Islands, China, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, France, Germany, Ireland,

Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Mongolia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine, and United Kingdom.

Notes: This species is newly reported from Iran.

9.7. *Microgaster hospes* Marshall, 1885

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Bostan-Abad, 2♀♀, ex *Archips rosana* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae), 10.viii.2014.

General distribution: Bulgaria, Canada, Czech Republic, Finland, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Switzerland, United Kingdom, United States of America, and Uzbekistan.

Notes: This species is newly reported from Iran.

9.8. *Microgaster luctuosa* Haliday, 1834

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Absh-Ahmad, 2♀♀, 21.v.2016.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Croatia, Finland, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, Moldova, Mongolia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Sweden, Switzerland, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, United Kingdom, and Uzbekistan.

9.9. *Microgaster rufipes* Nees, 1834

Material examined: Ardebil province, Aslanduz, 1♀, 14.vi.2015.

General distribution: Albania, Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canary, Islands, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Mongolia,

Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, and United Kingdom.,

9.10. *Microplitis stigmaticus* (Ratzeburg, 1844)

Material examined: Ardebil province, Germe, 2♀♀, 1♂, *Yponomeuta padella* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Yponomeutidae), 18.vi.2015.

General distribution: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Finland, Germany, Italy, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, and Uzbekistan.

9.11. *Microplitis tuberculatus* (Bouché, 1834)

Material examined: Ardebil province, Bilehsavar, 3♀♀, ex. *Euproctis chrysorrhoea* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Noctuoidea), 3.vii.2017.

General distribution: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Finland, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Moldova, Mongolia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, and United Kingdom.

Notes: This species is newly reported from Iran.

9.12. *Microplitis varipes* (Ruthe, 1860)

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Maragheh, 2♀♀, 1♂, ex *Noctua pronuba* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), 38.viii.2016.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, China, Finland, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan, Malta, Moldova, Mongolia, Montenegro, Netherlands, Poland, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Switzerland, Turkey, and Ukraine.

10. Subfamily Rogadinae Foerster, 1863

10.1. *Aleiodes compressor* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1838)

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Kaleybar, 2♀♀, ex *Archips rosana* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae), 11.viii.2014.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Kazakhstan, Korea, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Serbia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom, and former Yugoslavia.

10.2. *Aleiodes cruentus* (Nees, 1834)

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Horand, 2♀♀, 2♂♂, 24.viii.2016.

General distribution: Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Mongolia, Norway, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, United Kingdom, and former Yugoslavia,

Notes: This species is newly reported from Iran.

10.3. *Aleiodes miniatus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1838)

Material examined: Ardebil province, Aslanduz, 1♀, 14.vi.2015.

General distribution: Austria, Czech Republic, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan, Lithuania, Mongolia, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Syria, and Turkey.

10.4. *Aleiodes praetor* (Reinhard, 1863)

Material examined: Ardebil province, Tazeh Kandi, 2♀♀, ex *Euproctis similis* (Füssli, 1775) (Lepidoptera: Erebidae), 19.vi.2015.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Korea, Netherlands, Norway, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom, and former Yugoslavia.

Notes: This species is newly reported from Iran.

11. Subfamily Opiinae Blanchard, 1845

11.1. *Psytalia carinata* (Thomson, 1895)

Material examined: Ardebil province, Meshginshahr, 2♀♀, 1♂, ex *Rhagoletis cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758), 17.vii.2013.

General distribution: Armenia, Austria, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Malta, Moldova, Poland, Sweden, Switzerland, Uzbekistan, and former Yugoslavia.

Notes: This species is newly reported from Iran.

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Efficacy of chemical, biological insecticides and plant extracts against red palm weevil *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* (Curculionidae : Coleoptera) under laboratory and field conditions

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Abstract:

The red palm weevil *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* (Olivier) (Curculionidae : Coleoptera) is the most serious insect pest of cultivated palm trees in several date palm producing countries. The laboratory study was carried out during year 2020 in Research Laboratory of Red Palm Weevil, Plant Protection Research Institute. Field experiments were carried out at date palm farm of area 10 feddan planted with barhi date palm variety, at the Regional Research Station for Delta East, Qassasin, Ismailia Governorate, Egypt. The aim of research work is to evaluate the efficiency of different group of insecticides; chemical (Profenomex 44% EC), biological (Bio-Magic 1.15 WP) and plant extracts (Palmotto 60% EC) to control this insect under Laboratory and field conditions. Results indicated that the efficiency of tested insecticides varied considerably due to the chemical nature of testing insecticides and the concentrations used. Profenomex 44% EC proved to be the most effective compound followed by palmotto 60% EC and bio-magic 1.15% WP , respectively. Evaluation of the efficiency of certain insecticides to control this pest in field by injection palms, the results shown that profenomex 44% EC proved to be more effective against red palm weevil with low concentration compared with other pesticides.

Introduction

Date palm, *Phoenix dactylifera* (L.) (Family : Palmaceae) was an object of worship in Chaldeas (Babylon) in 7000 before Christ. Shat-Al-Arab is its original home (Sharif and Wajih, 1982).The total number of date palm trees recorded in the ancient life reached about 109 million, which yielded 4.2 million tons. Arab countries, however, contain 78.3% of

the total world date palm trees which demonstrate 75% of the production (Abdel-Megeed *et al.*, 2004).Unfortunately, during the last decade of the 20th century, a new most serious insect pest, namely the red palm weevil, *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* (Olivier) (Curculionidae: Coleoptera) was first recorded in date palm plantations of Sharkia and Ismailia Governorates in Egypt by Saleh (1992)

and Saleh and Gouhar (1993). It is worthy to mention that the damage of all pests invading date palm trees together cannot be comparable with that of the red palm weevil alone as the latter insect is considered a destructive pest. The red palm weevil is a serious pest of cultivated palm trees in India (Ghosh, 1912 and Nirula, 1956) and Srilanka (Brand, 1917). The present investigation was carried out with the aim of throwing more light and clarifying the toxicological study of following certain insecticides; profenomex 44% EC, bio-magic 1.15 WP and palmotto 60% EC against different stages of larvae and adults of the red palm weevil *R. ferrugineus* under laboratory and field conditions to evaluate the efficiency of tested insecticides to control this pest.

Materials and methods

The laboratory study was carried out during year 2020 in Research Laboratory of Red Palm Weevil, Plant Protection Research Institute, to evaluate the toxic effects of certain insecticides against fourth, eighth larval instars and adults of the red palm weevil *R. ferrugineus* under the constant temperature of $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

1. Tested insecticides:

1.1. Profenomex 44% EC Active ingredient: (Profenofos 40% + Cypermethrin 4%)

1.2. Palmotto 60% EC Active ingredient: (Jasmine oil + Citronella oil + Fulvic acid)

1.3. Bio-Magic 1.15% WP Active ingredient: Bio-Magic is a biological insecticide based on a selected strain of naturally occurring entomopathogenic fungus *Metarhizium anisopliae*. It contains spores and mycelial fragments of *M. anisopliae*.

2. Laboratory treatment of larval and adult stages of red palm weevil *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* :

Fourth, eighth larval instars, as well as adults of red palm weevil *R.*

ferrugineus were carefully selected for the present investigation from laboratory rearing of red palm weevil. Each of insecticides was dissolved in distilled water to preparing several concentration rates : (110, 220, 440 , 660 ppm) for profenomex 44% EC , (1800, 3600, 5400 ppm) for palmotto 60% EC and (57.5, 115, 230 ppm) for bio-magic 1.15% WP. Small square pieces of sugarcane (1.5 x 5 cm. in diameter and length) were dipped in the prepared concentrations for 30 minutes then allowed to dry in air for 2 hours before offering to tested larvae and adults. Treated pieces were transferred in a cylindrical plastic box (9.5 x 5.0 cm. in diameter and depth) and tightly covered with a perforated cover. fourth, eighth larval instars, as well as adults were introduced into the boxes (5 larvae or adult/box), using 20 individuals in 4 replicates for each concentration rate. Mortality records were taken after 24 h to several days. Bioassay data were corrected for control mortality according to Abbott's formula, (1925) and subjected to probit analysis (Finney, 1952) with a probity computer program. Values of LC50, LC90, slope and relative potency (Sun, 1950) were calculated from the results of the last day after treatment for larval and adult stages of red palm weevil.

3. Field injection experiments:

Field experiments were carried out at date palm farm of area 10 feddan planted with barhi date palm variety, at the Regional Research Station for Delta East, Qassasin, Ismailia Governorate, Egypt., to evaluate the effectiveness of using certain insecticides on infested date palm trees. A number of 72 heavily infested date palm trees (24 date palms for each insecticide), were selected and treated by injection with three concentration rates: (220, 440 , 660 ppm) for profenomex 44% EC , (1800, 3600, 5400 ppm) for palmotto 60% EC and (57.5, 115, 230 ppm) for bio-magic

1.15% WP, using 8 date palms as replicates for each concentration rate. The chemical treatment was carried out in the following steps: 1. Definition of heavily infested date palms showing obvious infestation symptoms. 2. Drilled holes inside date palm trunk around the infested places. 3. Injection of infested date palms with different rates of liquid insecticides. 4. Placing a small piece of dry date palm fibers in the opening of the holes. 5. Stopping the opening of the holes by a paste of cement and gypsum. All treated date palms were inspected after 30 days from treatment to assess the potency of tested insecticides that determined as a percentage of date palm recovery according to the disappearance of the most obvious infestation symptoms i.e., dryness of yellowish brown viscous liquid in the infested places of date palm trunk.

Results and discussion

1. Lethality effects of tested insecticides against larval and adult stages of red palm weevil *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus*:

The toxicity of the three tested insecticides profenomex 44% EC (Profenofos + cypermethrin), bio-magic 1.15 WP (Entomopathogenic fungi) and palmotto 60% EC was evaluated as stomach poisons against the fourth, eighth larval instars and adults. Data in Tables (1-3) showed that, the toxicant effects were varied considerably due to the mode of action of tested insecticide, concentration of tested insecticide and the treated stages of red palm weevil. Obtained data revealed that profenomex 44% EC proved to be the most effective insecticide against all tested larval instars and adults followed by palmotto 60% EC and bio-magic 1.15% WP, respectively. The highest percentage of mortality for profenomex 44% EC was in the fourth day either palmotto 60% EC in the fifth day and bio-magic 1.15% WP was in the ten day with

fourth, eighth larval instars and adults. As a general trend, the higher the concentration the higher was the mortality rates and vice versa. Data in Tables (4-6) and graphically illustrated as toxicity lines in Figures (1-3) indicated that the three tested insecticides had differently in their toxicity on different larval instars and adults of red palm weevil due to the chemical nature of testing insecticides. As shown profenomex 44% EC, was the most efficient toxicant at LC50 and LC90 values (149.864 ; 124.377 ; 210.595 and 850.308 ; 1791.656 ; 882.141) ppm., for the 4th, 8th larval instars and adults respectively, followed by palmotto 60% EC accordingly the LC50 and LC90 values (18563.71 ; 19644.02 ; 8501.16 and 43677.52 ; 12222.60 ; 143050.6) ppm., for the 4th, 8th larval instars and adults respectively, and bio-magic 1.15% WP, accordingly the LC50 and LC90 values (58.538 ; 84.149 ; 131.299 and 488.204 ; 819.925 ; 1240.681) ppm., for the 4th, 8th larval instars and adults respectively. The slope values of the three tested insecticides indicated that both eighth larval instar and adult were nearly parallel and were the steepest lines, whereas the fourth larval instar was the flattest one (Figures 1-3). Profenomex 44% EC was the standard at the two tested larval instars and adults, showing the highest efficiency at both LC50 and LC90, whereas the efficacy of the other tested insecticides was lower than the standard toxicant. In general, the tolerance of larvae to all tested insecticides (According to LC50 values) increased with the increment of larval age, accordingly eighth larval instars and adults proved to be more tolerant against all tested insecticides than fourth larval instars. The previous result can be attributed to the small weight of the fourth larval instar and its sensitivity to different concentrations of tested insecticides. From the present

results, it is worthy to mention that profenomex 44% EC applied as a stomach poison gave The highest mortality with the fourth larval instar followed by adult and eighth larval instar respectively. These results are confirmed by those of the previous studies of (Barranco *et al.*, 2000) showed that, the younger larvae of *R. ferrugineus* were more susceptible compared with the older ones. (Ajlan *et al.*, 2000) mentioned that, pirimiphos-methyl gave more toxic than chloropyrifos to the adults and larvae of the red palm weevil, *R. ferrugineus*, indicating the higher susceptibility of larval stage when compared with adults. (Cabello *et al.*, 1997 ; Abdulsalam *et al.*, 2001 ; Beevi *et al.*, 2004 ; Abbas, 2005 and Al-Rajhy *et al.*, 2005) who

evaluated some insecticides and plant extracts against different larval instars of red palm weevil as stomach or contact poisons under laboratory conditions, They found that the efficacy of pesticides varied according to both type of compound and used concentrations. Also, they mentioned that the susceptibility of larvae decreased with progressed instars age. The extra usefulness could achieve if these insecticides implemented in the integrated pest management programs (IPM), that delivered to control the red palm weevil. The advantages of palmotto 60% EC and bio-magic 1.15% WP are its broad-spectrum activity with relative low rate of application, long lasting efficacy and mode of action in addition of low toxicity to mammals.

Table (1): Relative mortality of tested insecticide profenomex 44% EC against 4th, 8th larval instars and adult stages of *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus*.

Days after treatment	4 th instar kill (%)				8 th instar kill (%)				Adult kill (%)			
	110	220	440	660	110	220	440	660	110	220	440	660
1 day	10	20	40	70	20	5	25	40	10	10	35	55
2 days	40	35	55	80	40	30	45	65	30	20	50	70
3 days	50	55	75	100	50	40	60	85	30	50	70	95
4 days	60	70	100	100	55	60	75	100	50	70	80	100

* No. of 20 individuals for each concentration rate.

Table (2): Relative mortality of tested insecticide palmotto 60% EC against 4th, 8th larval instars and adult stages of *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus*.

Days after Treatment	4 th instar kill (%)			8 th instar kill (%)			Adult kill (%)		
	18000	36000	54000	18000	36000	54000	18000	36000	54000
1 day	0	15	30	0	5	15	0	0	10
2 days	10	35	45	0	20	30	5	5	20
3 days	25	50	70	5	25	45	10	15	40
4 days	45	75	90	25	40	60	35	40	55
5 days	65	80	100	50	60	80	45	50	75

* No. of 20 individuals for each concentration rate.

Table (3): Relative mortality of tested insecticide bio-magic 1.15% WP against 4th, 8th larval instars and adult stages of *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus*.

Days after treatment	4 th instar kill (%)			8 th instar kill (%)			Adult kill (%)		
	57.5	115	230	57.5	115	230	57.5	115	230
5 days	5	10	20	0	0	0	0	0	5
6 days	5	10	30	0	0	20	0	5	15
7 days	20	30	45	10	15	30	5	15	35
8 days	35	50	65	30	40	55	15	30	50
9 days	55	65	80	40	60	70	35	45	65
10 days	60	75	90	45	65	70	50	55	75

* No. of 20 individuals for each concentration rate.

Table (4): LC values of tested insecticide profenomex 44% EC against 4th, 8th larval instars and adult stages of *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* after 4 days of treatment.

Stage	LC ₅₀ (ppm)	LC ₉₀ (ppm)	Slope (b)	Relative Potency
4 th	149.864 (124.9732 - 176.4327)	850.308 (643.0442 - 1254.401)	1.7	0.973
8 th	124.377 (67.396 8 - 171.9741)	1791.656 (1003.746 - 6390.488)	1.1062	0.9048
Adult	210.595 (176.3253 - 245.0302)	882.141 (679.5329 - 1306.301)	2.0602	0.9823

Table (5): LC values of tested insecticide palmotto 60% EC against 4th, 8th larval instars and adult stages of *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* after 5 days of treatment.

Stage	LC ₅₀ (ppm)	LC ₉₀ (ppm)	Slope (b)	Relative Potency
4 th	18563.71 (15391.63 - 21194.79)	43677.52 (38652.63 - 51595.07)	3.4489	0.9528
8 th	19644.02 (11913.5246 - 24927.3272)	12222.6 (40723.8-76948.78)	1.6143	0.9302
Adult	8501.16 (2012.179 - 10852.33)	143050.6 (115329.4 - 801979.3)	1.5955	0.9638

Table (6): LC values of tested insecticide bio-magic 1.15% WP against 4th, 8th larval instars and adult stages of *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* after 10 days of treatment.

Stage	LC ₅₀ (ppm)	LC ₉₀ (ppm)	Slope (b)	Relative Potency
4 th	58.538 (32.5155 - 77.9927)	488.204 (294.4875 - 1682.155)	1.3913	0.9988
8 th	84.149 (55.6045 - 108.9653)	819.925 (422.7379 - 4637.095)	1.2962	0.9851
Adult	131.299 (101.7239 - 182.8218)	1240.681 (565.4765 - 10270.36)	1.3139	0.9391

Figure (1): Toxicity lines of Profenomex 44% EC against different stage of *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus*

Figure (2): Toxicity lines of palmotto 60% EC against different stage of *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus*

Figure (3): Toxicity lines of bio-magic 1.15% WP against different stage of *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus*

2. Injection palms:

The results of injection date palms with tested insecticides; profenomex 44% EC, palmotto 60% EC and bio-magic 1.15% WP were tabulated in Table (7). The percentages of palm recovery due to injection with the tested insecticides being (62.5% ; 87.5% ; 100% at 220 ; 440 ; 660 ppm. respectively), for profenomex 44% EC and (50% ; 62.5% ; 87.5% at 18000 ; 36000 ; 54000 ppm. respectively), for palmotto 60% EC and (37.5% ; 62.5% ; 75% at 57.5 ; 115 ; 230 ppm. respectively), for bio-magic 1.15% WP after 30 days from application. The obtained results showed that, profenomex 44% EC proved to be more

effective against the red palm weevil in field injection followed by palmotto 60% EC and bio-magic 1.15% WP, respectively. The obtained results are in agreement with those recorded by many researchers who tried to evaluate the efficiency of certain insecticides with different methods of application as chemical control agents against the red palm weevil under field conditions such as (Saleh, 1992 ; Saleh and Gouhar, 1993 ; El-Sebay, 2004 and Muthiah and Nair, 2006). They recorded that the efficacy of the tested compounds that belonging to different groups varied against *R. ferrugineus* and resulted in good control for this pest.

Table (7): Numbers and Percentages of palm recovery due to injection with different rates of tested insecticides on *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* after 30 days of treatment.

Insecticides	Injection dose (ppm)	Number of palm recovery	Percentages of Palm recovery
Profenomex 44% EC	220	5	62.5%
	440	7	87.5%
	660	8	100%
Palmotto 60% EC	18000	4	50%
	36000	5	62.5%
	54000	7	87.5%
Bio-Magic 1.15% WP	57.5	3	37.5%
	115	5	62.5%
	230	6	75%

* No. of 8 date palms for each concentration rate.

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Five new records of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonoidea) from Iran

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Abstract:

In this faunistic paper, five new records of Ichneumonidae within three subfamilies, Cryptinae, Ctenopelmatinae, and Tryphoninae are represented for the fauna of Iran.

Keywords

Ichneumonidae, fauna,
new records and Iran.

Introduction

The family Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) with 47 generally recognized subfamilies, 1,601 genera, and 25,292 described species (Yu *et al.*, 2016) is a rich taxon of all organisms with an estimated 60,000 species in the world (Townes, 1969). The fauna of Iranian Ichneumonidae has poorly been studied. Kolarov and Ghahari (2005) listed 144 species from 14 subfamilies and seven years later Barahoei *et al.* (2012) listed 502 species belonging to 189 genera and 24 subfamilies. More recently, many authors (Ghahari, 2014, 2016; Ghahari and Schwarz, 2011; Ghahari and Jussila, 2011, 2014a, b, 2015, 2016a, b, c; Ghahari *et al.*, 2014a, b; Ghahari and Gadallah, 2017 and Barahoei *et al.*, 2014a, b, 2015) have made contributions to the knowledge of the Iranian fauna. The purpose of this paper is introducing of five

Ichneumonidae species as new records for the fauna of Iran.

Materials and methods

The Ichneumonidae recorded in this paper were sampled in five regions of Iran using malaise traps and sweeping net. Classification, nomenclature and distributional data suggested by Yu *et al.* (2016) have been followed.

Results and discussion

In this paper, five ichneumonid species in five genera, *Absyrtus* Holmgren, 1859; *Cycasis* Townes, 1965; *Labrossyta* Förster, 1869; *Netelia* Gray, 1860, and *Zoophthorus* Förster, 1869 under three subfamilies Cryptinae, Ctenopelmatinae, and Tryphoninae are given as new country records.

1. Subfamily Cryptinae Kirby, 1837

1.1. Genus *Zoophthorus* Förster, 1869

1.1.1. *Zoophthorus graculus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Arasbaran forest, 1♀, August 2007.

General distribution: Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Lithuania, Mexico, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Turkey, United States of America and United Kingdom.

2. Subfamily Ctenopelmatinae Förster, 1869

2.1. Genus *Absyrtus* Holmgren, 1859

2.1.1. *Absyrtus vicinator* (Thunberg, 1824)

Material examined: Guilan province, Talesh, Gisum forest, 2♀♀, September 2010.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Japan, Latvia, Libya, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

2.2. Genus *Labrossyta* Förster, 1869

2.2.1. *Labrossyta scotoptera* (Gravenhorst, 1820)

Material examined: Kordestan province, Saez, 1♀, July 2013.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy,

Poland, Romania, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey and United Kingdom.

3. Subfamily Tryphoninae Shuckard, 1840

3.1. Genus *Cycasis* Townes, 1965

3.1.1. *Cycasis rubiginosa* (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: Golestan province, Golestan National Park, 1♂, July 2011.

General distribution: Albania, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkmenistan, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

3.2. Genus *Netelia* Gray, 1860

3.2.1. *Netelia (Prosthodocis) japonica* (Uchida, 1928)

Material examined: Semnan province, Shahrud, Jangal-e Abr, 2♀♀, 1♂, June 2011.

General distribution: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, China, former Czechoslovakia, France, Georgia, Germany, India, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Moldova, Montenegro, Russia, Serbia, Switzerland, Taiwan, Turkey, Ukraine and former Yugoslavia.

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**Fluctuations in the population density of the red palm weevil
Rhynchophorus ferrugineus (Curculionidae : Coleoptera) in Ismailia Governorate,
Egypt**

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Abstract:

The Regional Research Station for Delta East, Qassasin, Ismailia Governorate, Egypt., planted with four varieties of date palm trees (Zaghlool, barhi, hayani and samani). Eight aggregation pheromone traps were uniformly distributed around 200 of palm trees (50 of each variety). Adult of red palm weevil (RPW) *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* (Olivier) (Curculionidae : Coleoptera) was collected twice monthly during the two successive years (2017-2018 and 2018-2019) to study the fluctuations in the population density of the red palm weevil *R. ferrugineus* on four types of date palm trees. Results were conducted on the percentages of date palm trees affected by red palm weevil. The percentages of infection with RPW were recorded, 48%, 42%, 34% and 30% for zaghlool, barhi, hayani and samani, respectively. In the first year of study total collected adults of RPW by pheromone traps were recorded 937 from all varieties. Zaghlool, barhi, hayani and samani varieties were recorded, 29.5% , 25.8% , 23.2% and 21.6%, respectively. In the second year of study total collected adults of RPW by pheromone traps were recorded 1114 from all varieties. Zaghlool, barhi, hayani and samani varieties were recorded, 28.5% , 24.7% , 23.9% and 23%, respectively. The results were showed that, April and May recorded the highest percentage of collected adults of RPW on zaghlool, barhi and samani varieties, while hayani variety was recorded the highest percentage of collected adults of RPW in March during the two successive years of study. Also, the correlations between the percentage of collected adults of RPW and climatic factors (Temperature and humidity) were studied.

Introduction

Date palm trees (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) are one of the important ecosystems for number of living organisms especially red palm weevil (RPW) *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus*

(Olivier) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). Date palm trees are cultivated and distributed all over Egypt. They are one of the major and earliest fruit crops. The RPW is an economically important tissue borer pest of date palm in many

pests of the world. The insect is a major pest of date palm in some of the Arabian gulf states including Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates, Sultanate of Oman and Egypt (Cox, 1993 and Abraham *et al.*, 1998). The agro climatic conditions prevalent in this region and the unique morphology of the crop coupled with intensive modern date palm forming have offered the pest an ideal ecological habitat (Abraham *et al.*, 1998). Aggregation pheromone traps have been reported as effective tools for monitoring and trapping the RPW in the field (Gunnawardena and Badarage, 1995). El-Lakwah *et al.* (2011), used attracting pheromone traps on date palm to study the population dynamics of RPW in Wardan and Abu-Ghalep villages, 6th October Governorate, Egypt. The recent discovery of the male of RPW produced aggregation pheromone trade name ferrugineol, (4-methyl- 5-nonanol) (Hallet *et al.*, 1993). According to Abd El-Kareim (1997 and 1998), pheromone traps not only used for detecting population activity of adult pest in the field but also could be incorporate in the management control program of this pest. The aim of this research work is to study the population density of adult RPW using aggregation pheromone traps at Ismailia Governorates, Egypt, during two successive years.

Materials and methods

Field experiments were carried out at date palm farm of area 25 feddan at the Regional Research Station for Delta East, Qassasin, Ismailia Governorate, Egypt. The chosen farm was cultivated with four varieties of date palm trees, zaghlool, barhi, hayani and samani aged from 10 to 15 years. From 200 date palm trees were chosen randomly and divided into 50 date palm trees for each variety, to study fluctuations in the population density of adult RPW *R. ferrugineus*. Eight

aggregation pheromone traps (Two traps for each variety) were used during two successive years (From April 2017 till March 2019). Trap design was a volume of 10 liters plastic bucket. It was punctured around its wall with four circular holes, each one of them was 5cm in diameter on distance of 20 cm from the bottom to facilitate entrance of adult RPW. Trap was covered on top with a plastic cover to avoid sun light and liquid evaporation. It was contained the following materials:

1. Aggregation pheromone:

Each trap contained the synthetic aggregation pheromone lures "Ferrugineol". It was a mixture of 4-methyl-5-nonanol manufactured by Chem Tica international S.A. company, Costa Rica. Pheromone bag was hanged underside the top cover surface of trap it released the active chemicals lures (Aggregation pheromone) via plastic membrane with average release rate (3 -10 mg/day).

2. Kairomone:

Dispenser of kairomone was a bottle containing 50 ml of liquid ethyl acetate. It used as a botanical synergist attractive to attract the adult of RPW to the trap. Bottle of kairomone was hanged underside the top cover surface of trap and the releasing rate of kairomone was (150-200 mg/day).

3. Liquid soap:

Liquid soap was mixed with 2 liters of water level in the inside bucket trap to catch and kill the adult of RPW.

4. Application method:

Eight aggregation pheromone traps were uniformly distributed in the infested study area by placed two traps in each variety of date palm under study. Traps were buried in the ground down to the level of 20 cm and arranged at equally spaced 100 meters between each other's and 5 meters away from date palm. Monitoring fluctuations in the population density of adult RPW were appreciated through the numbers

of collected adults of RPW from traps for each variety. The pheromone bag and dispenser of kairomone were replaced every two months, while the liquid soap mixed with water were replaced every two weeks. Collected adults of RPW from traps were counted and recorded twice monthly and calculated the monthly average for each variety separately during the two successive years of study.

Results and discussion

1. Estimating the rates of infection with red palm weevil *Rhyncophorus ferrugineus* on date palm varieties under study:

From 200 date palm trees were chosen randomly representing the four varieties zaghlool, barhi, hayani and samani at the Regional Research Station for Delta East, Qassasin, Ismailia Governorate, Egypt. Zaghlool and barhi varieties were recorded the highest rate of infection with RPW, 48% and 42%, respectively, while the hayani variety was recorded 34% of infection with RPW from infested palm. On the other hand, samani variety was recorded the lowest rate of infection with RPW 30%.

2. Total collected adult of red palm weevil *Rhyncophorus ferrugineus* from traps on date palm varieties under study:

The results of total collected adult of RPW during two successive years (2017-2018 and 2018-2019) by used aggregation pheromone traps were tabulated in Table (1). From total 937 adult of RPW were collected in the first year of study, zaghlool variety was recorded the highest percentage of total collected adult of RPW 29.5% followed by barhi, hayani and samani varieties

,25.8%, 23.2% and 21.6%, respectively. In the second year of study; From total 1114 adult of RPW were collected, zaghlool variety was recorded the highest percentage of total collected adult of RPW 28.5% followed by barhi, hayani and samani varieties, 24.7%, 23.9% and 23%, respectively. The results also indicated that, total collected adult of RPW in the second year of study during (2018-2019) was slightly higher than total collected adult of RPW in the first year of study during (2017-2018), which could be due to slight variation in the mean temperature during (2018-2019).

3. Fluctuations in the population density of adult red palm weevil *Rhyncophorus ferrugineus* on date palm varieties:

Results presented in Table (1) and illustrated in Figure (1, 2, 3 and 4) showed that, the fluctuations in the population density and percentage of collected adult of RPW from four varieties of date palms, zaghlool, barhi, hayani and samani by used aggregation pheromone traps during the two successive years of study (2017-2018 and 2018-2019).

3.1. On zaghlool variety in the first year of study, April and October were recorded the highest percentage of collected adult of RPW, 16.30% and 13.04%, respectively. On the other hand, August was recorded the lowest percentage of collected adult of RPW (1.44%). In the second year, May and October were recorded the highest percentage of collected adult of RPW, 15.77% and 12.61%, respectively. On the other hand; January was recorded the lowest percentage of collected adult of RPW 3.78% (Figure 1).

Table (1): Population density of total collected adults of *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* by pheromone traps from four varieties of date palm trees during two successive years.

Years	2017/2018				2018/2019			
Varieties	Zaghlool (%)	Barhi (%)	Hayani (%)	Samani (%)	Zaghlool (%)	Barhi (%)	Hayani (%)	Samani (%)
Months								
April	16.30%	9.50 %	1.84%	19.30%	9.14%	13.45%	4.88%	10.93%
May	7.24%	16.52 %	3.22%	8.91%	15.77%	5.45%	12.40%	16.40%
June	9.78%	1.65%	2.30%	5.44%	6.94%	7.27%	10.90%	9.76%
July	2.53%	3.71%	8.75%	3.96%	4.10%	6.18%	6.01%	9.37%
August	1.44%	10.33 %	11.05%	7.92%	9.46%	8%	4.13%	7.42%
September	6.88%	9.09%	12.44%	10.39%	9.14%	11.27%	1.50%	3.12%
October	13.04%	10.74 %	8.29%	15.84%	12.61%	10.54%	12.78%	1.17%
November	5.43%	7.02%	6.91%	10.89%	7.88%	6.90%	12.03%	11.32%
December	3.98%	8.67%	11.52%	8.41%	9.77%	9.45%	6.76%	10.15%
January	12.68%	7.43%	10.59%	1.98%	3.78%	9.09%	4.51%	8.59%
February	8.69%	6.61%	9.21%	2.47%	5.04%	9.09%	10.52%	4.68%
March	11.95%	8.67%	13.82%	4.45%	6.30%	3.27%	13.53%	7.03%
Total	276	242	217	202	317	275	266	256
(%)	29.5	25.8	23.2	21.6	28.5	24.7	23.9	23

Figure (1): Fluctuations in the population density of adult RPW on Zaghlool date palm variety during two successive years.

3.2. On barhi variety in the first year of study, May and October were recorded the highest percentage of collected adult of RPW ,16.52% and 10.74%, respectively. On the other hand, June was recorded the lowest percentage of collected adult of RPW 1.65%. In the

second year, April and September were recorded the highest percentage of collected adult of RPW ,13.45% and 11.27%, respectively. On the other hand, March was recorded the lowest percentage of collected adult of RPW 3.27% (Figure 2).

Figure (2): Fluctuations in the population density of adult *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* on barhi date palm variety during two successive years.

3.3. On hayani variety in the first year of study, March and September were recorded the highest percentage of collected adult of RPW,13.82% and 12.44%, respectively. On the other hand, April was recorded the lowest percentage of collected adult of RPW 1.84%. In the second year, March and

October were recorded the highest percentage of collected adult of RPW,13.53% and 12.78%, respectively. On the other hand, September was recorded the lowest percentage of collected adult of RPW 1.50% (Figure 3).

Figure (3): Fluctuations in the population density of adult *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* on hayani date palm variety during two successive years.

3.4. On samani variety in the first year of study, April and October were recorded the highest percentage of collected adult of RPW , 19.30% and 15.84%, respectively. On the other hand, January was recorded the lowest percentage of collected adult of RPW 1.98%. In the second year, May and

November were recorded the highest percentage of collected adult of RPW, 16.40% and 11.32%, respectively. On the other hand, October was recorded the lowest percentage of collected adult of RPW 1.17% (Figure 4).

Figure (4): Fluctuations in the population density of adult *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* on samani date palm variety during two successive years.

From previous results we can concluded that; the population dynamics of the adult RPW *R. ferrugineus* were existed in study area all over the year, in addition to the highest percentages of collected adult of RPW were recorded on April and May for zaghlool, barhi and samani varieties during the two successive years of study, while Hayani variety was recorded the highest percentage of collected adult of RPW on March during the two successive years of study. On the other hand, in the first year of study the lowest percentages of collected adult of RPW were recorded on months, August, June, April and January for zaghlool, barhi, hayani and samani varieties respectively, while in the second year of study, the lowest percentages of collected adult of RPW were recorded on months, January, March, September and October for zaghlool, barhi, hayani and samani varieties, respectively.

The obtained results agree with the findings of Abdallah and Al-Khatri

(2003) who observed that adult of RPW emerging continually throughout the year. Also, Abd El-Kareim (1997 and 1998) mentioned that, the minimum number of insects was recorded during December and January. In 1996 there were four peaks of emergence during March, May, July and October, where as in 1997 the peaks were recorded in April, May and September. In 1998 four peaks were recorded during April, May, August and October. These data confirm the previous data obtained by Qin *et al.* (2004) who found that, the population monitoring of red palm weevil occurred in four peaks during year in the area of Wenchang, Hainan Province. On the other hand, El-Sebaey (2003) in Egypt indicated that, *R. ferrugineus* had two main active seasons annually. The first adult brood was observed in April and the second one was in November. In addition, Al-Saoud (2007) and Faleiro (2005) also found that the adult of RPW were present throughout the year. Furthermore, El-Lakwah *et al.* (2011)

studied the population dynamics of the adult RPW in Wardan and Abu-Ghalep village, 6th October Governorate, they indicated that, adults emerging continually throughout the year. The lowest adults population was recorded during December and January. The population showed four peaks on months, June, August, November and March.

4. The effect of climatic conditions (Temperature and humidity) on the population density of adult red palm weevil *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* during the two successive years of study:

The results of mean temperatures in Ismailia Governorate, throughout two successive years of study (From April 2017 until March 2019) were shown that, mean temperatures increased during the

months, June, July and August, as they ranged between, 30.8 , 32.8 and 32°C, respectively. While January was shown the coldest month 16°C (Figure 5). On the other hand, the relative humidity on January was recorded the highest rate 60% RH., compared to the summer months, as the humidity ranged between 40% to 45% RH. during the two successive years of study (Figure 6). Obtained data indicated that there was significant positive correlation between mean temperatures and population dynamics of the adult of RPW during the two successive years of study, while the relative humidity had negative effect. Also, Abd El-Kareim *et al.* (2018) reported that, there was an effect of the climatic conditions of maximum and minimum temperature and the Relative Humidity on the population dynamics of adult RPW.

Figure (5): Mean temperature of Ismailia Governorate, throughout two successive years from April 2017 until March 2019.

Figure (6): Mean humidity of Ismailia governorate, throughout two successive years from early April 2017 until late March 2019.

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A faunistic study on Heteroptera (Insecta) in some regions of Iran
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Abstract:

Present study deals with faunistic surveys conducted in different regions of Iran. In total 29 species in 12 families were collected and identified: Acanthosomatidae (One species), Aradidae (One species), Berytidae (One species), Blissidae (One species), Coreidae (Two species and two genera), Lygaeidae (Two species and two genera), Miridae (Two species and two genera), Oxycarenidae (Two species and two genera), Reduviidae (Four species and four genera), Rhyparochromidae (Three species and three genera), Scutelleridae (Three species and two genera), and Tingidae (Seven species and six genera). Five species, *Berytinus consimilis* (Horváth, 1885) (Berytidae), *Rhynocoris bipustulatus* (Fieber, 1861), *Stenolemus novaki* Horváth, 1888 (Both Reduviidae), *Acalypta gracilis gracilis* (Fieber, 1844), and *Catoplatus distinctus* Montandon, 1895 (Both Tingidae) are newly recorded from Iran.

Introduction

True bugs (Heteroptera) with more than 40,000 described species worldwide are one of the most important insects (Weirauch and Schuh, 2011). Many species are economically important as crop pests, biological control agents of phytophagous insect pests (Schaefer, 2000), or vectors of diseases (Schofield and Dolling, 1993; Schaefer, 2000 and Garcia *et al.*, 2000). Suborder Heteroptera has been divided into seven Infraorders (including terrestrial and Waterbugs) Nepomorpha, Gerromorpha and

Leptopodomorpha these are aquatic, semiaquatic and riparian respectively; terrestrial Heteroptera has been divided into four Infraorders viz Enicocephalomorpha, Dipsocoromorpha, Cimicomorpha, and Penatatomomorpha. Enicocephalomorpha is an infraorder containing about 450 described numbers of species Dipsocoromorpha having about 300 species this is a very rare collected group of true bugs; Cimicomorpha is one of the largest infraorders in which family Miridae and

Reduviidae having the maximum number of species. Penatatomomorpha is having about 15,000 known species around the world (Schuh and Slater, 1995).

The fauna of Iranian Heteroptera was studied rather well which all the families have been catalogued (Ghahari *et al.*, 2009a, b, 2010a, b, 2012a, b, 2013a, b, 2014, 2016; Ghahari and Moulet, 2012a, b, 2013; Ghahari and Heiss, 2012; Ghahari and Cherot, 2014 and Ostovan *et al.*, 2017). The aim of study is representing the heteroptera

fauna different regions of Iran and introducing of some new country records.

Materials and methods

Classification, nomenclature, host plants and distributional data provided by Aukema and Rieger (1995, 1996 and 1999), and Aukema *et al.* (2013) have been followed. More faunistic survey and literature-based study is needful for enriching the faunal diversity of Iran. The provinces of Iran are represented in Figure (1).

Figure (1): Map of Iran with boundaries of provinces.

Results and discussion

During the present study 29 species in 12 families were collected and identified . Five of them are newly recorded from Iran.

Suborder Heteroptera Latreille, 1810

1. Infraorder Cimicomorpha Leston, Pendergrast and Southwood, 1954

1.1. Superfamily Reduioidea Latreille, 1807

1.1.1. Family Reduviidae Amyot & Serville, 1843

1.1.1.1. *Coranus kerzhneri* Putshkov, 1982

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Kaleybar, 2♂♂, August 2009.

1.1.1.2. *Rhynocoris bipustulatus* (Fieber, 1861)

Material examined: Kordestan province, Baneh, 1♀, June 2013.

1.1.1.3. *Sphedanolestes pulchellus* (Klug, 1830)

Material examined: Kordestan province, Saqez, 1♀, July 2009.

1.1.1. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2020), 3 (4):

4. *Stenolemus novaki* Horváth, 1888
Material examined: Khuzestan province, Andimeshk, 2♀♀, April 2014.

1.2. Superfamily Tingoidea Laporte, 1832

1.2.1. Family Tingidae Laporte de Castelnau, 1833

1.2.1.1. *Acalypta gracilis gracilis* (Fieber, 1844)

Material examined: Guilan province, Talesh (Subatan), 1♀, 14.vi.2009.

1.2.1.2. *Acalypta marginata* (Wolff, 1804)

Material examined: Golestan province, Golestan National Park, 2♀♀, April 2015.

1.2.1.3. *Catoplatus distinctus* Montandon, 1895

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Varzeghan, 1♂, August 2014.

1.2.1.4. *Dictyla lupulii* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1837)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Arasbaran forest, 3♀♀, September 2013.

1.2.1.5. *Dictyonota horvathi* (Kiritshenko, 1914)

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Piranshahr, 1♀, 1♂, July 2009.

1.2.1.6. *Monosteira lobulifera* Reuter, 1888

Material examined: Kermanshah province, Paveh, 1♂, June 2013.

1.2.1.7. *Tingis grisea* Germar, 1835

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Savadkooh, 1♂, August 2011.

1.3. Superfamily Miroidea Hahn, 1833

1.3.1. Family Miridae Hahn, 1833

1.3.1.1. *Campyloneura virgula* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Makoo, 1♂, September 2014.

1.3.1.1. *Dimorphocoris debilis debilis* (Reuter, 1880)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, around Aras River, 2♀♀, July 2010.

2. Infraorder Pentatomomorpha Leston, Pendergrast and Southwood, 1954

2.1. Superfamily Pentatomoidea Leach, 1815

2.1.1. Family Acanthosomatidae Signoret, 1864

2.1.1.1. *Elasmucha grisea grisea* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined: Guilan province, Talesh (Subatan), 2♀♀, 1♂, September 2009.

2.1.2. Family Scutelleridae Leach, 1815

2.1.2.1. *Eurygaster austriaca* (Schrunk, 1776)

Material examined: Ardebil province, Aslanduz, 2♂♂, June 2008.

2.1.2.2. *Odontoscelis litura* (Fabricius, 1775)

Material examined: Kermanshah province, Paveh, 2♂♂, July 2011.

2.1.2.3. *Odontoscelis minuta* Jakovlev, 1882

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Sardasht, 1♂, August 2012.

2.2. Superfamily Coreoidea Leach, 1815

2.2.1. Family Coreidae Leach, 1815

2.2.1.1. *Anoplocerus lutens* (Fieber, 1861)

Material examined: Chaharmahal & Bakhtiari province, Koohrang, 1♀, 1♂, September 2016.

2.2.1.2. *Ceraleptus lugens* Horváth, 1898

Material examined: Golestan province, Golestan National Park, 1♀, April 2015.

2.3. Superfamily Lygaeoidea Schilling, 1829

2.3.1. Family Berytidae Fieber, 1851

2.3.1.1. *Berytinus consimilis* (Horváth, 1885)

Material examined: Ardebil province, Germe, 2♀♀, August 2014.

2.3.2. Family Blissidae Stål, 1862

2.3.2.2. *Blissus putoni* Jakovlev, 1875

Material examined: Ardebil province, Germe, 1♂, August 2014.

2.3.3. Family Lygaeidae Schilling, 1829

2.3.3.1. *Hormopleurus nysioides* Horváth, 1884

Material examined: Khuzestan province, Andimeshk, 1♀, 2♂♂, April 2010.

2.3.3.2. *Melanotelus villosulus* (Stål, 1855)

Material examined: Sistan & Baluchestan province, 1♂, October 2009.

2.3.4. Family Oxycarenidae Stål, 1862

2.3.4.1. *Auchenodes costalis* (Lethierry, 1877)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Varzeghan, 1♀, 1♂, August 2014.

2.3.4.2. *Camptotelus lineolatus lineolatus* (Schilling, 1829)

Material examined: Kordestan province, Baneh, 2♀♀, June 2013.

2.3.5. Family Rhyparochromidae Amyot & Serville, 1843

2.3.5.1. *Drymus (Sylvadrymus) brunneus confinis* Reuter, 1893

Material examined: Zanjan province, Mahneshan, 1♀, June 2010.

2.3.5.2. *Hyalochilus dolosus* Horváth, 1897

Material examined: Northern Khorasan province, Lojley, 1♀, April 2012.

2.3.5.3. *Icus angularis* Fieber, 1861

Material examined: Golestan province, Minudasht, 3♀♀, 2♂♂, July 2011.

2.4. Superfamily Aradoidea Brulle, 1836

2.4.1. Family Aradidae Brullé, 1836

2.4.1.1. *Aradus cinnamomeus* Panzer, 1806

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Makoo, 1♀, September 2014.

The results of this faunistic investigation indicate that the species diversity of Iranian Heteroptera is very diverse and on the other hand rather unknown, because all the areas have not been sampled systematically. With considering of these five new country records, total number of Iranian Heteroptera (with 50 recorded families) reaches to 1588 species from 508 genera (see Ghahari *et al.*, 2016). Iran is a large country with various geographical regions and climates, so several other new records will be discovered after exact faunistic surveys in all the regions.

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Seasonal activity of jasmine moth *Palpita unionalis* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) in response to true spiders and temperature degrees in olive orchard

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Abstract:

The jasmine moth *Palpita unionalis* (Hübner) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) is one of the serious pests infesting olive trees. The present study aimed to study some ecological aspects of *P. unionalis* and true spiders in olive orchard at Dakahlia Governorate during two successive years (from the 25th of January 2018 till the 16th of January 2020). The obtained results indicated that larval population of *P. unionalis* exhibiting four and five peaks of abundance during the first and second year and the highest activity was recorded during autumn and spring of the first and second year. With respect to true spiders, it exhibited six and five peaks of abundance during the first and second year and the highest activity was recorded during spring of the two studied years. On contrary, the lowest activity of *P. unionalis* and true spiders was recorded during winter of the first year and summer of the second year. Statistical analysis indicated that *P. unionalis* population exhibited positively responses to the true spider population during the first ($r = 0.092^{ns}$) and second ($r = 0.601^*$) year. Both of *P. unionalis* and true spiders exhibited insignificant responses maximum, minimum and average temperature during the two studied years.

Introduction

Olive (*Olea europaea* L.) growing is of great economic and socio-cultural significance for the Mediterranean region, where 98% of the world's olive production is located (Civantos, 2001). The olive tree is attacked by various insect pests, which can cause considerable yield losses, and current olive cultivation involves regular use of plant protection products. However, frequent insecticide

applications pose the risk of environmental pollution and contamination of the olive products (Jardak and Ksantini, 1996; Calbras *et al.*, 1997; Cirio 1997 and Moustafa *et al.*, 2009). The jasmine moth *Palpita unionalis* (Hübner) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) is an international lepidopteran pest originating in the Mediterranean Basin (Hegazi *et al.*, 2012 and Ghoneim, 2015). It is a highly mobile moth and is known to disperse

even to Northern Europe (Tremewan, 2002). It attracted a considerable attention of some researchers during the last few decades because of its serious attack against young olive trees in nurseries. Where, it is feeding damage by larvae can reach up to 90% of the leaf area, thereby seriously affecting the development of the plant shoots. During the fruit ripening season, high larvae infestations may also reduce the fruit yield by 30% (Solaiman, 1997; Lopez-Villalta, 1999; Hegazi *et al.*, 2007 a, b and 2012 and Ghoneim, 2015). In years of high population densities, larvae attack also olive fruits, making them unsuitable for marketing (Antonelli and Rossi , 2004 and Mazomenos *et al.*, 2002). This pest is one of the serious olive pests in Egypt and several countries (Vassilaina-Alexopoulou and Santorini, 1973; Tremewan, 2002 and Hamadah and Abo Elsoud, 2018).

Spiders represent an abundant group of predators within the agroecosystems, and in olive groves of Europe spiders are important predators and may significantly reduce the attack of pests. Spiders comprise a large fraction of predator species in agroecosystems, where insects (especially flies and moths) are the main preys. These arachnids are more sensitive to pesticide application than their prey, and therefore are good bioindicators of the risk of an outbreak of pests in olive groves (Loverre and Addante, 2011). The intensive use of many conventional insecticides led to several dramatic problems, such as destruction of the natural enemies, environmental hazards and serious toxicological problems to humans, as well as the development of insect resistance toward different insecticides (Davies *et al.*, 2007; Costa *et al.*, 2008; Mosallanejad and Smagghe, 2009 and Sharifian *et al.*, 2012). There are several attempts to use different bio control tactics to control *P. unionalis*

populations such as *Trichogramma* spp. (Hegazi *et al.*, 2007a) and pheromone traps (Anthanassiou *et al.*, 2004 and Hegazi *et al.*, 2007b). Spiders are important predators of the olive moth *Prays oleae* (Bernard, 1788) (Lepidoptera: Yponomeutidae) and may reduce its population by 80%, being *Philodromus* spp., *Salticus* spp. and *Iciushamatus* the most common. They feed on eggs and larvae and in some cases have reduced the pest population by 60 to 80% in olive groves in Spain (Morris *et al.*, 1999 and Ghavami, 2006). The occurrence of spiders in olive groves can be an important contribution to reducing natural populations of phytophagous arthropods due to their exclusively predator diet (Rei *et al.*, 2011).

Efficient control of economic insect pests requires detailed investigations of its ecology as well as the recorded natural enemies. Some certain are essential for the control of insect pests such as population dynamics and peaks times of the pest and its associated natural enemies (Öztürk and Ulusoy, 2012 and Abdel Kareim *et al.*, 2018). According to Witzgall *et al.* (2010), the first step in managing any pest species begins with a proper monitoring program. Therefore, the present study deals with some ecological aspects of jasmine moth *P. unionalis* and true spiders in olive orchard at Dakahlia Governorate.

Material and methods

An area of two feddans (One feddan = 4200 m²) cultivated with olive trees was selected for the present study at Mansoura district, Dakahlia governorate. The present study lasted two successive years, starting from the 25th of January 2018 till the 16th of January 2020. Five trees (Homogenous in size and age) were selected randomly from all the area. Every week, five newly branches (Each branch was about 20 cm) of each tree were cut from the

cardinal direction (North, south, east and west) and center of the tree (On branch per direction). Then, branched were put in paper bags, well tied and transported to laboratory for investigation. On each branch, numbers of *P. unionalis* larvae and true spiders were counted and recorded. Among the available meteorological data of Dakahlia region, daily averaged temperature degrees (Maximum, minimum and average) were obtained from the Central Laboratory for Agricultural Climate, Agricultural Research Center, during the period from the 25th of January 2018 till the 16th of January 2020. The daily records of each temperature degree were grouped into weekly means according to the sampling dates. The mean weekly numbers of *P. unionalis* larvae as well

as true spiders were correlated with each temperature degree and the simple & multi regressions in addition to explained variance were analyzed by using the computer program of CoHort Software (2004).

Results and discussion

As shown as in Figure (1), larval population of *P. unionalis* occurred in olive trees during the period from 17th of May till 29th of November 2018 during the first year. The pest population was recorded four peaks. These peaks were recorded on the 17th of May (4 individuals / sample), 23th of August (6 individuals / sample), 13th of September (5 individuals / sample) and 11th of October (16 individuals / sample).

Figure (1): Seasonal abundance of *Palpita unionalis* and true spiders population on olive trees in Dakahlia Governorate during 2018/19.

With respect to true spiders, it was recorded all over the first year (Figure 1). True spiders exhibited six peaks of abundance recorded as 18, 9, 13, 13, 11, 6 and 16 individuals / sample (On 25th January, 8th of March, 5th of April, 17th of May, 5th of July, 4th of October and 8th of November 2018, respectively). During the second year, *P. unionalis* showed two periods of activity. The first period was recorded from the 21st of March till the 23rd of

May 2019; while, the second period was recorded from the 12th of September till the 26th of December 2019 (Figure 2). *P. unionalis* exhibited five peaks during the second year. These peaks were recorded during 11th of April (15 individuals / sample), 2nd of May (10 individuals / sample), 19th of September (6 individuals / sample), 10th of October (6 individuals / sample) and 19th of December 2019 (6 individuals / sample).

Figure (2): Seasonal abundance of *Palpita unionalis* and true spiders population on olive trees in Dakahlia Governorate during 2019/20.

As shown as in Figure (2), true spiders exhibited five peaks of activity during the second year. These peaks were recorded as 13, 4, 8, 8 and 6 individuals / sample on the 4th of April, 9th of May, 12th of September, 14th of November and 19th of December, respectively. Data illustrated in Figure (3) indicated that *P. unionalis* was recorded with no numbers during

January and February. On the contrary, this pest showed its highest population during October of the first year (with a mean of 14 individuals / sample) and during April of the second year (with a mean of 7 individuals / sample). During all of the rest months, the pest population showed moderate numbers and varied from year to other.

Figure (3): Monthly mean numbers of *Palpita unionalis* and true spiders on olive trees in Dakahlia Governorate during 2018/19 and 2019/20.

True spiders showed its highest activity during April and July of the first year with monthly means of 9.25 and 7.5 individuals / sample. While, during the second year, true spiders showed its highest population during March (with a mean of 5.75 individuals / sample) and April (with a mean of 4.50 individuals / sample). As shown as in Figure (4), the highest mean numbers of

P. unionalis were recorded during autumn of the first year and spring of the second year. On contrary, there were no recorded individuals of *P. unionalis* during winter of the first year and summer of the second year. The general mean number of *P. unionalis* was 2.21 and 1.67 individuals / sample all over the first and second year.

Figure (4): Mean of numbers of *Palpita unionalis* larvae and true spiders during annual seasons as well as all year on olive trees in Dakahlia Governorate during 2018/19 and 2019/20.

True spider recorded its highest activity during spring of the two studied years. While, its lowest activity was recorded during winter of the first year and summer of the second year. The general mean number of true spiders reached 4.71 and 2.77 individuals / sample all over the first and second year (Figure 4). The seasonal activity of *P. unionalis* in response to true spiders and temperature degrees was evaluated during two years of study. To determine the relation between these factors and population of *P. unionalis*, simple

correlation (r) and regression (b) were done, as well as multi regression analysis (Table 1). Correlation analysis indicated that *P. unionalis* population exhibited positively responses to the increase of true spider population during the first ($r = 0.092^{ns}$) and second ($r = 0.601^*$) year. With respect to temperature degrees, *P. unionalis* exhibited positively insignificant responses maximum, minimum and average temperature during the two studied years.

Table (1): The correlation and regression coefficients between *Palpita unionalis* population and true spiders as well as temperature degrees on olive orchard in Dakahlia Governorate during 2018/19 and 2019/20.

Factors	Simple correlation and regression				Multi regression		
	R	B	P	R ²	B	P	E.V %
2018/19							
True spider	0.092	0.066	0.777	0.8%	0.014	0.981	15.2
Max. T.	0.342	0.516	0.276	11.7%	0.680	0.557	
Min. T.	0.287	0.413	0.365	8.2%	-0.670	0.703	
Av. T.	0.305	0.457	0.335	9.3%	0.190	0.920	
2019/20							
True spider	0.601	0.344	0.039	36.1%	0.992	0.128	39.9
Max. T.	0.079	0.175	0.808	0.6%	1.520	0.654	
Min. T.	0.020	0.047	0.952	0.0%	1.060	0.668	
Av. T.	0.045	0.105	0.889	0.2%	-2.470	0.664	

The simple regression indicated that every increase of true spiders by one individual increased the pest population by 0.066 and 0.344 individuals during the first and second years (Table, 1). On another hand, every increase of maximum, minimum and average temperature by one degree increased *P. unionalis* population by 0.516, 0.413 and 0.457 individuals, respectively during the first year and by 0.175, 0.047 and 0.105 individuals, respectively during the second year. Also, regression analysis showed that the highest effective factor on *P. unionalis* population during the first year was that of maximum temperature ($R^2 = 11.7\%$); while, during the second year was that of true spiders ($R^2 = 36.1\%$). The explained variance attributed to combined effects of true spiders in addition to maximum, minimum and average temperatures on *P. unionalis* population reached 15.2 and 39.9% of the total factors affecting the pest population during the first and second year (Table 1). Multi regression analysis explained that the relationship between *P. unionalis* population and all

of true spiders (T.s.), maximum temperature (Max.T.), minimum temperature (Min.T.) and average temperature (Av.T.) could be represented as follows:

During the first year:

$$P. unionalis = - 6.84 + 0.014 \text{ T.s.} + 0.66 \text{ Max.T.} - 0.67 \text{ Min.T.} + 0.19 \text{ Av.T.}$$

During the second year:

$$P. unionalis = - 4.94 + 0.992 \text{ T.s.} + 1.52 \text{ Max.T.} + 1.06 \text{ Min.T.} - 2.47 \text{ Av.T.}$$

Data represented in Table (2) showed the effect of temperature degrees on true spiders' population. These data explained that true spiders' population were insignificantly correlated with temperature degrees during the two studied year. The correlation coefficient values (r) between true spiders' population and maximum, minimum and average temperature degrees were 0.394^{ns} , 0.401^{ns} and 0.425^{ns} during the first year, and were -0.101^{ns} , -0.194^{ns} and -0.154^{ns} during the second year, respectively.

Table (2): The correlation and regression coefficients between population of true spiders and temperature degrees on olive orchard in Dakahlia Governorate during 2018/19 and 2019/20.

Factors	Simple correlation and regression				Multi regression		
	R	B	P	R ²	B	P	E.V%
2018/19							
Max. T.	0.394	0.734	0.266	12.2%	-0.558	0.409	26.8
Min. T.	0.401	0.805	0.196	16.1%	-0.280	0.798	
Av. T.	0.425	0.890	0.168	18.1%	1.010	0.376	
2019/20							
Max. T.	-0.101	-0.41	0.734	1.1%	2.030	0.308	20.7
Min. T.	-0.194	-0.82	0.547	3.7%	1.070	0.469	
Av. T.	-0.154	-0.62	0.632	2.4%	-3.070	0.362	

Regression analysis showed that average temperature was the most effective factor of true spiders' population during the first year ($R^2 = 18.1\%$); while, during the second year was that of minimum temperature ($R^2 = 3.7\%$). Multi regression explained that the combined effects of the three tested temperature degrees on true spiders' population was 26.8 and 20.7% of the total factors affecting true spiders' population during the first and second year (Table 2). In Egypt, lepidopterous pests are important constraints for olive production, especially in recently established, intensively managed olive plantations (Hegazi *et al.*, 2012). The present study showed that there were observed differences in either weekly numbers of *P. unionalis* larvae or the time of its peaks. Similar findings were obtained by Osman *et al.* (2001), Hegazi *et al.* (2011) and Hegazi *et al.* (2012), they reported that the number of *P. unionalis* was generally varied from year to other and from site to other.

Many authors reported that *P. unionalis* is a multivoltine species with several overlapping generations per year (Ghoneim, 2015). As reported by Grossley (2000), the pest has 2-3 generations in cold to mild regions while more than 5-6 in mid-tropical and tropical regions. It has 5 generations per year in in Spain (Fodale and Mule, 1990), 4-5 in Italy (Martelli, 1916 and

Fodale and Mule, 1990). The present results showed that *P. unionalis* exhibited four to five peaks of activity on olive orchard annually in Dakahlia governorate. These results are approximately in agreement with those of Hegazi *et al.* (2011), they reported that *P. unionalis* exhibiting six to seven and three to four overlapping flight peaks in Alexandria governorate. Also, in Alexandria, Hegazi *et al.* (2012) reported that this pest recorded three to four peaks of activity annually. On another hand, the obtained data showed that the heist activity of *P. unionalis* was recorded during autumn (Especially in October) and spring (Especially in April). While, in Alexandria, the heist activity was recorded during summer especially in June (Hegazi *et al.*, 2012). In the coastal region and Middle Egypt, *P. unionalis* recorded its highest populations in May (El-Kenawy, 2012). In Iran, field observations indicated that the first generation being completed by the end of March and in early April. However, the population reaches its peak during the third and fourth generations (Noori and Shirazi, 2012). The differences between the present results and others may explained by the study of Ghoneim (2015), who reported that *P. unionalis* has varied number of generations annually in the same country, depending on the host plant, seasonal

temperature and other environmental conditions of over its universal or regional distribution. Also, Kacar and Ulusoy (2013) observed that shoot development and climatic factors (Temperature and humidity) affected the larval population fluctuation.

According to the present study, true spiders exhibited five to six peaks of annual activity. The highest activity was recorded during spring of the two studied years. On contrary, its lowest activities were recorded during winter and summer. These results approximately came in the same line with Mohafez *et al.* (2010), they reported that the population numbers of true spiders had two highest peaks in September and July on mango trees in Sohag Governorate; while, it started to increase gradually during Spring months to reach the first peak in early Summer season, then a sharp decline in spider population in late Summer, Autumn and winter; then, started to increase gradually to reach peak in September.

Statistically, the true spider population exhibited positively responses to the increase of *P. unionalis* population during the two studied years. So, it could play an efficient role as a biological control agent to reduce the pest population. This suggestion is supported by Morris *et al.* (1999) and Ghavami (2006) in Spain, they reported that spiders are important predators of the olive moth, *P. oleae* and may reduce its population by 80%. The same authors added the spiders feed on eggs and larvae in olive groves. Also, Rei *et al.* (2011) reported that the occurrence of spiders in olive groves can be an important contribution to reducing natural populations of phytophagous arthropods due to their exclusively predator diet.

On another hand, the present study explained that jasmine moth, *P. unionalis* (Pyrilidae) exhibited

positively insignificant responses maximum, minimum and average temperature during the two studied years. Also, Halder *et al.* (2017) reported *Diaphania indica* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) exhibited positive responses to maximum, minimum and average temperature degrees in India. In contrary, Rahmathulla *et al.* (2012) recorded negative responses of the pyralid, *Diaphania pulverulentalis* Hampson in mulberry plantations. The variation between the present results and other may be attributed to the variation of agroecosystems, ecological factors and/or the behavior of pest species. Dahi *et al.* (2017) reported that the most favorite temperature for *P. unionalis* (which recorded high hatch rate, emergence rate and sex ratio) was that of 22°C followed by 27°C. This may explain the highest activity of *P. unionalis* during April and October months (which the average temperature ranged between 21 and 25°C). Also, the same authors conducted a study which aimed to calculate temperature thresholds (t_0) and accumulated heat units (DD's) for each stage of *P. unionalis* as a primary step for developing a forecasting system that will help to define the most precise time for different control programs. They found that the time required for development through egg, larva, pupa and pre-oviposition increased at lower temperatures. The lower threshold of development (t_0) to complete a generation was 12.04°C and the average accumulated heat units required for its development was 443.07 degree-days.

According to Mohafez *et al.* (2010), true spider population in some fruit orchards in Sohag governorate decreased to form the lowest activity in winter and exhibited its highest activity during spring months. This may confirm the positively insignificant correlation between true spiders and

temperature degrees especially in the first year of the present study.

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Study the persistence of pesticides under certain different environmental condition and evolution of their impurities

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Abstract:

The present work was carried out to study the effect of storage under high temperature pesticides of naserzol (Propiconazole 25 % EC W/V), nofostar (Dimethomorph 5%WDG W/W), self (Fludioxonil 25 %WG W/W) butox (Deltamethrin 50 % W/v EC), lamba pauer (Lambda-cyhalothrain 10 % W/v Sc) and teknofos (Cholrpyrifos 45 % W/v EC).The stability of active ingredient of the tested pesticides under storage 54 °C for 14 days and influence direct sunlight were studied . The active ingredient were propiconazole, dimethomorph and fludioxonil 25.31, 5.03 and 10.21 before storage for propiconazole, dimethomorph and fludioxonil, respectively and become after storage 54 °C 18.65 , 4.67 and 7.68 at the end experiment .The loose percentages were 26.31, 7.15 and 24.77 % when the pesticides compound previously were stored at 54 °C for 14 days. Also, the stability active ingredient before influence sunlight 25.07 , 5.03 and 10.21 after influence sunlight 22.01, 4.10 and 9.11 % , respectively . Stability of active ingredient were deltamethrin, lambada-cyhalothrin and cholrpyrifos 50.45 ,10.23 and 45.03 before storage become after storage 54 °C 25.50 , 4.92 and 45.03 at the end experiment. The loose percentage were 49.45 , 51.91and 22.71%, respectively, were stored at 54 °C for 14 days . Deltamethrin impurities' before and after influence storage 54 °C for 14 days indictable but cholrpyrifos impurity of sulfotep (O,O,O',O'-tetraethyl dithiopyrophosphate) become storage 54 °C for 14 days 5.098 mg/kg.

Introduction

Pesticides general became an important component of worldwide agriculture systems during the last century, allowing for a noticeable increase food production and increase in crop yields (Alexandratos and Bruinsma, 2012). Influence on

pesticides and agrichemical can be through contact with the skin, inhalation or ingestion. The type of pesticide, the duration and route of exposure, and the individual health status (e.g., healthy/damaged and skin nutritional deficiencies) are determining factors he possible health

outcome. Within animal or human body, pesticides may be metabolized excreted, stored, bio accumulated in body fat or (WHO, 1990 ; Pirsahab *et al.*, 2015 and Alewu and Nosiri, 2011). The numerous negative health effects that have been associated with chemical pesticides include, among other effects, gastrointestinal, dermatological neurological, carcinogenic, respiratory, reproductive, and endocrine effects (WHO, 1990 ; Sanborn *et al.*, 2007; Mnif *et al.*, 2011 and Thakur *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, high occupational, accidental, or intentional exposure to pesticides can result in hospitalization and death (WHO, 1990 and Gunnell *et al.*, 2007). Pesticides and agrochemical pollution that enter waterways through agricultural runoff, industrial discharges and storm water drains may persist in the environment for long periods and be transported by water or air over long distances. They may

disrupt the function of the endocrine system, result-ing in reproductive, developmental, and behavioral problems (WHO and International Programme on Chemical Safety, 2002). In Egypt, as in many other agricultural countries, pesticides are widely accustomed control harmful pests, mainly, cotton, maize and rice. Nearly of these chemicals are readily soluble in plant oils and waxes; this common property places all under suspicion as food (Fatin *et al.* , 2016).

In this paper, we studied the effect of storage and influence direct sunlight of pesticides (Propiconazole, dimethomorph, fludioxonil deltamethrin , lambada-cyhalothrin and cholrpyrifos) and determination of impurities pesticides .

Materials and methods

Source of sample pesticides: Center Agric. Pesticides Laboratory (Table 1)

Table (1): Showed the formulation of pesticides .

Treed name for fungicides	Active ingredient	Types of pesticides	Formulation types	Structure	Impurities
Naserzol 25 %	Propiconazole	Fungicides	EC		UND
Nofostar 5%	Dimethomorph	Fungicides	WDG		UND
Self 25 %	Fludioxonil	Fungicides	WG		UND
Butox 50 %	Deltamethrin	Insecticides	EC		Bromovinyl) becisthemic acid chloride [(1R,3R)-3-(2,2-dibromovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane carboxoyl chloride]
Lamba - pauer 10 %	Lambada-cyhalothrin	Insecticides	SC		UND
Teknofos 45 %	Cholrpyrifos	Insecticides	EC		Sulfotep (O,O,O',O'-tetraethyl dithiopyrophosphate.)

1. Sample preparation for tested pesticides:

Accurately weighed enough samples formulation equivalent to 10 mg of standard in a different 25 ml volumetric flask for each sample, and slowly mixed with methanol and the volume was completed with methanol.

2. Storage stability tests:

The Previously fungicides (Propiconazole , fludioxonil and dimethomorph deltamethrin , lambadacyhathrin and cholrpyrifos) formulation were stored in oven at 54 °C for 14 days according to the (FAO, 1999, 2004, 2010 , 2016 and 2018), respectively 14 days storage. During the storage period the samples were taken at 0, 1, 3 ,7 and 14 , days from storage to determine the active ingredient for formulation under testes if is present .

3. Influence of direct sunlight:

The pesticides (Propiconazole , fludioxonil ,dimethomorph , deltamethrin , lambada-cyhathrin and cholrpyrifos) formulation were influence of direct sunlight for 14 ,The samples were taken at 0, 1, 3 ,7 and 14 days from influence direct sunlight to determine the active ingredient and impurities content for formulation under testes if is present .

4. Chromatographic High-performance liquid chromatography:

The type of Chromatographic High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) system model (Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity) with quaternary pump, UV-detector was employed. The chromatographic C18 stainless steal column (25 cm length, 4.6 mm inner diameter, and 4.0 µm particles) .

5. Determination of active ingredient Gas Liquid Chromatography (GLC):

Determination of cholrpyrifos residues by GLC analysis compared with the standard used cholrpyrifos was

carried out GLC model Agilent Technologies, column with flame ionization detector (FID).

Conditions

Injection temperature: 225 °C

Detector temperature: 300 °C

Oven temperature: 130 °C for 5 min., 4 °C/min., 184 °C

6. Determination of fungicides by GC/Ms:

Apparatus Agilent B, 5977 AMSD gas chromatography equipped with an agilent mass spectrometric detector , with a direct capillary interface and fused silica capacity colum (30 m x 0.025 mm HP -5 0.25 microm 60 to 325/325 °C). Samples were injected under the following condition ; Helium was used as carrier gas at approximately 1 ml /min , pulsed split mode , split ratio (10:1) split flow 10 ml /min . The solvent delay was 4 min and the injection size were 1 UL . Oven temperature program , %0 °C for O<5 min , the 10 /min ramp to 190 °C followed by a 10 °C /min ramp to 210 °C for 1 min followed by a 10 °C /min ramp to 300 °C and held for 2 min (total run time followed by a injection temperature was set at 280 °C. Wiley mass spectral data was used in the identification of the separated peaks .

Results and discussion

1. The effect of storage 54 °C and influence sunlight on propiconazole, dimethomorph and fludioxonil:

Date in Table (2) show that the active ingredient in tested propiconazole dimethomorph and fludioxonil formulation were affected by storage 54°C of exposure. Stability of propiconazole , dimethomorph and fludioxonil (a.i) 25.31, 5.03 and 10.21 before storage for propiconazole, dimethomorph and fludioxonil, respectively and become after storage 54 °C 18.65 , 4.67 and 7.68 at the end experiment .The loose percentages were 26.31, 7.15 and 24.77 % when the

pesticides compound previously were stored at 54 °C for 14 days.

Table (2): The effect of storage 54 °C Active ingredient (a. i) on propiconazole , dimethomorph and fludioxonil formulation .

Storage period (days)	Storage 54 °C					
	Propiconazole 25 %		Dimethomorph 5 %		Fludioxonil 10 %	
	(a.i)	Loss	(a.i)	Loss	(a.i)	Loss
0*	25.31	00	5.03	00	10.21	00
1	25.31	00	5.03	00	10.02	1.86
3	25.07	0.23	4.95	1.59	9.02	11.65
7	21.41	15.40	4.80	1.51	8.87	13.12
14	18.65	26.31	4.67	7.15	7.68	24.77

0*One hour before exposure to storage.

2. Effect of storage at 54 °C on active ingredient (a.i) of deltamethrin ,lambada-cyhalothrin and cholrpyrifos formulation :

Date in Table (3) showed that the stability of active ingredient was deltamethrin, lambada-cyhalothrin and cholrpyrifos before storage were 50.45 ,10.23 and 45.03 % , respectively and become after storage for 14 days 25.50 , 4.92 and 34.8 % , respectively at the end experiment. In general, increasing temperature and period of

exposure of increasing the rate of degradation insecticides El-Deeb *et al.* (1991) and Emara and Mohssen (2009). Deltamethrin impurity before and after influence storage 54 °C for 14 days indictable but cholrpyrifos impurity of sulfotep (O,O,O',O'-tetraethyl dithiopyrophosphate) become storage 54 °C for 14 days 5.098 mg/kg, this results with disagreement FAO maximum impurity 3mg/kg in cholrpyrifos.

Table (3): Effect of Storage at 54 °C on active ingredient (a.i) of deltamethrin ,lambada-cyhalothrin and cholrpyrifos formulation.

Storage period (Days)	Deltamethrin 50%			Lambada-cyhalothrin 10 %		Cholrpyrifos 45 %			
	Active Ingredient (a.i)	Loss	Dibro-movinyll	(a.i)	Loss	Active Ingredient (a.i)	Loss %	Sulf-otep	Sulfotep %g/kg Cholrpyrifos
0	50.45	00	UND	10.23	00	45.03	00	0.043	0.852
1	50.40	0.08	UND	10.20	0.03	45.00	0.06	0.043	0.853
3	40.66	19.40	UND	8.18	16.60	44.51	1.1	0.091	2.238
7	31.12	38.31	UND	6.22	39.19	42.08	6.55	0.130	4.177
14	25.50	49.45	UND	4.92	51.91	34.8	22.71	0.13	5.098

0* One hour before exposure to storage. UND Indictable.

3. Effect of influence sunlight on active ingredient (a.i) of propiconazole ,dimethomorph and fludoxanil formulation:

Date in Table (4) indicated that the stability of active ingredient

propiconazole, dimethomorph and fludoxanil were 25.07, 5.03 and 10.21 before storage and become 22.01, 4.10 and 9.11 after 14 days of influence sunlight respectively.

Table (4): Effect of influence sunlight on Active ingredient (a.i) of propiconazole ,dimethomorph and fludoxanil formulation.

Storage period (Days)	Sunlight					
	Propiconazole 25 %		Dimethomorph 5 %		Fludioxonil 10%	
	(a.i)	Loss	(a.i)	Loss	(a.i)	Loss
0	25.07	00	5.03	00	10.21	00
1	25.00	2.79	5.00	0.59	10.00	2.20
4	24.00	4.26	4.85	3.57	9.94	2.60
3	22.27	11.16	4.17	17.09	9.59	6.07
7	22.01	1.03	4.10	18.48	9.11	10.77
14	22.01	1.03	4.10	18.48	9.11	10.77

0* One hour before exposure to storage.

4. Effect of direct sunlight on active ingredient (a.i) of deltamethrin ,lambada-cyhalothrain and cholrpyrifos formulation:

Date in Table (5) showed that the stability of active ingredient was deltamethrin, lambada-cyhalothrin and cholrpyrifos before storage were 50.45 ,10.23 and 45.03 respectively and become after storage for 14 days 42.95 , 5.56 and 41.91 % respectively at the end experiment. Domout (1989) who reported that pyrethroid (Lambada-Cyhalothrin and deltamethrin) are a class of lipophilic insecticides very easily degradation in

natural environmental and the two main cause of degradation , photo and biodegradation often operate together , the pyrethroid are sensitive to sunlight , which triggers much alternation such as isomerisation ore cleavage of the original molecule. Also, determination of deltamethrin impurity before and after influence storage 54 °C for 14 days indictable but cholrpyrifos impurity of sulfotep (O,O,O',O'-tetraethyl dithiopyrophosphate) become storage 54 °C for 14 days 2.17 mg/kg, this results with agreement FAO maximum impurity 3mg/kg in cholrpyrifos.

Table (5) : Effect of direct sunlight on active ingredient (a.i) of deltamethrin , lambada- cyhalothrin and cholrpyrifos formulation.

Storage period (Days)	Deltamethrin 50%			Lambada-cyhalothrin 10 %		Cholrpyrifos 45 %			
	Active Ingredient (a.i)	Loss	Dibrom-ovinyll	Active Ingredient (a.i)	Loss	Active Ingredient (a.i)	Loss %	Sulfotep	Sulfotep %g/kg Cholrpyrifos
0	50.45	00	UND	0.23	00	45.03	00	0.023	0.51
1	50.35	1.98	UND	10.22	0.09	45.03	00	0.033	0.73
3	49.30	2.27	UND	8.45	17.39	44.00	2.28	0.071	1.61
7	45.50	10.87	UND	6.99	31.67	43.08	4.33	0.083	1.91
14	42.95	17.46	UND	5.56	45.65	41.91	6.9	0.091	2.17

0* One hour before exposure to storage.

5. The degradation product and possible pathway of pesticides by GC.MS .

The data in present in Table (6) show that Propiconazole degradation after 14 days 54 °C and influence sunlight products 2,4-dichlorophenyl 1,2,4-triazole-1-ylmethylketone,1-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-4-(hydroxypropyl)-1,3-dioxolan-2-ylmethyl] and

Propiconazole , Deltamethrin degradation after 14 days storage product Benzene ,1,3dimethylchloro-3,3,3-trifluoropropenyl)-2,2dimethylcyclopropanecarboxylate Also the degradation cholrpyrifos product benzene ,1,2,3,4, teramethyl , (O,O-diethyl O-3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridyl phosphorothioate) and 3,5,6 trichlor-2 pyridinol (Jayanthi, 2016) who report that biodegradation of cholrpyrifos and its hydrolysis.

Table (6): The degradation product on pesticides By GC/MS .

Pesticides	R.T.	Compound product
Propiconazole	28.022 26.79 26.66	Propiconazole 2,4-dichlorophenyl 1,2,4-triazole-1-ylmethyl ketone 1-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-4-(hydroxypropyl)-1,3-dioxolan-2-ylmethyl]-
Fludioxonil	25.27	Fludoxanil
Dimethomorph	38.71	4-[3-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-(3,4-dimethoxy-phenyl)-1-oxo-2-propenyl]-
Deltamethrin	8.01 8.22 28.02	Benzene propeyl Benzene 1- ethyl -2 methyl . O,O-diethyl O-(3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinyl) phosphorothioate
Lambda-cyhalothrin	6.33 28.49 38.50	Benzene ,1,3dimethyl . chloro-3,3,3-trifluoropropenyl)- dimethylcyclopropanecarboxylate (1,1-bispheny) -2 carboxamide , N 1,1 dimethylethyl
Cholrpyrifos	11.74 23.685	Benzene ,1,2,3,4, teramethyl O,O-diethyl O-3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridyl phosphorothioate 3,5,6 trichlor-2 pyridinol

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Vitamin C supplementation in honeybee *Apis mellifera* (Hymenoptera: Apidae) colonies to improve drone's quality

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Abstract:

Colony success of honeybee *Apis mellifera* L. (Hymenoptera: Apidae) depends partially on the reproductive success of the queen, which in turn directly impacted by drone's health and fitness. Drones are reared only during the reproductive season and can be affected by many environmental factors. The impact of hive supplements on drone fitness and quality is rarely documented but may improve drone reproductive health and colony survival. In this investigation, feeding sucrose syrup supplemented with vitamin C inserted to colonies in early spring. Drones assessed after emergence in regarding to body weight, total soluble protein, total carbohydrates content, carbohydrate hydrolysing enzymes in addition to sperm number in mature individuals. The mean body weight, total protein and carbohydrates content of newly emerged drones, as well as sperm numbers of matured drones were significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher in vitamin C colonies than control ones. Whereas, insignificant difference was observed in the activities of trehalase, amylase and sucrase enzymes between control and colonies receiving vitamin C as supplement.

Introduction

The survival of a honeybee *Apis mellifera* L. (Hymenoptera: Apidae) colony depends indirectly on rearing of healthy drones. Despite the transitory presence of drones in the hive, they have the important function of mating with virgin queens, transferring their colony's genes to their mates where, drones are responsible for producing semen which transmit to the queen during the mating flight (Czakońska *et al.*, 2013). Honeybee queen can mate with an average of 12 drones and able to hold about 4.3-7.0 million spermatozoa in her spermatheca to

fertilize eggs for the remainder of her life (Rhodes, 2002). Adequate numbers of mature age drones, each producing a large volume of semen with high number of sperms result in queen bees with the maximum number of sperms present in their spermathecae after mating. Low numbers of sperm in the queen spermathecae after mating contributes to early supersedure that increase costs to beekeepers due to queen replacement beside weaken in colonies strength and decrease their production during the period of queen replacement (Rhodes, 2008).

Therefore, factors affecting drone reproductive health may directly affect queen fitness and longevity, having great influences at the colony level. Quality and viability of drones particularly their sperm are influenced by several environmental factors and in-hive conditions including nutrition, temperature, age, size of comb cells and season. Pesticide exposure during and after development may also influence drone reproductive quality (Rangel and Fisher, 2019). Drones are also very sensitive to infestation with parasites, e.g. Varroa mites moreover, there is a strong preference for mite reproduction in drone brood over worker brood in a ratio of nine to one when both worker and drone brood are available (Martin, 1995). However, varroa parasitism negatively impacts colony fitness as it decreases drone weight and reduces the number of drones that survive to maturity (Collins and Pettis, 2001). Also, applying miticides to beehives can produce undesirable side effects in honeybees (Johnson *et al.*, 2010).

Previous work has demonstrated that the exposure of drones honeybee to miticides can result in decreased sperm viability (Johnson *et al.*, 2013) and has adverse effects on drone survival, drone weight, length and width of wings, and reduces the number of sperm production (Shoukry *et al.*, 2013). Excessive oxidative stress is the basis or result of many diseases including parasitosis (Halliwell, 2011). Subsequently, methods reducing the effects of oxidative stress can support the protective forces of an organism. Antioxidant levels and the activity of antioxidative enzymes, which prevent cell damage caused by oxidation, are important factors determining the good health of an organism (Mishra, 2007). One method for decreasing oxidative stress is administration of exogenous compounds with antioxidative characteristics as vitamin C (Ascorbic

acid) a natural antioxidant. The objective of this investigation was therefore to evaluate the effects of supplemental vitamin C in sugar syrup in early spring on body weight, sperm numbers in addition to biochemical parameters of honeybee drones .

Materials and methods

1. Field Work:

1.1. Supplemental feeding for colonies:

This study was conducted at the apiary of Plant Protection Research Institute, Agriculture Research Center. Experimental treatments began in early spring where six *A. mellifera* colonies with equivalent adult bee population headed by sister queens were used. Colonies were divided randomly into two experimental groups: Three receiving a sugar solution made up in the ratio of 1 kg sugar dissolved in 1 liter water (1:1) and supplemented with vitamin C at a rate of 1.8 mg per 1 kg syrup. The remaining three colonies received pure syrup as a control. Colonies were fed supplemental food weekly and each colony received 500 ml. Feeding began in early spring nearly 14 days prior the queens begin to lay eggs in drone cells and continued until the time that the experimental drone larvae had been capped.

1.2. Drones sampling:

Two days before drone's emergence, drone cells were held under protective cages that allowed the collection of emerged drones. Newly emerged drones were investigated for body weight and biochemical assay. Whereas, drones tested for sperms number remained in the colonies for sexual maturation.

2. Laboratory work:

2.1. Body weights:

Newly emerged drones from each group were individually weighed using an electrical balance.

2.2. Sperms number:

Drones remained in the colonies for about 21 days to allow full sexual maturation where, emerged drones were held in cages made with queen excluder material and placed into the hive allowing workers to enter and feed the drones (Collins, 2004). Drones of 21-days old, from each group, were chilled to prevent their ejaculation when dissected. The drones were dissected in 0.5% saline solution to remove the seminal vesicle. One seminal vesicle from each drone was placed in 10 ml 0.5% saline solution and punctured with a fine pair of needles. Sperms dispersed by the sucking and expelling action of a pipette. Sperm numbers were counted using a haemocytometer and light microscope (Rinderer *et al.*, 1985).

2.3. Biochemical assays:

Samples were homogenized in distilled water using a Teflon homogenizer surrounded with a jacket of crushed ice. The homogenates were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes at 5°C. The supernatants were immediately assayed to determine the following parameters: Total soluble protein and the activity of carbohydrate hydrolysing enzymes whereas, body homogenate used for total carbohydrates analysis.

2.4. Total soluble protein:

Colorimetric determination of total soluble protein in the supernatant of total homogenate was carried out as mentioned by Gornall *et al.* (1949).

2.5. Total carbohydrates:

Total carbohydrates were extracted from the body homogenate of drone's sample and prepared for assay according to Crompton and Birt (1967)

2.6. Carbohydrate hydrolysing enzymes:

The method used to determine the digestion of trehalose, starch and sucrose by trehalase, amylase and sucrase enzymes, respectively carried out the same method mentioned by Ishaaya and Swiriski (1976). The enzymatic activity was expressed as μg glucose released /g body weight/min.

3. Statistical analysis:

All collected data were statistically being analysed and the treatment means were compared using one-way test (ANOVA) by computer statistical COHORT SOFTWARE (2005). Probability value ($p \leq 0.05$) was considered significant.

Results and discussion

1. Body weights:

According to results, drones raised in colonies supplemented with vitamin C in spring weighed significantly more than drones in the control colonies (Table 1).

2. Sperms numbers:

High significant difference was observed between the spermatozoa numbers of drones reared in colonies receiving vitamin C and those reared in colonies fed no supplement ($P < 0.05$). Mean sperms number per one seminal vesicle of 5.25×10^6 was recorded for control group compared to 7.75×10^6 for vitamin C group (Table 1).

Table (1): Body weight and sperms number in one seminal vesicle of *Apis mellifera* drones supplemented with vitamin C.

Parameters Experimental Groups	Body weight (g) (Means \pm S.E.)	Sperms number ($\times 10^6$) (Means \pm S.E.)
Vitamin C group	0.2363 \pm 0.009 ^a	7.75 \pm 0.373 ^a
Control group	0.1819 \pm 0.005 ^b	5.25 \pm 0.167 ^b
P	0.0000 ***	0.0004 ***
LSD 0.05	0.01639	0.865

3. Biochemical assays:

3.1. Total soluble protein:

Data in Table (2) revealed significant higher protein content (33.24 ± 1.934 mg/gm. b. wt.) in supernatant of freshly emerged drones of the group receiving vitamin C in comparison to the control (27.42 ± 0.234 mg/gm. b. wt.).

3.2. Total carbohydrates:

An elevation in total carbohydrates content was recorded with vitamin C group compared to control ones. Such increase was statistically significant recorded (3.878 ± 0.024 mg glucose/gm. b. wt.) and (3.577 ± 0.076 mg glucose/gm. b. wt.) for vitamin c and control groups, respectively (Table 2).

Table (2): Effect of vitamin C on total soluble proteins (mg/g.b.wt.) and total carbohydrates (mg glucose/g.b.wt.) of *Apis mellifera* drones.

Parameters Experimental Groups	Total soluble proteins (mg/g.b.wt.)	Total carbohydrates (mg glucose/g.b.wt.)
Vitamin C group	$33.24^a \pm 1.934$	3.878 ± 0.024^a
Control group	$27.42^b \pm 0.234$	3.577 ± 0.076^b
P	0.0404*	0.0193*
LSD 0.05	5.408	0.220

3.3. Carbohydrate hydrolyzing enzymes:

The enrichment of bee diet with vitamin C induced insignificant

increase on the enzyme activity (Amylase, trehalase and sucrase) of newly emerged drones relative to the control group $p > 0.05$ (Figure 1).

Figure (1): Effect of vitamin C on amylase, trehalase and sucrase specific activity ($\mu\text{g glucose /g. b. wt./min}$) of *Apis mellifera* drones.

Based on previous literatures, it seems that vitamin C has antioxidative characteristics where, Farjan *et al.* (2012) found that colonies supplemented with vitamin C have

higher contents of antioxidative enzymes. Besides, its positive impact on brood rearing of honey bees and hypopharyngeal glands' development (Zahra and Talal, 2008). In addition,

vitamin C was used safely in the feeding sugar solution in honey bee colonies where, Harz *et al.* (2010) stated oral application of vitamin C has no lethal effect on *A. mellifera carnica* worker bees. Also, it constitutes a natural, safe and highly available dietary supplement for wintering and spring worker bees (Farjan *et al.*, 2012). Previous studies focused on studying the effect of supplemented feeding on workers' health and only few studies have examined their effects on drones specially vitamin C. Subsequently, the current work focused on improving honey bee drones health and quality where, sufficient rearing of healthy drones is the prime step for successful queen mating. Results showed that colonies supplemented with vitamin C significantly increased the weight of newly emerged drones in comparison to the control colonies. In the same context, body weight is one of the main indicators for determining the physiological state of honey bee. Larger drones are considered to have a competitive advantage over smaller ones when fighting for access to the queen during their mating flight (Couvillon *et al.*, 2010). In addition, body size might affect other traits as semen production where, bigger drones produce more sperms (Rousseau and Giovenazzo, 2016). This confirmed by the result in the current study where, drones reared in colonies receiving vitamin C had significantly higher spermatozoa numbers relative drones in control colonies. Thus, indicating that drones with a greater body weight produce more semen. Getting protein profiles can provide worth information about health, development and reproduction of an organism where, it can affect growth rate, body size and fecundity (Fagan *et al.*, 2002). In addition, the importance of body protein in honey bee, as storage body proteins affect wintering of honey bees

and life span (Otis *et al.*, 2004). Moreover, decrease in protein content is an important indicator for disturbance of physiological condition of an organism (Duay *et al.*, 2003). In the current experiment, a positive significant effect of vitamin C on body protein was detected in freshly emerged drones in comparison to control drones. Vitamin C is needed for protein synthesis as it is entering into the fat body, haemolymph and intestinal cells initiates the protein elevations depending upon the insect tissue (Sathesh and Kerenhap, 2016). Previous studies of worker bees showed an increase in the brood area, colony population, body weight and protein in colonies supplemented with vitamin C to spring nutrition (Andi and Ahmadi, 2014).

Carbohydrates are the main source of energy for bees where, the diet of honey bee is very rich in carbohydrates (Brodtschneider and Crailsheim, 2010). Saccharides are the major source of energy needed for pupation, and monosaccharides are involved in the synthesis of new carbohydrates such as chitin (Draczynski, 2008). And according to Kunieda *et al.* (2006) honey bee genome contains 174 genes responsible for carbohydrate metabolism, but only 28 genes responsible for lipid metabolism. In this study, vitamin C induced a significant increase of carbohydrates content of newly emerged drones. This finding is consistent with the results reported by Farjan *et al.* (2015) who recorded an increase in carbohydrates content in newly emerged workers supplemented with vitamin C where they attributed such increase to the reduction in the activity levels of α -glycosidases (Enzymes decomposing carbohydrates) in the last pupal stage which generated suitable conditions for the accumulation of carbohydrates in emerging honey

bees. This also confirmed by Żółtowska *et al.* (2012) the activity of α -glycosidases in developing drone brood of *A. mellifera carnica*. was negatively correlated with sugar levels. In the same context, insects become active immediately after hatching and reserved carbohydrates are the main source of energy till newly emerged bees begin to feed (Winston, 1987).

Generally, honeybee get carbohydrates from nectar or honey. Enzymes as sucrase and glycosidases break nectar sugars into glucose and fructose where, they used directly or transformed into fat body and glycogen. Trehalase is the enzyme that catalyzes the hydrolysis of disaccharide trehalose into two glucose molecules for internal supply for chitin synthesis, muscular activity during flight and other metabolic process (Rajitha and Savithri, 2014). Bee also gain carbohydrates from pollen in small amount and hydrolyses of starch contained in pollen into glucose depend mainly on amylase enzyme. Therefore, the energetic metabolism is based generally on carbohydrates. Studies of carbohydrate hydrolysing enzymes revealed that Ascorbic acid induced a minor increase in trehalase, amylase and sucrase activities in newly emerged drones but such increase was insignificant. The above observations indicate that supplement vitamin C can promote carbohydrate degradation in the enzymatic system of bees (Ohashi *et al.*, 1999).

The current study demonstrates that drones emerged in honey bee colonies feeding in spring with sucrose syrup supplemented with vitamin C were characterized by significantly higher body weights, sperm number, protein and carbohydrates contents which indicates that they were better health than control group which in turn plays an important role in colony health.

The present results suggest the importance of adding an antioxidant agent as vitamin C to spring nutrition for drone rearing in honey bee colonies that can improve their quality and reproductive health which in turn essential for colony build up. The diet supplemented with vitamin C positively enhanced drones body weight, spermatozoa number, total soluble protein and carbohydrate content in addition to its minor effect on the activity of carbohydrate hydrolysis enzymes. Consequently, vitamin C can be used as a natural, safe, and relatively cheap diet supplement that can enhance resistance to stress factors including exposure to elevated temperature, diseases and miticides.

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Impact of using pollen substitute on honeybee *Apis mellifera* (Hymenoptera: Apidae) colonies in Egypt

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Pollen substitute, brood areas, queen rearing and honey yield.

This study was conducted in the apiary at Bassiun City, Gharbia Governorate during the banana blooming season from 1st August 2019 to 10th October 2019 to find out the effects of using a pollen substitute to honeybee *Apis mellifera* L. (Hymenoptera: Apidae) colonies. Also, honeybee colonies which fed on pollen substitutes could produce more sealed brood area and more honey yield at the end of the blooming season. So, the utility of pollen substitutes during the banana flowering period is recommended for honeybee colonies and higher brood, bee population per colony, production of royal jelly, the queen rearing, the weight of virgin queens, stored pollen and honey production.

Introduction

Honeybee *Apis mellifera* L. (Hymenoptera: Apidae) use nectar and pollen of different flowering plants and the availability of flowering plants is very essential for honeybee to become colony strength (Shawer *et al.*, 2019). Pollen is considered as the essential source of amino acids, lipids, vitamins, and essential minerals in the nutrition of the honeybee colonies and the development of honeybee require these nutritive elements which ingested with nectar and water for their growth. One colony of honeybee require approximately 18 kg of pollen yearly to supply them with protein (Crailsheim *et al.*, 1992). The young honeybees feed on stored pollen grains, which were influenced by some microbes and this means bee bread. The honeybee workers need a large amount of pollen

for protein within the first six day of adulthood, which will encourage their full development.

Many biological activities of honeybees are increased by feeding on a protein source, particularly during the shortage times because it stimulates the different glands in charge of secretion of larval foods (Barker, 1971). Also, the incomplete amount of protein in the bee diet is a big problem, during the hypopharyngeal glands development (Funari *et al.*, 2003). Consequently, the reproduction and production of the honeybee colonies are influenced (Pereira *et al.*, 2006). Also, Haydak (1949) showed that the ability of brood-rearing of the honeybees without the pollen is mostly impaired because the different glands responsible for producing the food by nurse honeybees keep non-functional and undeveloped.

When the weather circumstances are inappropriate for the honeybee colonies and during the dearth period. During that time, the colony needs a pollen substitute, which means change the use of pollen by other substitutes. The most famous substitution contains the mix of soybean flour, brewer's yeast, and corn flour (House, 1961; Feng, 2002 and Saffari *et al.*, 2004). Feeding plays an essential role in defense against different pathogens and in preserving the gut fitness of honeybee colonies (Ritz and Gardner, 2006). The main agents affecting the feeding and its acceptable of pollen substitutes contain the level of lipids and protein (De Groot, 1953 and Schmidt *et al.*, 1987). The pollen substitutes help the honeybee colonies in preserving them with the appropriate total brood area (Imdrof *et al.*, 1988; Awad, 1998 and Mohammad, 2002). The Pollen trapping has some impacts on the colonies of the honeybee. Such as, the activities of foraging of pollen trapped bee colonies was declined over a period, although the proportion of forager return rate which gathering the pollen grains did not influence (Duff and Furgala, 1986). McLellan (1974) and Cook (1985) indicated the pollen trapping did not change brood area, while Nelson *et al.*, (1987) found a slight impact on the sealed brood area, and in Alberta, Canada, they indicated that trapping pollen decreased the total honey yield with 11 to 31%.

The chance of enhancing the beekeeping performance by adding protein source in pollen substitute to feed the honeybee colonies especially when pollen is rare (Zahra and Talal, 2008), particularly for the early blooming season (Skubida *et al.*, 2008) and they showed that adding a source of protein to encourage the strength of honeybee colony and assist, enlarge honey yield. Also, the abundance of pollen enhances the development of

glands which responsible for larval food production and it can produce enough amount of royal jelly which required for rearing of queen larvae (Svoboda *et al.*, 1986).

This aims of study was to estimate the effectiveness of pollen substitute in boosting brood rearing areas, bee numbers per colony, production of royal jelly, the queen rearing, the weight of virgin queens, honey production and stored pollen.

Materials and methods

This work was done at Bassiun City, Gharbia Governorate, (1813 feddan), through the banana blooming season during the period from 1st August 2019 to 10th October 2019 to study the impacts of using pollen substitute to honeybee colonies.

1. Activities of honeybee colonies:

Sixteen of honeybee colonies, roughly same-strength and each contained 10,000 individuals and open mated sister queens (*A.mellifera carnica*) and they were used in this investigation to study the effect of pollen substitutes in banana flowers season as an assistant factor for honeybees during the dearth period in Egypt. Colonies were divided into two equal groups. Group 1 fed on a diet of 120g brewer yeast paste (70g dry yeast + 50g honey) per colony. Group 2 did not receive any pollen substitutes (control). The diet was placed in waxed paper to prevent moisture loss and put directly over the brood nest placed. The area (inch²) of stored pollen and worker sealed brood were measured at 12 days intervals using an empty standard frame divided into square inches. By the end of the season, the number of combs covered with bees/colony was recorded to determine the colony population. And the population size per colony was counted as one well-covered comb of about 2000 bees on both sides (Taha, 2005). By the end of the flow season, the honey yield was estimated by the

difference between the weight of honeycombs before and after extraction. The number of incoming bees/min, number of pollen foragers/min was counted on the peak hours flying weekly during the period from 15th August until 2nd of October.

2. Queen rearing and royal jelly production:

Doolittle (1909) method was used for queen rearing. The experiment of queen rearing was done by using queenless rearing colonies for queen rearing and royal jelly production through the flowering period of banana during September. Eight colonies were divided into two equal groups, group 1 fed on previous pollen substitute while group 2 did not receive any pollen substitutes (Control). Every colony was provided with 30 wax cups and grafted with 24 hours-old larvae for queen rearing and 45 wax cups for royal jelly production. After three days, royal jelly was collected and weighted (mg). Repined queen cells were taken to emergence cages until the new queens were emerged and then weighted (mg).

3. Statistical analyses:

SPSS software (SPSS, 2006) was used to analyze the data and the statistical differences between the two treatments were determined by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Results and discussion

One of the essential nurturant materials of honeybee colonies is pollen substitute for many causes, maintain continued honeybee colony growth in times and places of a scarcity of nectar and pollen grains, to protect colonies with best numbers in the time of nectar flows, make honeybee colonies to high numbers for production of package-bee, and supply sufficient food reservoir for overwintering honeybee colonies.

The results this study showed that the effect of the use of the pollen substitutes on the brood rearing area, the stored pollen grains and the bee

numbers per colony as shown in Table (1). There was a statistically significant difference among treatments on the brood rearing activity as determined by one-way ANOVA ($F(1, 54) = 42.43, p \leq 0.001$). Also, the differences between the two treatments in bee numbers per colony were statistically significant ($F(1, 54) = 8.70, p \leq 0.005$). The brood-rearing in honeybee without the protein source (pollen) is mostly declined because the glands which are responsible for food production by nurse honeybees become undeveloped and non-functional (Haydak, 1949) so, the brood-rearing and bee numbers per colony increased with pollen substitutes treatment. And there were statistically significant differences in the stored pollen grains between the two tested groups as determined by one-way ANOVA ($F(1, 54) = 42.17, p \leq 0.001$).

The data in Table (2) showed that the colonies which fed on the pollen substitutes could produce significantly more honey yield compared with control as determined by one-way ANOVA ($F(1, 6) = 59.87, p \leq 0.001$). The honeybee colonies which consumed the greater amount of pollen substitutes could produce more of brood area and more bee numbers per colony resulted in significantly more honey yield. So that stronger honeybee colony store more honey yield compared with the weak one (Chhuneja *et al.*, 1992 and Kumar *et al.*, 1995).

The data in Table (3) showed that the impact of using pollen substitute on royal jelly production and there was a statistically significant difference in royal jelly production between the two tested treatments as determined by one-way ANOVA ($F(1, 22) = 9.93, p \leq 0.005$). Also, the results in Table (4) indicated that there was a statistically significant difference in percentage of accepted larvae between groups as determined by one-way ANOVA ($F(1, 4) = 30.25, p \leq 0.005$).

Also, there was a statistically significant difference in the weight of virgin queens between treatments as indicated by one-way ANOVA ($F(1, 22) = 17.17, p \leq 0.001$). The queen acceptance depends on some factors such as weather factors, particularly the temperature, humidity and length of daytime. Also, the food quality and

availability are very essential for honeybee hives, such as the plenty of pollen increases the growth of larval food production glands and can produce an appropriate amount of royal jelly which required for producing queen larvae of good bodies (Svoboda *et al.*, 1986).

Table (1): The impact of pollen substitute on some biological activities of honeybee colonies.

Day	1st August		13th August		25th August		5th September		17th September		29th September		11th October	
	D.	C.	D.	C.	D.	C.	D.	C.	D.	C.	D.	C.	D.	C.
Worker sealed brood	592.50 ±1.18	595.00 ± 21.01	608.75 ± 14.19	625.00 ±26.29	662.50 ±17.50	607.50 ±26.88	665.00 ± 15.54	540.00 ±24.83	715.00 ±11.90	550.00 ±26.45	717.50 ±6.29	532.50 ± 26.88	670.00 ±12.24	508.75 ±28.01
Stored pollen area	93.75 ± 2.39	96.25 ± 4.54	101.25 ± 3.14	95.00 ± 6.45	110.00 ± 7.07	88.75 ± 4.88	127.50 ± 11.08	95.00 ± 6.45	152.50 ±8.53	80.00 ± 4.08	140.00 ±9.12	76.25 ± 8.50	115.00 ±6.45	70.00 ± 4.08
No. honey bee /colony	9550.00 ± 210.15	9750.00 ± 478.71	10375.00 ± 554.33	10175.00 ± 283.94	11000.00 ± 408.24	11125.00 ± 426.95	12500.00 ± 500.00	11875.00 ± 657.84	13125.00 ± 314.57	11625.00 ± 375.00	14750.00 ± 478.71	11500.00 ± 353.55	15750.00 ± 478.71	11125.00 ± 426.95

C. Control D. Diet

Table (2): The influence of using pollen substitute to honeybee colonies on honey production.

Parameters	Honey yield (banana season)	
	Diet	Control
1 st September	115.00 ± 13.22	95.00 ± 6.45
15 th September	242.50 ± 24.62	150.00 ± 17.79
30 th September	400.00 ± 20.41	255.00 ± 21.01
Before extract	550.00 ± 20.41	362.50 ± 23.93
Kg.	4.82 ± 0.11	3.00 ± 0.20

Table (3) : The impact of using pollen substitute to honeybee colonies on royal jelly production.

Parameters	1 st September		15 th September		30 th September	
	Diet	Control	Diet	Control	Diet	Control
Number of queen cells	45	45	45	45	45	45
Percentage accepted larvae %	73%	68%	78%	66%	75%	67%
The weight of royal jelly (mg)/cup ± SE	109.25 ± 3.25	105.00 ± 4.56	117.50 ± 1.04	108.75 ± 3.14	118.25 ± 1.18	106.75 ± 3025

Table (4): The influence of using pollen substitute on queen rearing.

Parameters	1 st September		15 th September		30 th September	
	Diet	Control	Diet	Control	Diet	Control
Number of queen cells	30	30	30	30	30	30
Percentage accepted larvae %	73%	66%	76%	63%	73%	60%
The weight of virgin queens (mg)± SE	167.50± 3.22	161.25± 1.25	172.50± 3.22	165.00± 2.04	176.25± 2.39	162.50± 2.50

The data in Table (5) showed the effect of using pollen on the flight activities of bee workers and there was a statistically significant difference in the numbers of incoming bee between the treatments as determined by one-way ANOVA ($F(1,14) = 16.38, p = .001$). Also, by using one-way ANOVA, there was a significant difference in the numbers of pollen foragers between the tested treatments ($F(1,14) = 94.01, p = .00$). The colonies which fed on pollen

substitutes produced more of brood rearing area resulted in more bee numbers per hive and resulted in significant numbers of incoming bee per minute and significant numbers of pollen foragers per minute. The foraging activity is influenced by brood rearing activity and honeybee colony strength (Abou-Shaara *et al.*, 2013), and the abundance of pollen (Weidenmuller and Tautz, 2002).

Table (5) : The effect of using pollen substitute on the flight activity of honeybee.

Date	Numbers of incoming bee/min± SE		Numbers of pollen foragers/min± SE	
	Pollen substitute	Control	Pollen substitute	Control
15 th August	89.12±2.55	84.50±2.09	29.25±1.22	26.50±1.19
22 nd August	87.87±2.27	82.00±1.47	30.00±1.56	25.87±1.38
29 th August	88.75±1.61	81.00±2.59	31.37±1.32	26.62±1.19
6 th September	90.75±2.31	85.37±2.34	32.00±1.28	26.00±1.43
13 rd September	95.37±3.35	87.75±2.29	33.00±1.03	26.12±1.35
20 th September	98.55±3.65	90.12±2.08	33.50±1.13	25.62±1.65
27 th September	98.87±3.33	86.87±1.66	34.12±1.18	25.62±1.55
2 nd October	96.37±3.97	85.87±1.52	32.75±1.16	25.25±1.41

The results of this study showed that the use of pollen substitutes could increase colonies strength with higher brood production, bee numbers per colony, royal jelly production, the queen rearing, the weight of virgin queens, honey production and stored pollen.

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Assessment of pesticide residues in honey and their prospective risk to consumers in
Egypt

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Honeybees, pesticides residues, QuEChERS and estimated daily intake

Honeybees, *Apis mellifera* L. (Hymenoptera: Apidae) is one of the most important tasks of pollinating agricultural crops. The aim of this study is to detect of the pesticides remain in honeybee samples gathered from Egypt and compare the obtained results to the published Maximum Residue Limits (MRL's) values. Fifty honey samples were randomly gathered from local marketplaces of five Governorates viz: (Cairo, Giza, Qalyubia, Alexandria and Gharbia) in Egypt during 2020. The current study was performed to assess the residues levels of 38 pesticides in the major groups of pesticides (organophosphorus, organochlorine and Synthetic Pyrethroids) representative, using method based on the QuEChERS. The recovery results found ranged from 80% to 104 %. The results indicated that, total contamination with pesticides residues was 24%, dominant pesticides that were in the samples belonged to the organochlorine and organophosphorus groups. There are no demonstrable residues of synthetic pyrethroids pesticides in all gathered samples. All samples of honey are matched to MRLs. Data showed that, exposing to these pesticides in highly connected with evaluating the potential health risks. The acceptable daily intakes of the pesticide (ADIs) were so higher than estimated daily intake (EDI), which prove that consume honey has the lowest toxicological risk. This study confirms the need for recurrently monitoring scheme for pesticide residues in honey at the national concentration to protect the health of consume.

Introduction

Honey is one of the natural sweeties, as honeybees produced it from the blossom nectar. Honeybees, *Apis mellifera* L. (Hymenoptera: Apidae), perform the essential task of pollinating agricultural crops and native

species and are important to produce of honey and beeswax. 10,000–25,000 honeybee workers carry out about 10 trips daily to see the sights of about seven km² in the region around their hive, to collect nectar, water, and pollen from blooms. Throughout this trip, a lot

of microorganisms, chemical materials, and particles, hanging in the air, are captured by these workers and kept in their body surface hair, or respired and detained to their trachea (Hassan *et al.* , 2015). Thus, these easy to breed, almost omnipresent organisms, with simple food requirements, are highly sensitive to many factors that are physical, biological, and chemical, for instance fleas, industrial polluting materials, or insecticides and may be employed as one of the bio indicators to control the environmental stress (Celli and Maccagnani , 2003).

Honey is one of the natural sweet materials, that is created by honeybee. Regarding to its constant use, it may be polluted by pesticide remains. Nearly, no studies have dealt with pesticide remains in honey, estimated the risks, or argued their expected reproductive poisoning (El-Nahhal, 2020). Currently, with growing awareness of consumers over pesticide materials in food and the effect of crop safety practices on the environment, pesticide residues in agricultural crops should not cause a real health threat. Since the beginning of 1950s, organochlorine pesticides were used broadly in Egypt . Nevertheless, their use was legally forbidden since 1980. These compounds are characterized by stability, deep absorbance on sediments and land, so their residues may still occur in certain foods such as honey.

Organophosphorus compounds that have small perseverance and were readily decaying and used broadly nowadays for insect control all over the country as well as synthetic pyrethroid compounds which were used in cotton crop only. (Anonymous,1995). The existence of pesticide remains in honey revealed the necessity of creating control programs to evaluate properly the human exposure to pesticides and the possibility of taking policy decisions to avoid health hazards

(Wallner, 1999). Accordingly, the aim of this study is to detect of the organochlorine, organophosphorus and synthetic pyrethroid pesticide remains in honeybee samples gathered from Egypt in 2020 and compare the obtained results to the published Maximum Residue Limits (MRL's) values

Materials and methods

1. Samples:

Fifty honey samples were randomly gathered from local markets of five governorates viz: (Cairo, Giza, Qalyubia, Alexandria and Gharbia) in Egypt in 2020. Samples were titled according to the name of Governorate then transmitted immediately to the laboratory

2. Pesticides detection:

The samples were analysed to identify and quantify of 38 pesticides. The organophosphorus residues include: Azinphos-ethyl, chlorpyrifos, chlorpyrifos-methyl, cadusafos, diazinon, dichlorovs, disulfoton, cyanophos, ethion, ethoprophos, phorate, phenthoate, pirimiphos-ethyl, pirimiphos-methyl, profenofos, prothiofos, fenitrothion, fenamiphos, methamidophos, and triazophos. The organochlorine insecticides include: alpha-HCH, beta-HCH , gama-HCH , heptachlor , heptachlor-epoxide , aldrin , dieldrin , p,p-DDE , endrin , o,p-DDT , p,p-DDD , p,p-DDT. artificial Pyrethroids contained fenpropathrin, permethrin, lambda-Cyhalothrin, cypermethrin, fenvalerate, and deltamethrin.

3. Pesticides analysis:

The samples were mingled, (10 g) of each was put into 50 mL polyethylene tube. Extraction and cleaning up were instantly done after sampling using QuEChERS method (Anastassiades *et al.*, 2003 and Eissa *et al.*, 2014) . Acetonitrile (15 mL) was put in all tubes. The samples were well blended using a vortex mixer at the

utmost speed. Thereafter, 6 g of anhydrous magnesium sulfate and 1.5 g of sodium chloride were put, afterward extract by mingling strongly on vortex for 5 min and centrifuged for 10 min at 4,000 rpm. A portion of 4 mL was withdrawn from the supernatant to a new clean 15 mL centrifuge tube containing 100 mg PSA and 600 mg anhydrous magnesium sulfate. Once again, the samples were vortexed for 3 min, afterwards, centrifuged for 10 min at 4,000 rpm.

4. Gas chromatographic analysis:

Gas chromatography (GC) Hewlett Packard (HP) serial 6890 prepared with various detectors, i.e., electron capture (ECD) and flame photometry (FPD) were used. The pesticides analysis was carried out on two capillary columns, i.e., HP-5 (5%-Phenylmethylpolysiloxane) and DB-35 (35%-Phenyl-methylpolysiloxane).

The dimensions of each column were 30 m length x 0.25 mm internal diameter and covered with 0.25 µm film thickness of the still phase. Nitrogen was employed as a carrier gas at a flux rate of 1ml/min. The injector and interface temperatures were 250°C and 300°C, respectively. The GC temperature program was as follows; preliminary temperature was 100°C for 1min, increased at speed of 25°C/min to 170°C, isothermal for 1 min, increased at a speed of 3°C/min to 230°C, then isothermal for 1 min, finally increased at a rate of 8°C /min to 300°C, then isothermal for 5 min

5. Quality assurance procedure:

The Codex quality guarantee standards (Codex, 1993) were applied to establish the performance of the multiresidue technique. Recoveries and

limits of quantification (LOQ) were applied on samples at rising levels 0.01–0.05 mg/ kg from the pesticide blend standard. The average of recoveries ranged between 80% and 104 %, and limits of quantification between 0.001 and 0.043 mg/ kg. The analyses outcome was not adjusted for recoveries. Blank samples were supplemented with the pesticide mixture and analyzed as a normal sample with each set of samples. The results were recorded on control charts. Repetitive analysis of old models was frequently performed to control reproducibility.

Results and discussion

This study throw light upon the disparity between the pesticides concentrations in honey samples from various places. The greatest inclination for accumulation of pesticides was in heather honeys. The results of pesticides analysis in 50 samples are shown in Table (1) . Residues of 4 active compounds were found in 12 samples of bee honey. The most frequent residues identified were chloropyrifos (in 16% of samples), p,p-DDE (4%) and cadusafos, heptachlor-epoxide (2%). All collected honeybee samples (i.e. 50) were free from any detectable residues of synthetic pyrethroids pesticides. Total pollution with pesticides residues was 24%. All samples of honeybee under MRLs. Organophosphorus pesticides resiuces recorded highest frequencies of residues (75%), followed by organochlorine pesticides (25%). The highest contamination of pesticides was found in Cairo and Alexandria 25% followed by Giza, Qalyubia and Gharbia recording 16.66.

Table(1): Minimum, maximum, mean, frequency, contamination and violation of pesticides residues monitored in 50 samples of honeybee.

Governorate	Total no. of sample	Pesticides Found	Frequency No.	Range: Minimum-maximum (mean) (mg/kg)	Contaminated Samples No. %.	MRLs* (mg/kg)	Isolated Samples No. %
Cairo	10	p,p-DDE	1	0.004-0.004(0.004)	3 30	0.01	0 0
		Chloropyrifos	2	0.004-0.01(0.007)		0.05	0 0
Giza	10	Cadusafos	1	0.001-0.001(0.001)	2 20	0.02	0 0
		Chloropyrifos	1	0.002-0.002(0.002)		0.05	0 0
Qalyubia	10	p,p-DDE	1	0.003-0.003(0.003)	2 20	0.01	0 0
		Heptachlor-epoxide	1	0.003-0.003(0.003)		0.01	0 0
Alexandria	10	Chloropyrifos	3	0.005-0.02(0.002)	3 30	0.05	0 0
Gharbia	10	Chloropyrifos	2	0.005-0.05(0.005)	2 20	0.05	0 0
Total	50				12 24		0 0

These findings agree with those obtained by (Chauzat and Faucon, 2007) who monitored the quality of bee colonies (*A. mellifera*). Over 2 years, Beeswax samples were gathered once a year from 125 honey bee colonies totally. Multi remains analyses were carried out for these samples to identifying of 16 insecticides and acaricides and also two fungicides residues. Fourteen of studied compounds were found in samples. The most often detected remains were taufluvinate, coumaphos and endosulfan (61.9, 52.2 and 23.4% of samples respectively). Coumaphos was found in the highest value (792.6 μgkg^{-1}). Remains of cypermethrin, lindane and deltamethrin were found in 21.9, 4.3 and 2.4% of samples respectively According to the Statistical analysis, there is no difference among years of sampling, except for the rate of recurrence of pyrethroid remains. Both in-hive acaricide handlings and, to a lesser extent, ecological pollution are the reason behind Beeswax contamination. Also, one study estimated organochlorine pesticides remains in 178 samples of Polish honey using gas chromatography and found that the pesticide remains differentiated from trace concentrations to 60 $\mu\text{g/kg}$. Aldrin (l.o.d and 14,27 $\mu\text{g/kg}$), Endrin (trace and 65,3 $\mu\text{g/kg}$), dieldrin (l.o.d

and 5,93 $\mu\text{g/kg}$), o,p-DDT (Trace and 18,66 $\mu\text{g/kg}$), p,p-DDT (trace and 227,85 $\mu\text{g/kg}$), HCH (trace and 284,96 $\mu\text{g/kg}$), o,p methoxychlor (trace and 7,12 $\mu\text{g/kg}$) and p,p methoxychlor (trace and 38,67 $\mu\text{g/kg}$) residues were found in 38, 13, 32, 34, 108, 113, 17, 51 of honey samples, respectively (Wilczynska and Przybylowski, 2007). Choudhary and Sharma (2008) found that the HCH and its isomers were the most frequently found among various pesticides examined in honey followed by DDT and its isomers in various parts of Himachal Pradesh. Only cypermethrin was detected in honey samples in the studied synthetic pyrethroids. The remains that were not found are organophosphates viz. acephate, chlorpyrifos, ethion and monocrotophos; nevertheless Furthermore, honey from natural vegetation included lesser remains. Yavuz *et al.* (2010) gathered 109 different honey samples from shops and open markets in Konya, Turkey and determined of 24 organochlorine pesticide remains by gas chromatography-electron capture detection and observed that, Aldrin, *cis*-chlordane, *trans*-chlordane, *oxy*-chlordane, 2,4'-DDE, and 4,4'-DDE were found in all honey samples. *oxy*-chlordane (0.0540 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) was found in 55 samples. The

resulted levels of organochlorine pesticide remain of *oxy*-chlordane were decides to be higher than those of Turkish Alimentarius Codex maximum residual limits (MRLs), excepting *cis*-heptachlor epoxide and α -hexachlorocyclohexane. It is necessary for consumer health to control organochlorine pesticide residues in honey, as all of the honey specimens are contaminated found and most of these samples exceeded MRLs. Bargan_ska *et al.* (2013) studied the levels of 30 insecticides remains in honey samples gathered from apiaries in northern part of Poland using method based on the QuEChERS extraction then, by fluid chromatography cycle mass spectrometry with electron spray ionization (LC-ESI-MS/MS). The percentage of positive samples is 29% for some of the target compounds. The compounds exceeded maximum residue standards are bifenthrin, fenpyroximate, methidathion, spinosad, thiamethoxam, and triazophos (MRL) in five samples (11%), the kind of the remains that associated with agricultural practices in the region. The maximum values of these pesticides were 14.5, 16.3, 25.7, 20.6, 20.2 and 20.3 ng/g, respectively. The most dominant pesticide was Profenofos, as it ranged from <LOQ to 17.2 ng/g.

1. Dietary intake evaluation and hazard specification:

To estimate the toxicological importance of human exposure to the pesticide remains in honey, it is necessary to compare acceptable daily intakes (ADI) established by the FAO/WHO organization with the estimated daily intake (EDI). The comparison between EDI and the acceptable daily intake (ADI), proved that the daily dosage of a chemical which, during the entire lifetime, appears to be without appreciable risk on the basis of all the facts known at the time (FAO, 1965). The integration of

pesticide residue analysis data and food consumption assumptions is the basis of health risk assessment, which seeks to reflect the actual residue concentrations in food taken by the common people, with a weight of 60 kg. The source of food consuming data was WHO/Global Environment Monitoring System-Food Contamination Monitoring and assessment program average consumption cluster B diets (WHO/GEMS/FOODS, 2006). EDI was calculated using obtained findings and expressed as microgram pesticides per kilogram body weight per day ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg b.w}/\text{day}$). The EDI is the actual evaluation of exposing to pesticide that was evaluated for each one of the pesticides on honey in accordance with the international guiding principles (WHO, 1997 and FAO, 2002), applying this equation:
$$\text{EDI} = \frac{\sum C \times F}{D \times W}$$

Where C : The mean of pesticide residues concentration in honey ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$), F : mean annual intake of honey per person (2 kg per person approximately), D i: Number of days in a year (365), and W : Mean body weight (60 kg). As shown in Table (2), the ADIs were higher than the estimated daily intakes of detected pesticides, which proves that honey intake has a very low toxicological risk. These results match that those obtained by Blasco *et al.* (2003). So, in case the danger of a pesticide remains is not over unity, the user is sufficiently protected. Accordingly, the hazard index values show that all the intakes of pesticide remain undoubtedly are safe. Subsequently, data obtained from Eissa *et al.* (2014) were used for evaluating the expected health risks that could result from exposure to these insecticides. The acceptable daily intakes (ADIs) were higher than Estimated daily intake (EDI) of the observed pesticides. This finding

proves that honey intake has a very low toxicological risk.

Table (2): Estimated daily intakes (EDIs) and ADIs of pesticide remains in honey.

Pesticide	ADI* (mg/kg body weight/day)	EDI (µg/kg body weight/day)	Hazard index (EDI/ADI, %)	Health risk
p,p-DDE	0.05	6.33 e-6	0.006	No
Chloropyrifos	0.01	5.02 e-5	0.05	No
Cadusafos	0.01	1.29 e-6	0.001	No
Heptachlor-epoxide	0.01	1.01e-6	0.0009	No

*Established by Codex Alimentarius Commission on Pesticide Residues, JMPR (Joint FAO/WHO Meeting on Pesticide Residues), EPA (Environmental Protection Agency) and EFSA (European Food Safety Authority).

This study confirms the necessity of repeated monitoring programs for pesticide remains in honey at the national level to care for user health. Also, this study highlights the fact that dietary pesticide amount calculated related only to honey exposures and excludes other food products such as grains, vegetables, fruits, dairy, fish, and meats. Accordingly, assessments do not relate to total dietary exposition to the pesticides, nor to drinking water, inhabited, or professional exposures.

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Chemical quality parameters of three oilseeds influenced by both insect infestation and fumigation with phosphine in storage

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Abstract:

The purpose of the present study is to investigate the changes which occur for certain chemical quality parameters such as weight loss (WL), peroxide value (PV), free fatty acids (FFA) and protein content of some oilseeds affected by whether when their insect infestation in storage or its fumigation by phosphine gas. The results clearly showed that there was increase in WL and number of adult emergences with increasing of storage period. Also, results noticed that infested peanut seeds by *Ephestia cautella* (Walker) (Lepidoptera: Phycitidae) have higher PV, FFA and lower protein content, whilst, fumigated peanut seeds only significant higher protein content, but, did not induce any changes in PV and FFA. So, consider insect infestation had deleterious effect on the seeds and that phosphine fit as fumigant for peanut seeds as a result PV below the limit in the Codex standard of 10 mEqO₂ kg⁻¹ oil. Oppositely, sesame seeds, the results showed that fumigated and infested sesame seeds by *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* (L.) (Coleoptera: Silvanidae) have only significant higher PV and lower FFA and protein content which are consider indicator on quality deterioration of sesame seeds and phosphine unfit as fumigant for sesame seeds as a result PV higher of the limit in the Codex standard of 10 mEqO₂ kg⁻¹ oil. Also, fumigated and infested maize grains by *Rhyzopertha dominica* (F.) (Coleoptera: Bostrichidae), did not affect approximately all tested parameters with except protein content which significant increase in fumigated grains about infested and un-infested grains. So, phosphine fit as fumigant for maize grains.

Introduction

Oilseed crops are grown for their seeds purpose. Oilseeds are leading suppliers of superior quality and that of oilseeds add important nutritional value to the human diet due to high quality protein, vegetable oil (linoleic acid and oleic acid, Omega-6 fatty acids and Omega-3 fatty acids)

and vitamin E (Quamruzzaman *et al.* , 2016). Oilseeds are considered the major sources for extracting edible oils and for applications in pharmaceutical, confectionary, perfumery and cosmetics industries. Of these oilseeds, Peanut, sesame, sunflower, maize, cotton, sunflower, rapeseed and olive are most oil crops cultivated in Egypt

and their oils are the most common healthy cooking oils used. The oil content of cereal grains as wheat is only 1- 2 % and that of oilseeds ranges from about 20 % for soybean to over 40 % for sunflowers and rapeseed (Canola) (Weiss, 2000). The quality of the vegetable oils is one of the most important factors that affect their acceptability and market value (O'Brien, 2004). Vegetable oils are recommended for healthy life because their high content of polyunsaturated fatty acids which decreases the risk of cardiovascular diseases (Ganesan *et al.*, 2018). The quality of oilseeds depends on many factors, particularly chemical deterioration which occurs during its exposure either to different insect infestations in storage or its treatment by inadequate approaches. Chemical properties such as acidity value, free-fatty acids value, peroxide value and vitamin E used to measuring biochemical deterioration and the stability of oils (Mousavi *et al.*, 2012 and Mbata, 1994). Oilseeds are rich in proteins and therefore are vulnerable to infestation by many stored products insects in storage. Of these insects, *Ephestia cautella* (Walker) (Lepidoptera: Phycitidae), *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* (L.) (Coleoptera: Silvanidae) and *Rhyzopertha dominica* (F.) (Coleoptera: Bostrichidae), resulting in weight loss and deterioration in oil quality and formation of toxins. The almond moth, *E. cautella* is one of the most important pests infesting stored peanut, grain, nuts, dried fruits and other many stored products (Boshra, 2007). The economic losses by this pest are due to reductions in quantity and quality of stored products (Hussain and Jafar, 1968). Saw-toothed grain beetle, *O. surinamensis* is one of the most common insect pests of grains and a variety of different stored products such as dried fruits ,oilseeds and has been found in all storage facilities (Beckel *et*

al., 2007). They are two secondary pests in stored grain due to its inability to damage the whole grains. The lesser grain borer, *R. dominica* is a destructive insect pest of stored grains (Mayhew and Phillips, 1994). Both larvae and adults of this insect use their strong mandibles to attack whole, sound grains and cause extensive damage (Williams *et al.*, 1981). The adults chew grains voraciously which not only causes weight loss but also reduces grains germination (Jilani *et al.*, 1989). The purpose of the present study is to determine both effects of insect infestation and their control with phosphine gas on peroxide value (PV), free-fatty acids content (FFA) which are indices in measuring the oil quality in addition to protein content.

Materials and methods

1. Insect cultures:

The stocks of *O. surinamensis* used in these experiments were obtained from a stock culture maintained at the Stored Grain and Product Pests Department, Plant Protection Research Institute. It was reared on whole wheat flour for two months at $30 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 65 ± 5 R.H. in continuous darkness. *R. dominica* was reared on sound maize grains under the same previous conditions. *E. cautella* was reared on peanut for two generations at $28 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 70 ± 5 RH.

2. Used oilseeds crops:

Peanut seeds (*Arachis hypogea*), sesame seeds, (*Sesamu indicum*) and maize grains (*Zea mays*) are most oilseeds crops cultivated in Egypt.

3. Experiments procedures:

3.1. Determination oilseeds damage induce with different insects infestation for four months storage periods:

Hundred grams of each type were put in glass jars (Ca: 0.5 L. each), ten pairs of *O. surinamensis* and *R. dominica* adults (15 days old) were

introduced separately in jars containing sesame seeds and maize grains, respectively. Peanut seeds infested by three pairs of *E. cautella* moths (0-24 h. old). Jars were left in the laboratory into incubator for two and four months ($30 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 65 ± 5 RH.) for all previously mentioned insect species. The previous design was replicated three times to each insect species and two periods of storage. At the end of each storage period, the insects had been removed and were counted; the seeds samples were reweighed to determine weight loss, then samples analyzed to assessment effects of insect infestation on peroxide value (PV), free-fatty acids (FFA) as indicator on the products quality according to Mbata (1994) and protein. Weight loss (%) was calculated according to the equation of Khare and Johari (1984).

Weight loss (%) = (initial dry weight – final dry weight) / initial dry weight x 100

3.2. Determination oilseeds damage treated with phosphine fumigant at recommended dose (15 bellets /m³):

The experiments were conducted using jute bags: (Ca: 0.5 kg each): Four jute bags contained 25 g of peanut seeds were artificially infested by 25 larvae (4th instar) of *E. cautella*. In case of sesame seeds, four jute bags contained 25 g sesame seeds infested artificially by 25 adults of *O. surinamensis*. Also, four jute bags contained 25 g of maize infested by 25 adults of *R. dominica*. The bags were directly closed and exposed to phosphine gas at recommended dose (15 bellets /m³ or /ton and 4 days exposure periods) inside a plastic container (16-liter capacity) as fumigation chambers. Fumigation chambers were sealed by paraffin and adhesive tape. Four untreated jute bags were kept as control for each insect species. Jute bags for each replicate were observed after treatments to count

numbers of alive and dead and calculate mortality percent that was corrected according to Abbott's formula (1925), then, the seeds samples were analyzed to assessment effects fumigation with phosphine on PV, FFA in addition to protein content.

4. Chemical properties analysis of infested and fumigated oilseeds:

Peroxide value and free fatty acids are estimated using the method described by Sadasivam and Manickam (1991). Total Protein content of seeds samples was estimated by the method of Bradford (1976). Protein content was expressed as μg protein/g weight.

5. Statistical analysis of the obtained data:

The data were statistically analyzed using Costat Software Program (1985). Least Significant Differences test (LSD) was used for comparison between treatment means at 5 % level of probability according to Snedecor and Chachran (1981).

Results and discussion

1. Determination oilseeds damage induce with different insects infestation for two and four months storage periods:

Two storage periods and different oilseeds were investigated to determine weight loss of oilseeds due to different insect infestations at 2 and 4 months storage after infestation as well as study certain the changes which occur of quality parameters such as PV, FFA and protein of some oilseeds affected whether when their insect infestation during storage and or their fumigation by phosphine gas. The most important results can be summarized as follows. The data presented in Table (1) regarding peanut seeds infested with *E. cautella* during two observation periods. It was revealed that there were great variations in weight loss among infested and un-infested seeds. The weight loss % was significantly higher in infested peanut seeds (7.47 and 28.99

%) compared with un-infested peanut (0.8 and 1.2 %) at 2 and 4 months storage periods because cumulative number of *E. cautella* progeny, since, the means of emerged adult were 61.25 and 356.5 insects. These results are supported by the findings of Mali and Satyavir (2005) who observed that the insect damage increased by the storage period. The similar results were observed in case of other seeds. The highest weight loss of sesame seeds was recorded in infested seeds with *O. surinamensis* whether at 2 or 4 months, since, it recorded 2.57 and 4.1 % at 2 or 4 months, resp. compared to 0.3 and 0.57 % for control with significant differences between infested and un-

infested seeds. This is variation in loss correlated well with cumulative number of *O. surinamensis* progeny, where, the means of emerged adults were 39.5 and 62 insects at 2 or 4 months for infested seeds, resp. Similarly, the maximum weight loss of maize grains was recorded in infested grains with *R. dominica* either at 2 or 4 months, where, it recorded 4.65, and 6.16 % at 2 or 4 months resp. compared with 0.4 and 0.7 % for control at 2 or 4 months, resp. Also, loss correlated with cumulative number of *R. dominica* progeny, it was recorded 48.5 and 79.25 insects at 2 or 4 months, resp. but no adult emergence in all un-infested seeds (Control).

Table (1): Weight loss and cumulative number progenies of peanut, sesame and maize seeds affected by different insect infestation after 2 and 4 months of infestation

Treatments	After 2 months		After 4 months	
	Loss %	Cumulative no. of progenies	Loss %	Cumulative no. of progenies
Un-infested Peanut	0.8 ± 0.07 b	0.0 ± 0.0 B	1.2 ± 0.13 b	0.0 ± 0.0 b
Peanut infested with <i>E. c.</i>	7.47 ± 0.29 a	61.25 ± 4.25 a	28.99 ± 2.44 a	356.5 ± 15.55 a
LSD 0.05	0.745	10.39	5.96	20.04
Un-infested sesame	0.3 ± 0.04 b	0.0 ± 0.0 B	0.57 ± 0.08 b	0.0 ± 0.0 B
Sesame infested with <i>O. s.</i>	2.57 ± 0.41 a	39.5 ± 3.18 A	4.1 ± 0.54 a	62 ± 4.83 a
LSD 0.05	1.01	7.77	1.33	11.82
Un-infested maize	0.4 ± 0.05 b	0.0 ± 0.0 B	0.7 ± 0.07 b	0.0 ± 0.0 B
Maize infested with <i>R. d.</i>	4.65 ± 0.42 a	48.5 ± 5.04 a	6.16 ± 0.13 a	79.25 ± 1.89 a
LSD 0.05	0.74	8.28	0.37	4.62

Lack of data on insect infestation, control methods and pesticides residues in oilseeds have been highlighted. This is in line with the findings of Weiss (1983) who stated that losses in stored sesame seeds and cake are said to be substantial although there is little published information to back up this claim. Srivastava (1970) reported that loss in sesame stored in Uttar Pradesh, India, caused mainly by *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) and *Corcyra cephalonica* (Stainton) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) have reportedly reached 4.4 %. Gebremichael (2017) showed that weight loss of sesame seeds due to *Plodia interpunctella* was 17.8±5.5%. Kurdikeri *et al.* (1994) found that percentage seed damage and weight loss due to *R. dominica* (F.) infestation increased markedly with the increasing in storage period in all the maize hybrids. The results of Metwalley, *et al.* (2007) showed significant reduction in date weight as storage period increased resulted from infestation by *E. cautella*, and *O. surinamensis*.

2. Effect of *Ephestia cautella* infestation and phosphine gas on important nutrient elements composition of peanut seeds:

The results obtained presented in Table (2) shows the effect of peanut seeds infestation by *E. cautella* and fumigated with phosphine on important nutrient composition. The results showed that peanut seeds infested by *E. cautella* within 4 months storage had significant effect on all tested parameters, whereas, peanut seeds fumigated with phosphine did not significant effect on all tested parameters with exception protein content which increased compared to control. This is because there were significant differences between infested, fumigated and un-infested peanut seeds (Control). In case of PV, it

appears that the highest PV was 8.73 mEqO₂/kg in infested peanut seeds at 4 months of storage, but far below the limit in the Codex standard of 10 mEqO₂ kg⁻¹ oil, then significantly decreased to reach to 5.53 and 5.23 mEqO₂/kg in fumigated peanut seeds and un-infested seeds (control) with significant differences between them. Similar trend was observed in case of FFA where, it was noticed that highest FFA contents was 7.97 mg triolein % in infested peanut seeds. Whereas, FFA contents in peanut seeds fumigated with phosphine not affected compared with un-fumigated peanut seeds (Control), where, it were 4.63 and 3.95, resp. Protein content of stored peanut seeds for 4 months of storage was affected by both insect infestation and phosphine compared with (Control). Insect infestation for peanut by *E. cautella* caused significant reduction in protein contents, while, phosphine caused increased in protein contents, since, protein contents was 21.6 and 39.4 mg % in infested and fumigated peanut seeds by *E. cautella*, with significant differences, compared with control which recorded 31.63 mg % with significant differences. Mortality % of *E. cautella* presented on peanut seeds due to fumigation with phosphine (As recommended dose) was 100 % compared with un-fumigated *E. cautella*, which recorded 8 % mortality. Our results revealed that there is significant increase in FFA which considered as indicator to peanut seeds deterioration in storage by *E. cautella* infestation. These results were confirmed by results of Pomeranz (1982) reported that increase in fat acidity value are known to reflect product deterioration. Mbata (1994) showed that infestation of bambarra groundnuts (*Vigna subterranea*) with *Callosobruchus subinnotatus* (Pic.) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) increased free fatty acids and peroxides, which

are indices in measuring biochemical deterioration. Bamaiyi *et al.* (2007) who reported that qualitative deterioration of cowpea grains due to cowpea infestation by *Callosobruchus maculatus* (F.) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae). Babarinde *et al.* (2013) stated that voracious feeding on sound grains by *S. zeamais* causes

product quality loss through an increase in free fatty acids. But, in case of fumigation with phosphine, important nutrient composition of peanut seeds did not significant affect with phosphine. Current work showed that protein content increased when the level of insects rose.

Table (2): Change in important nutrient elements quality of peanut seeds as affected either by *Ephestia cautella* infestation or fumigation by phosphine gas.

Tested parameters Treatments	Peroxide value (mEqO2/kg)	Free fatty acid (mg triolein %)	Total protein mg %	Mortality %
Infested seeds	8.73 ± 0.27 A	7.97±0.43 A	21.6 ±0.86 C	--
Fumigated seeds	5.53 ± 0.24 B	4.63±0.19 B	39.4 ± 1.97 a	100 A
Control seeds	5.23±0.18 B	3.95±0.1 B	31.63±1.45 b	8 B
LSD 0.05	0.80	0.96	5.18	

This confirms by Sudesh *et al.* (1996) found that infestation of maize grains with single or mixed populations of *R. dominica* resulted in substantial reductions in total lipids contents, In contrast, other results were observed by Siddhuraju *et al.* (2002) reported that gamma irradiation did not induce any changes in protein and lipids contents of soybean and groundnut.

3. Effect of *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* infestation and phosphine gas on important nutrient elements composition of sesame seeds:

The results of the important element composition of the sesame seeds after both infestation by *O. surinamensis* and fumigation with phosphine gas are presented in Table (3).

Table (3): Change in important nutrient elements quality of sesame seeds as affected either by *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* infestation or fumigation by phosphine .

.Tested parameters Treatments	Peroxide value (mEqO2/kg)	Free fatty acid (mg triolein %)	Total protein mg %	Mortality %
Infested seeds	10.27 ± 0.15 a	2.89±0.07 b	12.43±0.76 c	--
Fumigated seeds	10.57±0.38 a	3.2± 0.08ab	18.3±0.66 b	100 a
Control seeds	4.1 ± 0.12b	3.33±0.12 a	23±0.95 a	5 b
LSD 0.05	0.85	0.32	3.56	

Results noticed that PV of infested and fumigated sesame seeds were significantly higher than those of the un-infested sesame seeds (control), it was recorded 10.27 and 10.57 for infested and fumigated sesame seeds, resp. without significantly differences and it is higher the limit in the Codex standard of 10 mEqO2 kg-1 oil (Alimentarius, 1999), then significant reduced to 4.1 for control. Consequently, become seeds unacceptable as a result for quality deterioration and that phosphine unfit

as fumigant for sesame seeds. As well, FFA was 2.89 and 3.2 mg triolein % for infested and fumigated sesame seeds, resp. then significant increased to reach to 3.33 for un-infested seeds (Control). The results are in agree with Semple (1986) reported that changes in quality of the grain during storage are often exacerbated by the insect infestation. Protein content, data revealed that infested sesame seeds with *O. surinamensis* had the lower protein content than fumigated and un-infested sesame seeds. It was recorded 12.43,

18.3 and 23 for infested, fumigated and un-infested seeds, resp. with significant differences between them. Complete mortality of *O. surinamensis* rearing on sesame seeds due to fumigation with phosphine compared with un-fumigated *O. surinamensis* which recorded 5 % mortality. These results are further supported by the findings of Lamboni and Hell (2009) found a reduction in the amount of proteins in stored grain can occur as a result of insect infestation. Akintunde (2012) reported that *C. maculatus* reduced the content of lipids of beans by over 50 %. Babarinde *et al.* (2010) reported that the proximate composition of the chips affected with infestation of plantain chips by *Tribolium castaneum*. The results are presented of Chattha *et al.* (2016) demonstrated that fat and protein loss of stored grain may be due to insect infestation which enhance the activity of proteolytic enzymes. *O. surinamensis* feeding activities could finger as a possible reason for this depletion. This is in consonant with the findings of El-Badawy *et al.* (2013)

Table (4) Change in important nutrient elements quality of maize seeds as affected either by *Rhyzopertha dominica* infestation or fumigation by phosphine gas.

Tested parameters Treatments	Peroxide value (mEqO ₂ /k)	Free fatty acid (mg triolein %)	Total protein mg %	Mortality %
Infested seeds	0.69±0.05 a	2.07±0.04 b	5.57±0.17 b	--
Fumigated seeds	0.75±0.03 a	2.25±0.02 a	7.97±0.32 a	100
Control seeds	0.79±0.06 a	2.19±0.06 ab	5.93±0.2 b	10
LSD 0.05	0.16	0.14	0.81	

Also, complete mortality of *R. dominica* reared on maize seeds due to phosphine compared with un-fumigated *R. dominica*, it was recorded 10 % mortality. These results in agreement with Muangkaeo *et al.* (2005) found a decrease in fat content of grain during storage. Other results were observed by Siddhuraju *et al.*, (2002) reported that protein and lipids contents in groundnut and soybean did not affect with gamma irradiation treatment. Bashir *et al.* (2013) reported that the deterioration of

significant decrease in the total lipid and protein contents were observed for irradiated peanut seeds and dry bean seeds.

4. Effect of *Rhyzopertha dominica* infestation and phosphine gas on important nutrient elements composition of maize grains:

Data in Table (4) show effect of maize grains infestation by *R. dominica* and their fumigated with phosphine on the important element composition. Results noticed that PV was not affected either with insect infestation or phosphine; it recorded 0.69, 0.75 and 0.79 for infested, fumigated and un-infested sesame seeds without significantly differences. Whereas FFA and protein content were only significant affect in maize grains treated with phosphine, it was 2.25 and 7.97 for FFA and protein content, resp. compared to 2.19 and 5.93, resp. for control, but in case infested maize grains not significant varies with un-infested maize grains, since it recorded 2.07 and 5.57 for FFA and protein content, resp.

nutritional and rheological properties of the stored wheat mainly occurs due to insect infestation after six months of storage. Finally, previous reports confirmed the impact of several factors on changes in important nutrient quality of stored grains such as the effect of insect infestation and storage periods (Bamaiyi *et al.*, 2007 and Babarinde *et al.*, 2010), product types (Babarinde, 2013), temperature and relative humidity (White and Jayas, 1989), storage methods (Chattha *et al.*, 2016)

and irradiation (El-Badawy *et al.*, 2013). But, investigation insect infestation and phosphine effects on important nutrient in oilseeds were rare or not found.

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Role of predatory ground beetles (Coleoptera : Carabidae) in managing sugar beet pests

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Abstract:

Carabidae are represent about 40000 species throughout the world. They feed on a diversity of prey such as, snails, larvae and pupae of Lepidoptera, Collembola, Cicadellidae, aphids, larvae and pupae of Coleoptera, larvae of Diptera and eggs of insects. Carabids had little attention to be studied in Egyptian sugar beet fields. Therefore, this work was undertaken for understanding the role of Carabidae in controlling sugar beet pests at Sakha Agricultural Research Station. The results showed that the dominant carabid species were, *Bembidion* spp., *Calosoma chlorostictum* Degen. *Pterostichus pharao* L. Highly significant positive correlations between carabids and cotton leafworms, *Agrotis ipsilon* (Hufnagel) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) larvae, aphids, Cicadellidae, Collembola, *Scrobipalpa ocellatella* Boyd. (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae), snails and *Cassida vittata* Vill. (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) during the three cultivations in 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 seasons. The major trapped pests by carabids were *S. ocellatella*, cotton leaf worms, *C. vittata*, *Pegomyia mixta* Vill. (Diptera: Anthomyiidae), Collembola, Cicadellidae, aphids, *Nezara viridula* L. (Hemiptera : Pentatomidae) , *A. ipsilon* and snails with 20, 13.84, 12.30, 10.76, 9.23, 7.69, 6.15, 4.61 and 4.61%, respectively in 2017/2018 seasons. 23.94, 15.49, 16.90, 12.67, 4.22, 5.63, 4.22, 7.04, 2.81 and 7.04%, respectively in 2018/2019. Also, raner 24% Sc was reduced carabid number with 10.49 and 17.17% in two seasons, respectively as, the conventional insecticides; Tac 48% Ec and Diracomel 90% Sp were reduced carabid number with 99.44 and 98.28% in 2017/2018, 100 and 99.34% in 2018/2019. In conclusion, these results proved that the importance of carabid species in managing sugar beet pests. In addition to, ecdysone agonists (IGRs) conserve the population of these carabid species in comparison with conventional insecticides. Thus, it is preferred to control sugar beet pests by spraying ecdysone agonists for maintaining the population of these predators.

Introduction

Sugar beet *Beta vulgaris* L. (Family : Chenopodiaceae) is

cultivated in about 40 countries of the world and accounts for 40 – 45% of the world total sugar production. It

provides about a third of all sugar consumed worldwide (Biancardi *et al.*, 2010). It is highly sensitive crop to pests (Kos *et al.*, 2013). Sugar beet is liable to infestation by numerous pests such as, aphids, leafhoppers, *Spodoptera littoralis* Boisd. and *S. exigua* (Hubner), *Pegomya mixta* Vill. (Diptera: Anthomyiidae), *Cassida vittata* Vill. (Coleoptera:Chrysomelidae), *Scrobipalpa ocellatella* (Boyd.) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae), *Nezara viridula* L. (Hemiptera : Pentatomidae) and snails, *Monacha* spp. (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) (Iskander, 1982; Abd El-Ghany, 1995; Shalaby, 2001; Bazazo, 2010; Khalifa, 2017 and Khalifa, 2018). Sugar beet fields have enormous insect predators which can manage these pests under the economic threshold levels (Mesbah, 1991; El-Zoghby, 1999; Shalaby and Hendawy, 2007; Khalifa, 2017; Khalifa, 2018 and El-Dessouki, 2019). From these major insect predators in Egyptian sugar beet fields are ground beetles (Coleoptera : Carabidae). Carabidae are known as important predatory organisms of the soil living pests (Sunderland, 2002). They are representing approximately 40.000 described species found throughout the world. Many carabids are easily recognized at the family level. Adults are well- proportioned beetles with pronounced mandibles, and palps, long slender legs, striate elytra, and sets of punctures with tactile setae.

They have undergone morphological adaptations to suit the habitat in which they are found. Such modifications have permitted running, burrowing in soil and sand, living under tree bark, climbing plants and swimming in water (Losey and Denno, 1998). They are known to search actively for food by means of random search vision, or chemical cues. They feed on a diversity of prey such as, snails, slugs, larvae of Lepidoptera,

Collembola, Cicadellidae, aphids, pupae of beetles, eggs of insects, gall midge (Cecidomyiidae) larvae, cabbage root fly, *Delia radicum* L. (Diptera: Anthomyiidae) eggs and larvae, pupae and eggs of onion maggot, *Delia antiqua* (Meigen) (Diptera: Anthomyiidae), eggs and larvae of colorado potato beetle, *Leptinotarsa decemlineata* Say (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) eggs and larvae of weevils (Curculionidae) and dipteran eggs (Riddick, 2005). Kromp (1999) reported that carabid beetles are usually beneficial to agriculture crops, preying on aphids, slugs and other pests. Holland and Luff (2000) showed that Carabidae occurs in all temperate agroecosystems and have been implicated as predators of many pests; aphids, lepidopterous larvae and slugs. Also, they indicated that Carabidae are an important component of integrated pest management (IPM). Rajagopal and Kumar (1992) clarified that carabids are known to prey upon caterpillars, pupae, larvae, aphids, termites etc. They are found in almost all habitats like agricultural fields, orchards, plantations, forest ect. Many species of carabids were recorded earlier as predators of crop pests. They are commonly associated with several crop pests under field conditions, but information on their distribution, seasonal abundance and feeding potential is lacking. Fournier and Loreau (1999) reported that carabids are generalist predators in crops and in natural habitats. They are cited as being predators of aphids, lepidopteran larvae, slugs, and herbaceous plant seeds. Also, many species of these beetles have a role in the natural biological control for several lepidopteran pests in different crops. Awad *et al.* (2014) investigated that intensive use of conventional insecticides led to numerous dangerous drastic problems, i.e. Environment

pollution, destruction of the natural enemies and incidence insect resistance to these insecticides. Ecdysone agonists (Methoxyfenozide) are novel and promising insecticides with high efficacy against various insects, at the same time almost non-toxic to predators and environment. The status of insect predators in Egyptian sugar beet fields was investigated by numerous authors (Talha, 2001; Bazazo, 2005; Hendawy, 2009; Bazazo, 2010 and El Dessouki, 2019), but carabids had little attention to be cited.

Thus, this study was done for investigating the seasonal abundance of some sugar beet pests and their associated carabid predators. Calculating the correlation coefficient values between them. Surveying certain prey of carabids by (Visual record and fine brush methods). Also, evaluating the efficiency of methoxyfenozide (Ecdysone agonists) as novel, ecofriendly insecticides in controlling sugar beet insects as well as carabids maintaining in comparison with conventional insecticides.

Materials and Methods

1. Seasonal abundance of carabids and certain sugar beet pests:

After thinning, biweekly samples were taken till harvest for two successive seasons, 2017/2018 and 2018/2019. During every sample (5 plants), a plastic bag was converted on a sugar beet plant to harbor the whole plant which cut at the soil surface. The bag was tightly tied at the bottom and transferred to the laboratory for further procedures. In the laboratory, a piece of cotton saturated with chloroform was introduced into the bag for 20 minutes to anesthetize the confirmed pests. The bag size varied during the season according to the growth of plants. The area of this experiment was 1/2 feddan planted with farida cultivar / each cultivation. The specimens were identified using stereoscopy (4.8 – 56.0 x magnification) the carabid species Figure (1) were identified by (Plant Protection Research Institute, Egypt).

Bembidion spp.

Calosoma chlorostictum Degen

Pterostichus pharao (Lutshnik)

Figure (1): The specimens of the carabid species.

2. Effect of certain methoxyfenozide (Ecdysone agonists) and conventional insecticides on carabids:

Another field about 1/2 feddan was performed to this experiment during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019

seasons. Three insecticides in Table (1) were applied and recommended against cotton leaf worms, each insecticide was replicated four times ($3 \times 4 = 12$ plots), each plot measured 42m², in addition to four plots as check. Knapsack sprayer

(20 L volume) was used for spraying. Number of carabids was counted by visual record one, three, seven and 10 days post spraying.

Reduction in carabids was calculated by Henderson and Tilton (1955) formula:

$$1 - \left(\frac{\text{No. in check before spray} \times \text{No. in treated after spray}}{\text{No. in check after spray} \times \text{No. in treated before spray}} \right) \times 100$$

Table (1): The insecticides used against cotton leaf worms during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 seasons.

Insecticide		Category	Rate / feddan
Common	Trade name		
Methoxyfenozide	Raner 26% sc	Ecdysone agonists	75 cm ³
Chlorpyrifos	Tac 48% Ec	Conventional	1000 cm ³
Methomyl	Diracomel	Conventional	300 gm

3. Identification the prey of carabid species:

Using visual record and a fine brush method were used to monitor carabids and their prey. Four hours for each sample 9.00 a.m to 13.00 p.m during third cultivation.

70% ethyl – alcohol was put into glass tubes, after that, the specimens were identified using stereoscopy (4.8 – 56.0 x magnification). 20 sample (4 hours / sample) were collected beginning from 15 November up to 30 March and 14 November up to 29 March during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019, respectively.

Results and discussion

1. Seasonal abundance of carabids and certain sugar beet pests:

In general, data in Tables (2,3,4,5,6 and 7) showed that the population density carabids were low on September and January, and then exhibited high numbers on October, November and December for the first cultivation during the two seasons. Low populations were showed on October and January, and then occurred high populations on November, December and February to the second cultivation during the two seasons.

Low numbers were found on November, January and February in 2017/2018, whereas on January in

Also, differences between the mean numbers of carabids were analyzed using Duncan test (1955). Date of spraying was 20 and 25 September in two seasons, respectively, Completely randomized block design was applied.

2018/2019. High numbers were detected on December and March during 2017/2018, while on November, December, February and March during 2018/2019.

Also, general carabid – prey ratio ranging between 1: 0.06 to 1: 0.21 and 1: 0.02 to 1: 0.15 and 1: 0.02 to 1: 0.28 for three cultivations, respectively during 2017/2018 seasons.

1: 0.03 to 1: 0.30 and 1: 0.01 to 1: 0.36 and 1: 0.05 to 1:0.57 for three plantations, respectively throughout 2018/2019 seasons.

Concerning the correlation coefficient values between certain sugar beet pests and their associated carabid were calculated according to Snedecor and Cochran (1989) considering population fluctuations of carabid species and pests during the two seasons 2017/2018 and 2018/2019. Data in Tables (8 and 9) showed that highly significant positive correlations were attained between carabids and cotton leaf worms, *A.ipsilon*, aphids, leafhoppers, Collembola, *S.ocellatella*, snails and *C. vittata* during the three cultivations. Significant positive correlations were calculated among carabids and *P. mixta* during the three cultivations. The raise of general carabid – prey ratio and the highly positive significant correlation

coefficient values between carabids and sugar beet pests during the two seasons, these carabids demonstrate that play a vital role in managing sugar beet pests. Ghoneim (2014) indicated that Carabidae is a large, cosmopolitan family of beetles (Coleoptera). Many species of these carabids have a role in the natural biological control for several pests. Holland and Luff (2000) showed that carabidae are an important component of an integrated pest management. Riddick (2005) reported that carabids were capable of reducing aphids population densities. Carabids, even when at relatively low - densities, were able to locate low density populations of aphids in sugar beet fields. Rajagopal and Kumar (1992) demonstrated that the management and

conservation of Carabidae is necessary for effective utilization in the integrated pest management program. Weseloh *et al.* (1995) investigated that carabids are one of the most important mortality agents of the larvae and pupae of Lepidoptera. Thus, it should be used intensively in the biological control of lepidopterous insects.

Data presented in Table (10) clarify that the major trapped pests by carabids were *S. ocellatella*, cotton leaf worms, *C.vittata*, *P.mixta*, Collembola, Cicadellidae, aphids, *N.viridula*, *A.ipsilon* and snails with 20, 13.84, 12.30, 10.76, 9.23, 7.69, 6.15, 4.61 and 4.61%, respectively in 2017/2018 seasons. 23.94, 15.49, 16.90, 12.67, 4.22, 5.63, 4.22, 7.04, 2.81 and 7.04%, respectively in 2018/2019.

Table (2): Seasonal abundance of major pests attacking sugar beet plants and their associated carabid species during 2017/2018 season, using bag and cut method, first cultivation.

Date	Carabids	Pests					
		Cotton leaf worms	<i>Agrotis ipsilon</i>	Aphids	Leafhoppers	Collembola	<i>Pegomyia mixta</i>
15/9/2017	4	3	1	0	0	0	0
30/9	13	4	2	0	0	2	0
15/10	13	6	3	0	1	3	0
30/10	17	5	4	0	1	5	0
15/11	18	5	6	0	0	4	0
30/11	19	4	3	2	1	0	0
15/12	23	2	4	3	3	2	1
30/12	28	1	4	5	4	2	2
15/1/2018	9	1	2	6	7	1	3
30/1	9	1	2	6	7	1	3
Total	153	32	31	22	24	20	9
General Predator – prey ratio	--	1: 0.21	1: 0.20	1: 0.14	1:0.16	1: 0.13	1: 0.06

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Table (3): Seasonal abundance of major pests attacking sugar beet plants and their associated carabids species during 2017/2018 season, using bag and cut method, second cultivation.

Date	Carabids	Pests							
		Cotton leaf worms	<i>Agrotis ipsilon</i>	Aphids	Leaf-Hoppers	Collem-bola	<i>Pegomyia mixta</i>	<i>Scrobipalpa ocellatella</i>	Snails
15/10	5	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
30/10	10	3	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
15/11	16	3	2	0	2	1	0	0	0
30/11	21	5	3	0	3	2	0	0	0
15/12	22	1	0	0	3	1	1	0	0
30/12	24	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
15/1	8	1	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
30/1	7	1	0	1	0	0	3	0	1
15/2	12	0	0	2	2	0	4	1	2
28/2	6	1	0	2	1	2	6	2	3
Total	131	18	7	5	11	8	19	3	6
General Predator – prey ratio	--	1 : 0.14	1 : 0.05	1 : 0.04	1 : 0.08	1 : 0.06	1 : 0.15	1 : 0.02	1 : 0.05

Table (4): seasonal abundance of major pests attacking sugar beet plants and their associated carabid species during 2017/2018 season, using bag and cut method, third cultivation.

Date	Carabids	Pests								
		Cotton leaf worms	<i>Agrotis ipsilon</i>	Aphids	Leaf-hoppers	Collembola	<i>Pegomyia mixta</i>	<i>Scrobipalpa ocellatella</i>	Snails	<i>Cassida vittata</i>
15/11	3	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30/11	11	2	1	0	2	0	1	0	0	0
15/12	18	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
30/12	22	0	0	0	1	1	3	0	0	0
15/1	7	0	0	0	0	1	4	0	0	0
30/1	6	0	0	0	0	1	4	0	0	0
15/2	5	0	0	0	0	1	5	2	2	2
28/2	9	0	0	1	0	0	6	2	3	3
15/3	23	2	1	0	2	2	6	6	4	9
30/3	26	1	0	2	3	3	7	7	5	11
Total	130	8	3	4	8	10	37	17	14	25
General Predator – Prey ratio	--	1 : 0.06	1 : 0.02	1:0.03	1:0.06	1:0.07	1:0.28	1:0.13	1:0.11	1:0.20

Table (5): Seasonal abundance of major pests attacking sugar beet plants and their associated carabid species during 2018/2019 season, using bag and cut method, first cultivation.

Date	Carabids	Pests					
		Cotton leaf worms	<i>Agrotis ipsilon</i>	Aphids	Leafhoppers	Collembola	<i>Pegomya mixta</i>
14/9	2	2	1	0	0	1	0
29/9	6	3	2	0	0	1	0
14/10	11	5	2	0	1	1	0
29/10	13	5	4	0	2	0	0
14/11	19	6	4	0	3	0	0
29/11	22	8	5	0	3	0	2
14/12	15	0	0	0	4	0	3
29/12	8	0	0	1	4	0	4
14/1	6	0	0	1	0	0	6
29/1	6	0	0	1	0	0	8
Total	108	29	18	3	17	3	23
General Predator – prey ratio	--	1 : 0.30	1 : 0.20	1 : 0.03	1 : 0.20	1 : 0.03	1 : 0.21

Table (6): Seasonal abundance of major pests attacking sugar beet plants and their associated carabid species during 2018/2019 season, using bag and cut method, second cultivation.

Date	Carabids	Pests								
		Cotton leaf worms	<i>Agrotis ipsilon</i>	Aphids	Collembola	<i>Pegomya mixta</i>	<i>Scrobipalpa ocellatella</i>	Snails	<i>Cassida vittata</i>	Leafhoppers
14/10	3	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29/10	9	6	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
14/11	16	7	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
29/11	21	9	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	2
14/12	23	2	0	1	1	3	0	0	0	3
29/12	9	0	0	0	1	4	0	0	0	3
14/1	9	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0
29/1	8	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0
14/2	13	1	0	0	0	12	2	1	1	0
28/2	18	0	1	0	0	13	3	3	1	0
Total	129	29	8	2	6	47	5	4	2	8
General Predator – prey ratio	--	1 : 0.22	1 : 0.06	1 : 0.01	1 : 0.04	1 : 0.36	1 : 0.03	1 : 0.03	1 : 0.01	1 : 0.06

Table (7): Seasonal abundance of major pests attacking sugar beet plants and their associated carabid species during 2018/2019 season, using bag and cut method, third cultivation.

Date	Carabids	Pests								
		Cotton leaf worms	<i>Agrotis ipsilon</i>	Aphids	Leaf-hoppers	Collembola	<i>Pegomyia mixta</i>	<i>Scrobipalpa ocellatella</i>	Snails	<i>Cassida vittata</i>
14/11	11	6	2	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
29/11	13	8	2	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
14/12	16	3	0	0	1	1	3	0	0	0
29/12	8	0	0	0	1	1	5	0	0	0
14/1	8	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0
29/1	9	0	0	0	0	1	8	0	0	0
14/2	10	0	0	0	0	1	9	1	2	2
28/2	17	0	0	1	0	0	13	3	3	3
14/3	23	1	1	3	3	0	17	5	6	9
29/3	29	1	3	4	3	3	19	9	8	13
Total	144	19	8	8	10	8	83	18	19	27
General Predator – prey ratio	--	1 : 0.13	1 : 0.05	1 : 0.05	1 : 0.06	1 : 0.05	1 : 0.57	1 : 0.12	1 : 0.13	1 : 0.18

Table (8): Correlation coefficient values between some sugar beet pests and their carabids during 2017/2018 season.

Relationship	"r" value			Status of significance		
	1 st cultivation	2 nd cultivation	3 rd cultivation	1 st cultivation	2 nd cultivation	3 rd cultivation
Carabids x cotton leaf worm	0.611**	0.610**	0.602**	Highly	Highly	Highly
Carabids x <i>Agrotis ipsilon</i>	0.701**	0.703**	0.712**	Highly	Highly	Highly
Carabids x aphids	0.811**	0.810**	0.813**	Highly	Highly	Highly
Carabids x leaf-hoppers	0.721**	0.722**	0.713**	Highly	Highly	Highly
Carabids x Collembola	0.801**	0.802**	0.811**	Highly	Highly	Highly
Carabids x <i>Pegomyia mixta</i>	0.550**	0.551**	0.541**	Significant	Significant	Significant
Carabids x <i>Scrobipalpa ocellatella</i>	--	0.813**	0.816**	--	Highly	Highly
Carabids x snails	--	0.822**	0.826**	--	Highly	Highly
Carabids x <i>Cassida vittata</i>	--	--	0.823**	--	--	Highly

Table (9): Correlation coefficient values between certain sugar pests and carabids during 2018/2019.

Relationship	"r" value			Status of significance		
	1 st cultivation	2 nd cultivation	3 rd cultivation	1 st cultivation	2 nd cultivation	3 rd cultivation
Carabids x cotton leaf worm	0.621**	0.623**	0.631**	Highly	Highly	Highly
Carabids x <i>Agrotis ipsilon</i>	0.651**	0.653**	0.656**	Highly	Highly	Highly
Carabids x Aphids	0.826**	0.838**	0.840**	Highly	Highly	Highly
Carabids x leafhoppers	0.712**	0.734**	0.719**	Highly	Highly	Highly
Carabids x Collembola	0.801**	0.812**	0.813**	Highly	Highly	Highly
Carabids x <i>Pegomyia mixta</i>	0.501**	0.511**	0.512**	Significant	Significant	Significant
Carabids x <i>Scrobipalpa ocellatella</i>	--	0.841**	0.861**	--	Highly	Highly
Carabids x snails	--	0.911**	0.922**	--	Highly	Highly
Carabids x <i>Cassida vittata</i>	--	0.913**	0.910**	--	Highly	Highly

Table (10): Prey of carabids in sugar beet fields during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 seasons, using visual record method.

Taxa	Stage	2017/2018		2018/2019	
		No.*	%	No.*	%
<i>Scrobipalpa ocellatella</i>	Larvae	13	20.00	17	23.94
Cotton leaf worm	Eggs + larvae	9	13.84	11	15.49
<i>Cassida vittata</i>	Larvae + pupae+ adults	8	12.30	12	16.90
<i>Pegomyia mixta</i>	Larvae + eggs	7	10.76	9	12.67
Collembola	Adult	7	10.76	3	4.22
Cicadellidae	Nymph + Adult	6	9.23	4	5.63
Aphids	Nymph + adults	5	7.69	3	4.22
<i>Nezara viridula</i>	Eggs+Nymph	4	6.15	5	7.04
<i>Agrotis ipsilon</i>	Larvae	3	4.61	2	2.81
Snails	Adult	3	4.61	5	7.04
Total	—	65	—	71	—

* 10 samples (4 hours for each sample)

2. Effect of certain methoxyfenozide (Ecdysone agonists) and conventional insecticides on carabids:

Table (11) elucidate that raner 24% Sc was reduced carabid number with 10.49 and 17.17% in two seasons, respectively as, the conventional insecticides; Tac 48% Ec and Diracomel 90% Sp were reduced carabid number with 99.44 and 98.28% in 2017/2018, 100 and 99.34% in

Table (11): Side effect of certain conventional and ecdysome agonists insecticides on carabids during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 seasons.

Compound	Before spray	After one day		After 3 day		After 7 day		After 10 day		Overall mean of reduction
	Mean	M.	Red.%	M.	Red.%	M.	Red.%	M.*	Red.%	
Tac	9.75	0.00	100	0.00	100	0.00	100	0.25 ^a	97.77	99.44
Diracomel	9.50	0.00	100	0.00	100	0.00	100	0.75 ^a	93.15	98.28
Raner	9.75	9.25	7.50	9.50	7.31	9.50	11.62	9.50 ^b	15.55	10.49
Check	9.75	10.00	--	10.25	--	10.75	--	11.25	--	--
Tac	7.00	0.00	100	0.00	100	0.00	100	0.00 ^a	100	100
Diracomel	7.00	0.00	100	0.00	100	0.00	100	0.25 ^a	97.39	99.34
Raner	7.50	7.00	13.10	7.50	10.00	7.50	18.18	7.50 ^b	27.02	17.07
Check	6.75	7.25	--	7.50	--	8.25	--	9.29	--	--

* The Duncan test at level of 5% probability was applied, the main followed by the same letter do not differ significantly.

3. Identification the prey of carabid species:

The survey showed the occurrence of 3 carabid species (Table 12). Most surveyed carabid species were; *Bembidion* spp (67.32, 91.60 and 86.15) followed by *Calosoma chlorostictum* Degen (18.95, 1.52 and 2.30), and *Pterostichus pharao* (13.72,

2018/2019. These results are agreement with those of several authors, Ishaaya (2005), Pineda *et al.* (2009) and Rani *et al.* (2018). They concluded that ecdysone agonists are promising insecticides with high efficacy against various insects, at the same time almost non-toxic to predators and have a minimum on the environment. It would be an ideal agent for IPM.

6.87 and 11.53) during three cultivations, respectively in 2017/2018. As, *Bembidion* spp (90.74, 77.51 and 97.22), *Calosoma chlorostictum* Degen. (7.40, 11.62 and 1.38) and *Pterostichus pharao* (1.85, 10.85 and 1.38) during three cultivations, respectively in 2018/2019.

Table (12): Survey of carabid Species during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019

Taxa	1 st Cultivation		2 nd Cultivation		3 rd Cultivation	
	No.	%	No	%	No.	%
2017/2018						
<i>Bembidion</i> spp.	103	67.32	120	91.60	112	86.15
<i>Pterostichus pharaoh</i>	21	13.72	9	6.87	15	11.53
<i>Calosoma chlorostictum</i> Degen.	29	18.95	2	1.52	3	2.30
Total	153	—	131	—	130	—
2018/2019						
<i>Bembidion</i> spp.	98	90.74	100	77.51	140	97.22
<i>Pterostichus pharaoh</i>	2	1.85	14	10.85	2	1.38
<i>Calosoma chlorostictum</i> Degen.	8	7.40	15	11.62	2	1.38
Total	108	—	129	—	144	—

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**Economic evaluation of different insecticides against cotton spotted bollworm
Earias insulana (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) on okra plant**

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Abstract

Field strain of cotton spotted bollworm *Earias insulana* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) on okra was treated by selected pesticide and natural compounds to evaluate their toxicity against *E. insulana*. Under okra field conditions, malathion, lambda, ahook, and naterlo oil. The 1st and 2nd spraying application of ahook® and naterlo oil® proved to have relatively, equal efficiency against the insect population and gave merely equal values of general mean of reduction comprised 53 , 55 . 59 and 45 % respectively. The results of the growing season of 2018 were similar to that obtained results in season of 2019 the general mean of reduction percentage for applied 1st spray of ahook® and naterlo oil® indicated that the efficiency of both tested oils upon the population were gave values of reduction comprised 47% and 40 % , respectively . These constant costs were expressed in the varied agricultural practices throughout the growing season of labour rases/ fed 200 for each of all performed treatments ahook and naterlo oil, 100 for malathion and lambda. Moreover, extracted values of the additional return over the untreated control, in the different treatments were 24000, 18000, 48000, 42000 and 0,00 for ahook, naterlo oil, malathion , lambda and control, successively. Through the profits for one Egyptian pounds investment were 2500, 2500, 10000, 10000 and 0, 00 for ahook, naterlo oil, malathion , lambda and control, respectively.

Introduction

Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L., Moench) is one of the most important and popular vegetables to be found in Egypt. The common names of the cultivated okra are known as Lady's finger, gumbo, ochro, okra that belongs to the Malvaceae family. This crop is a native to tropical Africa or possibly tropical Asia (Tindall, 1983) and is still found growing wild specially Ethiopia (Kochhar, 1986). The total production

of okra was 4.8 million ton pods all over the world in which India contributes 70%, Nigeria 15%, Pakistan 2%, Ghana 2%, Egypt 1.7% and Iraq 1.7% (Gulsen *et al.*, 2007). Net income is often used as the primary indicator of impact on poverty (Indicator 6.1). Although this is arguably the most accurate indicator for tracking impacts on poverty, the cost of collecting accurate, reliable data might be rather high FAO (2015). Shalan *et al.* (2011) showed that Egypt's

cultivated area of okra during 2009 is about 22203 feddans produced nearly 134665 metric tonnes with an average of 6,065 tons/fed (Economic Affairs Sector, Agriculture Ministry and Land Reclamation, 2010). The fresh immature pods are used as cooked or fried vegetables and the dried ones were also particularly popular for adding soups and stews. and may powdered for the application as a flavoring (Tindall, 1983).

Among the most important of these have been cotton spotted bollworms Figure (1) (Gulati, 2004). The crop damage is done via two ways, initially; the terminal portions of growing shoots are bored by the caterpillars, moving by inside it. The shoots decrease slightly downward or dry up as a result. The shoots droop downward or dry up. Second, the larvae enter the fruits by making holes,

rendering them unfit for human consumption. According to an estimate the spotted bollworm can cause 36-90% loss in the fruit yield of okra (Misra *et al.*, 2002). Like other insects, the population of spotted bollworms is governed by their inherent capacity to increase, under the influence of various environmental factors.

The cotton spotted bollworm *Earias insulana* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) vittella are important pests of cotton along with other bollworms and mainly feed on fruiting parts of the plant, resulting in considerable losses in quantity and quality (Naser *et al.*, 1980). The larvae of *Earias* spp. attack soft and growing tissues especially the terminal bud of main tissue and cause “top boring” and later on they attack the flower buds and bolls which ultimately shed (Atwal, 1994).

Figure (1): *Earias insulana* infested okra pods.

Aslam *et al.* (2004) tested ten insecticides under field conditions against the *Earias* spp. and *Helicoverpa armigera* Hübner (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) at recommended doses. For *Earias* spp. Nighaban 20EC (Fenprothrin) remained most effective up to 7 days after application. Gupta *et al.* (2005) tested some new insecticides along with some conventional ones against *E. vittella*.

The new insecticides, abamectin, emamectin benzoate, spinosad and beta-cyfluthrin effectively protected the cotton crop with minimum incidence of cotton bollworm.

The aim of this paper is determining the comparative efficacy of different insecticides and bio insecticides against cotton spotted bollworm on two growing season 2018 and 2019 at the experimental farm of

Agricultural Research Station, Sabaheya, Alexandria and determine the economic profit of its application.

Materials and methods

1. Insecticides:

1.1. Malathion:

synthetic phosphorous compound and cholinesterase inhibitor that is strictly used as a topical pediculicide. Malathion exerts its action on the nervous system of the lice by irreversibly inhibiting the activity of cholinesterase, thereby allowing acetylcholine to accumulate at cholinergic synapses and enhancing cholinergic receptor stimulation.

IUPAC: Diethyl 2-[(dimethoxyphosphorothioyl) sulfanyl] butanedioate

1.2. Achook 0.15 % EC

azadirachtin:

A chemical compound belonging to the limonoid group, is a secondary metabolite present in neem seeds. It is a highly oxidized tetranortriterpenoid which boasts a plethora of oxygen-bearing functional groups, including an enol ether, acetal, hemiacetal, tetra-substituted epoxide and a variety of carboxylic esters IUPAC Dimethyl (2aR,3S,4S,R,S,7aS,8S,10R,10aS,10bR)-10-(acetyloxy)-3,5-dihydroxy-4-[(1S,2S,6S,8S,9R,11S)-2-hydroxy-11-methyl-5,7,10-trioxatetracyclo[6.3.1.0^{2,6}.0^{9,11}] dodec-3-en-9-yl]-4-methyl-8-[(2E)-2-methylbut-2-enoyl]oxy}octahydro-1H-furo [3',4':4,4a]naphtho[1,8-bc]furan-5,10a(8H)-dicarboxylate.

1.3. Lambada cyhalothrin 10%WP:

Pyrethroids such as cyhalothrin are often preferred as an active ingredient in agricultural insecticides because they are more cost-effective and longer acting than natural pyrethrins. λ - and γ -cyhalothrin are now used to control insects and spider mites in crops including cotton, cereals, potatoes and vegetables IUPAC R)- α -

cyano-3-phenoxybenzyl (1S)-cis-3-[(Z)-2-chloro-3,3,3-trifluoropropenyl]-2,2-dimethylcyclopropanecarboxylate and (S)- α -cyano-3-phenoxybenzyl (1R)-cis-3-[(Z)-2-chloro-3,3,3-trifluoropropenyl]-2,2-dimethylcyclopropanecarboxylate.

1.4. Essential oil tested:

Naterlo oil (Soyabean oil 93% L) mixture of fatty acids triglycerides, soybean oil was first registered for use as insecticides and miticide in 1959.

2. Methods of insecticides

application:

The plot size was 16 m² (4x4). The seeds were sown in hills at distance of 25- 30 Cm apart, and in rows of 70 Cm width. The planting date of summer cultivations was fixed, and sowing date occurred on the 1st half of March. One variety of okra (lady fingers) was used during the experiment of this study. There were five treatments including untreated with three replicates, applied using a Knapsack sprayer with one nozzle (20L), the untreated plots of control treatment were sprayed by water. The experiment was divided into five lines or plots as treatments, which were divided into three sprays. The first is achook with naterlo oil, and the second achook with naterlo after 14 day, then third is to start with malathion and lambada 14 days after the second spray, and control. The insecticidal treatments were started after appearing of *E. insulana*, based on the average counts of the bollworm infestation per plant, that considered to be an indirect reflection of the efficacy of different insecticides applied.

After spraying, samples (Pods) from ten plants in each replicate were taken from the lower, middle and upper parts of each randomly sampled plant before spraying and along 1,3 and 14 days post treatment, all the collected samples examined in the laboratory. In the experiment, insecticides were used at

the rates recommended by the Ministry of Agriculture.

3. Data calculation:

The percentages of infestation reduction of occurring insects were calculated according to Henderson and Tilton's equation (1955) as follows:

$$\text{Reduction \%} = [1 - (A/B \times C/D)] \times 100$$

Where

A = population in treatment after spraying.

B = population in treatment before spraying.

C = population in check untreated (control) before spraying.

D = population in check untreated (control) after spraying.

Reduction percentages were calculated after 1,3 and 14 days from treatment. The 1st day represented the initial reduction of insects post application of chemical insecticides ; while the initial reduction of the tested natural and chemical-compounds was calculated after 3 days. Data were subjected to the analysis of variance test (ANOVA) as randomized complete block design. The least significant differences (LSD) at the 5% level were determined using a computer program (Costat) and Duncan's Multiple Range testes modified by Steel *et al.* (1981) and LSD values were used to compare the mean numbers of inspected pest infestation, or other characters.

Results and discussion

1. Effectiveness of the evaluated chemical and/or phyto-compounds on the inspected *Earias insulana* on okra plants:

1.1. Season of 2018:

The 1st spraying application of ahook® and naterlo oil® proved to have relatively, equal efficiency against the insect population and gave merely equal values of general mean of

reduction comprised 53%, 55%, respectively. After the 2nd spraying application of the same tested compounds, a highly efficiency of ahook® and naterlo oil® were detected, and the estimated general mean of reduction for both treatments comprised 59% and 45% , respectively. Moreover, the performed 3rd spraying application of both tested chemical insecticides (Malathion® and lambada) gave high general mean of reduction comprised 44% and 42 % , respectively (Table 1).

1.2. Season of 2019:

The results of the growing season of 2019 were similar to that results obtained in season of 2018. The general mean of reduction percentage for applied 1st spray of ahook® and naterlo oil® indicated that the efficiency of both tested oils upon the insect population gave values of reduction percentages 47 and 40% , respectively.

After the 2nd spraying application of the same tested phyto-natural Oils, these compounds showed lower values of deduced general mean of reduction percentages for ahook® followed by naterlo oil® and comprised 32 % and 27 % , respectively. In the carried out 3rd spray of both evaluated chemical. Insecticides,- malathion ® and lambda ®, general mean of reduction was detected and amounted to 37% and 32 % , respectively. In this concept, the above-mentioned results elucidate the possible use of consequent applications of natural plant oils and insecticides for controlling the occurring of the seed individuals on okra plants, and in the same time reduce the rate of insecticides application which mainly cause environmental pollution and hazardous problems related to agro-ecosystem (Table 2).

Table (1): Efficiency of both tested chemical / and phyto-compounds on the calculated reduction percentages of *Earias insulana* after three subsequent spray applications on okra plant in season of 2018.

Treatment	Inspected individuals	% Reduction						General reduction mean (%)
		(No.) pre-spray	Inspection period (days)					
	1		3		14			
	A *		B	A *	B **	A *	B **	
1st spray								
Achook®	30.00	21.00	45.00	19.00	50.00	12.00	65.00	53.00
Naterlo oil®	31.00	25.00	40.00	22.00	77.00	17.00	48.00	55.00
Control	35.00	33a		33a		30a		
L .S.D _{0.05}	3.38	1.99		2.95				
2nd spray								
Achook®	26a	20b	50.00	16a	60.00	13a	67.00	59.00
Naterlo oil®	33a	24b	24.00	23a	55.00	19a	58.00	45.00
Control	35a	30a		30a		30a		
L .S.D _{0.05}	2.61	2.06		2.06		1.77		
3rd spray								
Malathion®	33a	28	28.00	23.00	39.00	13a	65.00	44.00
Lambada®	33a	26	31.00	23a	39.00	16a	58.00	42.00
Control	36a	35		33a		26a		
L .S.D _{0.05}	1.77	4.43		2.38		1.77		

* A: mean number of insects **B : %Reduction .

Mean followed by the same letter(s) are not significantly different at 5% level .

Table (2) :Efficiency of both tested chemical / and phyto-compounds on the calculated reduction percentages of *Earias insulana* after three subsequent spray applications on okra plant in season of 2019 .

Treatment	Inspected individuals	% Reduction						General reduction mean (%)
		(No.) pre-spray	Inspection period (days)					
	1		3		14			
	A *		B **	A *	B **	A *	B **	
1st spray								
Achook®	37 ^a	20 ^a	45.00	20a	45.00	18.00	51.00	47.00
Naterlo oil®	30a	27a	43.00	26a	44.00	25.00	33.00	40.00
Control	30a	30a		5.67a		3a		
L .S.D _{0.05}	1.85	2.62		2.87		2.39		
2nd spray								
Achook®	27a	23a	20.00	16.00	44.00	17a	33.00	32.00
Naterlo oil®	27a	23a	26.00	22.00	23.00	19a	34.00	27.00
Control	30a	26a		26a		23a		
3rd spray								
Malathion®	37a	33a	46.00	30a	40.00	27a	27.00	37.00
lambada®	38.00	33a	45.00	27a	37.00	25a	16.00	32.00
Control	38a	36a		31a		30.00		
L .S.D _{0.05}	2.39	2.07		2.66		3.42		

* A: mean number of insects **B : %Reduction .

Mean followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different at 5% level .

2. Economic and profits of the tested insecticides to control *Earias insulana* in okra plant seasons (2018 and 2019).

1. Season of 2018:

This part of investigation is focused on the use of each of tested four chemical-compounds (Achook®, naterlo oil®, malathion® and lambad®), as tool for insects management, in order to push up the yield and to increase the return on the cash crop. The harvested post yields of the performed treatments as okra green pods for local marketing (Infested and healthy pods) amounted to (1 and 4.5),(1 and 4.5), (0.5 and 5) ,(0.5 and 5) and (2 and 4) ton/fed for achook®,naterlo oil®, malathion®,lambad® and control, in respect. The gross monetary return was worked out at 25000 pounds for healthy pods of okra pods and 10000 for infested okra pods. These returns amounted to 122500, 122500, 12970, 129710 and 120000 L.E./ fed for achook®,naterlo oil®, malathion ®, lambad® and control, in sequence. In general, spraying the different compounds gave higher yields of healthy pods rather than those obtained in the check (Table 3). In concern to the total costs of control/ fed (Treatments cost + labour costs). These constant service costs (Labourrases / fed) were expressed in the varied agricultural practices throughout the growing season of labourrases/ fed 200 (L.E.) for each of all performed treatments achook® and naterlo oil®, 100 (L.E.) for malathion ® and lambad®. Regarding the net returns; the calculated values were 122000, 122020, 129700, 129710 and 120000 L.E./ fed for achook®,naterlo oil®, malathion ®,lambad® and control, respectively. Moreover, extracted values of the additional return over the untreated control, in the different treatments were 2000, 2020, 9700, 9710 and 0,00 for achook®, naterlo oil®,

malathion ®,lambad®and control, successively. Through the profits for one Egyptian pounds (L.E.) investment were 2500, 2500 , 10000, 10000 and 0,00 for achook®,naterlo oil®, malathion ®,lambad® and control, respectively (Table 3). In the light of the calculated profits data, it could be concluded that the higher value is the utmost profitable treatment. However, depending upon the investment profits, the used chemicals could be arranged in a descending order as follows: malathion®>lambad®>achook ®>naterlo oil®.

2. Season of 2019:

At to for one season of 2018, season 2019 malathion ® and lambad® also gave the highest yield of harvested green pods 1-5 and 0,5-5 ton/ fed to infest and healthy okra pods. The gross monetary return was worked out at 120000 L.E./ ton for healthy pods of okra. These returns were 138000, 132000, 162000, 156000 and 114000 L.E./ fed for achook®, naterlo oil®, malathion ®,lambad®and control, in sequence. In general, spraying the different compounds gave higher yields rather than that obtained in the check (Table 4). In concern to the total costs of control were 500, 480, 300, 290 and 0.0 L.E./ fed for achook®,naterlo oil®, malathion ®,lambad® and control, respectively. Regarding the net returns, the calculated values L.E. / fed were 37500, 131520, 161700, 155710 and 114000 for achook®, naterlo oil®, malathion ®, lambad® and control, successively. But, for the estimated additional return over the untreated control in the different treatment ; it was comprising 23500,17520,47700,41710 and 0.00 , subsequent.(Table 4). The profits for one Egyptian pound (L.E.) investment were 24000,18000,48000, 42000 and 0.00 for achook®, naterlo oil®, malathion ®, lambad® and control. In the light of the obtained profits data, it could be mentioned that

the higher value is the utmost profitable treatment. However, depending upon the investment profits; these used insecticides could be arranged

descending as follows: Malathion > lambad > ahook > naterlo oil

Table (3): Economics and profits of certain treatments against the okra insect *Earias insulana* during the growing season of (2018) compared with untreated plants ((Control).

Treatments	No. of application	Okra pods Production (Ton/fed.)		* Infested Okra pods income/fed.	** Healthy Okra pods income/fed.	Gross income/fed. (L.E) (a)	Input costs/ feddan (L.E)			Net returns/fed. (L.E) (d)	Additional returns over untreated control (L.E) (e)	Profit of one pound investment (L.E) (f)
		Infested (Ton/fed.)	Healthy (Ton/fed.)				A treatment costs/fed. (L.E)	Labour wages/ fed. (b)	Total costs/ fed. (L.E) (C)			
Achook	2	1	4.5	10000	112500	122500	300	200	500	122000	2000	2500
Naterlo oil	2	1	4.5	10000	112500	122500	280	200	480	122020	2020	2500
Malathion	1	0.5	5	5000	125000	130000	200	100	300	129700	9700	10000
Lambad	1	0.5	5	5000	125000	130000	190	100	290	129710	9710	10000
Control	0	2	4	20000	100000	120000	0	0	0	120000	0	0

(a) : Worked out at L.E 25000/ ton for healthy pods of okra and 10000 for infested okra pods (ton/fed).

(b) : Worked out at L.E 100/ feddan × No. of sprays.

(c) : Total costs of control/ fedden = treatments costs +labour costs / feddan.

(d): Net returns/ feddan = (Gross income/ feddan) - (Total costs / feddan).

(e) : Additional returns= Net returns- control returns.

(f): Profit for one Egyptian pound= Additional returns÷ Total costs.

* Market price for one ton/ healthy okra pods = 25000 L.E.

Table (4): Economics and profits of certain treatments against the okra insect , *Earias insulana* during the growing season of (2018-2019) compared with untreated plants (Control).

Treatments	No. of application	Okra pods Production (Ton/fed.)		Infested Okra pods income/fed. *	Healthy Okra pods income/fed. **	Gross income/fed. (L.E) (a)	Input costs/ feddan (L.E)			Net returns/fed. (L.E) (d)	Additional returns over untreated control (L.E) (e)	Profit of one pound investment (L.E) (f)
		Infested (Ton/fed.)	Healthy (Ton/fed.)				A	Labour wages/ fed.	Total costs/ fed.			
control	0			24000	90000	114000	0	0	0	114000	0	0
lambada	1	0.5	5	6000	150000	156000	190	100	290	155710	41710	42000
Malathion	1	1	5	12000	150000	162000	200	100	300	161700	47700	48000
Naterlo oil	2	1	4	12000	120000	132000	280	200	480	131520	17520	18000
Achook	2	1.5	4	18000	120000	138000	300	200	500	137500	23500	24000

(a) : Worked out at L.E30000/ ton for healthy pods of okra and 12000 for infested okra pods (ton/fed).

(b) : Worked out at L.E 100/ feddan × No. of sprays.

(c) : Total costs of control/ fedden = treatments costs +labour costs / feddan.

(d) : Net returns/ feddan = (Gross income/ feddan) - (Total costs / feddan).

(e) : Additional returns= Net returns- control returns.

(f): Profit for one Egyptian pound= Additional returns† Total costs.

* Market price for one ton/ healthy okra pods = 30000 L.E.

** Market price for one ton / infested okra pods = 12000 L.E.

Okra crop are liable to attack by several insect- pests, throughout the elapsing period from the early stage up to the late

development and the post-harvest stage. Many insects belonging to the orders of Lepidoptera, Diptera, Hemiptera and

Homoptera are well known injurious insects of okra plants. The harvested post yields of the performed treatments as okra green pods for local marketing (infested and healthy pods) amounted to (1 and 4.5),(1 and 4.5), (0.5 and 5) ,(0.5 and 5) and (2 and 4) ton/fed for ahook®, naterlo oil®, malathion ®, lambda® and control, in respect. These returns amounted to 122000, 122020, 129700, 129710 and 120000 L.E./ fed as agross income for ahook®, naterlo oil®, malathion ®, lambda® and control, in sequence. These constant service costs (Labour rases / fed) were expressed in the varied agricultural practices throughout the growing season of labour rases/ fed 200 (L.E.) for each of all performed treatments ahook® and naterlo oil®, 100(L.E.) for malathion ® and lambda. Moreover, extracted values of the additional return over the untreated control, in the different treatments were 2000, 2020, 9700, 9710 and 0,00 for ahook®, naterlo oil®, malathion ®, lambda® and control, successively. Through the profits for one Egyptian pounds (L.E.) investment were 24000, 18000, 48000, 42000 and 0,00 for ahook®, naterlo oil®, malathion ®, lambda® and control, respectively. These net returns were 137500, 131520, 161700, 155710and 114000 L.E./ fed for ahook®, naterlo oil®, malathion ®, lambda® and control, in sequence season 2019. Cost of insecticide applications, development of resistance in pest population exposed to repeated insecticide treatments and adverse environmental effects of insecticides demand the minimization of chemical controls whenever possible.

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Ecological studies on two mealybug species (Hemiptera) and their predator on navel orange trees at Qalubiya Governorate, Egypt

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Abstract:

Citrus mealybug *Planococcus citri* (Risso) (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) and Egyptian fluted mealybug, *Icerya aegyptiaca* (Douglus) (Hemiptera: Monophlebidea) are serious insect pests, attack the navel orange trees and cause a severely considerable damage. The present study aimed to determine mealybug generations under the studied conditions and the proper time for their control. Field studies were carried out on *P. citri* and *I. aegyptiaca* on 100 navel orange leaves and 25 twigs in half monthly samples, at a private farm in Qalubiya Governorate, Egypt throughout two years 2018 and 2019. The obtained results showed that *P. citri* population had three peaks of infestation in the first year (2018) in June 1st, July 2nd and August 2nd. In the second year (2019) two peaks were recorded on 1st week of July and 2nd week of September. The Egyptian mealybug *I. aegyptiaca* had one peak in both years occurred in the second week of September in first year and in second week of October the second year. Two peaks of abundance during the first year 2018 recorded for the associated predator, *Rodolia cardinalis* (Mulsant) (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), in June 2nd and in the October 1st. During the second year of study, it had two peaks in June 1st and October 1st. There was simultaneous occurrence of the total population of *P. citri* and *I. aegyptiaca* and its associated predator *R. cardinalis*. Positive correlation between Max., Min. temperatures and the total population of *P. citri* and *I. aegyptiaca* was determined. On the other side there were negative correlation of relative humidity and total population during the two years of study.

Introduction

Citrus is the most important fruit in Egypt as far as its acreage, production and exportation potentials are concerned (El-Kassas, 1984). Mealybugs are serious insect pests, attack the citrus trees and cause a severely considerable damage under the prevailing agroecosystems in Egypt.

These insects are sucking pest of plant sap and secret large amount of the honey dew which encourage the growth of sooty mold fungi, that consequently reduce the photosynthesis and respiration of plant leaves. Usually, occurrence of the sever infestation lead to the death of the whole trees (Radwan, 2003).

The citrus mealybug, *Planococcus citri* (Risso) (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) is an important pest attacking several crops. Biotic and abiotic factors, as well as the substrate they feed on influence its population (Correa *et al.*, 2005). The citrus mealy bug infested 65 plant species belonging to 56 genera in 36 families and distributed in 20 Governorates. *P. citri* prefers citrus followed by guava and grape (Ahmed and Abd-Rabou, 2010).

The genus *Icerya* includes about 35 species in the world that are commonly known as fluted scales because of the fluted appearance of the ovisac. The Egyptian fluted mealybug, *Icerya aegyptiaca* (Douglus) (Hemiptera: Monophlebidea) has the most distributed in the world and with numerous host plants. It is commonly known as Egyptian *Icerya*, because of it is original description from Egypt. This monophlebid scale causes considerable damage on *Mangifera indica* and tropical fruit trees in Chahbahar (Moghaddam *et al.*, 2015).

Therefore, the present study aimed to shedding light on two species of mealybugs infesting navel orange trees and their associated predatory insect as well as their seasonal abundances in Qalubiya Governorate, Egypt. And to determine its generations under the studied conditions and the proper time for their control.

Materials and methods

The present studies were conducted at a private farm in Qalubiya Governorate, Egypt. All the agricultural practice was carried out except the insecticide's applications. To evaluate the seasonal abundance of the mealybug species and their associated predators, 100 navel orange leaves and 25 twigs were taken from five navel orange trees of the same age and same size as half monthly samples (each tree

was considered as a replicate and 20 leaves and five twigs were taken randomly from each tree representing the four cardinal directions). Samples were collected half monthly from early January till the end of December during the two successive years 2018 and 2019. The collected samples were transferred to the laboratory in paper bags for examination by the aid of a binocular stereomicroscope. Identification of mealybug species and their insect predator was done by taxonomy specialists at the Department of Scale Insects and Mealy bugs, Plant Protection Research Institute, Dokki, Egypt. The mealybug species and their associated insect predators for each sample were identified and counted. The upper and lower surfaces of the leaves were carefully examined. The rate of increase/decrease in population densities was calculated by dividing the mean number of insects found in the sample over that found in preceding one as described by (Bodenheimer, 1951). Statistical analysis for the data were analyzed by using one-way ANOVA by Costat software program (2004).

Results and discussion

1. The population abundance of two mealybug species and their predator:

1.1. Population density of *Planococcus citri*:

The obtained results in Figure (1) showed that the estimated fluctuating densities of the *P. citri* population indicated three peaks of infestation in the first year (2018). These peaks occurred in June 1st, July 2nd and August 2nd with values of 320, 512 and 685 individuals, respectively. In the second year (2019), two peaks were recorded on 1st week of July (362 individuals) and 2nd week of September (457 individuals) as shown in Figure (2).

Figure (1): Population density of *Planococcus citri* on navel orange trees in 2018.

Figure (2): Population density of *Planococcus citri* on navel orange trees in 2019.

1.2. Population density of *Icerya aegyptiaca*:

The Egyptian mealybug *I. aegyptiaca* had one peak in the first year, occurred in the second week of September (148 individuals) as shown in Figure (3). In the second year (2019) one peak was recorded in the second week of October (112 individuals) as shown in Figure (4). These results are similar to those of (Ghanim *et al.*, 2013) who studied the population density of mealybug species attacking mandarin trees. They found that, the highest peak of *P. citri* on October while, *I. seychellarum* and *I. aegyptiaca* were recorded in September during the two years of study. Another study by

(Moustafa, 2012) on citrus trees in Behira showed that the insect population of *P. citri* reached maximum population of *P. citri* reached maximum during May in first and second years, respectively, also results indicated that citrus mealybug, *P. citri* has two peaks on citrus trees in Cairo. Mesbah (2008) in Egypt recorded *P. citri* and *I. aegyptiaca* infesting pomegranate and occurred with high numbers during the two seasons 2005 and 2006. Our results of *P. citri* disagree with those of (Awadalla, 2017) who recorded two peaks of citrus mealybug *P. citri* on pomegranate trees in Mansoura, and agreed with those recorded for *I. aegyptiaca* (One peak of abundance during 2014 and 2015).

El-Sobky, 2020

Figure (3): Population density of *Icerya aegyptiaca* on navel orange trees in 2018.

Figure (4): Population density of *Icerya aegyptiaca* on navel orange trees in 2019.

1.3. Population density of associated predator *Rodolia cardinalis*:

Data illustrated in Figure (5) revealed that, *R. cardinalis* had two peaks of abundance during the first year 2018, the first one was recorded in the June 2nd (25 individuals) and the second peak in the October 1st (32 individuals). During the second year of study, *R.*

cardinalis had two peaks in June 1st and October 1st, and represented by 21 and 35 individuals, respectively as illustrated in Figure (5). (Ghanim *et al.*, 2013) recorded that this predator associated with the mealybug species and had three peaks in Mandarin trees at Mansoura district.

Figure (5): Population density of *Rodolia cardinalis* on navel orange trees in 2018 and 2019.

2. Number of annual generations:

The mealybug *P.citri* has three annual generations throughout the first year of study (2018), and two annual generations throughout the second year of study (2019) of the insect population under field condition at Qalubiya Governorate. During the first year of investigation, the percentage of nymphal population of *P.citri* recorded 84%, 74% and 72.7 % of total population through June 1st, July 2nd and August 2nd, respectively. In the 2nd year (2019), two annual generations existed, in July 1st (79 %) and September 2nd (74%). The mealybug *I. aegyptiaca* has one annual generation, and these results were ensured throughout the two years of study of the insect population under field condition at Qalubiya Governorate. The percentage of nymph population of *I. aegyptiaca* recorded 67.5% of total population in September 2nd and 64.3% of total population in October 2nd in first and second years of study, respectively.

Results concerning the Monthly variation rate (MVR) of population

density of *P. citri* clearly show that the favorable periods for its development and population increase were at April, June and September where (MVR) values averaged 2.1, 2.9 and 1.9, respectively as shown in Figure (6). In the second year the highest values of (MVR) were in February (1.5), July (2.4), and September (1.9) as shown in Figure (6). Monthly variation rate (MVR) of population density of *I. aegyptiaca* illustrated in Figure (7) shows that the favorable periods for its development and population increase were at February, July and August where (MVR) values averaged 1.8, 2.4 and 1.6, respectively. In the second year the highest values of (MVR) were in February (1.6), March (2.6), and June (2.1) as shown in Figure (7). These results are in harmony with (Khalil *et al.*, 2011) who found three annual generations of the purple scale *Lepidosaphes beckii* Newm. (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) on navel orange throughout the two years of study of the insect population under field condition at El-Behaira.

Figure (6): Monthly variation rate (MVR) of population density of *Planococcus citri* on navel orange trees in 2018 and 2019.

Figure (7): Monthly variation rate (MVR) of population density of *Icerya aegyptiaca* on navel orange trees in 2018 and 2019.

3. The relationship between *Planococcus citri* and *Icerya aegyptiaca* and their associated insect predator *Rodolia cardinalis*:

The obtained results showed that there was simultaneous occurrence of the total population of *P. citri* and *I. aegyptiaca* and its associated predator *R. cardinalis*.

The obtained results are in agreement with the finding of (Mesbah, 2008) in Egypt, suggested that, the relationship between the predator *R. cardinalis* and *I. aegyptiaca* showed a significant difference during the two season 2005 and 2006. Also, (Mani and Krishnamoorthy, 2000) in India, recorded that, the natural enemies parasitoids and predators effectively reduced the population density of *P. citri*. Developmental stages of *R. cardinalis* have been found to be associated with populations of *I. aegyptiaca* on *Ficus nitida* trees in the Mansoura district of Egypt. The development of *R. cardinalis* larvae when reared in culture on *Icerya aegyptiaca* (Douglas)

(Hemiptera: Coccoidea: Monophlebidae) was significantly faster than that fed on *Icerya purchasi* Maskell (Hemiptera: Coccoidea:

Monophlebidae). The results indicate that *R. cardinalis* is well adapted to *I. aegyptiaca* in Egypt (Ragab, 1991). This work agrees with the findings recorded by Hamid and Hassanian (1991) who recorded the predator *R. cardinalis* associated with monophlebid, *Icerya* spp.

4. Effect of prevailing hygro-thermic condition on the population density of *Planococcus citri* and *Icerya aegyptiaca*:

The effect of Max., Min. temperatures and relative humidity on the total population of *P. citri* and *I. aegyptiaca* during the two studied years determined positive correlation between Max., Min. temperatures and the total population ($r = 0.51$ and 0.53) in the two years of study respectively, while the higher temperatures, the higher population. On the other side there were week negative correlation of relative humidity and total population value (r) was -0.243 and -0.314 during the two years of study in Qalubiya Governorate respectively. Ahmed and Abd-Rabou (2010) observed that the host plants and temperature greatly influenced on the development of *P. citri* and the lowering of temperature increase the dimension of the mealybug

and lengthen the developmental period. These results agreed with (Zaki *et al.*, (2013) mentioned that there were significant effects of temperatures on *I. seychellarum* total population during 2011 and there were insignificant effects of relative humidity during the two years of study in Qalyubia and Giza Governorates. Also, (Moustafa, 2012) reported that there were positively high significant correlations between *I. seychellarum* population and both of mean temperature and relative humidity at Demyata Governorate.

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Aloencyrtus coelops (Hymenoptera: Encyrtidae) a new record of parasitoid associated with *Waxiella mimosae mimosae* (Hemiptera: Coccidae) in Egypt

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Abstract

Aloencyrtus coelops (Waterston) (Hymenoptera: Encyrtidae) is an endoparasitoid was found for first time in Egypt associated with *Waxiella mimosae mimosae* (Signoret) (Hemiptera: Coccidae) infesting tamarix trees in Giza Governorate during 2020.

Keywords

Parasitoid, *Aloencyrtus coelops*, *Waxiella mimosae*, new record and Egypt.

Introduction

Wax scale insects (Hemiptera: Coccidae) are considered a serious insect pest infesting horticultural plants causing severe damages. It has a piercing sucking mouth parts which suck the plant sap causing plant weakness especially in the heavy infestation and it turns to yellow then brown, dry and fell. Also, wax scale insects secrete honey dew in large amounts where the black sooty mould fungi grows and it blocks the photosynthesis and respiration processes of the plant. These insects located in most plant parts (Leaves, stem, and branches) and infesting several plant species like shrubs and trees (Copland, 1984 and Abd-Rabou, 2003).

Waxiella mimosae mimosae (Signoret) (Hemiptera: Coccidae) is a wax scale insect distributed mainly in the Afrotropical region (De Lotto, 1969 and Ben-Dov, 1993 and 2008). There were many parasitoids related to Family Encyrtidae were recorded associated

with *W. mimosae* in Egypt and around the world. These are *Anicetus africanus* (Girault), *Bothriophryne acaciae* (Risbec), *Bothriophryne tenuicornis* (Mercet), *Metaphycus aneckei* Guerrieri and Noyes, *Metaphycus lounsburyi* (Howard) and *Parechthrodryinus coccidiphagus* (Mercet) (Ben-Dov and Guerrieri, 2009 and Evans and Abd-Rabou, 2013).

The parasitoid *Aloencyrtus coelops* (Waterston) (Hymenoptera: Encyrtidae) is considered one of the most important parasitoids associated with *W. mimosae* (Trjapitzin, 2019). The aim of this study is to collect and identify the parasitoids associated with *W. mimosae* in different locations in Egypt.

Materials and methods

The infested leaves of tamarix trees, *Tamarix* sp. with *W. mimosae* were collected from Giza Governorate and were kept in polyethylene bags until transferred to the laboratory to be

examined by the aid of stereomicroscope binocular. The different stages of *W. mimosae* were separated and kept in a glass test tubes until emergence of adult parasitoid.

Results and discussion

The parasitoid *A.coelops* was collected for the first time as a new record in Egypt from Giza Governorate by the authors in 2020 and was found associated with *Waxiella mimosae mimosae* (Signoret) (Hemiptera:Coccoidea: Coccidae) infesting tamrix trees. The parasitoid *A. coelops* was found associated with coccids in several countries mainly in Afrotropical countries, *W. mimosae* in South Africa (Prinsloo 1983), Nigeria associated with *Ceroplastes vuilleti* Marchal, Republic of South-Africa from

Ceroplastes (Now *Waxiella*) *africana senegalensis* infesting *Acacia karroo* (Fabaceae), Eritrea from *C. africana* Green and from *Ceroplastes destructor* Newstead infesting *Melia azedarach* (Meliaceae) (Trjapitzin, 2019).

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**Organic acids as a botanical geographical marker of Egyptian, Chinese and German
bee pollens**

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Bee pollens, organic acids, high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) analysis, China and Germany.

Abstract:

Organic acids in bee pollen samples represented from different geographically regions of Egypt, China and Germany countries were estimated using high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) as a chemical marker of these regions. The number of organic acids present in samples of tested bee pollens were eight in Egyptian, six in Chinese and five in German organic acids bee pollens. There was only one organic acid (Citric acid) commonly found in the all tested types of bee pollens. Oxalic acid it can be used to differentiate between German bee pollen and the other under study. Also, malonic acid was absent in Chinese pollen while it was found in other bee pollens tested. So, organic acids can be used to distinguish among the main different types of pollens (Egyptian, Chinese and German).

Introduction

Bee pollen be a healthy foodstuff with an extensive variety of therapeutic properties (Feás *et al.*, 2012). Bees collect pollen from numerous plant anthers, mix it with secretions from their salivary glands or nectar, place it in specific baskets located at their hind legs, and transfer it to the hive (Komosinska-Vassev *et al.*, 2015). However, many factors can contribute for the composition of bee pollen, such as the plant source, the climate and weather conditions, the characteristics of the soil, as well as the actions of the beekeeper (Pereira *et al.*, 2006 and Shubharani *et al.*, 2013). A mixture of flower pollen from different species is agglutinated by nectar and honeybee enzymes (e.g. amylase, catalase) secreted by salivary glands

and pollen loads are formed, which are recognized as bee pollen in the form of granules, two hundred substances were found in the pollen grains from different plant species, the group of basic chemical substances is proteins, amino acids, carbohydrates, lipids and fatty acids, phenolic compounds, enzymes, and coenzymes as well as vitamins and bio elements (Campos *et al.*, 2008 and 2010).

Any significant deficiency in the elemental content of rock, soil, and water affects the elemental content of plants growing in a region, which directly affects the nectar and pollen (Hernández *et al.*, 2005). The chemical composition of pollen is diverse and complex (Kroyer and Hegedus, 2001). And it varies significantly, according to the botanical and geographical origin of

the pollen grains that make up the pollen loads. The composition of the grains, in their turn, suffers the influence of the soil and climate conditions, age and nutritional state of the plant during the development of the grain. In the same plant species there can be variations in pollen composition according to region, season of the year, and even between years (Funari *et al.*, 2003; Almeida- Muradian *et al.*, 2005; Melo *et al.*, 2009 and Silveira, 2012). Approximately 250 substances can be found in this product (Komosinska-Vassev *et al.*, 2015). Physico-chemical composition of pollen samples collected in State of São Paulo, Brazil, average were 21.5% proteins, 2.8% ashes, 23.6% moisture, 76.3% of dry residue, 3.5% lipids, 28.4% of total sugars, 20.7 mEq/kg of titrate acidity and pH = 5.1. The bromatological characterization of bee pollen from Argentina was made by (Coronel *et al.*, 2004). The organic acids composition varies depending upon the species, age of the plant and the vegetable tissue. In *E. plantagineum* bee pollen hydromethanolic extract eight organic acids were identified: oxalic, aconitic, citric, pyruvic, malonic, shikimic, acetic and fumaric acids. Although organic acids represent less than 0.5% of honey's constituent, they make important contributions to organoleptic, physical and chemical properties of honey (Inés *et al.*, 2006). Malonic and acetic acids are the precursors for fatty acids biosynthesis furthermore, shikimic and malonic acids are precursors of phenolic compounds, a heterogeneous group from a metabolic point of view, presenting antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anti-allergic activities (Avni *et al.*, 2014). Certain substances, such as ascorbic acid, amines, carbohydrates, and sulfur-containing compounds, can also react with phosphomolybdic and phosphotungstic acids of the reagent

used (Huang *et al.*, 2005). Organic acids can also be used as predictors of fermentation, antioxidant activity and as botanical geographical markers (Mato *et al.*, 2003).

The aim of this study was to use organic acid to distinguish among different types of bee pollen from Egypt, China and Germany.

Materials and methods

The present investigation was carried out in Bee Research Department, Plant Protection Research Institute, during year 2019 to determine organic acids in 3 types of Egyptian, China and Germany pollen's. Pollen samples were collected from different regions from Egypt, China and Germany. These pollen types were determination of organic acids by using high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).

1. Determination of organic compounds in pollen samples by HPLC:

Approximately, 3g of freeze-dried pollen were transferred to Eppendorf tube with 5mL of distilled water. Then the extract was centrifuged (15,000 rpm, 4°C, 10min) and the supernatant was separated with membrane filter (0.45µm) and transferred to vials. Organic acids in pollen were Identification by a JASCO HPLC, using a hypersil C reversed-phase column [250x4.66 mm] with 5 µm particle size. A constant flow rate of 0.7 ml/min sulphuric acid in distilled water Ph. 2.45 was used as mobile phases; the detector set at wavelength 210 nm, the concentration of individual compound was calculated on the basis of the peak area measurements. All chemicals and solvents were used in HPLC spectral grade (Anna *et al.*, 1994).

The data were statistically analyzed using one way ANOVA. LSD was used to evaluate the significant

difference between means (comparison of means) at the level of $P < 0.05$ level.

Results and discussion

Data in Table (1) and Figure (1) represent the organic acids that can be found in the bee pollens under investigation. Twelve organic acids were detected in analyzing of three bee pollen types under investigation by using HPLC (Figure 2). They were oxalic, formic, tartaric, shikmic, malonic, maleic, citric, succinic, proponic, butyric, lactic and adipic acids. Only one of them (Citric acid) commons and was in the all tested bee pollen; its highest concentrations was detected in Chinese bee pollen 0.5453 mg/100 followed by 0.0185, 0.0043 mg/100 in Egyptian and German bee pollen respectively. On the other hand, formic acid, it was absent in any bee pollen under investigation. However, tartaric and adipic acids was characterized of Egyptian bee pollen the concentrations were 0.3012, 0.0053 mg/100g respectively. While oxalic acid and malonic acid distinguishes alone of German bee pollen the concentrations were 0.0048, 0.0433

mg/100g. maleic acid not detected in the Chinese bee pollen but found high significant concentration in German and Egyptian bee pollen were 5.9715 and 0.0035mg/100g respectively. Four organic acids in different concentrations were detected in Egyptian and Chinese bee pollen its shikmic acid 0.0029, 0.0390 mg/100g, succinic acid 0.0940, 0.2118 mg/100g respectively without significant differences and proponic acid 2.6693, 5.2253 mg/100g, lactic acid 0.0744, 0.7181 respectively with high significant differences. Butyric acid detected only in Chinese and German bee pollen with high significant differences the concentrations were 5.8148, 0.7090 mg/100g respectively.

Finally, numbers of organic acids present in samples bee pollens was eight in Egyptian, six in Chinese and five organic acids in German bee pollens; but found highly significant differences in the sum organic acids concentrations of Chinese, German and Egyptian bee pollen were 12.5542, 6.7326 and 3.1789 mg/100g., respectively.

Table (1): Organic acids concentration (mg/100g) in three bee pollen types (Egyptian, Chinese and German).

Organic acids	Egyptian bee pollen	Chinese bee pollen	German bee pollen	P < 0.05
Oxalic	0.0000	0.0000	0.0048±0.0010	
Formic	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	
Tartaric	0.3109±0.0861	0.0000	0.0000	
Shikmic	0.0029±0.0005	0.0390±0.0098	0.0000	0.0031**
Malonic	0.0000	0.0000	0.0431±0.0101	
Maleic	0.0035±0.0012 ^b	0.0000	5.9715±1.0023 ^a	0.0005***
Citric	0.0185±0.0012 ^b	0.5452±0.1001 ^a	0.0043±0.0011 ^b	0.0004***
Succinic	0.0940±0.0104 ^a	0.2118±0.0993 ^a	0.0000±0.0000	0.1157 ^{ns}
Proponic	2.6693±0.9993 ^b	5.2253±0.9995 ^a	0.0000±0.0000	0.0315*
Butyric	0.0000±0.0000	5.8148±0.9997 ^a	0.7090±0.0997 ^b	0.0009***
Lactic	0.0744±0.0126 ^b	0.7181±0.1002 ^a	0.0000	0.0004***
Adipic	0.0053±0.0011	0.0000	0.0000	
Sum	3.1789±1.1123	12.5542±2.3085	6.7326±1.1141	0.0037***

Values within the same row with different superscript letters are significantly different, $P < 0.05$

Figure (1): Organic acids concentration in three bee pollen types (Egyptian, Chinese and German).

Figure (2): Peak intensity HPLC chromatogram of organic acids separation from Egyptian (E), German (G) and Chinese (C) bee pollens.

Many factors can contribute for the composition of bee pollen, such as the plant source, the climate and weather conditions, the characteristics of the soil, as well as the actions of the beekeeper (Pereira *et al.*, 2006 and

Shubharani *et al.*, 2013). The organic acids composition varies depending upon the species, age of the plant and the vegetable tissue. In *E. plantagineum* bee pollen hydromethanolic extract eight organic acids were

identified: oxalic, aconitic, citric, pyruvic, malonic, shikimic, acetic and fumaric acids were 51.05, 6.89, 10.24, 890.27, 8152.87, 2.20, 1132.02, 0.48 mg/kg respectively (Moita *et al.*, 2014). Malonic and acetic acids are the precursors for fatty acids biosynthesis. Furthermore, shikimic and malonic acids are precursors of phenolic compounds, a heterogeneous group from a metabolic point of view, presenting antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anti-allergic activities (Avni *et al.*, 2014). And according to Tomas-Lorente *et al.* (1992) bee pollen made up of natural flower pollen mixed with nectar and bee secretions, and was rich in sugars, proteins, lipids, vitamins and flavonoids (3–5% dry weight). Pollen may get to the nectar or honey by many ways (Jones and Bryant, 2014). Diversity of the physical and chemical properties of honey depends on the nectar and pollen of the original plant, colour, flavour, moisture and contents of proteins and sugars (Barth, 1989 and Pascoal *et al.*, 2014). Honey contains naturally organic acids (Bogdanov *et al.*, 1997). According to honey origin it is a wide range, found the organic acid of honey (Crane, 1990). The acids from clover honey were butyric, acetic, formic, lactic succinic, pyroglutamic, malic, citric and gluconic, while oxalic acid was tentatively identified when isolated by ion exchange adsorption (Stinson *et al.*, 1960). Zhu *et al.*, (2010) determined 5 organic acids (l-malic acid, malic acid, succinic acid, citric acid and d-malic acid) in honey. El Mohandes (2011) she found that Formic acid and Malonic acid were present in all Egyptian floral honeys. By Nelson and Mottern (1931) found that citric acid was present in all floral honeys. Also, Suarez-Luque *et al.*, (2002) identified malic, maleic, citric, succinic and fumaric acids in honeys. (Nafea *et al.*, 2013) oxalic, shikimic,

butyric and benzoic acids were not detected in any of the eight tested honeys of Saudi Arabia formic and malonic acid were present in all tested honeys and suggested that percentages of organic acid in Saudian honeys their differing due to the differences in location and botanical origin of honey.

Types and quantity of organic acids in Egyptian, Chinese and German bee pollen were due to the differences in location and botanical origin of bee pollen. Finally, organic acids may be used to distinguish among the main types for Egyptian, Chinese and German bee pollen.

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Coccoidea species infesting ornamental plants in the Royal greenhouse, Al-Montaza palace garden, Alexandria, Egypt with new hosts record and a key of the adult female Coccoidea

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Abstract:

This Investigation covers a survey of the scale insects (Hemiptera:Coccoidea) infesting ornamental plants in the Historical Royal greenhouse at Al-Montaza Palace garden, Alexandria Governorate, Egypt. A total of nine Coccoidea species following nine genera belonging to 3 families were observed infesting twenty ornamental plants in the greenhouse. New hosts recorded for the first time during the study as well as a key of the adult female Coccoidea to help in future investigations and identification in Egypt were given.

Introduction

The Royal greenhouse at Al-Montaza garden, Alexandria Governorate, Egypt concedes one of the most historical touristic attractions in Egypt. In 1934 King Fouad established the Royal greenhouse to become the most magnificent nature reserves. It is in the Eastern side of Montaza palace garden in Alexandria, Egypt. It is about one faddan with ten-meter-high, with glass roof. It includes rare species of palm trees and finest rare ornamental plants species. Insect pests are regarded as one of the important injurious responsible for the deterioration of ornamental plants especially in greenhouses, the warm, humid conditions and abundant food in inside provide an excellent, stable environment for pest development. Out of that pests, the Coccoidea which constitute the most common insect pests of ornamental plants (Mourad *et al.*, 2001 and Abdel-Razak, 2000).

Scale insects have been reported as serious pests attacking a huge number of host plants around the world (Miller *et al.*, 2002; Miller, 2005; Germain, 2008; Kondo *et al.*, 2008; Franco *et al.*, 2009; Pellizzari and Germain, 2010; Mazzeo *et al.*, 2014 and Mansour *et al.*, 2017). These insects are found on various parts of their hosts, and infest leaves, twigs, branches and roots (Kondo *et al.*, 2008). They feed almost exclusively on the phloem of their host plants to which they cause direct damage, but they can also cause indirect damage by transmitting plant pathogens through injection or through the build-up of honeydew (Ross *et al.*, 2010). Overall, scale insects that have worldwide been reported as economically important belong to the families Diaspididae, Coccidae, and Pseudococcidae. Soft scales and mealybugs secrete large amounts of honeydew on which a black fungus, known as "Sooty mould" grows. The

fungus covers the leaves and reduces their photosynthetic ability (Abdel-Razak, 2007). Gutierrez and Ponti, (2014) stated that, climate change is expected to alter the geographic distribution and abundance of many species, to increase the invasion of new areas by exotic species and in some cases, to lead to species extinction as well as the world-wide commerce can spread the injurious Coccoidea over the earth, as they are so easily carried with many different ways. Therefore, identification morphological keys to identify exist and nonsexist adult female Coccoidea species must be considered to help in the future identification.

Therefore, the present study was initiated for surveying and identifying Coccoidea species associated with ornamental plants and palm ornamental species in the Royal greenhouse at Al-Montaza garden to help in preserve the natural historical magnificent of that place for better controlling the found Coccoidea species.

Material and methods

In order to survey the Coccoidea species infesting ornamental plants and rare palm ornamental inside the Royal green house at Al-Montaza palace garden, Alexandria Governorate, Egypt. A total of 70 ornamental plants and palms ornamental were chosen belonging to 10 plant families. The surveyed plants for the study were, *Adiantum* sp. , (Pteridaceae), *Codiaeum variegatum pictum* , (Euphorbiaceae), *Polyscias balfourina*, *Schefflera actinophylla*, (Araliaceae), *Monstera acuminata deliciosa*, *Anthurium andraeanum*, *Anthurium pentaplyllum*, *Epipremnum aureum*, *Dieffenbachia seguine*, (Araceae), *Sanchezia speciose*, (Acanthaceae), *Beaucarnea recurvate*, *Dracena Marginata*, (Asparagaceae), *Nephrolepis exaltata*, (Nephrolepidaceae), *Howea belmoreana*, *Caryota mitis*, *Chamaedorea elegans*, *Dypsis lutescens*, *latania borbonica*, (Arecaceae), *Zamia fairchildiana*, (Zamiaceae), *Ficus benjamina*, (Moraceae) (Table 1).

Table (1): Host plant families selected to survey Coccoidea species at the Royal greenhouse, El-Montaza palace garden, Alexandria, Egypt.

Plant families	Host plants				
Acanthaceae	<i>Sanchezia speciose</i>				
Araceae	<i>Monstera acuminata deliciosa</i>	<i>Anthurium andraeanum</i>	<i>Anthurium pentaplyllum</i>	<i>Epipremnum aureum</i>	<i>Dieffenbachia seguine</i>
Araliaceae	<i>Polyscias balfourina</i>	<i>Schefflera actinophylla</i>			
Arecaceae	<i>Howea belmoreana</i>	<i>Caryota mitis</i>	<i>Chamaedorea elegans</i>	<i>Dypsis lutescens</i>	<i>latania borbonica</i>
Asparagaceae	<i>Beaucarnea recurvata</i>	<i>Dracena Marginata</i>			
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Codiaeum variegatum pictum</i>				
Moraceae	<i>Ficus benjamina</i>				
Nephrolepidaceae	<i>Nephrolepis exaltata</i>				
Pteridaceae	<i>Adiantum cuneatum</i>				
Zamiaceae	<i>Zamia fairchildiana</i>				

The Survey of the studied plants started from March, 2013 up to February, 2014. Five ornamental and palm plants of each species were chosen to the survey study.

Five leaves and five small branches were picked out at random or counting in the greenhouse depending on the rare of the plant at two weeks 'intervals.

Samples and collecting insects transferred to the laboratory for counting and classifying the existing individuals of detected species. Both upper and lower surface of the leaves were examined.

As for classifying the collected species, either temporary or permanent slides making techniques were made of the mature adult female as stated by McKenzie, 1969; Ezz, 1965 and Sirisena *et al.*, 2013 and examined microscopically and then classified taxonomically using scale insect's keys.

In order to design a key to the adult female Coccoidea for identify exist and nonsexist adult female Coccoidea species in Egypt .

For helping in the future identification, information for the character was compiled from the literature, Hall, 1922, 1924, 1925, 1926a, 1926b, 1926c; Ferris, 1950, 1953; McKenzie, 1956, 1969; Ezzat, 1958; Ezzat and Hussein, 1969; Ezzat and Nada, 1986; Watson, 1988; Mohammad and Ghabbour, 2008; (Monammad *et al.*, 1995; Williams and Watson, 1990; Williams and Hodgson, 1994; Hodgson, 1994; Mohammad and Nada, 1995 and Mohammad *et al.*, 1997.

Results and discussions

Data in Table (2) asserted that a total of nine Coccoidea species following nine genera belonging to 3 families were observed infesting twenty ornamental plants in the Royal greenhouse at Al-Montaza palace garden, Alexandria, Egypt from March, 2013 up to Feb, 2014.

The collected scale insect species could be listed taxonomically as follows: The capparidis wax scale, *Coccus capparidis* (Green) (Coccidae); the hemispherical scale, *Saissetia coffeae* (Walker) (Coccidae); the barnacle wax scale, *Ceroplastes cirripediformis* Comstock (Coccidae); the urbicola soft scale, *Pulvinaria urbicola* Cockerell (Coccidae); the latania scale, *Hemiberlesia lataniae* (Signoret) (Diaspididae); the boisduval scale *Diaspis boisduvalii* Signoret (Diaspididae); the date palm scale, *Parlatoria blanchardi* (Targioni Tozzetti) (Diaspididae); the black scale, *Chrysomphalus aonidum* (Linnaeus) (Diaspididae) and the citrus mealybug, *Planococcus citri* (Risso) (Pseudococcidae). Considering the host ornamental plants infested with the abovementioned Coccoidea species, the results could be presented as follows (Table 2):

1. Family: Pteridaceae

1.1. *Adiantum cuneatum*

Two species of soft scale insects belongs to Family: Coccidae, were recorded infesting *Adiantum cuneatum* in the Royal green house. They were the capparidis wax scale *C. capparidis* and the hemispherical scale *S. coffeae* . Ben-Dov (1980 and 2012) recorded *C. capparidis* for the first time in the Mediterranean region infesting Myoporaceae: *Myoporum acuminatum*. Rutaceae: *Citrus aurantium*, *C. paradise*. According to ScaleNet (2020), *S. coffeae* recorded from several host plants belonging to Family: Pteridaceae and *Adiantum* sp. from them.

2. Family: Euphorbiaceae

2.1. *Codiaeum variegatum pictum*

Two Coccoidea species recorded infesting the above host plants, the capparidis wax scale *C. capparidis* and the citrus mealybug, *P. citri*. According to Gill (1977), *C. capparidis* recorded infesting *Codiaeum* sp. in North America. Ben-Dov (1994) listed *P. citri* infesting *Codiaeum variegatum*.

3. Family: Araliaceae

3.1. *Polyscias balfourina*

The data revealed that this plant was infested by two species, the capparidis wax scale *C. capparidis* and the citrus mealybug *P. citri*. Hammon and Williams (1984) listed *Polyscias balfourina* as a host of *C. capparidis* in Florida, USA. Lincango *et al.* (2010) recorded *P. citri* from *Polyscias scutellaria* in Ecuador.

3.2. *Schefflera actinophylla*

Two Coccoidea species recorded infesting the above host plant, the capparidis wax scale *C. capparidis* and the citrus mealybug *P. citri*. The data agree with that obtained by Ben-Dov (2012) who recorded the citrus mealybug *P. citri* from *Schefflera* sp. According to ScaleNet (2020) the capparidis wax scale *C. capparidis* never recorded infesting *Schefflera actinophylla* before.

4. Family: Araceae

4.1. *Monstera acuminata deliciosa*

Four coccid species, *C. capparidis*, *C. cirripediformis*, *S. coffeae*, *P. urbicola*; one diaspidid, *C. aonidium* as well as one pseudococcid *P. citri* occurred on this plants during the period of the survey study. Nakahara (1981) recorded *C. cirripediformis* on a host plant belonging to Family: Araceae, *Philodendron* sp. in Hawaii. Abdel-Razak (2012) recorded *P. urbicola* for the first time in Alexandria, Egypt infesting *Cordia* sp. (Boraginaceae), *Psidium guajava* (Myrtaceae) and *Sanchezia speciosa* (Acanthaceae). In

Italy, Marotta (1987a) recorded *S. coffeae* infesting *Monstera deliciosa*. According to ScaleNet (2020) the capparidis wax scale *C. capparidis*; the black scale *C. aonidium* and the citrus mealybug *P. citri* never recorded infesting *Monstera acuminata deliciosa* before.

4.2. *Anthurium andraeanum*

Two species were found infesting the plant. They were, the soft scale *P. urbicola* and the diaspidid *C. aonidium*. Data obtained agree with Zimmerman (1948) who recorded *C. aonidium* infesting *Anthurium* sp in Hawaii. According to ScaleNet (2020) the *urbicola* soft scale *P. urbicola* never recorded infesting *Anthurium andraeanum* before.

4.3. *Anthurium pentaplyllum*

The data revealed that this plant was infested by two species, the soft scale *P. urbicola* and the citrus mealybug *P. citri*. Ben-Dov (2012) listed *Anthurium* sp. as a host of *P. citri*. Although *Anthurium pentaplyllum* never recorded as host plant of the soft scale *P. urbicola* before (ScaleNet, 2020).

4.4. *Epipremnum aureum*

Both of the scale insects, *C. capparidis* (Coccidae) and *P. citri* (Pseudococcidae) were recorded infesting *Epipremnum aureum* in the Royal green house at Al-Montaza palace garden, Alexandria Egypt. The data agree with that obtained by Marotta (1987b) and Ben-Dov (1994) who recorded this plant species as a host of *P. citri*. *C. capparidis* never recorded as a pest of *Epipremnum aureum* before (ScaleNet, 2020).

4.5. *Dieffenbachia seguine*

It recorded infested by only one scale insect species during the study, the pseudococcid *P. citri*. The data agree with that obtained by Marotta (1987b) and Ben-Dov (1994) who recorded this plant species as a host of *P. citri*.

6. Family: Acanthaceae

6.1. *Sanchezia speciosa*

The plant is mainly infested by four Coccoidea species, three of them belongs to Family: Coccidae, *C. capparidis*, *S. coffee* and *P. urbicola* as well as *P. citri* Family: Pseudococcidae. The data agree with that obtained by Abdel-Razak (2012) who recorded *P. urbicola* for the first time in Alexandria, Egypt infested *Sanchezia speciosa* (Acanthaceae). Choi and Lee (2017) listed *Sanchezia* sp. as a host plant to *S. coffee* in Korea. *C. capparidis* and *P. citri* never recorded as a pest of *Sanchezia speciosa* before (ScaleNet, 2020).

7. Family: Asparagaceae

7.1. *Beaucarnea recurvata*

The main scale insects infesting the plant was the coccid *P. urbicola*. According to ScaleNet (2020) *P. urbicola* never recorded as a pest of *Beaucarnea recurvata* before, but also listed as a pest of other host plants belonging to Family: Asparagaceae.

7.2. *Dracena Marginata*

It was noticed infested with *P. citri*. Williams and Granara de Willink (1992) and Ben-Dov (1994) listed the mealybug as a pest of *Dracena* sp.

8. Family: Nephrolepidaceae

8.1. *Nephrolepis exaltata*

It was infested by the soft scale *S. coffeae* during the study. The same data obtained by Nakahara (1983) who recorded the insect infesting the same host plant *Nephrolepis exaltata* in United States Virgin Islands.

9. Family: Arecaceae

9.1. *Howea belmoreana*

During the Experiment period the palm ornamental *Howea belmoreana* observed infesting by four scale insects, one of them belongs to Family: Coccidae, *C. capparidis* and the others, *C. aonidium*, *H. lataniae*, *D. boisduvalii* belongs to Family: Diaspididae. Balachowsky (1932) listed *C. aonidium* and *H. lataniae* as

pests of the palm ornamental *Howea* sp. in France. Watson (2002) listed *Howea* sp. as a host plant of the diaspidid *D. boisduvalii*. *C. capparidis* never recorded as a pest of *Howea belmoreana* before (ScaleNet, 2020).

9.2. *Caryota mitis*

It was recorded infested with *C. capparidis* and *C. aonidium*. According to ScaleNet (2020) the obtained data revealed that it is the first record of the two scale insect species in *Caryota mitis* internationally.

9.3. *Chamaedorea elegans*

The observation on the palm ornamental, *Chamaedorea elegans* indicated that this Plant species is infested by the capparidis wax scale *C. capparidis*. Data obtained clarified that the *Chamaedorea elegans* is a new host to *C. capparidis* according to (ScaleNet, 2020).

9.4. *Dypsis lutescens*

The observed scale insect species infesting this plant species was the date palm scale *P. blanchardi*. From the data collecting during the investigation, the palm scale considered as a new pest to *Dypsis lutescens* (ScaleNet, 2020).

9.5. *latania borbonica*

During the experiment the *latania borbonica* palm observed infested by the latania scale *H. lataniae*. The data agree with that obtained by Hall (1923) who recorded the pest from *latania* sp. palm from Egypt.

10. Family: Zamiaceae

10.1. *Zamia* sp.

The data obtained revealed that *Zamia* sp. is recorded infesting by *S. coffeae* at the Royal greenhouse at Al-Montaza Palace garden during the Experiment time period. It is agreeing with that obtained by Hamon and Williams (1984) they recorded the insect from the same host plant in Florida.

11. Family: Moraceae

11.1. *Ficus benjamina*

Abdel-Razak, 2020

Three species were found infesting this host plant. They were *C.capparidis*, *P. urbicola* and *P. citri*. According to ScaleNet (2020) *C. capparidis* and *P. urbicola* never

recorded infested in *Ficus benjamina* before. Moghaddam (2013) recorded *P. citri* infested *Ficus benjamina* trees in Iran.

Table (2): Host plants infested with Coccoidea in the Royal Greenhouse, Al-Montaza palace garden, Alexandria, Egypt.

Coccoidea species	Host plants
<i>Ceroplastes cirripediformis</i>	<i>Monstera acuminata deliciosa</i>
<i>Chrysomphalus aonidum</i>	<i>Monstera acuminata deliciosa</i>
	<i>Anthurium andraeanum</i>
	<i>Howea belmoreana</i>
	<i>Caryota mitis</i>
<i>Coccus capparidis</i>	<i>Adiantum cuneatum</i>
	<i>Codiaeum variegatum pictum</i>
	<i>Polyscias balfourina</i>
	<i>Monstera acuminata deliciosa</i>
	<i>Sanchezia speciose</i>
	<i>Schefflera actinophylla</i>
	<i>Epipremnum aureum</i>
	<i>Howea belmoreana</i>
	<i>Caryota mitis</i>
	<i>Chamaedorea elegans</i>
	<i>Ficus benjamina</i>
<i>Diaspis boisduvalii</i>	<i>Howea belmoreana</i>
<i>Hemiberlesia lataniae</i>	<i>Howea belmoreana</i>
	<i>latania borbonica</i>
<i>Parlatoria blanchardi</i>	<i>Dypsis lutescens</i>
<i>Planococcus citri</i>	<i>Codiaeum variegatum pictum</i>
	<i>Polyscias balfourina</i>
	<i>Monstera acuminata deliciosa</i>
	<i>Sanchezia speciose</i>
	<i>Dracena Marginata</i>
	<i>Schefflera actinophylla</i>
	<i>Anthurium pentaplyllum</i>
	<i>Epipremnum aureum</i>
	<i>Dieffenbachia seguine</i>
	<i>Ficus benjamina</i>
<i>Pulvinaria urbicola</i>	<i>Monstera acuminata deliciosa</i>
	<i>Sanchezia speciose</i>
	<i>Beaucarnea recurvata</i>
	<i>Anthurium andraeanum</i>
	<i>Anthurium pentaplyllum</i>
	<i>Ficus benjamina</i>
<i>Saissetia coffeae</i>	<i>Adiantum cuneatum</i>
	<i>Monstera acuminata deliciosa</i>
	<i>Sanchezia speciose</i>
	<i>Nephrolepis exaltata</i>
	<i>Zamia fairchildiana</i>

Climate change is expected to alter the geographic distribution and abundance of many species, to increase the invasion of new areas by exotic species and in some cases, to lead to species extinction as well as the world-wide commerce can spread the injurious Coccoidea over the earth, as they are so easily carried with many different ways. Therefore, identification Morphological keys to identify exist and nonsexist adult female Coccoidea species must be considered to help in future identification.

Key to families of adult female Coccoidea

Note: Family names given in [] have not yet been recorded from Egypt.

- 1 Abdominal spiracles present . 2
Abdominal spiracles absent .. 5
- 2(1) Antenna with spine at apex; ovisac band present, containing spines; ovisac not attached to host
Ortheziidae
-- Antenna without spine at apex; ovisac band, if present, sometimes containing spines; ovisac attached to host --- 3
- 3(2) Front legs greatly enlarged, more robust than other legs
Margarodidae sensu stricto
-- All legs of similar size and shape----- 4
- 4(3) Anal tube well developed; sclerotized anal ring present; cicatrices present on venter of abdomen; on various hosts **Monophlebidae**
-- Anal tube weakly developed; sclerotized anal ring absent; cicatrices absent; on *Pinus* spp. only
[Marchalinidae (Marchalina helenica (Gennadius))]
- 5(1) 8-shaped pores present on dorsum and/or margin 6

- 8-shaped pores absent from dorsum and/or margin 9
- 6(5) Antenna 1 segmented 7
Antenna with more than 4 segments-- 8
- 7(6) Anal plate presents, triangular; posterior spiracular furrow forked; cribriform plates present on dorsum of abdomen; 8-shaped pores present on dorsum, often arranged in concentric patterns **[Cerococcidae]**
-- Anal plate absent; posterior spiracular furrow single; cribriform plates absent; 8-shaped pores forming row around margin, present or absent from dorsum
Asterolecaniidae
- 8(6) Anal plate present, lobed or butterfly shaped; posterior spiracular furrow forked; antenna with 6-8 segments; on broad-leafed hosts
Lecanodiaspididae
-- Anal plate absent; posterior spiracular furrow single; antenna 5 segmented; on oak (*Quercus* spp.) or very closely genera (Fagaceae)
..... **[Kermesidae (in part)]**
- 9(5) Dorsal setae truncate conical; clusters of quinquelocular pores present, each associated with a tubular duct; on *Opuntia* spp. or closely related cacti
..... **Dactylopiidae**
-- If dorsal setae truncate conical, then body without clusters of quinquelocular pores; on various hosts including cacti 10
- 10(9) Anal plate present 11
-- Anal plate absent 12
- 11(10) Anal plate single, almond shaped; hind margin crenulate, without anal cleft; antenna 1 segmented; legs absent or reduced to sclerotized points;

on grasses and bamboos (Poaceae) only

Aclerididae

-- Anal plates paired, often each triangular; anal cleft present; antenna 2-8 segmented; legs present; on various hosts including Poaceae **Coccidae**

12(11) Posterior abdominal segments sclerotized and fused so that segmentation is not evident, forming a pygidium; anal opening simple; legs absent or reduced to sclerotized points

13

-- If posterior abdominal segments sclerotized, then segmentation still evident; legs present or absent; anal opening simple or complex; legs present or absent

..... 14

13(12) Pygidium with dorsal ducts and a marginal fringe of lobes, and plates or gland spines; usually living beneath a scale cover containing exuviae of previous instars, but sometimes adult female remains inside exuviae of previous stage (pupillarial); if hinged operculum present, then never feeding on palms

..... **Diaspididae**

-- Pygidium simple, without lobes, plates or gland spines; adult female pupillarial; posterior end of exuviae of previous instar with hinged operculum surrounded by a sclerotized rim; on palms and Pandanaceae only

Halimococcidae

14(13) Anal opening situated at center of dorsum; legs absent; crawlers dimorphic; on broad-leafed hosts

[Stictococcidae]

-- Anal opening situated situated towards, or at, posterior end; legs usually present; crawlers monomorphic; on various hosts including Monocotyledonae

15(14) Anterior spiracles much larger than posterior spiracles; sclerotized

dorsal spine and brachial plates present; legs absent

[Kerriidae]

-- Anterior spiracles similar size to posterior spiracles; sclerotized dorsal spine and brachial plates absent; legs present or absent

16(15) Anal ring simple, with 2 setae and no pores; entire cuticle rugose; legs absent; antenna 1 segmented; on palms only

Phoenicococcidae

-- Anal ring simple or complex, with or without setae and pores; cuticle smooth; legs present or absent; antenna 1-9 segmented; on various hosts including palms

17(16) Possessing one or more of: paired ostioles; cerarii; one or more circuli; swirled trilocular pores

Pseudococcidae

-- Without paired ostioles; cerarii; one or more circuli; swirled trilocular pores -- 18

18(17) At least 1 posterior abdominal segment sclerotized, forming a pseudopygidium; multilocular pores present on both surfaces of abdomen; legs usually present, each with tibia and tarsus fused; tubular ducts absent

[Conchaspididae]

-- Posterior abdominal segments not sclerotized to form a pseudopygidium; multilocular pores often confined to venter of abdomen, legs with tibia and tarsus separate; tubular ducts present, each with cup-shaped inner end

19(18) Anal ring bearing setae; anal lobes usually protruding (but sometimes absent); ventral macrotubular ducts, if present, scattered; microtubular ducts present; on various hosts including oaks

Eriococcidae

-- Anal ring without pores or setae; anal lobes not protruding; large ventral tubular ducts present in

submarginal zone; microtubular ducts absent; on oak (*Quercus* spp.) or very closely related genera (Fagaceae)
 [Kermesidae (in part)]

It can be concluded that, a total of nine Coccoidea specie following nine genera belonging to 3 families were observed infesting twenty ornamental plants in the Historical Royal greenhouse at Al-Montaza palace garden, Alexandria Governorate, Egypt. New hosts recorded for the first time infesting with Coccoidea species during the study were illustrated and discussed as follows: the capparidis wax scale *C. capparidis* recorded for the first time infesting *Schefflera actinophylla*, *Monstera acuminata deliciosa*, *Epipremnum aureum*, *Sanchezia speciose*, *Howea belmoreana*, *Caryota mitis*, *Camaedorea elegans* and *Ficus benjamina*. The black scale *C. aonidum* recorded for the first time infesting *Monstera acuminata deliciosa* and *Caryota mitis*. The urbicola soft scale *P. urbicola* recorded for the first time infesting *Anthurium andraeanum*, *Anthurium pentaplyllum*, *Beaucarnea recurvate* and *Ficus benjamina*. The citrus mealybug *P. citri* recorded for the first time infesting *Monstera acuminata deliciosa* and *Sanchezia speciose*. From the data collecting during the investigation, the palm scale *P. blanchardi* considered as a new pest to *Dyopsis lutescens*. A key of the adult female Coccoidea were given for helping researchers in the future identification and investigation.

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Ecological studies on the cotton mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) on maize in Upper Egypt

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Abstract

Maize crop is one of the food crops that played an important role in the Egyptian economy. it's important came from its several uses, whether as a food for man or as animal feed. Recently, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) recorded infesting maize crop, *Zea Mays* L. across Egypt. This paper covers the population fluctuations of *P. solenopsis* and its associated parasitoid, *Aenasius arizonensis* (Girault) (Hymenoptera: Encyrtidae) during two successive growing seasons of summer 2019 and 2020 in two varieties of maize plantation (White corn and yellow singular Hybrid 168) in Albalina, Sohag Governorate, Egypt. The results obtained clarified that *P. solenopsis* and its associated parasitoid have three peaks of abundance in both years in the selected maize varieties. The correlation of the abiotic factors (Daily mean temperature and relative humidity) and biotic factors (Parasitoid and the plant age of maize varieties) with the population fluctuation of the cotton mealybug were studied.

Introduction

Maize crop is one of the food crops that played an important role in Egyptian economy. it's important came from its several uses, whether as a food for man or as animal feed. Recently, maize crop noticed infesting with the newly introduced pest in Egypt the cotton mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera:Pseudococcidae). Since 2005, the cotton mealybug *P. solenopsis* has emerged as a serious pest of cotton in Pakistan and India. It spread rapidly and has been reported from 173 species in 45 plant families and from 26 countries in different

ecological zones. Most of these hosts belongs to the families: Malvaceae, Solanaceae, Asteraceae, Euphorbiaceae, Amaranthaceae and Cucurbitaceae. Economical damage was observed on cotton, brinjal, okra, tomato, sesame, sunflower and china rose and reached plant death in severe conditions (Arif *et al.*, 2009; Abbas *et al.*, 2010; Fallahzadeh *et al.*, 2014 and Badr *et al.*, 2020). It was recorded for the first time in Egypt in September, 2009 by (Abd-Rabou *et al.*, 2010) infesting *Hibiscus* sp., from that time the pest was spreading rapidly across Egypt and recorded from different host plants. In tomato plant it was recorded

for the first time by (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2015). After that it was recorded from 29 new host plants from them corn plantation by Attia, and Abdel Aziz (2015) and Abdel- Razzik *et al.* (2015). Abd El-Wareth (2016) recorded the pest for the first time from several host plant at Fayoum Governorate from them, maize. (Beshr *et al.* , 2016) submitted 20 host plants infested by the pest 8 of them new host in Egypt (Moharum *et al.*, 2017) recorded the pest from 18 host plants belonging to 11 families at Dakahlia Governorate. Ecological studies were conducted on the pest at Sharkia Governorate on Eggplants by (Nabil, 2017). The annual generations with biology and thermal development of the *P. solenopsis* was carried out by Shehata (2017) on okra leaves. The impact of weather factors on the population density of *P. solenopsis* and its natural enemy were studied by (Nabil and Hegab, 2019) on okra plants.

The aim of this study is to estimate the population fluctuation of the cotton mealybug *P. solenopsis* and its parasitoid, *Aenasius arizonensis* (Girault) (Hymenoptera: *Encyrtidae*) in maize as an economic important crop in Egypt for better controlling this endemic pest. As well as, estimate the effect of selected biotic and abiotic factor affecting its population at Albalina, Sohag Governorate, Egypt during two successive years of 2019/2020.

Materials and methods

1. Population fluctuations of the cotton mealybugs *Phenacoccus solenopsis*:

In order to study the population fluctuations of the cotton mealybug *P. solenopsis*, an experiment carried out during two successive growing seasons of summer 2019 and 2020, in a chosen private area of one Fadden to every variety of maize plant (White corn and yellow singular Hybrid

168) *Zea mays* L. in Albalina, Sohag governorate, Egypt. The experimental plots received the standard cultivation practices of that area, including organic and mineral fertilization and mechanical control to remove weeds. No insecticides were applied during the period of the experiment. Sample content of 15 cm leaves from twenty-five plants were chosen randomly having similar size, shape and height from all directions of each tree in two weeks' intervals.

The cuttings leaves were put in cloth bags and transferred to the laboratory in order to classify and count the existing individuals by using stereoscopic binocular microscope. The upper and lower surface of the leaves were examined. All stages of the insect as well as parasitized stages of the inspected insects were counted and recorded. Cutting leaves with the counted insects were then confined in glass jars and kept in the laboratory for securing and emerging parasitoids. During the two successive years of the experiment the endoparasitoid, *A. arizonensis* was recorded infesting the cotton mealybug.

2. Effect of biotic and abiotic factors on the abundance of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* :

Weather factors (Abiotic factors) as maximum and minimum temperature as well as relative humidity were considered from the [http://: www: Weather underground.eg](http://www.Weather underground.eg). The week maximum and minimum temperatures as well as relative humidity were calculated. Plant phenology emulating plant nutritional value dynamics over the growing season was considered as plant age (X) (biotic factors). This relation was presented by polynomial equation of third degree ($Y = a + b_1x + b_2x^2 + b_3x^3$). Multiple regressions were conducted for weather factors combined as well as the plant age as described.

3. Statistical analysis

The obtained determination factor (R²) of expected value (E.V.%) percentage was used to explain the effect of testing factors. Correlation and regression were used in SAS program to analysis the obtained data (SAS Institute, 1998).

Results and discussion

1. Population fluctuations of the cotton mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley on corn *Zea mays* Varsity, white corn and yellow singular Hybrid 168).

1.1. Seasonal activity of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* in white corn variety:

Population fluctuations of the cotton mealybug, on maize crop white corn Varsity was estimated during summer 2019 and 2020 in Albalina, Sohag Governorate. The seasonal activity of *P. solenopsis* as total number of nymphs and adults from the fourth directions (West, north, east and south) were illustrated for the both years of study of 2019 and 2020 in (Figure 1 A and B) and (Figure 2 A and B).

In this experiment samples collected from 22nd of May to 25th of September. In first year of study 2019 the total number of infestations by mature and immature stages of the cotton mealybugs recorded few numbers in 19th of June. After that the population increased rapidly recorded its first peak in 31st of July, second peak reached its maximum in 21st of August and the third peak of abundance existed in 18th of September 2019 (Figure 1 A and B). Data obtained during the second year of study, 2020 clarified that, the population of the studied stages take the same trend as first year of 2019. We noticed that cotton mealybug nymphs achieved three peaks in 24th of July, 14th of August and 11th of September 2020, respectively (Figure 2 A). Whereas, adults achieved its three population fluctuation abundance peak in 31st of July, 21st of August and 18th of

September 2020 (Figure 2 B). The obtained data showed that, the population of *P. solenopsis* was in general high in the second year than the first year on white corn.

1.2. Seasonal activity of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* in yellow singular Hybrid 168 corn:

Population fluctuations of the cotton mealybug, on maize crop yellow singular Hybrid 168 was estimated during summer 2019 and 2020 in Albalina, Sohag governorate, Egypt. The seasonal activity of *P. solenopsis* as total number of nymphs and adults from the fourth directions (West, north, east and south) were illustrated for the both years of study of 2019 and 2020 in (Figure 3 A and B) and (Figure 4 A and B).

In this experiment samples collected from 22nd of May to 25th of September 2020. In the first year of study 2019 the total number of infestations by mature and immature stages of the cotton mealybugs recorded few numbers in 26th of June. After that the population increased rapidly to record the insect first peak in 31st of July, second peak reached in 21st of August and the third peak of abundance existed in 18th of September 2019 (Figure 3 A).

While the obtained results indicated that adult individuals recorded few numbers in 26th of June. Accordingly, the population increased to record the first peak of abundance in 31st of July, the second peak in 28th of August and the third peak in 18th of September 2019 (Figure 3B) respectively. In the second year of study, 2020 the seasonal population fluctuation of the pest takes the same trend. We noticed that the nymphs achieved three peaks in 17th of July, 14th of August and 11th of September 2020, respectively (Figure 3A). whereas, adult of *P. solenopsis* reached three peaks of abundance respectively in 17th

of July, 14th of August and 11th of September 2020 (Figure 2B). The population of *P. solenopsis* on yellow singular Hybrid 168 corn was in general the same in both years of study.

2. Population fluctuations of the primary parasitoid; *Aenasius arizonensis*, of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* on *Zea mays* variety, white corn and yellow singular Hybrid 168.

Population fluctuations of the primary parasitoid; *A. arizonensis* is a solitary, endoparasitoid emerged from its host, the adult stage of the cotton mealybug, on maize crop white corn and yellow singular Hybrid 168 was estimated during summer 2019 and 2020 in Albalina, Sohag governorate, Egypt.

2.1. Seasonal activity of the endoparasitoid of *Phenacoccus solenopsis*, *Aenasius arizonensis* infesting white corn variety:

The seasonal activity of *A. arizonensis* from the fourth direction (West, north, east and south) (Figure 1C) and (Figure 2C) were illustrated for the years of study. In both years of study 2019 and 2020 the first appearance for the parasitoid was in 3rd of July. Subsequently, the population of *A. arizonensis* increased rapidly to record first peak in 31st of July, and its second peak in 21st of August and finally its third peak in 18th of September 2019 (Figure 1C).

In the second year of the study *A. arizonensis* achieved two peaks in 17th of July and 18th of September 2020, respectively (Figure 2C). The obtained results showed that, the population of *A. arizonensis* was in general high in the first year comparing with second year on white corn.

2.2. Seasonal activity of the endoparasitoid of *Phenacoccus solenopsis*, *Aenasius arizonensis* infesting yellow singular Hybrid 168:

The seasonal activity of the parasitoid individual of *A. arizonensis*

from the fourth direction (West, north, east and south) (Figure 3C) and (Figure 4C) were illustrated for 2019 and 2020. In both years of study 2019 and 2020 the first appearance for the parasitoid was in 3rd of July and 10th of July, respectively. Consequently, the population of *A. arizonensis* in 2019 increased to record its first peak in 31st of July, second peak reached its maximum in 21st of August and finally the third peak was in 18th of September 2019 (Figure 3C). In the second year of study the *A. arizonensis* achieved three peaks in 17th of July, 21st of August and 18th of September 2020, respectively (Figure 4C). The population of *A. arizonensis* was in general high in the first year than the second year on yellow singular Hybrid 168. Fand and Suroshe (2015) reported that, about 28 species of natural enemies including 12 predators and 16 multiple parasitoids of *P. solenopsis* have been reported throughout its range, but only the encyrtid species *Aenasius bambawalei* Hayat has been instrumental in controlling *P. solenopsis* natural population in a range 30- 60%.

3. Effect of biotic and abiotic factors on the abundance of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* in white corn:

The total nymph and adult population of *P. solenopsis* on white corn insignificantly correlated with maximum and minimum temperature in both year of study, while with RH.% was significant on first year and insignificant on second year. Whereas, multiple regression between total nymph population and weather factor was (E.V.%) 51.70 and 7.24% on both year of study on white corn. Whereas, multiple regression between total adult population and weather factor was (E.V.%) 56.39 and 9.99% on both year of study on white corn (Table 1). Multiple regression between total nymph population and the parasitoid *A. arizonensis* was (E.V.%) 85.17 and

75.92% on both year of study on white corn. While, between total adult population and the parasitoid *A. arizonensis* was (E.V.%) 91.81 and 79.86% on both year of study on white corn. Data obtained suggested that, plant age of white corn was affected on population fluctuation of *P. solenopsis* nymphs and adult females by 60.83 and 34.77% and 63.08 and 34.58%, respectively. The common effect of weather factor, parasitoid and plant age effect on nymphs and adult population fluctuations recorded 87.81 and 85.59% and 93.99 and 87.33%, respectively (Table 1).

4. Effect of biotic and abiotic factors on the abundance of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* in yellow singular Hybrid 168 corn:

The total nymphs and adult population of *P. solenopsis* on yellow singular Hybrid 168 corn insignificantly correlated with maximum and minimum temperature in both years of study, while with RH.% it was correlated significantly in both years of study. Whereas, multiple regression between total nymph population and weather factor was (E.V.%) 55.05 and 17.80% in both years of study on yellow singular Hybrid 168 corn. Whereas, multiple regression between total adult population and weather factor was (E.V.%) 62.52 and 13.04% in both years of study on yellow singular Hybrid 168 (Table 2).

Multiple regression between total nymphs' population and biotic factor as the parasitoid *A. arizonensis* was (E.V.%) 92.26 and 95.73% in both years of the study on yellow singular Hybrid 168 corn. While, between total adult's population and the parasitoid *A. arizonensis* it was (E.V.%) 87.43 and

91.24% on both year of study on yellow singular Hybrid 168 (Table 2). The plant age of white corn was affected on population fluctuation of *P. solenopsis* nymphs and adult females by 75.63 and 44.11% and 68.87 and 40.17%, respectively. The common effect of weather factor, parasitoid and plant age effect on nymphs and adult population fluctuations recorded 97.35 and 97.05% and 95.42 and 92.25%, respectively (Table 2). Data obtained indicated that, there were insignificant correlation with maximum and minimum temperature. That is agree with (Singh and Kumar, 2012) who stated that the mealybug population was showing positive correlation with higher temperature.

The plant age of maize had higher effective on population fluctuation of *P. solenopsis* than weather factor this result similar to (Moharum *et. al.*, 2018) they reported that the plant age of tomato in summer and winter season were affected on nymph and adult female by (90.33 and 84.80%), (81.93 and 71.54%) at Ismailia and (89.95% and 80.45%), (90.18 and 89.95%) at Kafr El-Sheikh.

It can be concluded that the cotton mealybug, *P. solenopsis* and the associated parasitoid, *A. arizonensis* has three annual Population fluctuations in the two maize crop varieties, white corn and yellow singular Hybrid 168 corn in two successive years 2019/2020 in Albalina, Sohag governorate, Egypt. In white corn the common effect of weather factor, parasitoid and plant age effect on nymphs and adult population fluctuations recorded 87.81 and 85.59% and 93.99 and 87.33%, respectively, while in yellow singular Hybrid 168 recorded 97.35 and 97.05% and 95.42 and 92.25%, respectively.

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure (1 A, B and C): Population fluctuations of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* during the summer season of 2019 infesting white maize variety, compared with the number of parasitoid individuals of *Aenasius arizonensis* in Albalina, Egypt.

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure (2 A, B and C): Population fluctuations of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* during the summer season of 2020 infesting white maziie varity, compared with the number of parasitoid individuals of *Aenasius arizonensis* in Albalina, Egypt.

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure (3 A, B and C): Population fluctuations of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* during the summer season 2019 of yellow mazie, compared with the number of parasitoid individuals *Aenasius arizonensis* in Albalina, Egypt.

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure (4 A, B and C): Population fluctuations of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley during the summer season 2020 of yellow maize, compared with the number of parasitoid individuals *Aenasius arizonensis* in Albalina, Egypt.

Table (1): The simple correlation (r) and regression coefficients (b) and multiple regressions (F and E.V.%) between the different stages of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* and biotic and abiotic factors on white corn.

Factor		Simple correlation and regression			Multiple regression		
		r	B	P	F	E.V.%	
2019	Nymph	T. Max.	-0.06	-21.56	0.8146	5.35	51.70
		T. Min.	-0.31	-71.75	0.1971		
		RH.%	0.52	51.11	0.0223		
		<i>Aenasius arizonensis</i>	0.92	3.08	0.0001	97.63	85.17
		Age plant				7.76	60.83
		All above				11.32	87.81
	Adult	T. Max.	-0.09	-24.65	0.7280	6.47	56.39
		T. Min.	-0.35	-62.51	0.1424		
		RH.%	0.53	40.19	0.0194		
		<i>Aenasius arizonensis</i>	0.96	2.46	0.0001	190.51	91.81
		Age plant				8.54	63.08
		All above				24.59	93.99
2020	Nymph	T. Max.	-0.23	-102.98	0.3454	0.39	7.24
		T. Min.	-0.07	-12.65	0.7684		
		RH.%	0.22	24.48	0.3605		
		<i>Aenasius arizonensis</i>	0.87	5.33	0.0001	53.60	75.92
		Age plant				2.66	34.77
		All above				9.34	85.59
	Adult	T. Max.	-0.26	-97.75	0.2806	0.56	9.99
		T. Min.	-0.12	-18.07	0.6130		
		RH.%	0.25	22.80	0.3051		
		<i>Aenasius arizonensis</i>	0.89	4.56	0.0097	67.40	79.86
		Age plant				2.64	34.58
		All above				10.8	87.33

T. Max.: Maximum temperature T. Min.: Minimum temperature RH. %: Percent relative humidity.

Table (2):The simple correlation (r) and regression coefficients (b) and multiple regressions (F and E.V.%) between the different stages of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* and biotic and abiotic factors on yellow singular Hybrid 168.

Factor		Simple correlation and regression			Multiple regression		
		r	b	P	F	E.V.%	
2019	Nymph	T. Max.	-0.18	-49.77	0.4614	6.12	55.05
		T. Min.	-0.37	-64.03	0.1154		
		RH.%	0.54	38.91	0.0181		
		<i>Aenasius arizonensis</i>	0.98	3.17	0.0001	341.54	95.26
		Age plant				15.52	75.63
		All above				57.87	97.35
	Adult	T. Max.	-0.17	-37.21	0.4851	8.34	62.52
		T. Min.	-0.45	-60.28	0.0557		
		RH.%	0.51	29.42	0.0245		
		<i>Aenasius arizonensis</i>	0.94	2.40	0.0001	118.22	87.43
		Age plant				11.06	68.87
		All above				32.76	95.42
2020	Nymph	T. Max.	-0.30	-71.23	0.2108	1.08	17.80
		T. Min.	-0.23	-20.76	0.3534		
		RH.%	0.31	17.99	0.1964		
		<i>Aenasius arizonensis</i>	0.98	2.74	0.0001	380.78	95.73
		Age plant				3.95	44.11
		All above				51.72	97.05
	Adult	T. Max.	-0.26	-44.45	0.2767	0.75	13.04
		T. Min.	-0.12	-7.61	0.6370		
		RH.%	0.31	12.94	0.1929		
		<i>Aenasius arizonensis</i>	0.96	1.91	0.0001	177.12	91.24
		Age plant				3.36	40.17
		All above				18.70	92.25

T. Max.: Maximum temperature T. Min.: Minimum temperature RH. %: Percent relative humidity.

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Survey and taxonomic notes on the coleopterous (Coleoptera) insect fauna of the New Valley, Egypt

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Abstract:

A survey together with faunistic studies of the coleopterous insects were carried out in the New Valley Governorate using light traps and sweeping nets during a period covered two years, 2017 - 2018. The survey revealed the presence of 93 species under 76 genera belonging to 24 families. The largest number of species was belonged to family Tenebrionidae (20 species), followed by family Carabidae (9 species), then family Cocinellidae (8 species). Families Curculionidae and Dytiscidae, each of 7 species. Other families were represented by smaller number of species. 9 species are common, 44 species were found in considerable numbers and 35 species are rare. Thirty species are pests of which 5 are major pests, 28 species are predators, and 27 species are of less economic importance. The distribution of each species in the deferent geographical regions of Egypt is also included.

Introduction

The New Valley is the largest Governorate in Egypt, representing approximately over 1/3 of the total area of Egypt and characterized in a whole by desert environment including several Oases. Although, there is ambitious and promising agriculture work are performed in the New Valley, there is no detailed study on the diversity of insects in this area and most of the faunistic insect work in this area was no more than fragment and scattered work carried out by Gough (1917 and 1918), Gabriel and Corbet (1949), Hanna (1966), Badran and Nakhla (1969) , Saleh (1974), Moustafa *et al.* (1983), Ahmed (1991), Al-Gamal *et al.* (2001) and Mahbob. and Mahmoud (2013).

As for the coleopterous insect fauna of Egypt, Shalaby (1958) listed in alphabetical order the Egyptian insects

in the insect collection of the Plant Protection Research institute, Min. of Agriculture, Egypt. El Moursy (1996) in the work "Biological diversity of Egypt" listed the coleopterous insects of Egypt together with their distribution. Salem (2017) in his book "The insect fauna of Egypt" presented a comprehensive checklist of insects recorded in Egypt including the coleopterous insects and in 2018 recorded the coleopterous predators in Egypt.

Concerning the fauna of the coleoptera in the New Valley Governorate , very little is known and a very little studies were carried out. On account of the scarcity of knowledge regarding the coleopterous insect fauna in the New Valley, the present work is presented to overcome the lack of information and to assist in recognizing

the insect fauna in this area. It is hoped to be of assistance for more detailed and prospective studies.

Materials and methods

The present work was carried out at the New Valley using light traps and sweeping net during two years (2017 – 2018), and covered the following areas in the New Valley Governorate: Dakhla, Kharga, and Paris Oases. The surveyed areas were cultivated with variable field crops, vegetables and fruit trees. Captured insects were sorted out into species, identified and recorded, then listed in alphabetical order according to families, genera and species. Data are presented in a Table (1) showing the recent scientific names and position of the species together with their collecting method, state of abundance (Common, fair and rare) and their distribution in the geographical regions in Egypt. Identification of species with updates of nomenclature and species status were carried out in the Insect Identification and Classification Department (IICD) in the Plant Protection Research Institute (PPRI), Agricultural Research Center (ARC), Egypt.

Results and discussion

The present survey recorded 93 species under 76 genera belonging to 24 coleopterous families (Anthicidae, Aphodiidae, Bostrychidae, Bruchidae, Buprestidae, Carabidae, Cerambycidae, Chrysomelidae, Cicindellidae, Coccinellidae, Curculionidae, Dermestidae, Dytiscidae, Elateridae, Hydrophilidae, Malachidae, Meloidae, Melolonthidae, Melyridae, Nitidulidae, Ptinidae, Scarabaeidae, Staphilinidae and Tenebrionidae. The survey also indicated that, the largest number of species was belonged to family Tenebrionidae (20 species), followed

by family Carabidae (9 species, then family Coccinellidae (8 species). Families Curculionidae and Dytiscidae, each of 7 species. Other families were represented by smaller number of species. It is noticed that, most of the species were collected by the light traps (76 species), and 28 species by sweeping net. It is also found that 9 species were much abundant, and 44 species were found in considerable numbers, whereas, 35 species are rare. From the economic point of view, 33 species are considered pests, of which 5 species are major pests. 28 species are predators, whereas, other species (27 species) are of not known or of less economic importance.

On the other hand, and according to the records of distribution for the recorded species in the geographical regions of Egypt, it is noticed that, 39 of the surveyed species were recorded from the coastal region, 45 species were previously recorded from the western desert, in addition to 48 species recorded in the present work from this region, 47 species from lower Egypt, 28 species from Upper Egypt, 11 species from eastern desert, 10 species from Gebel Elba and 41 species from Sinai peninsula. It is found also that, four species are found inhabiting all the geographical regions in Egypt, these are: *Callosobruchus chinensis* (Bruchidae), *Straspes squamosa* (Buprestidae), *Croscheria sanguinolenta* (Meloidae) and *Pentodon algrinum* (Scarabaeidae). One species was collected from 6 regions, 6 species were recorded from 5 regions, 12 species from four regions, 22 species from 3 regions, 19 species from 2 regions and 21 species from only one region.

Table (1): List of coleopterous insects as surveyed in the New Valley Oasis, Egypt, together with their economic status, abundancy, means of collection and distribution in Egypt.

Taxa	Collection		Economic status			Abundancy	Distribution in Egypt					
	Light trap	Net	Pest	Predator	Others		N. Coast	W. Desert	Delta	U. Egypt	E. desert	G. Elba
Fam. Anthicidae												
<i>Anthicus crinitus</i> Laferte-Senectere, 1849 (= <i>Hirticomus hispidus</i> Rossi, 1792) (= <i>Anthicus laeviceps</i> Marseul, 1879) (= <i>Anthicus communimacula</i> Fairmaire, 1896)	*			*		++	*	*	*			
<i>Hirticollis hispidus</i> (Rossi, 1792) (= <i>Anthicus hispidus</i> Rossi, 1792)	*			*		+	*	*	*			
Fam. Aphodiidae												
<i>Aphodius lividus</i> (Olivier, 1789)	*				*	+++		*				
<i>Rhyssmodes orientalis</i> (Mulsant, 1874) (= <i>Rhyssmodes aspericeps</i> Reitter, 1892) (= <i>Rhyssmodes parvus</i> Balthasar, 1963) (= <i>Rhyssmodes reitteri</i> D'Orbigny, 1896) (= <i>Rhyssmodes transversus</i> Reitter, 1892) (= <i>Rhyssmodes aspericeps</i> Chevrolat, 1861) (= <i>Rhyssmodes aspericeps</i> Reitter, 1892) (= <i>Rhyssmodes bremeri</i> Endrödi, 1979) (= <i>Rhyssmodes gemmifer</i> Marseul, 1878) (= <i>Rhyssmodes hybridus</i> Reitter, 1892) (= <i>Rhyssmodes obsoletus</i> Reitter, 1887) (= <i>Rhyssmodes orientalis</i> Mulsant and Godart, 1875) (= <i>Rhyssmodes reitteri</i> D'Orbigny, 1896) (= <i>Rhyssmodes transversus</i> Reitter, 1892)	*				*	++	*	*	*			*
Fam. Bostrychidae												
<i>Bostrychoplites zickeli</i> (Marseul, 1867)	*		*			++		*	*			
<i>Phonapate frontalis</i> (Fahraeus, 1871)	*		**			++	*	*	*	*		*
Fam. Bruchidae												
<i>Callosobruchus chinensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) (= <i>Bruchus barbicornis</i> Fabricius 1801) (= <i>Bruchus bistriatus</i> Fabricius 1801) (= <i>Bruchus chinensis</i> Linnaeus 1888) (= <i>Bruchus scutellaris</i> Fabricius 1792) (= <i>Callosobruchus barbicornis</i> Fabricius 1801) (= <i>Callosobruchus bistriatus</i> Fabricius 1801) (= <i>Callosobruchus scutellaris</i> Fabricius, 1801) (= <i>Curculio chinensis</i> Linnaeus 1758) (= <i>Mylabris chinensis</i> Linnaeus 1878) (= <i>Pachymerus chinensis</i> Linnaeus 1905)	*		**			++	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Callosobruchus maculatus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	*		*			++		*				*

(= <i>Bruchus maculatus</i> Fabricius, 1775) (= <i>Bruchus quadrimaculatus</i> Fabricius, 1775) (= <i>Callosobruchus quadrimaculatus</i> Fabricius, 1792)												
Fam. Buprestidae												
<i>Anthaxia angustipennis</i> (Klug, 1829) (= <i>Anthaxia stupida</i> Marseul, 1860) (= <i>Anthaxia moises</i> Obenberger, 1921)	*		*			+		*		*		*
<i>Cyphosoma lawsoniae</i> (Chevrolat, 1838) (= <i>Buprestis lawsoniae</i> Chevrolat, 1838) (= <i>Coeculus buqueti</i> Gory and Laporte, 1839) (= <i>Coeculus gravidum</i> Gory and Laporte, 1839) (= <i>Cyphosoma buqueti</i> Gory and Laporte, 1839) (= <i>Cyphosoma gravidum</i> Gory and Laporte, 1839) (= <i>Cyphosoma houskai</i> Obenberger, 1946) (= <i>Cyphosoma interruptum</i> Obenberger, 1918)	*		*			+		*	*			
<i>Sphenoptera trispinosa</i> (Klug, 1829) (= <i>Buprestis trilineata</i> Palisot de Beauvois, 1807) (= <i>Buprestis trispinosa</i> Klug, 1829) (= <i>Sphenoptera owariensis</i> Gory and Laporte, 1839) (= <i>Sphenoptera trilineata</i> Palisot, 1807)	*		*			++		*	*			
<i>Straspes squamosa</i> (Klug, 1829)	*		*			++		*	*	*	*	*
Fam. Carabidae												
<i>Acupalpus marginatus</i> (Dejean, 1829) (= <i>Stenolophus marginatus</i> Dejean, 1829) (= <i>Badister piceus</i> Ballion, 1871) (= <i>Egadroma marginata</i> Dejean, 1829) (= <i>Stenolophus klettei</i> Gerhardt, 1899) (= <i>Stenolophus piceus</i> Ballion, 1871)	*		*			+		*		*		
<i>Bembidion atlanticum</i> Wollaston, 1854 (= <i>Bembidion megaspilum</i> Walker, 1871)	*		*			+		*	*		*	*
<i>Bembidion latiplaga</i> (Chaudoir, 1850) (= <i>Bembidion telemus</i> Ragusa 1892) (= <i>Emphanes latiplaga</i> Chaudoir, 1850)	*		*			+		*	*	*		*
<i>Brachinus latipennis</i> Motschulsky, 1864 (= <i>Brachinus latipennis</i> Peyerimhoff, 1907)								*				
<i>Brachinus oblongus</i> Dejean, 1825	*		*			++		*	*	*		
<i>Chlaenius spoliatus</i> Rossi, 1792 (= <i>Carabus spoliatus</i> Rossi, 1792) (= <i>Chlaenites spoliatus</i> Rossi, 1792)	*		*			+		*	*	*		
<i>Glycia castanea</i> (Klug, 1831)	*		*			+		*			*	*
<i>Lebia arcuata</i> (Reiche and Saulcy, 1855) (= <i>Glycia arcuata</i> Reiche and Saulcy, 1855) (= <i>Glycia circumducta</i> Reitter, 1890) (= <i>Lebia circumducta</i> Reitter, 1890)	*		*			+		*				
<i>Pheropsophus africanus</i> (Dejean, 1825)	*		*			++		*			*	*
<i>Pheropsophus parallelus</i> (Dejean, 1825)	*		*			+		*	*			
<i>Tachys lucasi</i> Duval, 1852	*		*			++		*	*	*	*	
Fam. Cerambycidae												
<i>Chlorophorus varius</i> (Müller, 1766)	*		*			++		*	*	*		

(= <i>Clytanthus varius</i> Kiseritzky, 1915) (= <i>Clytus aegyptiacus</i> Ganglbauer, 1882) (= <i>Clytus ornatus</i> Brullé, 1832) (= <i>Clytus verbasci</i> Küster, 1847) (= <i>Clytus viridicollis</i> Gemminger and Harold, 1872) (= <i>Leptura gammoides</i> Geoffroy, 1785) (= <i>Leptura nigro-fasciata</i> Goeze, 1777) (= <i>Leptura strigosa</i> Gmelin, 1790) (= <i>Leptura varia</i> Müller, 1766)													
Fam. Chrysomelidae													
<i>Antipa chobauti</i> Pic, 1902 (= <i>Gynandrophthalma chobauti</i> Pic, 1902) (= <i>Titubaea chobauti</i> Pic, 1902)		*	*			+	*	*					
<i>Diorhabda elongata</i> (Brune, 1832) (= <i>Chrysomela elongata</i> Brulle, 1832) (= <i>Chrysomela costalis</i> Olivier, 1807) (= <i>Galeruca elongata</i> Brulle, 1832) (= <i>Chrysomela carinulata</i> Desbrochers, 1869)		*	*			+		*					
<i>Hypocassida subferruginea</i> (Schrank, 1776) (= <i>Cassida subferruginea</i> Schrank, 1776) (= <i>Cassida ferruginea</i> Goeze, 1777)		*	*			++		*			*		
Fam. Cicindellidae													
<i>Cicindela aulica</i> Dejean, 1831 (= <i>Cicindela bahreïnica</i> Ali, 1978) (= <i>Cicindela cupraria</i> Mandl, 1959) (= <i>Cicindela cyanicolor</i> Mandl, 1959) (= <i>Cicindela hesperidum</i> Wollaston, 1861) (= <i>Cicindela laetecupreoviridis</i> W.Horn, 1891) (= <i>Cicindela massauensis</i> Dokhtoureff, 1887) (= <i>Cicindela orienticola</i> Tschitscherine, 1903)	*			*		++	*	*					*
<i>Cicindela lunulata</i> Fabricius, 1781 (= <i>Calomera lunulata</i> Fabricius, 1781) (= <i>Cicindela barbara</i> Laporte, 1840) (= <i>Cicindela barthelemyi</i> Gené, 1836) (= <i>Cicindela oranensis</i> Schulz, 1909) (= <i>Cicindela otthi</i> Gistel, 1837) (= <i>Cicindela rectangulata</i> Beuthin, 1890) (= <i>Cicindela tripolitana</i> Schulz, 1909) (= <i>Lophyridia lunulata</i> Fabricius, 1781)	*			*		++	*	*	*				*
<i>Lophyra flexuosa</i> (Fabricius, 1787) (= <i>Cicindela flexuosa</i> Fabricius, 1787)	*			*		++	*	*	*				*
Fam. Coccinellidae													
<i>Hippodamia variegata</i> (Goeze, 1777) (= <i>Adonia variegata</i> Goze, 1777) (= <i>Coccinella variegata</i> Goeze, 1777)	*			*				*					*
<i>Coccinella septempunctata</i> Linnaeus, 1758	*	*		*		+	*	*	*	*			*
<i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i> Linnaeus, 1758	*	*		*		++	*	*	*	*		*	*
<i>Chnootriba elaterii</i> (Rossi, 1794) (= <i>Coccinella chrysomelina</i> Fabricius, 1775) (= <i>Epilachna chrysomelina</i> Fabricius, 1775) (= <i>Coccinella elaterii</i> Rossi, 1794) (= <i>Henosepilachna elaterii</i> Rossi, 1794)		*	*			+++		*	*			*	*
<i>Exochomus nigripennis</i> (Erichson, 1843)	*			*		+	*	*	*	*			*

(= <i>Chilocorus nigripennis</i> Erichson, 1843)														
<i>Nephus kiesenwetteri</i> Mulsant, 1850 (= <i>Scymnus kiesenwetteri</i> Mulsant, 1850)								*		*				
<i>Rodalia cardinalis</i> (Mulsant, 1850)	*			*		+	*	*	*	*				
<i>Scymnus interruptus</i> (Goeze, 1777)								*		*				*
Fam. Curculionidae														
<i>Ammocleonus hieroglyphicus</i> Olivier, 1807	*		*			++		*						
<i>Coniatus aegyptiacus</i> Capiomont 1868	*		*			++	*	*						
<i>Lixus anguinus</i> Linnaeus, 1767 (= <i>Curculio anguinus</i> Linnaeus, 1767) (= <i>Curculio bufo</i> Herbst, 1795) (= <i>Curculio mucronatus</i> Fabricius 1792)		*	*			++								
<i>Hypolixus pica</i> (Fabricius, 1798) (= <i>Curculio pica</i> Fabricius, 1798) (= <i>Lixus nubilosus</i> Boheman, 1835) (= <i>Lixus pulvisculosus</i> Boheman, 1835) (= <i>Lixus ornatus</i> Reiche, 1857)		*	*			++	*	*						
<i>Hypera postica</i> (Gyllenhal, 1813) (= <i>Curculio brunnipennis</i> Boheman, 1834) (= <i>Hypera brunnipennis</i> Boheman, 1834) (= <i>Hypera variabilis</i> Herbst, 1795) (= <i>Phytonomus posticus</i> Gyllenhal, 1813) (= <i>Rhynchaenus posticus</i> Gyllenhal, 1813) (= <i>Phytonomus transsylvanicus</i> Petri, 1901) (= <i>Phytonomus variabilis</i> Herbst, 1795)		*	**			++	*	*	*					
<i>Tanymecus migrans</i> Fahrhraeus, 1840	*		*			++		*	*					
<i>Tanymecus musculus</i> Fahrhraeus, 1840	*		*			++		*	*	*				
Fam. Dermestidae														
<i>Attagen scalaris</i> Pic, 1893	*	*	*			++	*	*						*
<i>Dermestis frischi</i> Kugelann, 1792 (= <i>Dermestes pollinctus</i> Hope, 1834)		*	**			+	*	*		*	*			
Fam. Dytiscidae														
<i>Bidessus major</i> Sharp, 1882	*			*		++		*	*					*
<i>Hydroglyphus signatellus</i> (Klug, 1834) (= <i>Hydroporus signatellus</i> Klug, 1834) (= <i>Bidessus signatellus</i> Klug, 1834)	*			*		+		*	*					*
<i>Cybister tripunctatus</i> Olivier, 1795	*	*		*		++	*	*	*					*
<i>Nebrioporus lanceolatus</i> (Walker, 1871) (= <i>Hydroporus insignis</i> Walker, 1871) (= <i>Hydroporus lanceolatus</i> Walker, 1871) (= <i>Deronectes arabicus</i> Sharp, 1882)	*			*		+		*						*
<i>Herophydrus musicus</i> Klug, 1833		*	*			+		*						
<i>Herophydrus solieri</i> Aube, 1838 (= <i>Hyphoporus solieri</i> Aubé, 1838)	*	*		*		++		*						
<i>Rhantus elevates</i> Sharp, 1882	*			*		+		*						*
Fam. Elateridae														
<i>Agrypnus notodonta</i> Latreille, 1827	*	*	**			+++	*	*		*				
<i>Hemicleus ferrantei</i> Buysson, 1911	*		*			+		*	*					
<i>Aeoloides grisescens</i> (Germar, 1844) (= <i>Cryptohypnus grisescens</i> Germar, 1844)	*		*			+		*	*					
<i>Cardiophorus dilutus</i> Erichson, 1840 (= <i>Craspedostethus dilutus</i> Erichson, 1840)	*		*			+		*	*					*
Fam. Hydrophilidae														
<i>Enochrus bicolor</i> (Fabricius, 1792) (= <i>Dytiscus chrysomelinus</i> Fabricius, 1787)	*	*		*		+++		*						

(= <i>Hydrobius ferrugineus</i> Küster, 1849) (= <i>Hydrophilus bicolor</i> Fabricius, 1792) (= <i>Hydrophilus fulvus</i> Marsham, 1802) (= <i>Hydrophilus grisescens</i> Gyllenhal, 1827) (= <i>Philhydrus mediterraneus</i> Sahlberg, 1900) (= <i>Philydrus atricornis</i> Kuwert, 1888) (= <i>Philydrus sahlbergi</i> Fauvel, 1887)													
<i>Sternolophus solireri</i> Castelnau, 1840 (= <i>Sternolophus aeratus</i> Reiche, 1854) (= <i>Sternolophus punctulatus</i> Schaufss, 1883) (= <i>Helobius noticollis</i> Mulsant, 1851) (= <i>Hydrous graecus</i> Baudi, 1864)	*			*	+++		*						
Fam. Malachidae													
<i>Malachius alferii</i> Pic, 1919	*			*	+		*				*	*	
Fam. Meloidae													
<i>Alosimus viridissimus</i> (Lucas, 1847) (= <i>Lydus viridissimus</i> Lucas, 1847) (= <i>Cantharis viridissimus</i> Lucas, 1847) (= <i>Cantharis opacipennis</i> Fairmaire, 1871) (= <i>Lydus coeruleus</i> Escherich, 1896) (= <i>Oelosimus intermedius</i> Pic, 1897) (= <i>Alosimus bipartitus</i> Pic, 1905) (= <i>Lydus purpurascens</i> , Pic, 1939)						*	*	*	*	*			
<i>Croscherichia sanguinolenta</i> (Olivier, 1811) (= <i>Mylabris sanguinolenta</i> Olivier, 1811) (= <i>Mylabris incerta</i> Klug, 1845) (= <i>Mylabris latrellei</i> Billberg, 1813) (= <i>Zonabris notatipennis</i> Pic, 1897) (= <i>Zonabris ghardaiensis</i> Pic, 1897) (= <i>Zonabris nedjalensis</i> Pic, 1920)						*	*	*	*	*	*	*	
<i>Hycleus quatuordecimsignatus</i> (Marseul, 1870) (= <i>Mylabris quatuordecimsignatus</i> Marseul, 1870) (= <i>Zonabris pharius</i> Pic, 1916) (= <i>Mylabris peyerimhoffi</i> Pic, 1929)							*	*	*				
<i>Mylabris sisymbrii</i> Klug, 1845							*	*	*	*			
<i>Mylabris tenebrosa</i> Laporte, 1840 (= <i>Zonabris mohtari</i> Escalera, 1910) (= <i>Zonabris postluteofasciata</i> Pic, 1921) (= <i>Zonabris soufensis</i> Pic, 1921) (= <i>Zonabris triluteofasciata</i> Pic, 1921) (= <i>Zonabris uniluteofasciata</i> Pic, 1921) (= <i>Mylabris satanas</i> Mader, 1929) (= <i>Mylabris exuta</i> Normand, 1950) (= <i>Zonabris diverseluteonotata</i> Pic, 1953) (= <i>Zonabris oberthuri</i> Pic, 1953) (= <i>Zonabris pauloluteobifasciata</i> Pic, 1953) (= <i>Zonabris septemnotata</i> Pic, 1953)						*	*						
Fam. Melolonthidae													
<i>Schizonycha nilotica</i> Blanchard, 1851	*			*	+		*	*					*
Fam. Melyridae													
<i>Melyris oblonga</i> (Fabricius, 1775) (= <i>Zygia oblonga</i> Fabricius, 1775)	*	*		*	+		*						
Fam. Nitidulidae													

<i>Carpophilus dimidiatus</i> (Fabricius, 1792) (= <i>Carpophilus auropilosus</i> Wollaston, 1854) (= <i>Carpophilus contingens</i> Walker, 1858) (= <i>Carpophilus dilutus</i> Murray, 1864) (= <i>Carpophilus halli</i> Dobson, 1954) (= <i>Carpophilus lewisi</i> Reitter, 1884) (= <i>Carpophilus limbalis</i> Murray, 1864) (= <i>Carpophilus luridus</i> Murray, 1864) (= <i>Carpophilus nigritus</i> Murray, 1864) (= <i>Carpophilus ochropterus</i> Klug, 1862) (= <i>Carpophilus puberulus</i> Montrouzier, 1860) (= <i>Carpophilus pusillus</i> Stephens, 1830) (= <i>Carpophilus robustus</i> Murray, 1864) (= <i>Carpophilus testaceus</i> Murray, 1864) (= <i>Carpophilus vittiger</i> Murray, 1864) (= <i>Nitidula dimidiatus</i> Fabricius, 1792)							*	*				*
<i>Carpophilus hemipterosus</i> Linnaeus, 1758							*	*				*
Fam. Ptinidae												
<i>Xyletinus bucephalus</i> (Illiger, 1807) (= <i>Ptilinus bucephalus</i> Illiger, 1807) (= <i>Xyletinus striatipennis</i> Fairmaire, 1857) (= <i>Calypterus sericans</i> Mulsant and Godart, 1859) (= <i>Xyletinus brunnescens</i> Obenberger, 1917) (= <i>Xyletinus bicoloricornis</i> Pic, 1924)	**		**			++	*					
Fam. Scarabaeidae												
<i>Adoretus graniceps</i> Reitter, 1889	*			*		+	*		*		*	*
<i>Chironitis pamphilus</i> Menetries, 1849 (= <i>Onitis pamphilus</i> Ménériés, 1849) (= <i>Onitis eumenes</i> Motschulsky, 1859) (= <i>Cheironitis ponticus</i> Lansberge, 1875)	*		*			+	*					
<i>Pentodon algerinum</i> (Herbst, 1789) (= <i>Scarabaeus algerinum</i> Herbst, 1789) (= <i>Pentodon dispar</i> Baudi, 1870)	*		*			+++	*	*	*	*	*	*
Fam. Staphilinidae												
<i>Paederus alfieri</i> Koch, 1934	*	*	*			+++	*	*				
<i>Pinophilus aegyptius</i> Erichson, 1840	*			*		++	*					
<i>Philonthus concinnus</i> (Gravenhorst, 1802) (= <i>Philonthus imperfectus</i> Sahlberg, 1903) (= <i>Philonthus melanarius</i> Mulsant and Rey, 1876) (= <i>Philonthus minor</i> Erichson, 1840) (= <i>Philonthus ochropus</i> Gravenhorst, 1802) (= <i>Staphylinus concinnus</i> Gravenhorst, 1802) (= <i>Staphylinus irregularis</i> Mannerheim, 1830) (= <i>Staphylinus ochropus</i> Gravenhorst, 1802)	*	*		*		++	*	*				
<i>Carpelimus memnonius</i> Erichson, 1840 (= <i>Trogophloeus memnonius</i> Erichson, 1840)	*	*		*		++	*	*				*
Fam. Tenebrionidae												
<i>Adesmia bicarinata</i> Klug, 1830	*			*		+	*	*				*
<i>Adesmia cothurnata</i> Forskal, 1775 (= <i>Tenebrio cothurnata</i> Forskal, 1775) (= <i>Adesmia subserrata</i> Chevrolat, 1877) (= <i>Pemelia bicarinata</i> Klug, 1830)	*			*		+	*					*
<i>Akis elevata</i> Solier, 1836	*		*			+++	*	*	*		*	*

<i>Alphitobius laevigatus</i> Fabricius, 1781 (= <i>Alphitobius piceus</i> Olivier, 1792) (= <i>Dendarus piceus</i> Olivier, 1811) (= <i>Opatrum laevigatum</i> Fabricius, 1781) (= <i>Opatrum piceus</i> Olivier, 1811)	*		*			+++	*	*	*				
<i>Anemia sardoa</i> (Gene, 1839) (= <i>Cheirodes sardoa</i> Gene, 1839)	*			*		++	*	*	*		*		*
<i>Erodium gibbus</i> Fabricius, 1775	*			*		+	*	*					*
<i>Trachyderma hispida</i> (Forskål, 1775) (= <i>Tenebrio hispidus</i> Forskål, 1775) (= <i>Ocnere hispida</i> Forskål, 1775)		*		*		+	*	*	*	*			*
<i>Trachyderma leprieuri</i> (Allard, 1886) (= <i>Ocnere sparsispina</i> Boehm, 1914)	*			*		++		*					
<i>Opatroides punctulatus</i> Burelle, 1832	*			*		++	*	*	*	*			*
<i>Pimelia angulata</i> Fabricius, 1775 (= <i>Pimelia consobrina</i> Lucas, 1858) (= <i>Pimelia retrospinosa</i> Lucas, 1858)		*		*		++		*	*	*			*
<i>Pimelia canescens</i> Klug, 1830 (= <i>Pimelia depilata</i> Solier, 1836)	*	*		*		+	*	*					*
<i>Pimelia nilotica</i> Snec, 1884 (= <i>Pimelia angulata nilotica</i> Snec, 1884)		*		*		+	*	*	*	*			
<i>Pimelia sericea</i> Olivier, 1795	*	*		*		+	*	*					
<i>Pimelia spinulosa</i> Klug, 1830		*		*		+	*	*					
<i>Scelosodis castaneus</i> (Eschscholtz, 1831)	*	*		*		+		*	*		*		*
<i>Zophosis abbreviata</i> Solier, 1834 (= <i>Zophosis semilineata</i> Deyrolle, 1867)	*			*		++		*	*				
<i>Zophosis carinata</i> Solier, 1834	*			*		++		*		*			
<i>Zophosis plana</i> Fabricius, 1775 (= <i>Erodium planus</i> Fabricius, 1775) (= <i>Zophosis carinata</i> Solier, 1834)	*			*		+		*	*				
<i>Zophosis sulcata</i> Deyrolle, 1867 (= <i>Zophosis bohemanni</i> Deyrolle, 1867) (= <i>Zophosis maeklini</i> Deyrolle, 1867)	*			*		+		*		*		*	
<i>Zophosis pygmaea</i> Solier, 1834 (= <i>Thrioptera crinita</i> klug, 1830) (= <i>Thrioptera maillei</i> Solier, 1836) (= <i>Ocnere pygmaea</i> Miller, 1861)	*			*		+	*	*					

Northern Coast: N. Coast Western : W. Desert Upper Egypt: U. Egypt Eastern Desert: E. desert
Gabal Elba: G. Elba.

Common +++ Fair ++ Rare + Major pest **

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Seasonal abundance of the cabbage aphid *Brevicoryne brassicae* (Hemiptera :
Aphididae) infesting canola plants in relation with associated natural enemies and
weather factors in Sohag Governorate

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Abstract:

Canola (*Brassica napus* L.) is grown in more than 120 countries around the world, including Egypt, hold the third position oil crop after palm and soybean oils . the cabbage aphid *Brevicoryne brassicae* (L.) (Hemiptera : Aphididae) is distributed in many parts of the world and is present in Egypt, especially in Upper Egypt. Its damage occurs on the plant leaves and transmit plant viruses. The present studies were carried at The Experimental Farm of Shandweel Agricultural Research Station, Sohag Governorate, Egypt during the winter seasons of 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 to investigate the population density of the cabbage aphid *B. brassicae* infesting canola in relation to some biotic and abiotic factors in Sohag Governorate. Data revealed that aphid started to take place in canola fields during the first week of December in both seasons (36 days after planting), then increased to reach its peak in at 20th and 13th February in the two seasons (Between 106 to 113 days after planting), respectively. The parasitism rate by *Diaeretiella rapae* (MacIntosh) (Hymenoptera: Braconidae) simultaneously increased as aphid populations increased in both seasons, also, the highest parasitism percentages were synchronization of the aphid numbers reduction in both seasons. *Coccinella undecimpunctata* L. (Coleoptera : Coccinellidae), *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) and *Syrphus corollae* Fabricius (Syrphidae: Diptera) were the main predators inhabiting canola plants, started to take place in canola fields after 2-3 weeks from aphid infestation. Predators showed their highest abundance during February and simultaneously increased as aphid populations increased in both seasons. Using simple correlation and simple regression values, the effects of parasitoid and predators showed positive, highly significant and significant effects, respectively, on *B. brassicae* during the two seasons. However, none of abiotic factors (Maximum and minimum temperature and mean relative humidity) showed significant effects in the two seasons.

Introduction

Canola (*Brassica napus* L.: Cruciferae) became one of the most important oil crops all over the world. In Egypt, it is cultivated in winter and can grow in the new reclaimed lands. Therefore, canola is one of the promising oil crops which could help in reducing the gap between the local production and the consumption in Egypt (Abdrabou *et al.*, 2017). Canola crop was attacked by several insect pests, but one of the most important insects is the cabbage aphid *Brevicoryne brassicae* (L.) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) was the most serious one (Mazeed, 2006; Amer *et al.*, 2009 and Syaid *et al.*, 2020). The population trend of the pest is the central corner to select the best time insecticide applications against cabbage aphid in canola fields. So, several authors studied the population density of this pest (Khan and Begum, 2005 and Temerak *et al.*, 2014). The parasitoid *Diaeretiella rapae* (MacIntosh) (Hymenoptera: Braconidae) is described as the main primary parasitoid of cabbage aphid and considered as one of the most effective factors decreased cabbage aphid population in canola fields (Sayed and Teilep, 2013 and Abdel-Galil and Mahmoud, 2019). The insect predators, *Coccinella undecimpunctata* L. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) and *Syrphus corollae* Fabricius (Syrphidae: Diptera) was reported as the most prevalent predator species found associated with the aphid in canola fields and their role in suppressing aphid populations in canola fields was studied by many authors (Saljoqi *et al.*, 2012 and Abbas *et al.*, 2017). Weather, especially, temperature and relative humidity play a major role in the development of aphid populations (Abbas *et al.*, 2014; Nematollahi *et al.*, 2016 and Akbar *et*

al., 2019). The present work was oriented to obtain better knowledge about *B. brassicae* population infesting canola in relation to some biotic and abiotic factors at Sohag Governorate.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental design:

The present studies were carried at The Experimental Farm of Shandweel Agricultural Research Station, Sohag Governorate, Egypt during the winter seasons of 2017/2018 and 2018/2019. An area of about half feddan (2100 m²) was cultivated with canola plants (Cultivar pactol) in completely randomized block design. Normal agricultural practices were performed, and no insecticidal treatments were used during the whole study period.

2. Population trend of aphid:

In order to study the population density of *B. brassicae*, ten canola plants were randomly selected, and the number of aphids was counted in each replicate. Data were collected at weekly intervals from emergence to the harvesting time.

3. Population trends of natural enemies:

In order to study the population trends of insect predators associated with cabbage aphid infesting canola plants, the numbers of *C. undecimpunctata*, *C. carnea* and *S. corollae* larvae were counted on 10 randomly plants selected from each replicate. Data were collected at weekly intervals from emergence to the harvesting time.

For the main associated parasitoid, *D. rapae*, the number of mummified aphids was counted from the first inspection date and continued to the end of the two seasons. The percentage of parasitism caused by aphid parasitoid was calculated in each sampling date according to following formula:

$$\text{Parasitism percentage} = \frac{\text{Number of parasitoid aphids}}{\text{The total number of aphids}} \times 100$$

4. The effect of some biotic and abiotic factors on population trend of cabbage aphid:

The effects of plant age, maximum temperature, minimum temperature, average relative humidity, total predator number and parasitoid number were tested for population fluctuation of aphid infesting canola using simple correlation according to Gomez and Gomez (1984).

Results and discussion

1. Population trend of *Brevicoryne brassicae* on canola plant:

The seasonal abundance of cabbage aphid inhabiting canola plants during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 growing seasons at Sohag Governorate was presented in Figure (1). Data revealed that the cabbage aphid started

to take place in canola fields during the first week of December in both seasons (36 days after planting). A gradual increase in aphid numbers were recorded until the appearance of its peak at 20th and 13th February in 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 seasons (Between 106 to 113 days after planting), respectively, with 591.33 and 904.33 aphids/ plant. Then the numbers of aphid decreased until the end of the two seasons. The highest aphid population was observed during February, followed by January in both seasons.

In agreement with the above results, Khan and Begum (2005) who found that the population of aphid on canola peaked in 3rd week of February, and Amer *et al.* (2009) who found that the highest population was recorded during the last week of February to the second week of March. Also, Temerak *et al.* (2014) showed that the highest population density of cabbage aphid was recorded during the plant age of 108-125 days old.

Figure (1): Population trend of *Brevicoryne brassicae* infesting canola plants during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 seasons at Sohag Governorate.

2. Population trends of natural enemies associated with *Brevicoryne brassicae* on canola plant:

2.1. *Diaeretiella rapae* parasitoid:

The mean percentage of cabbage aphid parasitized by *D. rapae* during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 growing seasons at Sohag Governorate was estimated as shown in Figure (2). The first mummified aphids appear was observed during the last week of December in both seasons, the seasonal mean of parasitism percentage maximized two times in both seasons. The peaks were observed in 16th January (12.03%) and 13th March (39.99%) in 2017/2018 season. While, in 2018/2019 season, the peaks

recorded in 9th January (15.58%) and 27th February (43.01%). The parasitoids appear delay by about three weeks after canola infestation by aphids. However, the parasitism rate simultaneously increased as aphid populations increased in the both seasons, also, the highest parasitism percentages were synchronization of the aphid numbers reduction in both seasons.

Relations between *B. brassicae* and its parasitoids were clarified by Temerak *et al.* (2014). The previous results support the findings of Abdel-Galil and Mahmoud (2019) who reported that the aphid number decrease was in simultaneous with the increase of its parasitoid.

Figure (2): Mean percentage of *Diaeretiella rapae* parasitism on *Brevicoryne brassicae* infesting canola plants during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 growing seasons at Sohag Governorate.

2.2. Predators:

The seasonal abundance of *C. undecimpunctata* associated with cabbage aphid inhabiting canola plants during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 growing seasons at Sohag Governorate was presented in Figure (3). Data revealed that the coccinellid predator started to take place in canola fields the last half of December (After 2 weeks of aphid infestation) and recorded two peaks in both seasons. During first season, the peaks observed in 2nd

January (3.33 larvae/ plant) and at 13th February (4.00 larvae/ plant). However, in the second season, the peaks recorded in 2nd January (2.33 larvae/ plant) and at 20th February (3.67 larvae/plant). After that, the numbers decreased to the end of the two seasons. It is clear that the highest abundance of this predator was detected during February followed by January and simultaneously increased as aphid populations increased in both seasons.

Figure (3): Population trend of *Coccinella undecimpunctata* inhabiting canola plants during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 growing seasons at Sohag Governorate.

The seasonal abundance of *C. carnea* associated with cabbage aphid inhabiting canola plants during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 growing seasons at Sohag Governorate was presented in Figure (4). Data revealed that the chrysopid predator started to take place in canola fields the last half of December (After 2 weeks of aphid infestation) and recorded three peaks in both seasons. During the first season, the peaks were obtained in 26th December (2.33 larvae/ plant), 23rd January (3.33 larvae/ plant) and in 27th February (2.33 larvae/ plant). However, in the second season, the peaks were recorded in 26th December (3.33 larvae/ plant), 6th February (3.67 larvae/ plant) and in 20th February (2.00 larvae/plant). After that, the numbers decreased to the end of the two seasons. The highest abundance of this predator was detected during February followed by January and simultaneously increased as aphid populations increased in both seasons.

The seasonal abundance of *S. corollae* associated with cabbage aphid inhabiting canola plants during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 growing seasons at Sohag Governorate was

presented in Figure (5). Data revealed that the syrphid predator started to take place in canola fields the last week of December (After 3 weeks of aphid infestation) and recorded one and two peaks in the two seasons, respectively. During the first season, the predator maximized at 6th March (3.33 larvae/ plant). However, in the second season, the predator maximized at 9th January (1.67 larvae/ plant) and at 27th February (2.33 larvae/plant). After that, the numbers decreased to the end of the two seasons. The highest abundance of this predator was detected during February followed by March and January in the two seasons, respectively, and simultaneously increased as aphid populations increased in both seasons.

In harmony with the previous results, Saljoqi *et al.* (2012) found that at the time when the aphid population started to increase the population peaks of *C. septempunctata* and *C. carnea* was recorded. Also, Abbas *et al.* (2017) reported that among the various natural enemies, the dominions were coccinellid followed by green lacewings and syrphid flies.

Figure (4): Population trend of *Chrysoperla carnea* inhabiting canola plants during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 Growing seasons at Sohag Governorate.

Figure (5): Population trend of *Syrphus corollae* inhabiting canola plants during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 growing seasons at Sohag governorate.

3. Effect of biotic and abiotic factors on population of *Brevicoryne brassicae* infesting canola plants:

The effect of biotic factors (Plant age, parasitoid and total predators) and abiotic factors (Maximum and minimum temperatures and mean relative humidity) on the population of *B. brassicae* infesting canola plants was worked by processing

the data of simple correlation and simple regression analysis (Table 1).

The parasitoid gave highly positive and significant effects of simple correlation and simple regression values on the population of *B. brassicae* during the two seasons. Also, total predators gave positive and significant effects of simple correlation and simple regression values on the population of *B. brassicae* during the

two seasons, no effects were observed for plant age in both seasons. In contrast with these results, Sayed and Teilep (2013) found that the effects of predators and percent parasitism showed insignificant effects of simple correlation values on the population of canola aphid. While, Abdel-Rahman *et al.* (2020) suggested that the differences in levels of infesting between the seasons might be attributed to the differences in weather factors and / or the effect of natural enemies in each season.

However, it is evident from the results that the effects of abiotic factors (Maximum and minimum temperatures and mean relative humidity) showed insignificant effects of simple correlation and simple regression values on the population of cabbage

aphid. In agreement with these results, Abbas *et al.* (2014) found that none of abiotic factors were significantly correlated with *B. brassicae* population except minimum temperature in the second season. Akbar *et al.* (2019) found that the aphid abundance showed non-significant association with mean temperature, humidity and sunshine.

From the values of R-Squared (R^2) in the simple regression analysis, the most effective factor in the population of *B. brassicae* during the two seasons was the parasitism followed by the total predator number. The high R-Squared (R^2) value has been considered as evidence of the responsibility of parasitoids and predators to serve as a good biological control agent against *B. brassicae* populations.

Table (1): Simple correlation (r), simple regression (b) and R-Squared (R^2) between *Brevicoryne brassicae* and certain abiotic and biotic factors on canola at Sohag Governorate during 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 seasons.

Tested factors	2017/2018 season			2018/2019 season		
	Simple correlation (r)	Simple regression		Simple correlation (r)	Simple regression	
		b	R^2		b	R^2
Plant age	0.294	1.434	0.086	0.174	1.258	0.030
Parasitoid	0.962**	4.735**	0.925	0.976**	3.415**	0.953
Total predators	0.689**	42.458**	0.474	0.572*	55.877*	0.327
Maximum temperature	-0.027	-1.030	0.001	0.001	0.069	0.000
Minimum temperature	0.062	3.214	0.004	-0.194	-28.794	0.038
Mean relative humidity	-0.105	-1.656	0.011	-0.149	-5.068	0.022

*: Significant ($p < 0.05\%$) **: Highly significant ($p < 0.01\%$)

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Effect of biotic and abiotic factors on *Rhopalosiphum maidis* (Hemiptera: Aphididae) populations in corn fields at Sohag Governorate, Egypt.

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Abstract:

Abundance and fluctuation of *Rhopalosiphum maidis* (Fitch) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) and its predatory insects was studied on both sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.), maize (*Zea mays* L.) and their intercropping of both crops related weather factor through the two plantation dates of 15th June and 15th July for the two successive seasons of 2019 and 2020, respectively. Regression and correlation analysis between the aphid and predator densities were carried out. Nine predacious species were collected from corn fields, these species included: Four coleopterous, i.e. *Coccinella undecimpunctata*. (L.) , *Scymnus pallidivestis* Mulsant, *Stethorus gilvifrons* Mulsant (Coccinellidae) and *Paederus alfieri* Koch (Staphylinidae), two hemipterous *Orius albidipennis* (Reuter) and *O. laevigatus* Fieber (Anthocoridae), dipteran syrphid hover flies, *Xanthogramma aegyptium* Wied. and *Sphaerophoria flavicauda* Zett. (Syrphidae) and Neuropteran *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Chrysopidae).

Introduction

Sorghum plants *Sorghum bicolor* L. is an important cereal crop worldwide that is widely cultivated for food, fiber, forage, ethanol, and sugar production (Andy, 2007 and Liu *et al.* , 2009). In Egypt, more than 70% of cultivated area with sorghum is in Upper Egypt, i.e. Assiut, Sohag and Fayoum Governorates, (FAO, 2012). Furthermore, maize (*Zea mays* L.) is one of the principal cereal crops. Egypt represents the third place for production at the level of the African continent (Abd El-Fatah *et al.* , 2015). It is the most important source of food for livestock and poultry. It is also used for human food alone or mixed with wheat flour for bread making. It is a major

component in several industries such as corn oil and starch (Nagarjuna *et al.*, 2015). The abundance of pests in maize, sorghum plants and the intercropping between them at earlier and late plantations were studied by many authors such as Daware *et al.* (2004) and Maluleke *et al.* (2005).

Piercing sucking insect pests especially aphids are considered as one of the most serious pest infesting sorghum crops, aphids affect cereal by direct feeding on plants, and or by transmitting virus (El-Gepaly, 2007 and Youssef, 2013). Populations of aphids, *Rhopalosiphum maidis* (Fitch) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) were significantly affected by temperature and relative humidity (Farag *et al.*,

1992). Pfannenstiel and Yeargan (2002) and Musser *et al.* (2012) mentioned the predators collected in the different corn fields. Predators were present in association with both aphids the dominant foliar-feeding insects on sorghum, *R. maidis* and *S. graminum* and their numbers oscillated during the season in Texas, predators did not suppress increase in numbers of *S. graminum* in late July and August (Archer *et al.*, 1990). Several studies dealt with the susceptibility of corn to different insect pests (El-Mandarawy *et al.*, 2000; Muhammad *et al.*, 2010 and Babu *et al.*, 2017).

Therefore, the present work is conducted to monitor aphids, *R. maids* inhabiting corn field in Sohag Governorate, Egypt and their population dynamics in relation to weather factors.

Materials and methods

The population fluctuation of *R. maids* on maize (*Z. maize*), sorghum (*S. bicolor*) and the intercropping of both crops were recorded while other species of pests have been neglected due to their occurrence by few numbers. An area of half feddan was divided into 9 plots cultivated at Shandaweel Research Station, Sohag Governorate, Egypt, during the summer seasons 2019 and 2020. Maize variety “Single Hybrid 10 (S.H. 10)” and Sorghum variety “Dorado” and them intercropping was planted in two plantations; the first plantation date on 15th June and the second one on 15th July throughout both seasons. Each tested cultivar was represented by three replicates which were arranged in a randomized complete block design. The experimental area was kept free from any pesticide treatments.

1. Estimation of aphid numbers:

To estimate the infestation of *R. maids* individuals, samples of ten plants /plot from each variety were randomly

picked at weekly intervals started after two weeks plant age until the end of this experiment. aphids infested plants were counted and collected in a bag, then transferred to the laboratory in the same day to identify the species. The daily mean of minimum, maximum temperatures and relative humidity %, were obtained from the meteorological records of Central Laboratory for Agriculture Climate, Agriculture Research Center at Dokki, Egypt.

2. Natural enemies:

Insect predators were counted by either direct counts from ten randomly chosen plants /plot or yellow sticky cards were placed in the fields to attract the predators. Predators were collected and preserved for identification in tubes containing 70% ethyl alcohol.

Identification of these species carried out by Dr. Ayman Mohyieldeen (Department of Taxonomy, Plant Protection Research Institute, ARC, Giza, Egypt).

3. Statistical analysis:

Statistical analyses were performed using ANOVA and mean values were separated by the least significant difference (L.S.D.) procedure (Snedecor and Cochran, 1980) at $P = 5\%$. To find the differences between seasonal mean numbers of tested pest on investigated maize and sorghum varieties

Results and discussion

1. Population dynamics of *Rhopalosiphum maids* on corn fields population:

Fluctuations in the population density of *R. maidis* inhabiting maize, sorghum and the intercropping of both crops sown in two different dates during two successive seasons 2019 and 2020 at two different planting dates 1st plantation on 15th June and 2nd plantation on 15th July, respectively illustrated in (Figure 1).

Figure (1): Mean number of *Rhopalosiphum maidis* / plant from maize, sorghum and the intercropping plots on two planted dates (15th June and 15th July) in the seasons of 2019 and 2020, at Sohag Governorate.

On the 1st plantation at the season of 2019, for the sole plots, the occurrence of *R. maidis* began from the 2nd week of July. In sole plots, the mean numbers of aphids increased gradually reaching its peak of 231.67 insects/maize plant on 22nd August and 492.33 insects/sorghum plant on 29th

August and decreased to reach its minimum 56.33 insects/maize plant and 147.67 insects/sorghum plants on 3rd October. For the intercropping plots, the peaks of aphids reached to 252 insects/ plant on 19th September in maize and 544.67 insects/plant on 29th August in sorghum (Figure 2).

Figure (2): Fluctuation of *Rhopalosiphum maidis* collected from maize, sorghum and the intercropping of both crops on Sohag Governorate during 2019 season and 1st plantation 15th June.

While in the second plantation, *R. maidis* started to appear on 8th August and 15th August for sole plots of maize and sorghum, respectively. Also, in the intercropping plots it began for both on 22nd August, at season of 2019. The numbers of insects reached its maximum on 3rd October in sole plots

(188.00 and 156.67 insects/ plant of maize and sorghum, respectively) and on 12th September (205.33 insects/ plant) and on 19th September (271.33 insects/ plant) in the intercropping maize and sorghum plots, respectively (Figure 3).

Figure (3): Fluctuation of *Rhopalosiphum maidis* collected from maize, sorghum and the intercropping of both crops on Sohag governorate during 2019 season and 2nd plantation 15th July.

The mean numbers of *R. maidis* increased in the intercropped of both crops than those of the monoculture plots of the same plant, during the 1st

and 2nd plantation at season 2019 (Figure 4)

Figure (4): Mean of population fluctuation of *Rhopalosiphum maidis* throughout the 1st and 2nd plantation (15th July and 15th June) through the season 2019 on Sohag Governorate.

Meanwhile, 1st plantation at the season of 2020, the aphid occurred from 23rd July to early October in sole maize plots, intercropping maize plots and sole sorghum plots, but in the intercropping sorghum plots it appeared from 9th July to early October. Aphids increased gradually reaching their climax of 143 individuals/plant on 24th

September and then decreased to be 80.33 individuals/plant in early October in sole maize plots. In addition, aphids peaked on 27th August, 24th September and 17th September (456, 317.67 and 197 individuals/plant, respectively) in the monoculture sorghum and the intercropping of both crops, respectively (Figure 5).

Figure (5): Fluctuation of *Rhopalosiphum maidis* collected from maize, sorghum and the intercropping of both crops on Sohag Governorate during 2020 season and 1st plantation 15th June.

In 2020 at 2nd plantation, aphids began to appear on 6th August for the

sole and intercropped systems. It maximized on 24th September (182.33

insects/ plant) in sole maize, on 10th September (158.00 insects/ plant) in the sole sorghum plots and on 3rd September (268.33 and 216.67 insects/

plant) on 10th September for the intercropped of both crops respectively, (Figure 6).

Figure (6): Fluctuation of *Rhopalosiphum maidis* collected from maize, sorghum and the intercropping of both crops on Sohag Governorate during 2020 season and 2nd plantation 15th July.

The mean numbers of *R. maidis* increased in the intercropped plots than those of the monoculture plots of the

same plant, during the 1st and 2nd plantation of the season 2020 (Figure 7).

Figure (7): Mean of population fluctuation of *Rhopalosiphum maidis* throughout the 1st and 2nd plantation (15th July and 15th June) of the season 2020 on Sohag Governorate.

These results agree mostly with those of Archer *et al.* (1990) who found that the highest densities of the aphid (about 200 aphids / plant) occurred on sorghum planted on first of May or in June. Borade *et al.* (1993) noticed that the least percentage of infected leaves (15.3%) was on the sorghum sown in the last week of September. Ibrahim *et*

al. (1995) observed that the corn leaf aphid, *R. maidis* was reduced to 21 aphids/leaf in 2: 2 maize: cowpea intercrop as compared to 34 aphids/leaf on sole maize. Gad-Elrab (1997) indicated that there was significantly more infestation by *R. maidis* when sorghum intercropped with soybean than on sorghum grown alone. Kuroli

(2002) found that the average number of aphids was 24.99 per plant. *R. padi* and *M. dirhodum* were the most dominant species.

2. Effect of abiotic factors (Maximum, minimum temperatures and relative humidity) on the abundance of *Rhopalosiphum maidis*:

Simple correlation coefficients presented in Table (1) showed variable relationships between weather factors and *R. maidis* density on maize, sorghum and their intercropping plantations during 2019 and 2020

seasons. The partial regression analysis in terms of regression (b) and explained values (E.V. %) are also summarized in Table (1). Regression values showed that the increasing of minimum night and daily maximum temperatures was almost decreased the aphid numbers, however, the increase of R.H. % showed a positive or negative reduction in the aphid density.

Table (1): Simple correlation and partial regression coefficient of three weather factors on the population density of *Rhopalosiphum maidis* through tow plantation dates in 2019 and 2020 seasons, at Sohag Governorate.

Seasons	Plantations	Factors		Maize			Sorghum			Intercropping Maize			Intercropping Sorghum		
				R	b	E.V.%	R	b	E.V.%	r	b	E.V.%	r	B	E.V.%
2019	1 st plantation	Temperature	Max.	-0.394	-9.159	39.63	-0.223	-6.777	25.40	-0.358	-10.950	49.16	-0.337	-	31.04
			Min.	-0.380	-15.480		-0.335	-17.558		*-0.557	-29.537		-0.280	-	
		Mean RH.%	0.444	14.870	0.345		41.639	0.371		13.828	0.449		43.997		
	2 nd plantation	Temperature	Max.	0.069	-5509.000	66.67	-0.060	6.818	69.32	-0.151	3.468	25.87	-0.209	-1.185	16.58
			Min.	*-0.566	-11048.00		*-0.758	-23.053		-0.483	-20.572		-0.399	-	
		Mean RH.%	-0.359	-1038.830	-0.479		-1.070	-0.169		12.641	-0.156		6.670		
2020	1 st plantation	Temperature	Max.	-0.319	-5.883	65.41	-0.345	-13.419	54.64	-0.149	-1.166	54.12	-0.238	-7.541	78.78
			Min.	*-0.753	-22.595		*-0.647	-66.897		*-0.707	-48.634		*-0.855	-	
		Mean RH.%	-0.128	-1.356	0.080		15.552	-0.025		10.861	-0.260		-5.560		
	2 nd plantation	Temperature	Max.	-0.373	8.834	70.48	*-0.696	-10.079	65.97	*-0.709	-11.440	71.92	-0.465	0.069	62.07
			Min.	*-0.808	-42.847		*-0.660	-13.072		*-0.739	-23.217		*-0.742	39.629	
		Mean R. H.%	-0.167	0.550	-0.011		17.712	-0.094		14.292	-0.029		31.688		
r= Simple correlation		b= Partial regression coefficient					E.V.%= Explained variance								

Results of *R. maidis* occurrence harmony with Ahmed (1996) who observed that *R. maidis* started early July and continued up to late September. Sorghum plantation on 10th June showed the greatest population of *R. maidis*. Early plantation on 20th May received the lowest population for pests. Kuroli (2002) observed that the population of the aphids first peaked in July. In September, the number of aphids began to increase, resulting in a second population peak in October. Finally, Hanafy (2005) stated that *R. maidis* attacking sorghum in Upper Egypt, began to build up its population at late of July and early August, then, it decreased gradually till the end of the growing season. This may be due to the lower temperature at the beginning of September and because of the maturity of maize plants that become unsuitable for aphid feeding.

3. Effect of biotic factors (Predacious insects) on the abundance of *Rhopalosiphum maidis*:

3.1. Predacious insect species:

Data presented in Table (2) summarize the number of predators collected from maize, sorghum and their intercropping of both crops at the 1st and 2nd plantation date of the two seasons 2019 and 2020. Nine predacious species were collected during experimental period. These species included: Four coleopterous, i.e. *Coccinella undecimpunctata* (L.) , *Scymnus pallidivestis* Mulsant, *Stethorus gilvifrons* Mulsant (Coccinellidae) and *Paederus alfieri* Koch (Staphylinidae), two hemipterous *Orius albidipennis* (Reuter) and *O. laevigatus* Fieber (Anthocoridae), dipteran syrphid hover flies, *Xanthogramma aegyptium* Wied. and *Sphaerophoria flavicauda* Zett. (Syrphidae) and Neuropteran *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Chrysopidae). The linear regression coefficient of *R.*

maidis population and each of the collected predators from maize, sorghum and intercropping of both crops were summarized in the two plantations and seasons are shown in (Tables 2).

Population density of *R. maidis* inhibiting maize, sorghum and the intercropping of both crops sown in two different dates during two successive seasons 2019 and 2020 at two planting dates, on 15th June and 15th July showed that, The mean numbers of *R. maidis* increased in the intercropped of both crops than those of the monoculture plots of the same plant, during the 1st and 2nd plantation at the seasons 2019 and 2020. Regression values showed that the increasing of minimum night and daily maximum temperatures was almost decreased the aphid numbers, however, the increase of R.H. % showed a positive or negative reduction in the aphid density.

Nine predaceous species were collected during experimental period. These species included: Four coleopterous, i.e. *C. undecimpunctata*, *S. pallidivestis*, *S. gilvifrons* and *P. alfieri* , two hemipterous *O. albidipennis* and *O. laevigatus* , dipteran syrphid hover flies, *X. aegyptium* and *S. flavicauda* and Neuropteran *C. carnea* .

Table (2): Linear regression coefficient of the different predator species on the population density of aphids, *Rhopalosiphum maidis* infesting maize, sorghum and the intercropping of both crops on the 1st and 2nd plantation dates in of 2019 and 2020 seasons, at Sohag Governorate.

Plantations	Predator Species	Maize		Sorghum		Intercropping Plots	
		r	b	R	b	R	b
Seasons 2019							
1st plantation	<i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i>	0.505	0.010	0.672	0.010	0.671	0.006
	<i>Scymnus spp.</i>	0.397	0.010	0.406	0.004	0.267	0.004
	<i>Orius spp.</i>	0.534	0.054	0.561	0.017	0.698	0.032
	Syrphids	0.466	0.019	0.562	0.018	0.557	0.012
	<i>Paederus alfieri</i>	0.212	0.002	0.440	0.002	0.115	0.000
	<i>Chrysoperla carnea</i>	0.438	0.008	0.509	0.004	0.606	0.005
	Total No.	0.549	0.102	0.629	0.056	0.667	0.064
2nd plantation	<i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i>	0.685	0.015	0.411	0.016	0.909	0.019
	<i>Scymnus spp.</i>	0.289	0.013	0.371	0.013	0.575	0.021
	<i>Orius spp.</i>	0.546	0.054	0.649	0.041	0.951	0.068
	Syrphids	0.400	0.007	0.892	0.084	0.917	0.029
	<i>Paederus alfieri</i>	0.613	0.006	0.912	0.010	0.613	0.002
	<i>Chrysoperla carnea</i>	0.301	0.002	0.002	0.000	0.111	0.001
	Total No.	0.416	0.073	0.559	0.120	0.964	0.141
Seasons 2020							
1st plantation	<i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i>	*0.674	0.016	*0.920	0.008	*0.795	0.011
	<i>Scymnus spp.</i>	*0.551	0.017	*0.551	0.006	*0.673	0.016
	<i>Orius spp.</i>	*0.858	0.114	*0.612	0.023	*0.779	0.069
	Syrphids	0.490	0.017	0.484	0.019	*0.650	0.033
	<i>Paederus alfieri</i>	0.291	0.003	0.291	0.001	0.376	0.002
	<i>Chrysoperla carnea</i>	*0.692	0.022	*0.627	0.009	*0.780	0.027
	Total No.	*0.861	0.188	*0.705	0.067	*0.790	0.147
2nd plantation	<i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i>	*0.773	0.014	*0.751	0.027	*0.921	0.015
	<i>Scymnus spp.</i>	*0.726	0.040	0.510	0.027	0.538	0.023
	<i>Orius spp.</i>	*0.783	0.092	*0.886	0.058	*0.951	0.066
	Syrphids	0.410	0.006	*0.847	0.120	*0.828	0.032
	<i>Paederus alfieri</i>	*0.577	0.004	*0.793	0.009	*0.811	0.005
	<i>Chrysoperla carnea</i>	0.485	0.006	0.403	0.013	0.489	0.005
	Total No.	*0.837	0.159	*0.938	0.253	*0.854	0.130
* Significant effect							

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Controlling of some honeybee *Apis mellifera* (Hymenoptera: Apidae) colonies diseases
by bee venom

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Abstract:

Controlling of some diseases in honeybee *Apis mellifera* L. (Hymenoptera: Apidae) colonies such as bacterium (*Paenibacillus larvae*), fungus (*Aspergillus flavus*), protozoa (*Nosema apis*), mite (*Varroa destructor*) and the monitoring activities of honeybee colonies after controlling by bee venom had performed. Feeding with bee venom solution gave the highest mean of infect reduction with American foul brood disease compared with other treatment. Spraying with bee venom solution gave the higher mean of infect reduction with the stone brood disease than feeding with bee venom. The reduction percentage of honeybee workers infected with *N. apis* that treated with bee venom were 41.0, 50.0, 50.8, 46.0 and 3.7 % for feeding, spraying for bee venom solution, positive control (Artemisia), (Septazole) and negative control, respectively. The bee venom solution gave highest values of fallen varroa mite followed by (Formic acid and negative control), respectively in sealed brood and adult. The worker brood rearing activity after the treating with bee venom solution had a major peak of rearing in next summer and spring (653.7 inch²/col.) while the spring season (544.2 inch²/col.). The general adult population mean of workers recorded for the treated colonies were (25700 worker/colony), it is also appeared that the highest population of colonies recovered from *V. destructor* was recorded (28800 worker/colony) followed by colonies treated against *P. larvae*, *A. flavus*, *N. apis*, and untreated colonies were recorded (28400, 24900, 23200 and 23100 worker/colony), respectively.

Introduction

The apiculture industry plays an important role in generating employment and in increasing family income in the rural areas of the world. Many developing countries are trying to improve the quality of their honeybee products, but they frequently encounter the main obstacle in apiculture; The diseases and pests of honeybees. Therefore, it is very important to

prevent and control them (Wahba *et al.*, 2020). The use of manufactured chemicals (Whether pesticides or antibiotics) which is used to control diseases and pests inside the honeybee colonies represents a risk to consumer health and reduces the efficiency of vital honeybee products. The use of natural materials secreted by honeybees such as bee venom and other products and use it to combat some diseases and

pests of honeybee colonies to obtain clean honeybee products free from any harmful residues, whether from pesticides or manufactured antibiotics, which increases their biological efficiency (Wang *et al.*, 2014). The use of bee venom solution feeding or spraying on bees inside laboratory cages has increased the longevity of workers and improves some of the characteristics of honeybee colonies such as hoarding behavior, bee population, brood rearing, stored pollen, stored honey areas, hygienic behavior, and foraging activity inside honeybee colonies, the bee venom contains many proteins, lipids, some enzymes and vitamins, (Metwally, 2016; El-Ettreby, 2018 and Wahba *et al.*, 2020). One of the most important diseases is dangerous for honeybee colonies, varroa mite, *Varroa destructor*, is external parasite attacks three castes of the honeybee colony, *A. mellifera* ., at their different ages preferred to the drone broods, workers and queen, and the parasite destroys the honeybee colony if mite was not noted and early controlled (Al-Abbadi and Nazer, 2003 and Mabrouk *et al.*, 2019),

American foulbrood is a disease of the larval stage of honey bees (Species of the genus *Apis*) caused by *Paenibacillus larvae* (*P. larvae*), which is widely distributed. *P. larvae* is a bacterium that can produce over one billion spores in each infected larva. The spores are very long living and extremely resistant to heat and chemical agents and only the spores can induce the disease. used concentrations of bee venom treatment succeed to inhibiting *P. larvae* bacterium except the last three concentrations that exhibited non-antibacterial activity against this bacterium (Wahba, 2020). Stone brood is a fungal disease associated with honeybee brood, caused by *Aspergillus flavus*, and is a common and widespread disease that can result in

severe reduction of emerging worker bees and thus overall colony productivity, the highest three concentrations of bee venom that induced weak activity against the growth of *A. flavus* fungus. (Jensen *et al.*, 2013 and Wahba *et al.* , 2020). *Nosema apis* and *cerana* are an obligate microsporidian intracellular parasite infectious to honey bees. *Nosema apis* and *N. cerana* both parasitize honeybees, *N. cerana* has geographically outcompeted *N. apis*. Severe *N. cerana* infections (Nosemosis) can cause bee mortality and have been correlated with colony losses (Li *et al.*, 2018).

Therefore, this work aims to study the controlling with bee venom inside the honeybee colonies on the bacteria (*P. Larvae*), fungi (*A. flavus*), protozoa (*N. apis*) and mite (*V. destructor*) and the monitoring activities of honeybee colonies after controlling by bee venom inside honeybee colonies.

Materials and methods

The present investigation was carried out as a field trial to controlling the causes of American foul brood (AFB) , stone brood, nosema and varroa diseases at the apiary of the Bee Research Department, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Ministry of Agriculture, Giza, Egypt, during years, 2019-2020.

1. Effect of bee venom on *Penibacillus larvae* bacterium:

The efficiency of the bee venom in controlling the causative agent of the bacterial disease was examined in private colonies placed away from the apiary; nine honeybee colonies of about equal strength (3 brood and 2 honey with pollen combs / hive) headed by open mated hybrid Carniolan queens, all colonies divided into 3 groups, each group treated with a different treatment and consisted of 3 replicates.

On July 2019, 100 ml spore suspension of pure bacterial isolate was prepared, completed to 450 ml with sugar syrup (w: v, 1:1), and its germ concentration was estimated by microscopy counting slide as 10^4 spore / ml, whereas each replicate of honeybee colonies was fed with 50 ml, and replicated three times by interval on week between each twice, then colonies were daily examined until the AFB symptoms appeared in all colonies after 21 days from the last feeding.

Whereas the AFB disease symptoms can be recognized by inserting a matchstick into the infected brood cell and drawing out, it is giving a threadlike longer than 2.5 cm (Morse and Nowogrodzki, 1990 and Hashish *et al.*, 2008 and 2016).

Hence, on the same day of disease symptoms appearance, all honeybee colonies treated three times by intervals one week with the following materials and manner:

Group (1): (Bee venom): Three infected colonies were treated with bee venom solution by feeding (5 mg/100 ml sugar syrup).

Group (2): (Positive control): Three infected colonies were treated by the veterinary antibiotic Tylosin as a positive control, since it received to each colony 200 mg of Tylosin tartrate antibiotic mixed with 20 g sugar powder on top of the brood frames (Peng *et al.*, 1996).

Group (3): (Negative control): Three infected colonies were fed with sugar syrup only as a negative control.

Subsequently, the progress of disease was evaluated during and after treating by weekly inspection of all experimental groups. The diseased larvae were counted until the end of the experiment. The colonies with no visible signs of AFB disease were considered recovered.

2. Effect of bee venom on stone brood disease (*Aspargillus flavus*):

Nine honeybee colonies appeared signs of stone brood disease in spring season 2019 were subjugated to honey bee venom according to the following plan; before the trial, both the stone brood infestation level and the size of all colonies were monitored to obtain three homogeneous experimental groups of bee colonies as the following: **Group (1): (Feeding treatment):** 3 replicates of honeybee colonies were fed with mixture of bee venom with sugar syrup solution as 5 mg venom/ 100 ml sugar syrup 1:1.

Group (2): (Spraying treatment): 3 replicates of honeybee colonies were subjugated to bee venom solution (5 mg venom/ 100 ml distilled water) spraying on the workers and brood combs.

Group (3); (Positive control): 3 replicates of honeybee colonies were treated by human antibiotic Ultragriseofulvine and that used as a positive control to decrease a stone brood infestation by dose of 12.5 mg / Liter water spraying on the bees and wax combs.

Group (4): (Negative control): The honeybee workers and combs of 3 replicates were sprayed by only diluted sugar syrup (1/2 : 1) as a negative control colonies.

3. Effect of bee venom on honeybee workers infected with *Nosema apis*:

Fifteen colonies were equalized to 8 combs covered with bees contain (5 brood combs + 3 honey combs) during late Autumn, 2019. One hundred honeybee workers infected by *Nosema* spores were collected from each colony, analyzed and checked by a microscope. Fresh *Nosema* spores from honeybee colonies were collected from each colony and processed separately according to (Botías *et al.*, 2012 and Martín-Hernández *et al.*, 2012).

Five groups of honey bee worker each group contain 3 colonies (Infected replicates with *Nosema*) were made as the following:

Group (1): (Feeding treatment): The colonies were fed with bee venom solution (5 mg/100 ml sugary solution).

Group (2): (Positive control of feeding): The colonies were fed on sugar syrup with Artemisia (100 ml boiled Artemisia/ litre of sugar surup).

Group (3): (Spraying treatment): The colonies were sprayed with bee venom solution (5 mg/100 ml distilled water).

Group (4): (Positive control of spraying): The colonies were were sprayed with septazole solution (2ml/ Liter of sugar syrup).

Group (5): (Negative control): Honeybee colonies fed on sugar syrup without any treatment.

Then, all colonies were treated once a week for six weeks to get rid a Nosema. One hundred bees were removed randomly from each colony and dissected to assess their degree of infection, the abdomens were introduced into sterile eppendorf microtubes filled with 200 µl of distilled water, and after crush of them, the spores were counted using a haemocytometer.

4. Efficacy of bee venom against *Varroa destructor* :

This application was performed from November to February 2019 in nine colonies infested with varroa mites, whereas before start of the treating, the infestation percentage was determined by immersion of 100 honeybee workers/ colony in soap solution, fallen varroa numbers observed and caculated on sheet paper per adult workers, the same matter was also performed for the brood cells. Then, The colonies were divided into three groups, each group contains on three replicates that subjugated along 8 weeks (56 days) to different treatment as the following;

Group (1): Spraying with bee venom solution (5 mg/100 ml water)/ replicate.

Group (2): Treated with Formic acid solution 65% as a positive control by

vaporization using cardboard slices satisfied with this formic.

Group (3): Used as a negative control (Untreated colonies).

However, for along eight weeks that estimated the means of vival varroa mites on adults' workers and brood cells of all colonies before and after treating, and then the reduction percentages of infesting with Varroa mites were calculated by using of Henderson and Tilton equation (1955) which is:

$$\% \text{ Reduction} = (1 - T_a \times C_b / T_b \times C_a) \times 100$$

T_a = after Treatment T_b = before Treatment

C_a = after control C_b = before control

5. Biological activities of honeybee colonies:

Some population biomarkers were measured as indicators of the effect of the infection and treatments on the honeybees in comparison with the none-treated colonies. The biological activities of the honeybee workers; brood rearing and worker population were recorded at 21 days' intervals (Marzouk, 2009).

5.1. Activity of colonies in rearing worker brood:

The areas that occupied by unsealed and sealed worker brood were measured by using a frame divided into square inches. The measurements were taken at 21 day intervals included a complete generation of bee's worker.

5.2. Worker population:

This Parameter was determined one hour before sun set; combs of each colony were weighed with and without the adhesive workers, (workers covering them). On the other hand, sample of workers from each colony was taken, weighed and the average weight of a bee worker was estimated and recorded according to formula of (Abd Al-Hady, 2007 and Marzouk, 2009).

Average weight of a worker =
Weight of worker's sample

No.

of workers in this sample

5.3. The number of workers (in thousand) / colony =

Total weight of workers (in gm.)

Average weight of one worker (in gm.)

6. Statistical analysis

The results were described with means and standard deviation, data of all treatments were analyzed in a randomized complete block design (ANOVA) by MSTAT-C version 1.41 (Sendecor and Cochran, 1980). In addition, using graph pad prisma version 3.03 for windows, software. All means were compared by Duncan's

multiple range test at level 0.05 (Duncan, 1955).

Results and discussion

1. Effect of bee venom against *Penibacillus larvae* bacterium:

Data in Table (1) showed the means of reduction% of infection with AFB disease inside honeybee colonies which treated with bee venom and Tylosin, whereas they were 66.7±19.1, 54.8±15.8, and 7.8±3.2 opposite feeding with bee venom solution, positive control and negative control, respectively. These results indicated that feeding with bee venom solution gave the highest mean of reduction of infection with American foul brood disease followed by the positive control treatment, then negative control.

Table (1): The mean of reduction (%) of infection with American foul brood disease inside honeybee colonies treated with bee venom during year, 2019.

Treat.	Rep	1 st week		2 nd week		3 rd week		4 th week		Mean/week		% Red
		Before	After	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	
Bee venom (Feeding)	R1	100	45	45	22	22	9	9	0	44	19.0	66.7 ±19.1 ^A
	R2	100	42	42	19	19	5	5	1	42	16.8	
	R3	100	39	39	16	16	3	3	0	40	14.5	
Mean		100	42.0	42.0	19.0	19.0	5.7	5.7	0.3	41.7	16.8	
% Red		53.2		52.3		68.2		93.2		66.7		
Positive control (Veterinary antibiotic Tylosin)	R1	100	50	50	38	38	13	13	3	50	26.0	54.8 ±15.8 ^B
	R2	100	43	43	20	20	10	10	4	43	19.3	
	R3	100	38	38	21	21	9	9	0	42	17.0	
Mean		100	43.7	43.7	26.3	26.3	10.7	10.7	2.3	45.2	20.8	
% Reduction		51.3		36.4		56.8		74.7		55		
Negative control (Sugar syrup)	R1	100	86	86	81	81	78	78	70	86	78.8	7.8 ^C ±3.2
	R2	100	90	90	79	79	81	81	72	88	80.5	
	R3	100	93	93	95	95	80	80	65	92	83.3	
Mean		100	89.7	89.7	85.0	85.0	79.7	79.7	69.0	88.6	80.8	
% Red		10.33		4.7		5.3		10.7		7.8		

The statistical analysis of data indicated that there were significant differences between feeding with bee venom solution compared with a negative control (Fed on sugar syrup only), also the positive control (Tylosin), the present investigations are

supported by similar results were obtained by Metwally (2016) and El-Etreby (2018), they mentioned that bee venom had inhibitory affect on viability and growth of *P. larvae* under field conditions, and the bee venom had a direct effect *in vivo* against the

vegetative cells of *P. larvae* bacterium and that very low concentrations of bee venom required to inhibit this bacterial growth, and this result also based on the bee venom component (milliten, 26 amino acids, phospholipase A2 and minerals) these compounds are responsible for the main parts of the biological activity of bee venom and these substances were that the reason to having of the bee venom on the antibacterial activity, On the other hand it's important to note that the concentration of experimental substances were significantly different, especially in regard to the active components.

2. Effect of bee venom against stone brood disease (*Aspargillus flavus*):

Data in Table (2) showed the mean percentage of reduction of infection with stone brood disease inside honeybee colonies which treated with bee venom and Ultragrizeofulvine as a positive control, it happened little of more reduction of the disease in the treated hives with bee venom spraying than feeding, whereas the mean

reduction% of infection were 35.2 ± 14.84 and 33.7 ± 8.81 for spraying and feeding respectively, but not significant difference presented between both of them on bee, while the treating of the colonies with Ultra grizofulvine had the highest and significant effect against the fungus which resulted in 85.53 ± 6.546 as a mean reduction% of infection, and all those compared by the negative control hives which recovered from disease by mean of reduction% equaled 7.01 ± 1.993 .

The statistical analysis of data indicated that there were significant differences between the treatment with bee venom whether feeding or spraying in a side and the positive control (Ultra grisevulvin) in other side, and these results were agreed by Zolfagharian *et al.* (2016) and Sang *et al.* (2016). They mentioned that the increasing the antimicrobial activity of bee venom could not be due to the antimicrobial effect of *A. flavus* fungus, because the *A. flavus* fungus has an inhibitory effect at high concentrations.

Table (2): The mean of reduction (%) of infection with stone brood disease inside honeybee colonies treated with bee venom during year, 2019.

Treatment	Rep.	Number of mummies		Reduction %
		Before	After	
Bee venom (Feeding)	R1	45	30	29.7
	R2	38	25	27.6
	R3	42	22	43.8
Mean ± Sd		41.67 ± 3.512	25.67 ± 4.041	33.7 ± 8.81 ^B
Bee venom (Spraying)	R1	42	19	52.3
	R2	48	35	27.6
	R3	39	27	25.7
Mean ± Sd		43.0 ± 4.583	27.0 ± 8.0	35.2 ± 14.84 ^B
Positive control (Ultragriseovulvin)	R1	48	9	80.24
	R2	40	6	83.5
	R3	30	2	92.85
Mean ± Sd		39.33 ± 9.018	5.67 ± 3.512	85.53 ± 6.546 ^A
Negative control	R1	39	37	5.13
	R2	44	40	9.1
	R3	59	55	6.8
Mean ± Sd		47.33 ± 10.408	44.0 ± 9.644	7.01 ± 1.993 ^C

3. Effect of bee venom against *Nosema apis* :

Data in Table (3) showed that the percentages of adult honeybee workers infected with *N. apis* were 41.0, 50.0, 50.8, 46.0 and 3.7 % in the colonies which treated with bee venom feeding, and spraying, and with Artemisia as a natural positive control, septazole as antiseptic positive control and negative control respectively. These results indicated that spraying with bee venom solution gave the highest mean of reduction of infection with *N. apis*

disease followed by feeding with bee venom solution. Statistical analysis from the data indicated that there were significant differences between feeding, spraying for bee venom solution compared with negative control (Fed on sugar syrup), while there were insignificant differences between the mean of reduction of infection with *N. apis* by effect of the spraying with bee venom solution and the natural positive control (Artemisia), these results are agreed with (Yemor, 2016).

Table (3): Effect of bee venom solution on the mean number of honeybee workers infected with *Nosema apis* during period from 1/11/2019 to 15/12/2019

Treatment		Feeding				Spray				Negative control	
		Bee venom		Positive control natural material (Artemisia)		Bee venom		Positive control antiseptic (Septazole)		Sugar syrup	
		Mean ±SD	% Red	Mean ±SD	% Red	Mean± SD	% Red	Mean± SD	% Red	Mean± SD	% Red
1 st week	Before	100.0±0.0		100.0±0.0		100.0±0.0		100.0±0.0		100.0±0.0	
	After	55.0±5.0	43.4	68.3±12.58	29.8	53.0±7.0	45.5	62.3±6.51	35.9	97.3±2.52	2.7
2 nd week	Before	55.0±5.0		68.3±12.58		53.0±7.0		62.3±6.51		97.3±2.52	
	After	37.0±10.44	30.3	40.7±10.02	51.1	38.3±5.51	25.1	46.7±5.77	22.4	94.0±4.58	3.4
3 rd week	Before	37.0±10.44		40.7±10.02		38.3±5.51		46.7±5.77		94.0±4.58	
	After	23.7±7.37	39.6	23.3±5.77	46.0	19.7±2.08	51.5	30.8±3.82	37.8	99.7±0.58	0.0
4 th week	Before	23.7±7.37		23.3±5.77		19.7±2.08		30.8±3.82		99.7±0.58	
	After	9.3±1.53	57.9	9.0±2.0	58.6	9.7±0.58	47.2	10.3±2.52	64.1	93.0±2.65	6.7
5 th week	Before	9.3±1.53		9.0±2.0		9.7±0.58		10.3±2.52		93.0±2.65	
	After	4.0±1.0	55.0	4.0±1.73	53.5	2.7±1.53	70.9	4.7±1.53	52.3	89.0±2.65	4.3
6 th week	Before	4.0±1.0		4.0±1.73		2.7±1.53		4.7±1.53		89.0±2.65	
	After	0.3±0.58	20.8	1.3±1.53	65.7	1.0±1.0	60.8	1.7±1.53	61.8	84.3±5.13	5.3
Mean/week	Before	38.2±3.46		40.9±3.0		37.2±2.43		42.5±0.79		95.5±2.08	
	After	21.6±3.59	41.0	24.4±2.61	50.8	20.7±2.41	50.2	26.1±0.66	46.0	92.9±2.87	3.7
% Reduction		41.0 b		50.8 a		50.0 a		46.0 b		3.7 c	

4. Efficacy of bee venom against *Varroa destructor* :

Data in Table (4) showed that the mean number of fallen varroa mite on paper sheet during the experiment from the brood and adult bees that treated spraying with bee venom solution (5 mg venom /100 ml water) against the formic acid as a positive

control and the negative control (Sugar syrup only), respectively. Whereas, these results indicated that treating with bee venom solution gave highest values of fallen varroa mite followed by formic acid treatment then the negative control respectively whether in sealed brood or adult. Statistical analysis from the data indicated that there were insignificant

differences between bee venom solution on fallen varroa, formic acid as positive control compared with control colonies in brood and adult. At the end of the treatment, more brood was presented in treated colonies with bee venom (81.8±2.13) and not significant differences between the mean brood on colonies treated with formic acid (79.1±1.44), whereas the extension of the sealed brood area of the treated hives of formic acid was significantly difference from that of the control colonies (57.4±4.88). In adult workers was presented in treated colonies with bee venom (83.6±1.31) and not significant differences between the mean of colonies treated with formic acid (81.9.1±1.95), whereas the extension of the adult workers by formic acid was significantly differences from that of the control colonies (57.5±2.57). The mean of percentage reduction of varroa mites on adult worker and brood cells during 8th week were recorded 100% inner colonies treated with bee venom compared with control colonies.

In addition, more adult bee infestation was recorded in treated hives. The percentage of reductions of

the daily fallen mites increase in treated groups (Bee venom and positive control (Formic acid) than the control group), respectively, these results are agreed with (Rashid *et al.*, 2011).

The results showed that the bee venom is a promising candidate for controlling *Varroa* mites. it has many advantages easy to use, safe for beekeepers, it also causes no honeybee toxicity, no loss of queen or brood, adult bee mortality, Furthermore, it can also be concluded from this study that, bee venom proved as effective against mites control, therefore they can be used safely without any side effects in controlling *Varroa* mites, it proved the effectiveness of bee venom as a natural compound in reducing the varroa parasite population in honey bee colonies, and this is consistent with Lodesani *et al.* (2008) and Mabrouk *et al.* (2019), they mentioned that the use of natural compounds against *V. jacobsoni* in honey bee colonies occurred mortality reached 95% such as coumaphos (Preizin), fluvalinate (Apistan), flumethrin (Bayvarol), powder of thymol and formic acid.

Table (4): Weekly mean no. of the fallen varroa mites/col. after treating the honeybee colonies with bee venom solution during period from 1/11/2019 to 1/1/2020.

Treatment		Bee venom (Spraying)	Positive control (Formic acid)	Negative control
1 st week	Brood	43.7±8.74	39.7±2.08	19.0±2.0
	Adult	48.3±3.06	43.0±6.24	19.0±4.58
2 nd week	Brood	60.7±1.53	55.7±4.93	31.7±2.52
	Adult	61.7±4.73	55.3±6.51	35.0±6.56
3 rd week	Brood	72.3±3.06	69.0±2.65	46.0±5.29
	Adult	78.0±3.0	74.0±6.24	44.7±6.66
4 th week	Brood	86.0±4.0	81.3±3.06	55.0±6.56
	Adult	88.3±2.08	89.7±1.53	54.7±4.16
5 th week	Brood	93.0±1.0	93.0±2.0	63.0±8.0
	Adult	94.7±0.58	95.3±2.08	67.7±2.52
6 th week	Brood	99.0±1.0	96.0±1.0	77.0±6.08
	Adult	98.0±1.0	98.3±1.53	72.0±2.65
7 th week	Brood	99.7±0.58	98.0±1.0	82.3±7.51
	Adult	99.7±0.58	99.7±0.58	79.7±1.53
8 th week	Brood	100.0±0.0	99.7±0.58	85.0±5.0
	Adult	100.0±0.0	100.0±0.0	87.7±3.21
Mean/week	Brood	81.8±20.13 a	79.1± 1.44 a	57.4±4.88 b
	Adult	83.6± 1.31 A	81.9± 1.95 A	57.5±2.57 B

Table (5): Effect of bee venom on the mean of survival number and percentage of reduction of Varroa mites/100 adult worker and 100 brood cells during period from 1/11/2019 to 1/1/2020.

Treatment		Bee venom	% Red.	+ve control (Formic acid)	% Red.	-ve control	% Red.	
1 st Week	Brood	Before	100.0	30.4	100.0	25.5	100.0	19.0
		After	56.3		60.3		81.0	
	Adult	Before	100.0	36.1	100.0	29.6	100.0	19.0
		After	51.7		57.0		81.0	
2 nd Week	Brood	Before	52.0	14.7	58.3	14.3	77.0	11.3
		After	39.3		44.3		68.3	
	Adult	Before	51.7	7.6	57.0	2.2	81.0	19.8
		After	38.3		44.7		65.0	
3 rd Week	Brood	Before	39.3	10.8	44.3	11.4	68.3	20.9
		After	27.7		31.0		54.0	
	Adult	Before	38.3	32.4	44.7	41.0	65.0	14.9
		After	22.0		26.0		55.3	
4 th Week	Brood	Before	27.7	39.3	31.0	27.6	54.0	16.7
		After	14.0		18.7		45.0	
	Adult	Before	22.0	35.0	26.0	51.6	55.3	18.0
		After	11.7		10.3		45.3	
5 th Week	Brood	Before	14.0	39.1	18.7	54.4	45.0	17.8
		After	7.0		7.0		37.0	
	Adult	Before	11.7	36.4	10.3	36.0	45.3	28.7
		After	5.3		4.7		32.3	
6 th Week	Brood	Before	7.0	77.0	7.0	8.0	37.0	37.8
		After	1.0		4.0		23.0	
	Adult	Before	5.3	56.4	4.7	58.2	32.3	13.3
		After	2.0		1.7		28.0	
7 th Week	Brood	Before	1.0	61.0	4.0	35.0	23.0	23.0
		After	0.3		2.0		17.7	
	Adult	Before	2.0	79.3	1.7	75.6	28.0	27.5
		After	0.3		0.3		20.3	
8 th Week	Brood	Before	0.3	100.0	2.0	82.3	17.7	15.3
		After	0.0		0.3		15.0	
	Adult	Before	0.3	100.0	0.3	100.0	20.3	39.4
		After	0.0		0.0		12.3	
Mean /week	Brood	Before	30.2	25.3	33.2	21.6	52.8	19.3
		After	18.2		21.0		42.6	
	Adult	Before	28.9	28.6	30.6	25.6	53.4	20.4
		After	16.4		18.1		42.5	

5. Biological activities of honeybee colonies:

The results obtained in Table (6) showed that the worker brood rearing activity after the treating with bee venom solution and other components inside honeybee colonies was continued on years-around during 2019-2020 years of study. This activity had a major peak of rearing in next spring and summer and reached the highest in May (881.4 inch² /col.). After that, the worker brood rearing curve was

gradually declined until recorded the least brood quantity at the end of November (6.1 inch²/colony)

This activity had a major peak of rearing in the summer season, (Mean of June, July and August) was recorded (653.7 inch²/colony) while spring season (544.2 inch²/colony). After that, the worker brood rearing curve was gradually declined until recorded the lowest brood quantity at Winter season (97.4 inch²/colony).

The numbers of adult workers population (in thousands) after treating with bee venom solution of honeybee colonies treated from some pathogens during different periods and seasons of the year study. The increase in colony population followed the brood trend. The general adult population mean of workers recorded for the treated colonies were (25700 worker/colony), It is also appeared that the highest population for colonies which recovered from *V. destructor* was recorded (28800 worker/colony) followed by colonies treated against *P. larvae*, *A. flavus*, *Nosema apis*, and control colonies were record (28400, 24900, 23200 and 23100

worker/colony) respectively, the colonies were significantly differed. The highest mean number of worker population was recorded during May, (46400 worker/colony) followed by July, (43200 worker/colony), but the lowest mean number of worker population was recorded in November, (8100 worker/colony). The recorded data showed the positive effect of using bee venom for treating certain pathogens in increasing the amount of worker brood areas and increasing of adult worker population, these results agreed with (El-Ettreby, 2018 and Wahba *et al.*, 2020).

Table (6): Mean of worker brood areas (inch²) and mean no. of worker population (Inthousands) produced at 3 week intervals by honeybee colonies treated with bee venom solution during period from 1/9/2019- 25/8/2020.

Date	<i>P. larvae</i>		<i>A. flavus</i>		<i>Nosema apis</i>		<i>V. destructor</i>		Control		Mean	
	Brood	Population	Br.	Pop.	Br.	Pop.	Br.	Pop.	Br.	Pop.	Br.	Pop.
01\09\2019	200.8	13.4	199.5	13.3	193.7	13.9	183.5	13.4	8.1	13.1	191.1 F	13.4 g
21\09\2019	213.8	13.3	173.5	12.8	273.0	9.5	270.5	7.9	2.6	8.0	239.2 E	10.3 h
12\10\2019	210.1	7.9	113.8	7.9	196.1	9.3	131.5	7.9	2.6	8.3	155.5 F	8.3 k
02\11\2019	61.1	7.9	11.1	8.4	1.1	10.9	24.5	9.7	4.4	9.8	23.4 I	9.3 j
23\11\2019	9.8	7.1	16.1	7.1	4.5	9.1	0.0	9.1	0.0	8.3	6.1 J	8.1 k
14\12\2019	195.9	9.1	138.1	8.1	188.4	10.8	161.1	9.8	4.5	9.4	167.9 F	9.4 j
03\01\2020	116.8	9.1	46.8	7.1	44.8	13.5	23.5	12.0	6.7	11.6	50.0 H	10.7 i
24\01\2020	129.8	10.5	136.8	9.6	51.5	11.1	88.5	10.3	5.0	9.8	97.9 G	10.3 i
14\02\2020	123.3	12.0	91.8	10.6	48.2	24.3	56.0	25.1	19.8	23.0	73.9 G	19.01 f
07\03\2020	277.8	25.1	216.1	23.5	109.5	37.3	121.8	49.5	44.2	35.0	168.3 F	34.1 d
28\03\2020	481.1	47.2	294.5	33.5	167.8	38.1	167.5	51.8	46.5	38.2	254.6 E	41.8 b
18\04\2020	934.1	51.8	726.1	41.1	342.8	33.2	548.5	42.1	36.9	32.1	618.9 C	40.1 b
09\05\2020	1402.8	51.8	1004.5	41.1	699.5	35.6	652.8	54.1	48.8	40.2	881.4 A	44.5 a
30\05\2020	1053.1	52.7	870.1	54.1	822.8	35.5	624.5	51.3	46.0	38.3	797.9 B	46.4 a
21\06\2020	847.8	55.5	614.5	44.1	878.5	29.4	669.5	42.9	37.6	33.8	734.9 B	41.1 b
13\07\2020	732.8	51.3	728.5	44.1	887.8	33.5	662.1	49.4	44.2	37.4	733.6 B	43.2 b
04\08\2020	474.5	52.7	523.1	45.5	536.8	22.2	532.1	27.9	22.6	22.3	518.7 D	34.1 d
25\08\2020	810.1	33.1	581.1	37.0	716.8	40.0	518.1	43.8	38.5	37.1	627.7 C	38.2 c
Mean	459.8 a	28.4 A	360.3 b	24.9 B	342.42 c	23.2 B	301.9 d	28.8 A	297.0 d	23.1 B	352.3	25.7

From the previous results, it could be concluded that the diseases and pests of honey bee colonies are very dangerous that led to destroying bee colonies in a short time. On the other hand bee venom collected from honeybee colonies had the highest

activities and inhibiting substances against the diseases. Since bee venom it could be a potential alternative natural antibiotic without any harmful for bees and having no chemical toxic residues in honey bee products and its improves the defense and immune system of the

worker body by increasing the defense cells such as plasmatocytes, granulocyte, and coagulocyte, which leads to increase the life of the worker bees (El-Ettreby, 2018 and Wahba *et al.*, 2020).

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Histopathological, biological and biochemical effects of lufenuron on *Schistocerca gregaria* (Orthoptera: Acrididae)

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Abstract:

Locusts are considered a dangerous insect attacking almost the important economic crops. One of these injurious insects is the desert locust *Schistocerca gregaria* Forskål (Orthoptera: Acrididae), which has a great economic importance in Egypt. Newly moulted second, third, fourth and fifth instar nymphs of the desert locust, *S. gregaria* was sprayed with the chitin synthesis inhibitors cymax, lufenuron in a recommended dose 40ml/100L water to assignment the percentages of mortality, malformation and prolongation in life period also to evaluate histological changes in testis compared with the normal histological structure of control testis and determine total protein. Mortality percentages were 26.67, 23.33, 16.67, 10 and 10% for second, third, fourth, fifth nymphal instars and adult insects respectively, but were 40, 46.67, 36.67 and 36.67% through moulting. Also, malformation percentages were 30, 23.33, 20 and 23.33% in second third fourth fifth nymphal instars respectively. The life period of the treated nymphs reached at 7.33, 8.33, 8.67 and 10.33 days to second, third, fourth and fifth nymphal instar, respectively, but normally the duration of life to untreated nymphs were 5.67, 6.33, 7 and 7.67 days, respectively. The treatment induced variable histological changes in the testis. Effects on the testis were manifested by cytoplasmic vacuolation. Also, the treatment caused many ultrastructural changes in male germ cells including scattered vacuoles, degeneration, ad-electron mitochondria and many vacant areas. The levels of haemolymph protein decreased after 5,10 and 15 days when the males were treated for one day old and reached 61.25, 40.53 and 26.59 mg/100 ml, respectively as compared with 79.86, 75.42 and 82.03 mg/100ml of untreated males, respectively. Those changes may lead to infertile males.

Introduction

Throughout the world are spreading locusts and grasshoppers widely. Locusts occur great damage in Egypt to many economic crops as, clover, maize, sugarcane, cotton,

leguminous and cereals, one of these insects is the desert locust, *Schistocerca gregaria* Forskål (Orthoptera: Acrididae) (Soliman, 2019). The desert locust *S. gregaria* is invading many countries in Africa and Asia (Hamadah

et al., 2013). Locust and grasshoppers have ability to eat their own weight (2-3g) of invaded plants every day (Alomenu, 1998). Chemical insecticides are the common method to locusts control with using Ultra Low Volume application method. Protection plants from locusts infestation needs using fast acting pesticides, like Organophosphorous and Pyrethroids. The widespread use of traditional insecticides has caused serious environmental impacts. To avoid these risks, proceed has been made through last decades to develop new pesticides. This trend has led to find Insect Growth Regulators (IGRs) (Abdel-Kerim and Shebl, 2002). IGRs are different groups of chemical compounds which are highly effective against immature stage of insects, also they have a well border of safety to generality non-target organisms such as invertebrate also, to domestic animals and human, they will play an essential role in control programs in the future (Mulla, 1995). The major types of IGRs which used commercially are Juvenile hormone analogues and chitin synthesis inhibitors (Parrella and Murphy, 1998). IGRs can be divided according to the mode of action as: chitin synthesis inhibitors and substances that intervene with insect hormone action (i.e. JH analogues, and ecdysteroids) (Tunaz, and Uygun, 2004). The lufenuron (Match) is chitin synthesis inhibitor that overlaps with chitin synthesis (Oberlander and Silhacek, 1998). As little attention has been given to the effect of IGR, such as lufenuron on desert locust. The present study is undertaken to appear the effect of this IGR on the second, third, fourth and fifth nymphal instars mortality and malformed percentages and to determine the total proteins and examine the histological effects in the male testis.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental Insect:

Experimental Insect was desert locust *S. gregaria* which took from the culture of department of locust and grasshopper, agricultural research center. The insects were reared according to Hassanein (1965). Fresh clover leaves, *Trifolium alexandrinum* were presented during the period of study.

2. Insect growth regulator:

Cymax 5% EC (Lufenuron) It was obtained from Shoura Chemicals Company, Km 28, Cairo- Alexandria desert road.

3. Treatment of the desert locust with chitin synthesis inhibitor:

Newly moulted adult and 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th instar nymphs and fresh clover, *Trifolium alexandrinum* was sprayed with chitin synthesis inhibitor (CSI), Lufenuron which was prepared as recommended concentration 40ml/100L. water. and leaved even feed on treated clover leaves for 24hrs. The control insects were fed on untreated clover leaves and kept under the same conditions. Each treatment was divided to three replicates (10 nymphs/rep.). Surviving nymphs were kept at 32 ± 2 °C to follow up its moulting to the next instar.

4. Histological preparations:

Electron microscope: Immature adult males treated with Lufenuron and leaved even became mature males were dissected in insect saline solution. For transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and examined with JEOL JEM-1400 Electron microscope Kv 120.

5. Determination of the total proteins

Samples collection and preparation: Adult were taken for experiments where, the biochemical effects of Lufenuron on haemolymph components were evaluated. The experiments were carried out by treatment of 1-day old under laboratory conditions (Robert *et al.*, 2002). Samples of the haemolymph were taken

at different intervals of 5, 10, and 15 days after treatment. Total proteins were determined by the method of Bradford (1976).

Results and discussion

1. Mortality and malformed percentages of *Schistocerca gregaria* after treated with lufenuron:

Table (1) and Figure (1) showed the effectiveness of chitin synthesis inhibitor (CSI), lufenuron on the 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th nymphal instar and adult of *S. gregaria* during one-day old by spraying technique. Data cleared that the percentages of nymphal mortality were 26.67, 23.33, 16.67 and 10% after treatment with recommended concentration of Lufenuron, respectively, comparing with control (0.0%). When the 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th nymphal instar of *S. gregaria* were treated, some nymphs were unable to moult into next stage and died without completing the moulting process where mortality percentages through moulting were 40, 46.67, 36.67 and 36.67%, respectively. Different deformities were observed, some were able to split the old cuticle but unable to complete

the moulting process but the old cuticle connected with the resulting adults in different positions as legs or wings malformation percentages were 30, 23.33, 20 and 23.33% and some were able to complete the moulting process without any deformity in the resulting adults. Most of adult emerged were unable to fly and sluggish in walking, jumping and climbing. All adults, which resulted of treatment, showed the following morphological changes, hypertrophied and twisted wings, absence of the most wing patches, also they have curled wings. It was noticed that, the duration of the treated nymphs was prolonged as result of usage lufenuron. This duration reached to 7.33, 8.33, 8.67 and 10.33 days to second, third, fourth and fifth nymphal instar, respectively, but normally the duration of untreated nymphs was 5.67, 6.33, 7 and 7.67 days to second, third, fourth and fifth nymphal instar, respectively.

Table (1): Mortality percentages and mlaformes of Lufenuron on nymphal instars and adult of the desert locust.

Effect Treat.	Mortality percentage	mortality percentage through moulting	Duration of untreated instars/day	Duration of treated instars/day	Malformed percentage	emergence percentage	Total percentage
2 nd instar	26.67	40	5.67±0.38	7.33±1.45	30	3.33	100
3 rd instar	23.33	46.67	6.33±0.26	8.33±0.88	23.33	6.67	100
4 th instar	16.67	36.67	7	8.67±0.33	20	26.66	100
5 th instar	10	36.67	7.67±0.26	10.33±0.67	23.33	30	100
Adult	10	0	0	0	0	90	100

Means +/- Standard Error

Figure (1): Malforms of Lufenuron on nymphal instars of the desert locust *Schistocerca gregaria*
A. Curled wings – E. Twisted wings – B and C. Old cuticle connected with the result adults in different positions D., F. and G. Nymphs were unable to moult into adult stage and died without completing the moulting process.

Lufenuron may be considered selective and safe compound to target insects only. This study is a step in understanding histological, biological and biochemical effects of the Chitin synthesis inhibitor, Lufenuron on the desert locust *S. gregaria*. Usage chitin synthesis inhibitor CSI, lufenuron (Cymax 5% EC) on the desert locust in a recommended dose was used through the spray on the newly moulted adult and nymphal instars second, third, fourth and fifth. The lethal action of Lufenuron was detected for either the nymphal instars or adult stage. The present results agree with Taha and El-Gammal (1985) found that diflubenzuron (DFB) caused some mortalities to *S. gregaria* during the ecdysis to the last instar. Also, Tiwari (2000) appeared that chlorfluazuron affected the survival potential. When treatment of the second nymphal instar with diflubenzuron caused various mortality percentages after 14 days (Azam and Al-Seegh, 1993). The CSI, IKI-7899 caused high mortality during the fourth and fifth instars (Abdel-Magid, 1993). After treatment insects with 100 µg/insect Imidazole

compound caused 80% mortality (Kumari *et al.*, 2001). The present study showed different degrees of the mortal potential of (Cymax) depending on nymphal instar and adult. Probably, mortalities percentages ascribed to inhibition of chitin synthesis or to indirect effects on hormones levels (Hajjar and Casida, 1978). Also, the insect death by Lufenuron may be causing as a result to some attribution in the newly formed cuticle (Fytizus and Mourikis, 1979). Or that insects were unable to moult into next stage. These suggestions can be showed for the killing power of Lufenuron as recorded in the present study on *S. gregaria*.

2. Histological studies on testis of the desert locust *Schistocerca gregaria* :

Histological examination of sections of testes of *S. gregaria* treated with lufenuron showed some alterations in primary spermatogonium. Many spermatocyte nuclei show pyknosis where the chromatin contracts into a dense, deeply stained irregular mass and Spermatids are reduced in number showing either degeneration or malformation, also spermatocytes showed degeneration (Figures 2 and 3).

Figure (3): Photomicrograph of a longitudinal section of the testis of treated *Schistocerca gregaria* showing definitive primary spermatogonium. Nucleus (n) with irregular outline; nucleolus (nu) Apical cell cytoplasm

Figure (2): Photomicrograph of a longitudinal section of the testis of control *Schistocerca gregaria* showing definitive primary spermatogonium. Nucleus (n) with irregular outline; nucleolus (nu): apical cell cytoplasm

The male reproductive system of *S. gregaria* in this study showed like that in chrotogonus trachypterus trachypterus (Wagan, 1977), *P. pictus* (Wagan and Pitafi, 1990) and the histology of *S. gregaria* testis agrees with conformable structures of the acridids *Locusta migratoria* L. (Chapman, 1985) and *Poeciloceris pictus* (Fabr.) (Orthoptera: Acrididae) (Saxena and Aditya, 1969). The present study on the desert locust *S. gregaria* treated with lufenuron demonstrated histopathological changes of treated males. Those changes because of the impact of lufenuron appear as degeneration of spermatogenic stages and cytoplasmic vacuolation. These results agree with Saxena and Aditya (1969) who showed on *P. pictus* after treatment with apholat and with Shayin and Usharani (1996) who used cypermethrin and sodium selenite on *P. pictus*. Also, with *L. migratoria* treated with hempa (Güven, 1989); on *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) treated with pyriproxyfen (Hussein *et al.*, 1993); These vacuolation reflects the primary morphological response to cell injury in several ways. This is due to the detrimental or toxic impacts of treatment on the cell membrane; this induces significant disruptions both structurally and functionally within its

permeability system. This can contribute to an increased impregnation of water into the cells if it accumulates enough in the cell, these intracellular waters create transparent cytoplasmic vacuoles suggesting the presence of generally referred to as hydropic degeneration pathological symptoms (Sakr *et al.*, 2000).

Application of pyriproxyfen to *S. gregaria* caused cytoplasmic vacuolation in the testis which was known to be the primary stage of cell deterioration. Among other studies Cellular vacuolation was identified as associated with fatty degeneration that occurs under the influence of a deferent of chemical and physical factors (Saleh, 1996). These findings are close to those reported in apholate-treated grasshopper *P. pictus* (Saxena and Aditya, 1969), cypermethrin and sodium selenite (Shayin and Usharani, 1996); hempa-treated *L. migratoria* (Güven, 1989) and in *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) treated with extracts of some botany (Assar *et al.*, 2001).

Many authors documented the reduction and damaging effect of these chemosterilant on the number and structure spermatids. Hussein *et al.* (1993) revealed in this respect decrease in the number of spermatids produced

in the testis of pyriproxyfen-treated *E. insulana*. They have also noted that the testicular follicles inhabit only early stages of spermatogenesis. Also noted reduction and degradation of different stages of spermatogonic clumping in *Eyprepocnemis plorans* (Charpentier) (Orthoptera: Acrididae) which have been treated with lead nitrate. Similarly, Assar *et al.* (2001) noted depletion of various spermatogenesis stages in *T. castaneum* treated with some extracts of the botany.

This study showed that lufenuron was responsible for significant histopathological changes. When the male of *S. gregaria* treated with lufenuron has identified cellular degeneration and vacuolation. It can be concluded that lufenuron is successful at the histological level which leads to the prevention of normal sperm formation of ending with distorted sperm that cannot fertilize the ovum. Hence, Lufenuron may cause the male fertility reduction of *S. gregaria*. There are conflicting views regarding lufenuron's role in testis production and the spermatogenesis process in insects. Spermatogenesis occurs in many species of insect in the larval or pupal stage when the hormone from the prothoracic glands may induce the process (Engelmann, 1970) possibly under a low titre of lufenuron. Foster (1967) has stressed that spermatogenesis doesn't seem to be under the influence of the corpus allatum, Metwally (1979) studies on *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera:Noctuidae), Yagi and

Kuramochi (1976) on *S. littoralis* and Leviatan and Friedlander (1979) on *Ectomyelois ceratoniae* Zeller (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) have showed, however, that corpus allatum hormone or its analogs can alter or inhibit the spermatogenesis process or can produce defective sperms. Thus, two mechanisms tend to clarify lufenuron's mode of action on *S. gregaria* testis. The first of these is a clear influence on testis. The lack of spermatide and sperm indicates a separation mechanism has been compromised. This seems to point to an impact overloading caused by Lufenuron. Lufenuron's this morphogenetic action. The second mechanism that may account for the pathological condition is that the corpora allata interferes with natural hormone production. Since differentiation regulation is believed to be in the corpora allata (Wigglesworth, 1973), it could be argued that one of the modes of action may be the corpora allata's reduction in the production of hormones.

3. Effect of lufenuron on the total protein of the desert locust *Schistocerca gregaria*:

Data in Table (2) and showed that, the levels of haemolymph protein decreased after 5,10 and 15 days. After 5,10 and 15 days the haemolymph protein levels in male reached 61.2533, 40.5267 and 26.59mg/100ml respectively as compared with 79.86, 75.42333and 82.02667 mg/100ml of untreated males (F = 327.9 and LSD = 5.45).

Table (2): Effect of lufenuron on the total protein of the desert locust *Schistocerca gregaria*:

Days after application	Lufenuron			mg Protein \100ml haemolymph (Mean±S.E)	Control			mg Protein \100ml haemolymph (Mean±S.E)
	Rep.1	Rep.2	Rep.3	mean	Rep.1	Rep.2	Rep.3	Mean
5 th days	60.56	63.35	59.85	61.2533+/-1.068a	80.54	77.91	81.13	79.86+/-0.99b
10 th days	40.4	41.8	39.38	40.5267+/-0.7a	77.3	75.64	73.33	75.42333+/-1.15b
15 th days	29.9	22.27	27.6	26.59+/-2.26a	83.16	82.2	80.72	82.02667+/-0.71b

^b significant; ^a non-significant

Means, within row, bearing different subscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05\%$)

In this study lufenuron appeared reduction in protein level in treated insects of *S. gregaria* as a compare with untreated insect. Those changes in total protein may be due to the toxic action of CSI, this tested compound changes the expression process of protein. Specific biological processes occur as a result of protein (Bakr *et al.*, 2010). The total protein concentration of treated insects decreased during the study period after 5,10 and 15days after treatment than in untreated insects. The decline in protein content gradually increased until reached minimum value after 15th day of application.

Some of this protein contents use in the synthesis structural proteins and enzymes and may be storage compounds. Part of them is used as an energy source or in the developing larva is used in the synthesis of nonprotein components. haemolymph protein is considered importance for the understanding many different physiological processes that are very important for the reproduction in insects, such as, maturation, egg production, development and ecdysis therefore, quantitative assay of protein is important. Changes in proteins are great during stages of development and tissues differentiation such as, during metamorphosis (Alrubeai and Gorell, 1982) and sexual maturity of the reproductive organs (Engelmann, 1970). Normally, in the case of normal

male, total protein declined due to the tissues differentiation of reproductive organs and spermatogenesis process in testes. In addition to, the result indicated that Lufenuron after 15th days of treatment caused decrease of total protein in adults of *S. gregaria* less than the control insects. Those results were likewise demonstrated by Lusi (1963) who detailed that, the neurosecretion from the standards intercerebralis of the brain influenced proteins synthesis in the fat body. In this manner, lacking incitement of neurosecretory activity would prompt protein insufficiency and decreased the measure of the protein, which required for oocytes development, and consumed from the haemolymph. Comparative results were accounted in ladybird beetles, Slogget and Lorenz (2008) observed that protein content decays pitifully over development. The results concur with Steel and Hall (1985), they reported that protein levels of the treated nymphs were not exactly in the control individuals, when treated the 5th nymphal instar of *S. gregaria* by benzoyl-phenyl urea (S-71624). likewise, the protein levels were decreased in the haemolymph of the treated females and males of the fifth nymphal instar of *S. gregaria* was found by Badawy and El-Gammal (2000), who treated the fifth male and female nymphal instar by (S-71624). The decrease of the concentrations of

protein, ecdysteroids and juvenile hormone in the haemolymph of the fourth and fifth nymphal instars of *L. migratoria* were also noted by Baehr *et al.* (1979) when examined the impact of ecdysteroids and juvenile hormone, on protein levels in the haemolymph of the fifth nymphal instar.

It can be concluded that those changes which occurred as result to use Lufenuron may lead to infertile males. Lufenuron also caused similar damaging effects to those caused by many chemical insecticides and chemosterilants which have many hazardous effects on livestock and household including mammals. This suggests that the applying this IGR on a wide scale safely, especially among illiterate farmers.

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New trend for controlling *Thrips tabaci* (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) infesting Onion plants in Egypt

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Abstract:

Onion thrips *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) It is a serious pest of onions. During two successive seasons evaluated the effect of certain insecticides against adults of onion thrips *T. tabaci* were carried out by Al-Alamia Company Farm, Nubaria region, Beheria Governorate, Egypt. The results cleared that the effect of eight insecticides bio-Catch[®], admire[®], actellic[®], 'lannate[®], tracer[®], emacit[®], nimbecidine[®] and admiral[®] towards *T. tabaci* at their recommended rates under field conditions. Admire[®] was the most efficient among the tested insecticides gave 98.08%, followed by nimbecidine[®] 94.88% and tracer[®] gave 94.34% against thrips adults after seven days of application, at first season. The insecticides recorded significant reduction values of infestation. For the residual effect, the insecticides gave significant reductions in thrips numbers at the 7th day except for bio-Catch[®] and admiral[®], where they gave the lowest values 85.89% and 86.55% of reduction percentage, respectively , at the same too.

Introduction

In Egypt onion is considered one of the most important crops grown. The harvested area during season 2011 recorded about 63,723 (Ha.) according to (FAO, 2011) whereas, the national production was about 2,304,210 tons (FAO, 2011) according to the Ministry of Agriculture Statistics, Egypt. Péntes *et al.* (1996), Theunissen and Schelling (1998) and Richter *et al.* (1999) reported that *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) is polyphagous pest which has been recorded from 29 plant families, but is particularly damaging to Brassicaceae, Liliaceae and Solanaceae. Comegeys and Schmitt (1965) found that onion

thrips feed by scraping the plant surface and sucking out the cell contents. Whereas, a lot of researchers , Cabrera *et al.* (1997), Schumeterer (1990), Shelton *et al.*(1987) recorded that onion thrips is one of the most important insect pests of onion in the Hispaniola Island and the Caribbean. Cabrera and Velez (2000) reported yield losses of 50% due to thrips infestations. Kendall and Capinera (1987) and Vierbergen and Ester (2000) found that heavy infestation leads to decrease of quality as well as quantitative losses in the yield. Feeding damage in bulbs lowers bulb quality and value for export and has been an

important issue for New Zealand onion exporters since 1997 (Wood, 2001).

So that, cleared the effect of certain pesticides against the onion thrips as new approaches for controlling onion thrips *T. tabaci*.

Materials and methods

The field trials were conducted by cultivating the Onion (*Allium cepa*, L.) during the two successive seasons, 2012 and 2013 at the Al-Alamia Company Farm, Nubaria region, Beheria Governorate, Egypt. The experimental area was divided into plots, each of which was 100 m². The plants were grown along distance of 8 cm apart and in rows of 120 cm width. The experimental areas were treated according to the normal agricultural practices and recommendation guidance. Seedlings were sown on 1st January in both 2011 and 2012, seasons.

To evaluate the performance of the tested spray able pesticides on the incidence of thrips population, plants were sprayed with the evaluated compounds to show what extent they might be included in an IPM program of Onion. Treatments included the eight compounds (Table 1) plus an untreated check control. Treatments were applied with knapsack sprayer (20 L) at the rate of 200 Liters / Feddan, to give a complete coverage of whole plants. The compounds were used according to their recommended field rate. Two rows were used as a barrier between each treatment and others. Treatments were arranged in a complete randomized block design with three replicates for each.

Samples were inspected out before and after treatment at periods of

0, 2, 5, and 7 days post treatment to determine the numbers of thrips on 10 plants from each plot. The degree of infestation was estimated by counting the number of living insect (Immature and Adult stages).

The percentages of infestation reduction were calculated according to Henderson and Tilton's equation (1955) as follows:

$$\text{Reduction \%} = \left(1 - \left(\frac{A}{b} \times \frac{c}{d}\right)\right) \times 100$$

Where:

a = Population in treatment after spraying

b = Population in treatment before spraying

c = Population in check untreated (control) before spraying

d = Population in check untreated after spraying

Reduction percentages were calculated after 2, 5 and 7 days after treatment for adult and the immature stages.

Data were subjected to the analysis of variance test (ANOVA) via Randomized Complete Block Design (F. test). The least significant differences (LSD) at the 5% probability level were calculated according to computer program Costat and Duncan's Multiple Range testes modified by Steel and Torrie (1981) to compare the average numbers of inspected pest infestations.

Table (1): List of pesticides and their rates of application during two onion growing seasons of 2012 and 2013.

Compounds			Recommended Rate/ 1 L water
Trade name	Formulation type	Common name	
Bio-Catch®	in liquid (1x10 ⁹ CFU's/ml)	<i>Verticillium lecanii</i>	5 Cm ³
Admire®	24 % FL	imidacloprid	0.5 Cm ³
Actellic®	50%EC	pirimiphos-methyl	5 Cm ³
'Lannate®	90% WP	Methomyl	1.5g
Tracer®	24% SC	Spinosad	0.25 Cm ³
Emacit®	5% SG	Emamectin benzoate	0.20g
Nimbecidine®	0.03% EC	Azadirachtin	5 Cm ³
Admiral®	10 % EC	Pyriproxyfen	0.25Cm ³

Results and discussion

1. Effect of certain insecticides against *Thrips tabaci* during first season 2012:

The results showed in (Table 2 and Figure 1) reported the influence of insecticides application on thrips populations during the first season 2012. The results recorded the significant effect of the application of pesticides, where after two days from application the highest reduction percentage was achieved by 'lannate® (Methomyl) followed by actellic® (Pirimiphos-methyl) and admiral® (Pyriproxyfen) showing the values of 94.72% , 92.24 % and 91.51% ,respectively. At the same time, the lowest reduction of percentage of

number of adult thrips achieved by bio-catch® (*Verticillium lecanii*) (70.00%). After five days from application, obtain results cleared that the most effective reduction of onion thrips was achieved in the first season by admire® (Imidacloprid) (97.58%), while less census has been achieved by emacit® (Emamectine benzoate) (85.45%). The greatest reduction percentage of the number of adult onions thrips was obtained by admire® (Imidacloprid) (98.08%) after seven days of application, while, the lowest reduction percentage was recorded by bio-catch® (*Verticillium lecanii*) (85.89%). Generally, the evaluated treatments approved to be effective against onion thrips.

Table (2): Effect of insecticides on the mean numbers of adult onion thrips *Thrips tabaci* during season 2012.

Treatment	Pre-spray	No. of adult insects			% Reduction		
		2 days	5 days	7 days	% 2 days	% 5 days	% 7 Days
Bio-Catch®	9.6	7.2	2.4	5.8	70 ^{f*}	92.5 ^b	85.89 ^d
Admire®	14.6	5.6	1.2	1.2	84.65 ^d	97.58 ^a	98.08 ^a
Actellic®	13.4	2.6	4	5.6	92.24 ^{ab}	91.04 ^{bc}	90.24 ^c
'Lannate®	18.2	2.4	5.2	9.4	94.72 ^a	91.42 ^{bc}	87.94 ^{cd}
Tracer®	19	6	4.6	4.6	87.36 ^c	92.73 ^b	94.34 ^b
Emacit®	13.2	8.6	6.4	5.6	73.93 ^e	85.45 ^d	90.09 ^c
Nimbecidine®	21	8.8	6	4.6	83.23 ^d	91.42 ^{bc}	94.88 ^b
Admiral®	13.2	2.8	4.5	7.6	91.51 ^b	89.77 ^c	86.55 ^d
Control	12	30	40	51.4	-	-	-

*Means followed with same letter (s) are not significantly different.

2. Effect of certain insecticides against *Thrips tabaci* during first season 2013:

The obtained results showed in (Table 3 and Figure 2) cleared significant differences between the treatments after interval days. The highest reduction percentage of thrips recorded by admiral® (Pyriproxyfen) followed by 'lannate® (Methomyl) and actellic® (Pirimiphos-methyl) after two days of application. Whereas, the lowest reduction percentage of adult thrips was recorded after the application of bio-catch® (*Verticillium lecanii*) (60.00). After seven days from application the greatest reduction percentage of adult thrips occurred by admire® (Imidacloprid) (95.80%), but the lowest value was achieved by admiral® (Pyriproxyfen) (84.96%).

Our experiments confirmed by the findings of previous investigators, Gandhale *et al.* (1984), Kisha (1979) and Hussain *et al.* (1997), who used synthetic insecticides for the management of onion thrips in different parts of the world and got a considerable knockdown effect. Kisha (1979) found that onion thrips can be controlled by methomyl (0.53 a.i. kg ha-1), malathion (1.0 kg ha-1) and phenthoate (1.08kg ha-1), if applied at 14 days interval. It showed that the residue lasted for 14 days, which

confirm the finding of the present studies, although different insecticides were used in different agro- ecological zones. Wheras, Gandhale *et al.* (1984), reported a good control of onion thrips and the residual effect could last for a period of one week or so. Since the examined insecticides lost their effect after 15 days, it is assumed that pre harvest interval supposed to be somewhat longer than over twenty days. However, instrumental residual analysis studies are needed for definite and safe pre-harvest period. Hussain *et al.* (1997) found that methamidophos was the most effective insecticides for the control *T. tabaci* followed by dicrotophos and endosulfan. cypermethrin and monocrotophos. Mahmoud and Osman (2007) found that spinosad, mectin, neemix and biofly gave the best control and continued to give significant reduction in thrips populations till 21 days of treatment compared to the other insecticides. Also, Sadozai *et al.*(2009) found that karate 2.5, thiodan 35 EC, confidor 20 SL, curacron 500 EC and crown 200 SL were significantly better than untreated check in reducing onion thrips on onion bulb crop population. Thiodan proved to be the best one followed by curacron and karate.

Generally, the obtained results of our study cleared that the

differences can be attributed to different modes of action of the insecticides and also to the developmental stage of onion thrips, *T. tabaci*. The best overall results were obtained with admire[®], nimbecidine[®] and tracer[®] that are provided excellent control through 7

days period at the recommended rates. The bio-rational insecticides look promising and could be alternative insecticides in the future for controlling onion thrips and be safe at the same time for natural enemies.

Table (3): Effect of insecticides on the mean numbers of adult onion thrips *Thrips tabaci* during season 2013.

Treatment	Pre-spray	No. of adult insects			% Reduction		
		2 days	5 days	7 days	% 2 days	% 5 days	% 7 Days
Bio-Catch [®]	12.2	10.3	2.1	6.9	60.00 ^e	92.79 ^b	85.45 ^c
Admire [®]	13.5	4.2	1.1	2.2	85.26 ^{bc}	96.58 ^a	95.80 ^a
Actellic [®]	15.2	2.5	3	5.2	92.20 ^a	91.73 ^b	91.20 ^b
'Lannate [®]	13.4	2	3	7.2	92.93 ^a	90.62 ^b	86.18 ^c
Tracer [®]	13.8	3.9	2.8	3.4	86.61 ^b	91.50 ^b	93.66 ^a
Emacit [®]	16.2	7.9	5.5	5.9	76.90 ^d	85.78 ^c	90.63 ^b
Nimbecidine [®]	17.9	6.4	4.1	3.9	83.06 ^c	90.41 ^b	94.39 ^a
Admiral [®]	19.5	2.9	3.9	11.4	92.95 ^a	91.62 ^b	84.96 ^c
Control	18	38	43	70	-	-	-

*Means followed with same letter (s) are not significantly different.

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Spider biodiversity in connection with the vegetation structure and
its surrounding soil

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Abstract:

Spider activity occurred in four ornamental plants was assessed for a whole year using pitfall traps for ground spiders and sweeping net for vegetation or aerial spiders. A total of 456 individuals of ground and aerial spiders were collected. They belonged to 38 species, 38 genera of 7 families. Family Lycosidae was found the dominant recorded 158 individuals (61.9%) of ground spider, while family Salticidae of the aerial spiders recorded 70 individuals (33.3%) of the total aerial collected spiders. By using shannon wiener and simpson indices, results revealed that species diversity were high under Plumbago shrubs for ground spider while the highest diversity of aerial spiders was recorded on red acalypha shrubs. Monthly fluctuation of the total number of spiders should high population between May to August for ground spiders and in August to September for aerial spiders.

Introduction

The Orman garden, which was founded in 1875, is one of the most famous and oldest botanical gardens in Egypt (Diwan *et al.*, 2004) and occupies an area of 28 feddans. Spiders are an important component of most terrestrial ecosystems. They have conquered all environments, they are found in forests, desert regions, and open environments, in bodies of water, under stones and on the ground, on bushes and in burrows or caves. The spiders live in the gardens and even the houses (Bourbia *et al.*, 2018). True spiders are one of the most abundance predatory groups in terrestrial ecosystems.

Spiders have proved to be beneficial in regulation of agricultural pests and their role as natural enemies has recently been more and more

stressed (Ghabbour *et al.*, 1999). Few studies have compared differences in the abundance of spiders on foliage of different shrubs and tree species (Souza, 2005). Ghallab (2013) studied the spiders inhabiting two ornamental plants in Orman garden. Hassan *et al.* (2016) studied spiders population inhabiting the ornamental plants at Cairo and Giza Governorates in four public parks, five plants of each park to estimate the effect of different vegetation's on the spiders populations.

El-Hennawy (2017) who listed the Egyptian spider species (405 species, belonging to 204 genera and 41 families) in a checklist which included scientific names of spider species recorded from Egypt, with their distribution localities. Riechert and Lockley (1984) observed associations

between spiders and certain plant species, in a study on the effect of prairie fires on spider distribution. They attributed these associations to structural characteristics of the plants. Habashy *et al.*, (2005) indicated that the diversity of the spider fauna in each site is often related to the structural diversity of the habitat.

Indirectly, the surface vegetation affects spider population density and biodiversity, which is influenced by microclimate of the plant. These variations in sun and shade have a marked effect on the horizontal distribution patterns of many pests affected directly on the growth rate of spiders.

The present work study the abundance, spider density and diversity in two different communities of four different evergreen shrubs represented, aerial spiders and ground spiders inhabiting under those shrubs in Orman garden.

Materials and methods

1. Study area:

This work was conducted in Orman garden, Giza, Egypt for a whole year. Four evergreen shrubs were chosen to study the effect of plant structures and compositions on spider biodiversity.

They were red acalypha (*Acalypha wilkesiana marophylla* Müll), twisted acalypha (*Acalypha wilkesiana haffnanni* Müll), single green acalypha (*Acalypha wilkesiana marginata* Müll) and plumbago (*Plumbago auriculata*). Active population density of spiders fauna was measured for one year through four seasons from January to December 2018.

2. Sampling method:

Spiders were collected from the study area by two methods:

2.1. Pitfall trap method:

Spiders were collected by pitfall traps as described by Southwood and

Henderson (2000). Three traps/plant/two weeks was regularly applied for each of the four plants chosen.

Seventy eight traps per plant were undertaken for a year of total 312 pitfall collections. The pitfall traps were remained open for 24 hours to obtain both diurnal and nocturnal species. Obtained spiders were preserved in 70 % ethyl alcohol, counted and identified to species level as much as possible and deposited in plant protection research institute collection. We removed the traps between collecting periods, but these were placed in the same locations when sampling again. The recipients were filled with water and a small quantity of detergent added to lower the surface tension. It has been shown that these traps are efficient to assess spider communities (Pearce *et al.*, 2005).

2.2. Sweeping net:

A net with a deep mesh bag is used to collected spiders inhabiting foliage by sweeping over foliage or by shaking the vegetation. Everyone is kept in a vial so that they do not prey on each other; samples were taken every two weeks.

3. Identification of spiders:

All the adults and juveniles were determined to species level or morpho species. Specimens were identified to the family and genus levels according to (Ubick *et al.*, (2005) and, when possible, to the species level with the taxonomic works of various authors.

Scientific names were checked in the World spider catalogue (2016). Spiders were identified according to Kaston (1978), Roberts (1987), Levi (2002), Oger (2002), Ovtsharenko and Tanasevitch (2002), Prószyński (2003), Huber (2005), El-Hennawy (2017), and Platnick (2012). Juvenile spiders were identified to family or genus level, if possible.

4. Data analysis:

4.1. Frequency and abundance values:

The frequency values of the most abundant species were classified into three classes according to the system adopted by Weis Fogh (1948), "Constant species" more than 50% of the samples, "accessory species" 25-50 % of the samples and "Accidental species" less than 25%.

On the other hand, the classification of dominance values were done according to Weigmann (1973) system in which the species were divided into five groups based on the values of dominance in the sample; eudominant species (> 30% individuals), dominant species (> 10-30% individuals), subdominant (5-10% individuals) recedent species (1-5% individuals) and subrecedent species (1% individuals).

4.2. Species diversity:

The biodiversity of spiders collected were estimated by using equilibrium. Diversity of collected spiders was determined for samples pooled over one whole year of four different patterns of vegetation's. It was measured in each tested vegetation by diversity index that reflected the number of species (Richness) in the samples. Three common indices were computed, shannon-wiener index "H", simpson index "S" and species evenness. They were calculated as described by Ludwig and Reynolds (1988).

$$H' = -\sum (ni / n) \ln (ni/n) \text{ and } S = \sum (ni/n)^2$$

Where ni is the number of individuals belonging to the i^{th} of "S" taxa in the sample and "n" is the total number of individuals in the sample. "H" is more sensitive to changes in number of species and diversity, while "S" is more responsive to changes in the most dominant species (Ludwig and Reynolds 1988).

Species evenness = $i / \ln((s-1) / \ln(n))$

Where, i = Shannon Diversity Index
 s = Number of Species Recorded
 n = Total Number of Individuals in the Sample

Results and discussion

1. Species richness of the collected spiders in ground and leaves inhabiting different plants evergreen shrubs:

1.1. Ground spiders:

Table (1), showed that a total of 45 spiders were collected from red acalypha shrubs. They represented 9 families, 17 genera and 17 species. Juvenile comprised 44.44%; while adults average 55.55%. The sex ratio was 5.25♂:1♀. Of the most abundance species was *Hogna ferox* (13 individuals) followed by *Trochosa urbana* (6 individuals) and *prinerigone vagans* (5 individuals). A total of 50 spiders were collected from twisted acalypha shrubs.

They represented 10 families, 14 genera and 14 species. Juvenile comprised 32%; while adults average 68%. The sex ratio was 2.09♂:1♀. Of the most abundance species was *Hogna ferox*(18 individuals)followed by *Plexippus paykulli* (5 individuals) and *Hasarius adansoni* (6 individuals).We found more spiders at single acalypha of a total of 122 spiders. They represented 7 families, 11 genera and 11 species. Juvenile comprised 80.33%; while adults average 19.67%.

The sex ratio was 1.67♂:1♀. Of the most abundance species was *Trochosa urbana* (65 individuals) followed by *Hogna ferox* (35 individuals).The lowest number of spiders was collected from *Plumbago* shrubs of a total of 38 spiders. They represented 8 families, 9 genera and 9 species. Juvenile comprised 36.84%; while adults average 63.16%. The sex ratio was 2.4♂:1♀. Of the most abundance species was *Hogna ferox* (14 individuals) followed by *H. adansoni* (8 individuals).

1.2. Leave spiders:

Table (2), showed that a total of 43 spiders were collected from red acalypha shrubs. They represented 5 families, 14 genera and 14 species. Juvenile comprised 72.09%; while adults average 27.91%. The sex ratio was 1♂:1♀. Of the most abundance species was *Philodromes* sp. (11 individuals) followed by *Cheiracanthium* sp. (6 individuals). A total of 40 spiders were collected from twisted acalypha shrubs. They represented 7 families, 9 genera and 12 species. Juvenile comprised 65%; while adults average 35%. The sex ratio was 1♂:1♀. Of the most abundance species was *Cheiracanthium* sp. (10 individuals) followed by *Plexippus* sp. (8 individuals).

But at single green acalypha the total number of spiders decreased to 32 spiders inhabiting, they represented 4 families, 8 genera and 10 species. Juvenile comprised 78.13%; while adults average 21.88%. The sex ratio was 1.33♂:1♀. The most abundant species was *Cheiracanthium* sp. and *Plexippus* sp. (7 individuals) the same number.

The highest numbers of spiders were collected from plumbago shrubs.

A total of 95 spiders were collected from Plumbago, they represented 7 families, 15 genera and 19 species. Juvenile comprised 48.42%; while adults average 51.58%. The sex ratio was 1.58♂:1♀. The most abundant species was *Philodromus* sp. (20); *Thomisus spinifer* (19 individuals) and *Pullchellodromes glaucinus* (15 individuals).

2. Rank abundance of spider families:

Table (3) was presented by families and showed their abundance. The greatest number of collected ground spiders presented by family Lycosidae 158 (61.96 %) and Salticidae 37 (14.51%) while, those collected

from vegetation were family Saiticidae 70 (33.33 %) and Philodromidae 56 (26.67%) followed by Linyphidae 17 (6.67%) of ground spider.

Vegetation spiders were more diverse than ground spiders and their families were more active. Activity density of families Cheiracanthiidae, Theridiidae and Thomisidae were 29, 25 and 24 individuals of 13.81, 11.90 and 11.43%. Members of Dictynidae were the least presence in both ground and vegetation spiders.

3. Relative abundance-Frequency relationship of spider communities inhabiting ground and leaves:

3.1. Ground spiders:

Table (4) showed that the frequency and abundance values among Weis Fogh of the most abundant spiders in evergreen shrubs (red acalypha, twisted acalypha, single green acalypha and plumbago) during 2018. According Weis Fogh system, members of Family Lycosidae were considered accessory (ac) in red acalypha, twisted acalypha, Plumbago and also members of Salticidae under Plumbago; they recorded 44.44, 48, 36.84 and 31.58% respectively. While members of Lycosidae recorded 81.97 in single green acalypha considered as Constant (C) while all the remaining families were considered accidental.

Members of family Salticidae: *P. paykulli* and *H. adansoni* "dominant" according to Weigmann classification of dominance. Also, family Theridiidae, Thomisidae and Dictynidae were disappeared from Plumbago shrubs. But family Dysderidae, Eutichuridae, Thomisidae and Dictynidae were disappeared from single green acalypha. Also, family Thomisidae and Dictynidae were disappeared from red acalypha. But only one family Philodromidae was disappeared from twisted acalypha. Members of family Lycosidae: *Hogna ferox* ranged between "dominant" and "Eudominant"

according to Weigmann classification of dominance.

According to Weigmann classification, members of Lycosidae were "Eudominant" under the four shrubs investigated, the same family Linyphiidae was "Eudominant" under red acalypha and family Salticidae under Plumbago plant. Members of Gnaphosidae and Salticidae were considered "dominant" under twisted acalypha and plumbago. All the remaining families were "accidental" while their members ranged between "sub-dominant" and "Recedent"

Our results agree with the results which were obtained by (Abd El-Karim *et al.*, 2016) who found that family Lycosidae: *Hogna* sp., *Pardosa* sp. and *Wadicosa fidelis* were dominant and eudominant. Also, Shuang-Lin and Bo-Ping (2006) who indicated that Lycosidae was the dominant family and occupied more than 60% of individuals community.

3.2. Leaves spider:

Table (5) showed that the frequency and abundance values of the most leaves spiders in evergreen shrubs, According "Weis Fogh system" members of family Salticidae were "Constant" 59.38% on leaves of single green acalypha. Members of Philodromidae and Salticidae were "accessory" while the remaining families were "accidental". Members of families Salticidae: *Thyene imperialis*, *Thyene* sp. and *Bianor* sp. ranged between "Dominant" and "subdominant".

According to weigmann dominance classification, the most dominant species recorded in members of family Salticidae under sigle green acalypha and twisted acalypha considered as "Eudominant" (E). Members of Cheiracanthiidae were "Dominant" (D) under the three species of acalypha and also members of Theridiidae under red and twisted

acalypha, in addition members of Thomisidae on leaves of Plumbago.

The remaining families ranged between "sub-dominant" and "Recedent" . This study indicated the influence of vegetation structure on the diversity of resident spider communities. Plumbago shrubs seemed to have a higher amount of diversity than the three types of acalypha, because it had the greatest number of species.

4. Monthly fluctuation of spider population "Catch Size":

Table (6) showed that the total number of spiders collected from ground 255 individuals more than spiders collected from leaves 210 individuals. The most counts of spiders collected from ground were recorded during August 92 individuals decreased to 58 individuals in May. While during August and September the highest numbers of spiders were collected from leaves were 29 individuals for both. No spiders were found by two methods (Pitfall traps and sweeping net) during November and January from ground or leaves.

These results confirmed by Mushtaq *et al.* (2000) , Ghallab (2013) and Abd El-Karim *et al.* (2016) who indicated that total monthly count of spiders collected in early summer during May and the lowest numbers were recorded during February.

Spider diversity: Table (7) compared the biodiversity of collected spiders in different vegetation spider associated with foliage and ground spider by using Shannon-Wiener "H" and Simpson "S" indices of diversity. These results revealed that the highest "H" value recorded on spiders of foliag in red acalypha 2.40 followed by 2.16 in twisted acalypha so red acalypha had a high diversity. The lowest "H" value recorded 1.34 in single green acalypha. Ground spiders revealed that the highest "H" value recorded in

Plumbago 2.4, the lowest value 2.09 in single green acalypha.

Consequently, these values demonstrated that spiders collected from pitfall trap "ground spiders" more than spider associated from foliage and diverse also. According to Simpson "S" index, which reflect the measure of dominance, it was found the highest value recorded in ground spider 0.37 under single green acalypha shrubs and the lowest under red acalypha 0.13. also leaves spider show that the highest value recorded in single green acalypha shrubs 0.15 and the lowest under red acalypha 0.12.

These results revealed that the highest species evenness value recorded on spiders of ground in Plumbago 2.30 and the lowest value in red acalypha 1.67. While leaves spiders revealed that the highest number of Species Evenness

recorded in single green acalypha 2.19 and the lowest value in twisted acalypha 1.28.

This result related to the highest content of dropping soil and insects as feeding. Habashy *et al.* (2005) indicated that soil texture may have an important influence on the distribution patterns of spiders that deposit their cocoons in the soil.

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Table (3): Rank abundance of spider families occurred in ground and leaves under different evergreen shrubs

Families	Number of collected ground spiders				Total	%	Number of collected leaves spiders				Total	%
	Red acalypha	Twisted acalypha	Single green acalypha	Plumbago			Red acalypha	Twisted acalypha	Single green acalypha	Plumbago		
Araneidae							0	1	0	2	3	1.43
Lycosidae	20	24	100	14	158	61.96	0	1	0	0	1	0.48
Cheiracanthiidae							8	11	8	2	29	13.81
Gnaphosidae	3	5	2	4	14	5.49						
Linyphiidae	11	2	3	1	17	6.67						
Salticidae	2	11	12	12	37	14.51	12	15	19	24	70	33.33
Theridiidae	1	1	1	0	3	1.18	7	9	0	9	25	11.90
Philodromidae	2	0	1	3	6	2.35	13	2	4	37	56	26.67
Oecobiidae	2	2	3	2	9	3.53						
Dysderidae	1	2	0	1	4	1.57						
Eutichuridae	3	1	0	1	5	1.96						
Filistatidae												
Thomisidae	0	1	0	0	1	0.39						
Uloboridae							0	1	0	0	1	0.48
Thomisidae							3	0	1	20	24	11.43
Pholicidae											0	0.00
Dictynidae	0	1	0	0	1	0.39	0	0	0	1	1	0.48
Total	45	50	122	38	255		43	40	32	95	210	
	255						210					

Table (4) The dominance-frequency relationship of ground spider communities inhabiting evergreen shrubs.

Families and taxa names	Red Acalypha			Twisted acalypha			Single green acalypha			Plumbago					
	No.	Sp.%	Dom.	F.%	Freq.	No.	Sp.%	Dom.	F.%	Freq.	No.	Sp.%	Dom.	F.%	Freq.
Lycosidae															
<i>Wadecosa fidelis</i>	1	2.22	R	44.44	ac	1	2.00	R	48.00	ac	35	28.69	D	81.97	C
<i>Pardosa</i> sp.	13	28.89	D			18	36.00	E			65	53.28	E		
<i>Hogna ferox</i>	6	13.33	D			5	10.00	Sd						36.84	Ac
<i>Trochosa urbana</i>															
Gnaphosidae															
<i>Micaria dives</i>	1	2.22	R	6.67	A	3	6.00	Sd	10.00	A	1	0.82	Sr	1.64	A
<i>Zelotes</i> sp.	1	2.22	R			2	4.00	R			1	0.82	Sr		
<i>Drassodes</i>	1	2.22	R												
Linyphiidae															
<i>Erigone dentipalpis</i>	3	6.67	sd	24.44	A				4.00	A	2	1.64	R	2.46	A
<i>Prinerigone vagans</i>	5	11.11	D								1	0.82	Sr		
<i>Sengletus extricates</i>	3	6.67	sd			2	4.00	R							
Salticidae															
<i>Plexippus paykulli</i>	1	2.22	R	4.44	A	5	10.00	Sd	22.00	A	5	4.10	R	9.84	A
<i>Hasarius adansoni</i>	1	2.22	R			6	12.00	D			7	5.74	Sd		
Thridiidae															
<i>Steatoda erigoniformis</i>	1	2.22	R	2.22	A	1	2.00	R	2.00	A				0.82	A
<i>Kochiura aulica</i>															
<i>Theridion</i> sp.															
Philodromidae															
<i>Philodromus cespitum</i>	1	2.22	R	4.44	A						1	0.82	Sr	0.82	A
<i>Thanatus albini</i>	1	2.22	R												
Oecobiidae															
<i>Oecobius nava</i>	2	4.44	R	4.44	A	2	4.00	R	4.00	A	3	2.46	R	6.25	A
Dysderidae															
<i>Dysdera crocata</i>	1	2.22	R	2.22	A	2	4.00	R	4.00	A					
Eutichuridae															
<i>Cheiracanthium</i> sp.	3	6.67	sd	6.67	A	1	2.00	R	2.00	A					
Thomisidae															
<i>Thomisus spinifer</i>						1	2.00	R	2.00	A					
Dictynidae						1	2.00	R	2.00	A					
Total	45					50					122				
Frequency (abundance), by Weis Fog	Dominance, by Weigmann			Dominance, by Weigmann			Dominance, by Weigmann			Dominance, by Weigmann			Dominance, by Weigmann		
> 50 % = Constant (C)	> 30 % = Eudominant (E)			> 30 % = Eudominant (E)			> 30 % = Eudominant (E)			> 30 % = Eudominant (E)			> 30 % = Eudominant (E)		
25 - 50 % = Accessory (ac)	10 - 30 % = Dominant (D)			10 - 30 % = Dominant (D)			10 - 30 % = Dominant (D)			10 - 30 % = Dominant (D)			10 - 30 % = Dominant (D)		
> 25 % = Accidental (A)	5 - 10 % = Subdominant (sd)			5 - 10 % = Subdominant (sd)			5 - 10 % = Subdominant (sd)			5 - 10 % = Subdominant (sd)			5 - 10 % = Subdominant (sd)		
	1 - 5 % = Reccedent (R)			1 - 5 % = Reccedent (R)			1 - 5 % = Reccedent (R)			1 - 5 % = Reccedent (R)			1 - 5 % = Reccedent (R)		
	> 1 % = Subreccedent (Sr)			> 1 % = Subreccedent (Sr)			> 1 % = Subreccedent (Sr)			> 1 % = Subreccedent (Sr)			> 1 % = Subreccedent (Sr)		

Table (5) The dominance-frequency relationship of leaves spiders communities inhabiting evergreen shrubs.

Families and taxa names	Spider name	Red acalypha				Twisted acalypha				Single green Acalypha				Plumbago																	
		No.	Sp.%	Dom.	F.%	Freq.	No.	Sp.%	Dom.	F.%	Freq.	No.	Sp.%	Dom.	F.%	Freq.	No.	Sp.%	Dom.	F.%	Freq.										
Araneidae	<i>Araneus</i> sp.						1	2.50	R	2.50	A					1	1.05	R			1	1.05	R	2.11	A						
	<i>Spiderling</i>															1	1.05	R			1	1.05	R								
Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium</i> sp.	6	13.95	D	18.60	A	10	25.00	D	27.50	ac	7	16.28	D	25.00	ac					2	2.11	R			2	2.11	R	2.11	A	
	<i>Cheiracanthium isiacum</i>	2	4.65	R			1	2.50	R			1	2.33	R							1	1.05	R			1	1.05	R	1.05	A	
Dictynidae	<i>Dictyna</i> sp.																														
Lycosidae	<i>Trochosa</i> sp.						1	2.50	R	2.50	A																				
	<i>Pulchellodromus glaucinus</i>	1	2.33	R																											
Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus</i> sp.	11	25.58	D	30.23	ac	2	5.00	R	5.00	A	2	4.65	R	12.50	A					20	21.05	D			20	21.05	D	38.95	Ac	
	<i>Thanatus</i> sp.	1	2.33	R								2	4.65	R							2	2.11	R			2	2.11	R			
Salticidae	<i>Thyene imperialis</i>	3	6.98	sd			3	7.50	Sd												4	4.21	R			4	4.21	R			
	<i>Thyene</i> sp.	3	6.98	sd								5	11.63	D							4	4.21	R			4	4.21	R			
Therididae	<i>Heliophanus</i> sp.											2	4.65	R							4	4.21	R			4	4.21	R			
	<i>Hasarius adansoni</i>	2	4.65	R	27.91	ac	8	20.00	D	37.50	ac	7	16.28	D	59.38	C					1	1.05	R			1	1.05	R	25.26	As	
Thomisidae	<i>Plexippus</i> sp.	3	6.98	sd			4	10.00	Sd			3	6.98	sd							7	7.37	sd			7	7.37	sd			
	<i>Plexippus paykulli</i>	3	6.98	sd								2	4.65	R							4	4.21	R			4	4.21	R			
Uloboridae	<i>Bianor</i> sp.	1	2.33	R			4	10.00	R			2	4.65	R							1	1.05	R			1	1.05	R			
	<i>Spiderling</i>	2	4.65	R			4	10.00	R			4	10.00	R							1	1.05	R			5	5.26	sd			
Thomisidae	<i>Theridion melanosictum</i>	2	4.65	R			4	10.00	R			4	10.00	R							1	1.05	R			1	1.05	R			
	<i>Theridion</i> sp.	3	6.98	sd	16.28	A	1	2.50	R	22.50	A										5	5.26	sd			1	1.05	R	9.47	A	
Thomisidae	<i>Kochitara atilica</i>	2	4.65	R			4	10.00	Sd												1	1.05	R			1	1.05	R			
	<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i>																				2	2.11	R			2	2.11	R			
Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus</i> sp.																														
	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i>	3	6.98	sd	6.98	A						1	2.33	R	3.13	A					1	1.05	R			19	20.00	D	21.05	A	
Uloboridae	<i>Uloborus</i> sp.						1	2.50	R	2.50	A																				
	Total	43					40					32									95										

Frequency (abundance), by Weis Fog
 > 50 % = Constant (C)
 25 - 50 % = Accessory (ac)
 > 25 % = Accidental (A)
 Dominance, by Weigmann
 > 30 % = Eudominant (E)
 10 - 30 % = Dominant (D)
 5 - 10 % = Subdominant (sd)
 1 - 5 % = Recedent (R)
 > 1 % = Subrecedent (Sr)

Table (6): Monthly fluctuation of spider population "Catch size" in evergreen shrubs

Month	Pitfall traps (ground spiders)				Total	Leaves (sweeping net)				Total
	Red acalypha	Twisted acalypha	Single green acalypha	Plumbago		Red acalypha	Twisted acalypha	Single green acalypha	Plumbago	
Jan-18	2	5	0	2	9	0	0	0	0	0
Feb-18	3	2	0	2	7	0	0	0	10	10
Mar-18	3	6	3	2	14	2	0	6	4	12
Apr-18	4	0	2	6	12	3	1	7	1	12
May-18	11	8	36	3	58	2	3	1	5	11
Jun-18	2	10	2	4	18	6	4	2	8	20
Jul-18	3	2	1	4	10	5	7	5	6	23
Aug-18	8	9	68	7	92	6	13	3	7	29
Sep-18	3	1	1	4	9	10	6	4	9	29
Oct-18	1	2	3	2	8	2	3	2	12	19
Nov-18	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	1	18	22
Dec-18	5	5	6	2	18	5	2	1	15	23
Total	45	50	122	38	255	43	40	32	95	210

Table (7): Estimation of shannon-wiener (H), simpson indices (S) and species evenness of spider diversity.

	Ground spider				Leaves spider			
	Red acalypha	Twisted acalypha	Single green acalypha	Plumbago	Red acalypha	Twisted acalypha	Single green acalypha	Plumbago
Shannon-Wiener Index (H)	2.40	2.16	1.34	1.81	2.39	2.16	2.09	2.4
Simpson Index (S)	0.13	0.18	0.37	0.21	0.12	0.14	0.15	0.13
Species Evenness	1.67	1.80	1.83	2.30	1.92	1.28	2.19	1.75

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Toxicity of apricot seeds extracts as a rodenticide for climb rats *Rattus rattus*
(Rodentia: Muridae)

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Abstract:

This study investigated the efficacy of the apricot seeds extracts in *Rattus rattus* L. (Rodentia: Muridae). The used of 28 rats has been selected to study acute and chronic toxicity to start a trial in the non-choice test. three animals for each of acetone, ethanol, hot water, cold water extract , and powder seeds. Five animals were used for hexane extract twice LD₅₀ apricot seeds crushed maize bait and seven animals were used for LD₅₀ apricot seeds hexane extract crushed maize bait. The concentration used for LD₅₀ and twice LD₅₀ were calculated 2.14 and 4.28%, respectively. The experiment in a non-choice laboratory test, results indicated for an experiment that LD₅₀ of hexane apricot seeds extract highest toxicity treatment after 48 hrs was recorded 71.43% and acceptability 48.87%, twice LD₅₀ of apricot seeds hexane extract bait recorded mortality 60% and acceptability 41.47%. The most acceptable bait was cold water apricot extract recorded 92.76%. Histopathological changes after 28 days for twice hexane extract and seeds powder in kidney showing membranoproliferative glomerulonephritis and the renal tubules some renal tubules showing costs, liver showing widely dilated hepatic sinusoids, ballooning degeneration and disorganization of hepatocytes. Testis showing undulation and buckling of basal laminae of the seminiferous tubules, there is maturation arrest at various stages of spermatogenesis. Ovary showing without any cellular content and atrophied.

Introduction

Many plant extracts show a broad spectrum of activity against pests and such products have long been touted as attractive alternatives to synthetic chemical pesticides for pest management because they pose little threat to the environment, the Among these extracts are bitter apricot seeds (Cho *et al.*, 2013). The cyanogenic compound is present mainly as glycoside in more than 2650 plant species. Apricot kernel, peach kernel,

cassava, almond, bamboo shoot, sorghum, Japanese apricot, flaxseed among others have been consumed by humans worldwide either as food or as herbal medicine. Cyanogenic glycosides are natural plant toxicants (Bolarinwa *et al.*, 2015). Hydrogen cyanide (HCN) is a powerful and rapidly acting poison. There are various forms of cyanogenic compounds that release hydrogen cyanide upon breakdown. Amygdalin is one of the nitrilside, natural cyanide-containing

substances abundant in the seeds of plants of the prunasin family (Chang *et al.*, 2006). It is a major component of apricot kernels, bitter almonds, peach, plum, pear, and apple seeds (Conn, 1974 and Tanyildizi, 1997). It is widely distributed in plants, especially in the rosaceous plant seed, for example, apricot, peach, cherry, plum. Side effects of amygdalin ingestion in humans mirror symptoms of cyanide poisoning which includes nausea, vomiting, headache, dizziness, bluish coloration of the skin, liver damage, hypotension, nerve damage, fever, mental confusion, coma, and death (Howard-Reuben and Miller, 1984). Rodents are one of the most dangerous pests in Egypt. Among the common types of rodents (Climb and Norway rats). Rodents were also considered a serious pest on crops and stored goods and have behavioral phenomena such as high intelligence and a strong sense of smell, which makes it difficult to control.

The repeated use of chemical rodenticides, in agriculture pest control programs, led to the development of many serious problems affecting the control success. These problems are pest resistance to these rodenticides and the pollution of the environment. Therefore, there is a growing need to find new natural extractions, which have a strong effect against pests but . (2001) was adopted for the preparation of water extracts 200 gm. of apricot fruit powder soak about 400 ml water in a 1000 ml flask . The powder is mixed with water in the electric mixer; the solution is covered and left for 72 hours. The solution is then filtered and used to obtain dry raw materials. The same method was followed with the remaining seed

safe and friendly to the environment to ensure the future safety of agricultural food required for the world population without destroying the ecosystems.

The aim of this study developing a method to control the rats by using natural plant extracts environmentally safe that has no side effect on non-target (Human, animal, and plant) in the environment.

Materials and methods

1. Collection of apricot seed samples:

Apricot seeds are self-collected from apricot available on the market from different varieties. Seeds were washed with water to remove contaminating materials then left the seeds in the air to dry completely until they are suitable for grinding. Vetter (2000) recorded; apricot seeds contain approximately 20 – 80 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ and 100 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ of amygdalin, respectively. Amygdalin is also called bitter apricot, laetrile, almond; it is a cyanogenic compound and belongs to the aromatic cyanogenic glycoside group (Holzbecher *et al.*, 1984 and Santos Pimenta *et al.*, 2014). Molecular formula is: $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{27}\text{NO}_{11}$, the molecular weight is 457.42. The chemical structure is D-mandelonitrile- β -D-glucoside-6- β -glucoside.

2. Preparation of seed water extracts:

The method of Metspalu *et al* extracts but by replacing the cold water with boiling water. Then, test the raw materials to see the effect of cold water and boiled water extracts on rats *R. rattus*.

3. Solvent extracts:

The extracts were prepared by grinding apricot seeds until obtaining a fine powder, weighing 250 g of powder sock about 400 ml,

and placing it in a 1000 ml flask. The powder is soaked in a solvent (Ethanol – Hexane – Acetone) for 72 hours. The solution is then filtered and used to obtain dry raw materials. The solution extracted by a rotary evaporator is evaporated to full dryness, then weighed and dissolved in a certain amount of ethanol to prepare the stock solution.

4. Animals test:

Healthy animals elected climbing rat's *R. rattus*, from Abou-Rawash District, Giza governorate. Rats were individually caged in wire cages (50 x 30 x 20 cm), acclimatized for at least 2 weeks. Food (Dried bread) and water were provided *ad*

A known amount (25g) of crushed maize was placed in a buttery dish in pre-treatment and a known amount (Twice LD₅₀, LD₅₀) of amygdalin apricot seed extract bait mixing was provided daily to each of 3,5,7 caged rats for 4 days in the treatment test. The concentration used from the extract of apricot seeds and seed powder twice LD₅₀, LD₅₀ (0.15% / rat) were 4.28 and 2.14% respectively. Water was provided to rats *ad libitum*. Consumption has been, a number of dead rats were daily recorded. Rats of each treatment were

$$\text{Acceptability \%} = \frac{\text{Average daily consumption of treated food (g)}}{\text{Total average daily consumption of (treated + untreated) food (g)}} \times 100$$

6. Histopathological examination:

For histopathological examination, the collected specimens were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin for at least 24 hours and then routinely processed by conventional method and finally stained with heamatoxyline and Eosin (Suvarna *et al.*, 2013).

The preparations were examined by the light microscope for identifying the presence of histopathological changes for

libitum. Inactive (Unhealthy) rats were excluded. Choice of 28 rats has been selected to start the trial. Three animals for each treatment of extract acetone, ethanol, hot water, cold water, and powder seed twice LD₅₀ and used 5,7 animals of twice LD₅₀ and LD₅₀ hexane extract. Studies were conducted on rats to test the effect of apricot seeds extract toxicity/bait formulations and its histopathological effect. Studies were conducted on rats to test the effect of apricot seeds extract toxicity/bait formulations and its histopathological effect.

5. Study the effect of climb rats in non-choice feeding tests:

sacrificed by an overdose of chloroform, kidney, liver, testis and ovary and, were dissected out for gross as well as for histopathological examination. Males and females of the group were sacrificed after 28 days of treatment.

The acceptability and mortality of rats were calculated. Finally, observation to period 4week with plain bait (Crushed maize) *ad libitum*. The acceptability and mortality of rats were calculated using the following equation (Mason *et al.*, 1989).

kidney, liver testis, and ovary for different treatments of apricot seeds extract.

7. Statistical analysis:

The results were statistical analyses using the standard statistical methods LSD- test was applied in the analysis by SAS (2003).

Results and discussion

1. The effect of climb rats in non-choice feeding tests:

The mean lethal dose (LD₅₀) of amygdalin in rats was reported to be 880 mg/kg body weight (BW) by oral administration (Adewusi and Oke, 1985 and Park *et al.*, 2005).

The number of cyanogenic glycosides in plants varies with plant species and environmental effects (Conn, 1979). After oral administration, amygdalin is hydrolyzed by ruminal microorganisms and released as benzaldehyde, glucose, and cyanide. Both glycosides and released cyanide have toxic effects on animals (Majak, *et al.*, 1990 and Tanyildizi, 1997).

This glycoside is absorbed unmetabolized in the jejunum of the rat via the transport system of glucose to the blood and is then concentrated in the spleen, liver, kidney, stomach, and intestines (Strugala *et al.*, 1995 and Adewusi and Oke, 1985). Action by endogenous plant enzymes can release hydrogen cyanide causing potential toxicity issues for animals including humans (Bolarinwa *et al.*, 2015) including cell death by blocking cytochrome oxidase and the arrest of ATP production.

The acute toxicity experiments of amygdalin have proved that the toxicity of the oral administration route is far greater than the intravenous route (Oyewole and Olayinka 2009). Oral administration of amygdalin at its therapeutic dose to rats for 14 days resulted in death and toxicity due to cyanide poisoning. Co-administration of amygdalin with hydroxocobalamin prevented mortality and significantly reduced amygdalin toxicity in the blood and

liver of rats. Therefore, conclude that co-administration of amygdalin with hydroxocobalamin effectively reduced the extent of cyanide poisoning arising from oral amygdalin ingestion in rats.

The results indicated in Table (1) that the high acceptability of rats was recorded 92.76% of cold water extract bait high than hot water, power seed, ethanol, acetone, and hexane extracts bait. The results are recorded 72.25, 55.43, 48.74, 42 and 39.22% apricot seeds extract crushed maize baits, respectively. Rats mortality was observed during the treatment and after 96 hrs.of treatment in the case of hexane extract bait recorded 60% death rates did not appear in the remaining treatments.

That the average daily consumption significant change between the pre-treatment and treatment test for rats in hexane extract bait was 8.71 and 6.17g., acetone extract 9.49 and 6.87g., hot water extract 4.96 and 6.90g, and powder seed apricot bait 5.44 and 6.98g., respectively. Non-significant change between the average daily consumption in pre-treatment and treatment test for rats in ethanol extract bait 8.51 and 8.09g., cold water extract bait 6.36g and 6.86g respectively.

Table (1): Effect of average for apricot seed extracts crush maize bait 4.28% for climb rats daily consumption (g±SD), acceptability, and mortality under laboratory conditions.

Treatment twice (LD ₅₀)	R	Average daily consumption g/rat												M%	A%
		Pre-treatment				Treatment									
		1 st day	2 nd day	3 rd day	4 th day	A	1 st day	2 nd day	3 rd day	4 th day	A				
Hexane extract	5	9.25±1.21	8.74±0.81	8.59±0.87	8.28±1.10	8.71±0.19 ^A	6.16±1.10	6.21±0.78	6.05±1.41	6.27±1.29	6.17±0.28 ^B	60	41.47		
Acetone Extract	3	9.66±1.36	9.34±1.05 ^A	8.92±1.52	10.05±0.82	9.49±0.31 ^A	6.95±0.06	6.73±0.07	6.85±0.26	6.96±0.07	6.87±0.10 ^B	0	42		
Ethanol	3	9.86±0.81	9.48±0.53	7.28±2.60	7.40±2.74	8.51±1.16 ^A	6.17±2.92	7.86±4.20	7.21±5.34	11.12±7.18	8.09±1.81 ^A	0	48.74		
Hot water extract	3	5.05±0.47	4.83±0.28	5.04±0.54	4.91±0.21	4.96±0.16 ^B	6.94±0.05	6.83±0.15	6.88±0.19	6.93±0.07	6.90±0.07 ^A	0	72.25		
Cold water extract	3	6.36±1.02	6.04±1.12	6.86±1.13	6.36±1.07	6.36±0.05 ^A	6.88±0.12	6.78±0.13	6.83±0.25	6.94±0.08	6.86±0.07 ^A	0	92.76		
Powder seed	3	5.56±0.12	4.75±0.25	5.85±0.54	5.72±0.10	5.47±0.20 ^B	7.61±1.21	6.73±0.20	6.80±0.35	6.77±0.39	6.98±0.45 ^A	0	55.34		

The vertical columns marked with the same letters are not significantly different by SAS (2003).

R: Replicate A: Average M%: Mortality A %: Acceptability.

Table (2) showed that the average daily consumption and acceptability of hexane extract crush maize bait 2.14% of rats (LD₅₀), was 48.87%. Rats mortality was recorded at 71.43% during the treatment after 48h and 72hrs.of treatment. Non-significant change between the average daily consumption in pre-treatment and treatment test for rats of hexane apricot seeds extract 7.02g and 6.70g respectively with 1.8 fold in crushed maize. From the data mention above the acceptability increased when decreased treatment and increased mortality of in case hexane from LD₅₀ from twice LD₅₀ hexane extract bait. Amygdalin itself is non-toxic, but its production of HCN decomposed by some enzymes is a poisonous substance (Suchard *et al.*, 1998). Both glycosides and released cyanide have toxic effects on animals (Strugala *et al.*, 1995 and Adewusi and Oke, 1985). Action by endogenous plant enzymes can release

hydrogen cyanide causing potential toxicity issues for animals including humans after the incubation of amygdalin, the Amygdalin and laetrile (a synthetic form of amygdalin) are commonly used as complementary or alternative medicine (CAM) for the treatment of cancer. Vitamin C is known to increase the in vitro conversion of amygdalin to cyanide and reduce body stores of cysteine, which is used to detoxify cyanide. Amygdalin has been used for decades by patients with cancer who are seeking alternative therapies, and severe reactions have not been reported with this dose. An interaction with vitamin C is a plausible explanation for this life-threatening response. The use of the drug was discouraged when it was demonstrated that amygdalin is metabolized in the body to release a significant amount of cyanide thus leading to cyanide poisoning (Bromley *et al.*, 2005; Chandler *et al.*, 1984).

Table (2): Effect of average hexane apricot seed extract crush maize bait 2.14% for climb rats daily consumption (g±SD), acceptability, and mortality under laboratory conditions.

Treatment (LD ₅₀)	R	Average daily consumption g/rat										M%	A%
		Pre-treatment					Treatment						
		1 st day	2 nd day	3 rd day	4 th day	A	1 st day	2 nd day	3 rd day	4 th day	A		
Hexane extract	7	7.06± 2.20	7.05± 2.48	7.07± 2.94	6.89± 2.44	7.02±0 .31 ^A	6.14± 1.14	7.02± 2.14	6.51± 1.13	7.14± 0.97	6.70± 0.53 ^A	71.43	48.87

The vertical columns marked with the same letters are not significantly different by SAS (2003).

R: Replicate A: Average M%: Mortality A%: Acceptability.

2. Histological studies:

Histopathological changes in liver, kidney, testis, and ovary in survived rat fed apricot seeds extract crushed maize bait during 4 days in non-choice test after 28 days of treatment in the following.

2.1. The kidney of the rat was treated with apricot seeds hexane extract and

powder seeds 4.28% apricot crush maize bait:

The kidney of rat treated with apricot seeds extraction with hexane Figure (1), showing membranoproliferative glomerulonephritis and the tubules illustrating necrobiotic changes of the renal tubular epithelium where the cells revealing deeply eosinophilic

cytoplasm with pyknotic nuclei and some renal tubules showing renal costs. The kidney of rat treated with apricot seeds power Figure (2), the glomeruli showing membranoproliferative glomerulonephritis and the renal tubules showing necrobiotic changes of renal tubular epithelium, some renal tubules showing costs. Normal of kidney Figure (3) showed no alteration observed and normal histological structure of the glomeruli and renal tubules in cortex. Results of our previous apricot seeds/amygdalin studies described variety of effects a slight increase in renal parenchyma

dystrophy of rabbits fed apricot seeds (Kolesárová *et al.*, 2017) Anyway, consumption of bitter apricot seeds (60 mg/kg bw) for 42 days had a significant effect on amount of calcium excreted in human urine and significant changes were also observed in phosphorus levels in urine after apricot seed ingestion. In another study, we observed decrease in calcium in human urine after 84 days of apricot seeds consumption. The same study showed decreasing tendency in urine urea (Tušimová, Kováčik *et al.*, 2017).

Figure (1): Kidney apricot seeds extract with hexane (H and E X400).

Figure (2) : Kidney apricot seeds power (H and E X400)

Figure (3): Normal kidney (H and E X100).

2.2. Liver of the rat was treated with apricot seeds hexane extract and powder seeds apricot 4.28% apricot crush maize bait:

Liver of rat treated with apricot seeds extraction with hexane Figure (4). Showing widely dilated hepatic sinusoids and most of the hepatocytes showing ballooning degeneration and others showing granular degeneration, also the hepatocytes showing disorganization. Liver of rat treated with apricot seeds power Figure (5). The hepatocytes showing ballooning degeneration and disorganization of hepatocytes with focal area individual cellular necrosis Figure (6) The normal

histological structure of liver with no alteration observed and normal histological structure of the center veins, hepatic cords and sinusoids. Some reports indicate a toxicity problem after consumption of apricot and other fruit seeds represented by elevated liver chemistry tests (Seghers *et al.*, 2013). Contrary, Abdel-Rahman (2011) suggested amygdalin to be a possible option in hepatic fibrosis prevention. Increase in serum ALT indicates liver damage more specifically than AST. It has been reported.

Figure (4): Liver apricot seeds extract with hexane (H & E X400)

Figure (5): Liver apricot seeds powder (H & E X400)

Figure (6); Normal liver (H & E X100)

2.3. The testis of rat treated with apricot seeds powder crush maize 4.28%:

The testis of rat treated with apricot seeds powder Figure (8) showing undulation and buckling of basal laminae of the seminiferous tubules with interstitial edema decreased the number of germinal epithelium and also there is maturation arrest at various stages of spermatogenesis. The testis of control showed Figure (7) normal histological structure of the active mature seminiferous tubules and interstitial leydig cells. (Eduard *et al.*, 2015). Describe the characteristics, metabolism, and possible effects of amygdalin on reproductive processes. Previous studies describe the effects of natural compound amygdalin on female and male reproductive systems focused on the process of steroidogenesis, spermatozoa motility, and morphological abnormalities of spermatozoa. In accordance to the previous studies on amygdalin, its benefit is controversial. The resulting sperm are malformed and are

morphologically similar to abnormal sperm seen in some cases of human male infertility. The spermatozoa motility decreased very significantly ($P<0.001$) in a dose-dependent manner and all spermatozoa were immobile at 10 min. Besides, the percentages of morphological abnormalities did not change in comparison with the control group. The control values were between 4.21% and 6.87% (Tanyildizi and Bozkurt, 2004). It is not known whether the amygdalin crosses the blood-testes barrier. It has been reported that the hyaluronidase enzyme plays an important role in supporting spermatozoa penetration into the cumulus oophorus matrix (Meyers and Rosenberger, 1999). Hyaluronidase activities were inhibited significantly by amygdalin ($P<0.01$) (0.4 to 2 μM). The inhibition of spermatozoa hyaluronidase activity and spermatozoa motility showed that these compounds have deleterious effects on bull spermatozoa in vitro (Tanyildizi and Bozkurt, 2004).

Figure (7): Normal testis (H & E X400)

Figure (8): Testis treated apricot seeds powder (H & E X400)

2.4. The ovary of the rat was treated with apricot seeds hexane extract crush maize bait 4.28%:

Ovary of female rat treated with apricot seeds extraction with hexane Figure (9) showing the graafian follicle without any cellular content and atrophied high power and necrosis of ova of ovary. Figure (10) cycling active ovary female rat showing mature ovarian follicle secondary follicle with oocyst and its nucleus in the center and antrum antrum. Previous studies examined the effects of natural compound amygdalin on female reproductive system concentrated on secretion activity of porcine ovarian granulosa cells (GC) in vitro (Halenár *et al.*, 2013a). The release of steroid hormone progesterone by granulosa cells from cyclic and non-cyclic porcine

ovaries was not affected by the amygdalin addition (1, 10, 100, 1000, 10 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). But on the other hand, amygdalin (at 10 000 but not at 1, 10, 100, 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) combined with mycotoxin deoxynivalenol (DON) (1000 ng/mL) significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) stimulated the release of steroid hormones progesterone and estradiol by granulosa cells from non-cyclic porcine ovaries (Halenár *et al.*, 2013b). Richard *et al.* (2000) impaired reproductive function accompanies chronic renal insufficiency (uremia) in the experimental animal. Clinical hypogonadism occurs in both genders anti-ovulatory effects of uremia in the female rat were recorded.

Figure (9): Ovary treated apricot seeds powder (H&EX400).

Figure (10): Normal ovary (H&EX400).

This study indicates that Amygdalin itself is non-toxic, but HCN production decomposed by some enzymes is a toxic substance. The possible effects of natural compound amygdalin on reproduction were shown in previous studies. The mechanism of action of amygdalin is unknown. The toxic effect of amygdalin or its benefit is controversial, and the realization of in vivo and vitro experiments is necessary.

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True spiders inhabiting ornamental trees and perennial plants

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Abstract:

Spiders are abundant and widespread in almost all ecosystems and constitute one of the most important components of global biodiversity. The aim of this research work is to clarify the relationship between spider density, diversity and habitat structure. The effects of vegetation structure on communities of spiders by comparing the spider fauna on tree species (Severinia, dombeya and feijoa), flowering annuals (Crinum) and evergreen herbs (Pelargonium). The number of collecting spiders found in ground under each tree were 33 and 42 individuals, while those in foliage were 30 and 12, respectively. The number in flowering annuals (Crinum) and evergreen herbs (Pelargonium) was 37 and 45 in ground and 11 and 41 in foliage. The importance of activity density in determining the composition of each group is discussed relative to structural differences of the trees, flowering annuals (Crinum) and evergreen herbs (Pelargonium).

Introduction

Orman botanical garden is rich and high in tree diversity. Orman botanical garden also defined as urban forest (Bahnasy and Khamis, 2019). Spiders are abundant and widespread in almost all ecosystems and constitute one of the most important components of global biodiversity. It is not only found in agriculture field but also considered as the most diverse groups of organisms on earth (Hassan *et al.*, 2016).

Few studies have compared differences in the abundance of spiders on foliage of different shrubs and tree species (Souza, 2005). Rizk *et al.* (2012) studied the incidence of medicinal and ornamental plants in Fayoum Governorate. Ghallab (2013) studied the spider fauna associated with lantana and croton in Orman garden and

the most abundant families were Miturgidae, Philodromidae, Salticidae, Theridiidae and Araneidae. Hassan *et al.* (2016) found that Zoheria and Orman gardens were the most harbored spider. The most dominant families recorded the largest number of species were Salticidae, Gnaphosidae, Thridiidae and Oonopidae.

Habitat selection in spiders is strongly influenced by physical factors include the structural complexity of the habitat (Turnbull, 1973; Halaj *et al.*, 2000; Rinaldi and Trinca, 2008 and Villanueva-Bonilla *et al.*, 2017). Structural complexity comprises the size, shape, and spatial arrangement of structures in the habitat where the spiders occur (Uetz, 1991 and Ehmann, 1994). For example, differences in the complexity of tree trunks contribute to the structuring of spider communities

(Szinetár and Horváth, 2005). For spiders associated with tree substrates, the bark provides important niches for resting or locating food resources (Southwood, 1978 and Pinzón and Spence, 2010), as well as appropriate structures for camouflage and to attach webs (Messas *et al.*, 2014).

The present study clarifies the relationship between spider density, diversity and habitat structure. The effect of vegetation structure on communities of spiders by comparing the spider fauna on tree species (*Severinia*, *dombeya* and *feijoa*), flowering annuals (*Crinum*) and evergreen herbs (*Pelargonium*) in Orman garden were discussed.

Materials and methods

1. Study area:

This work was conducted in Orman garden, Giza, Egypt for a whole year (2018). Three trees, one flowering annual and one evergreen herbs were chosen to study the effect of plant structures and compositions on spider biodiversity. They were trees *severinia* (*Severinia monophylla* L.); *dombeya* (*Dombeya wallichii* Lind.) and *feijoa*, (*Feijoa sellowiana*), flowering annuals (*Crinum asiaticum* L.) and evergreen herbs (*Pelargonium geranium* Bailly). Population density of spiders fauna was measured for one year through four seasons from January to December 2018.

2. Sampling method:

Spiders were collected from the study area by two different collecting techniques were used to get a good representation of spiders:

2.1. Pitfall trap method:

This method was described by Southwood and Henderson (2000). Three traps per plant for two weeks were regularly applied for each of the five presented plants. Seventy eight traps per plant were undertaken for a whole year of total 390 traps. The pitfall traps were remained open for 24 hours

to obtain both diurnal and nocturnal species. We removed the traps between collecting periods, but these were placed in the same locations when sampling again. Each trap consisted of a plastic recipient (15×8 cm). The recipients were filled with water and a small quantity of soap to lower the surface tension. Obtained spiders were preserved in 70 % ethyl alcohol, counted and identified to species level as much as possible.

2.2. Sweeping net:

A net with a deep mesh bag is used to collect spiders inhabiting foliage by sweeping over foliage or by shaking the vegetation. Everyone is kept in a vial so that they do not prey on each other; samples were taken every two weeks.

2.3. Identification of spiders:

Voucher specimens were preserved in 70% ethyl alcohol and deposited in an Arachnology Collection in the Plant Protection Research Institute, Giza, Egypt. All the adults and juveniles were determined to species level or morphospecies. Specimens were identified to the family and genus levels according to Ubick *et al.*, (2005) and when possible, to the species level with the taxonomic works of various authors. Scientific names were checked in the World spider catalogue (2016). Also, spiders were identified according to Kaston (1978), Roberts (1987), Levi (2002), Oger (2002), Ovtsharenko and Tanasevitch (2002), Prószyński (2003), Huber (2005), El-Hennawy (2017), and Platnick (2012). Juvenile spiders were identified to family or genus level, if possible. Identification of female was depending on the epigynum plate, but in case of male the palp anatomy was an important factor.

3. Data analysis:

3.1. Frequency and abundance values:

The frequency values of the most abundant species were classified

into three classes according to the system adopted by Weis Fogh (1948); "Constant species" more than 50% of the samples, "accessory species" 25-50 % of the samples and "accidental species" less than 25%. On the other hand, the classification of dominance values were done according to Weigmann (1973) system in which the species were divided into five groups based on the values of dominance in the sample; eudominant species (> 30% individuals), dominant species (> 10-30% individuals), subdominant (5-10% individuals) recedent species (1-5% individuals) and_subrecedent species (1% individuals).

3.2. Species diversity:

The biodiversity of ground spiders and leaves spiders collected were estimated by using equilibrium. Diversity of collected spiders was determined for samples pooled over one whole year by different patterns of vegetation's. It was measured in each tested vegetation by diversity index that reflected the number of species (richness) in the samples. three common indices were computed, Shannon-Wiener index "H", Simpson index "S" and species Evenness. They were calculated as described by Ludwig and Reynolds (1988).

$$H' = -\sum (ni/n) \ln (ni/n) \quad \text{and} \quad S = \sum (ni/n)^2$$

Where ni is the number of individuals belonging to the i^{th} of "S" taxa in the sample and "n" is the total number of individuals in the sample. "H" is more sensitive to changes in number of species and diversity, while "S" is more responsive to changes in the most dominant species (Ludwig and Reynolds 1988).

$$\text{Species evenness} = i / \ln((s-1) / \ln(n))$$

Where, i = Shannon Diversity Index
 s = Number of Species Recorded n = Total Number of Individuals in the Sample

Results and discussion

1. Species richness of the collected spiders in ground and leaves inhabiting different plants:

1.1. Ground spiders:

1.1.1. Species richness of the collected ground spiders inhabiting trees:

Table (1) showed that a total of 33 spiders were collected from ground under severinia tree. They represented 8 families, 14 genera and 14 species. Juvenile comprised 39.39%; while adults average 60.61%. The sex ratio was 1.2♂:1♀. Of the most abundance species was *H. ferox* (9 individuals) followed by *H. adansoni* (8 individuals). Also, a total of 42 spiders were collected from dombeya tree. They represented 6 families, 10 genera and 10 species. Juvenile comprised 23.81%; while adults average 76.19%. The sex ratio was 1.67♂:1♀. Of the most abundance species was *H. ferox* (13 individuals) followed by *P. paykulli* (8 individuals). But a total of 42 spiders were collected from feijoa tree; they represented 9 families, 15 genera and 15 species. Juvenile comprised 23.81%; while adults average 76.19%. The sex ratio was 1.13♂:1♀. Of the most abundance species was *H. ferox* (13 individuals).

1.1.2. Species richness of the collected ground spiders inhabiting evergreen herbs:

A total of 45 spiders were collected from pelargonium. They represented 5 families, 8 genera and 8 species. Juvenile comprised 13.33%; while adults average 86.67%. The sex ratio was 0.95♂:1♀. Of the most abundance species was *H. ferox* (19 individuals) followed by *Pardosa* sp. (16 individuals).

1.1.3. Species richness of the collected ground spiders inhabiting flowering annuals:

A total of 37 spiders collected from crinum. They represented 7 families, 10 genera and 10 species. Juvenile comprised 51.35%; while

adults average 48.65%. The sex ratio was 1.6♂:1♀. Of the most abundance species was *H. adansoni* (12 individuals) followed by *H.ferox* (11 individuals).

1.2. Leave spiders:

1.2.1. Species richness of the collected leaves spiders inhabiting trees:

Table (2) showed that a total of 30 spiders were collected from vegetation of severinia tree. They represented 6 families, 9 genera and 13 species. Juvenile comprised 53.33%; while adults average 46.67%. The sex ratio was 1♂:1♀. The most abundant species was *Theridion* sp. (7 individuals) followed by *Philodromus* sp. (6 individuals).

But number of spiders decreased to 12 individuals from Dombeya tree. They represented 5 families, 8 genera and 9 species. Juvenile comprised 58.33%; while adults average 41.67%. The sex ratio was 1.5♂:1♀. The most abundant species was *Thomisus* sp. (3 individuals).

1.2.2. Species richness of the collected leaves spiders inhabiting evergreen herbs:

A total of 41 spiders were collected from pelargonium (evergreen herbs). They represented 7 families, 14 genera and 16 species. Juvenile comprised 63.41%; while adults average 36.59%. The sex ratio was 1.5♂:1♀. Of the most abundant species was *Philodromus* sp. (10 individuals) followed by *Kuchiur aaulica* (8 individuals).

1.2.3. Species richness of the collected leaves spiders inhabiting flowering annuals:

A total of 11 spiders were collected from crinum (flowering annuals). They represented 4 families, 8 genera and 8 species. Juvenile comprised 81.82%; while adults average 18.18%. The sex ratio was 0♂:2♀. Of the most abundance species

was *Philodromus* sp., *Plexippus* sp. and *H. adansoni* (2 individuals) for each species.

2. Rank abundance of spider families occurred in ground and leaves inhabiting tree, evergreen herbs and flowering annuals:

Table (3) was presented by families and showed their abundance. The greatest number of collected ground spiders presented by family Lycosidae 106 individuals (53.27 %) and Salticidae 50 individuals (25.13 %) while, those collected from vegetation were family Philodromidae 25 individuals (26.60%) and followed by Saiticidae and Thridiidae 24 individuals (25.53 %) for each family. Also, a total of 117 spiders inhabiting trees (Severinia, dombeya and feijoa) which collected 33, 42 and 42 individuals, respectively. This number decreased to (30 and 12 individuals) which collected from (Severinia, and dombeya) leaves. The number of spiders was collected from pelargonium (Evergreen herbs) and crinum (Flowering annuals) which collected 82 spiders from soil and 52 spiders from leaves. These results indicated that the various families occurred in soil and leaves peaked at different levels of canopy openness. The type of vegetation acts as a filter for spider families. Ludwig and Reynolds (1988), indicated that the type of vegetation and management are factors that most effect the spider families. Abo-Zaed et al. (2019), found that the highest numbers of spider occurrence were collected from rose, Rose geranium, chamomile, sweet basil, neem and *Mentha piperita* composed of 52, 39, 35, 28, 20 and 20 individuals, respectively While marigold and carnation received the lowest number of spider of 10 and 8 individuals, respectively.

3. Relative abundance-frequency relationship of spider communities habiting ground and leaves:

3.1. Ground spiders:

From Table (4), it was indicated that, according Weis Fogh frequency classification, members of Family Lycosidae were considered constant (C) species in abundance under feijoa tree and pelargonium herb which recorded 52.38 and 84.44% respectively. While member Lycosidae was considered as accessory (ac) in severinia tree, dombeya tree, and flowering annual crinum with 39.39, 50 and 32.43, respectively. Members of Salticidae considered as accessory (ac) species under severinia, dombeya trees and the annual flowering annual crinum, the recorded 30.3, 33.33 and 48.65 respectively. Moreover, all the remaining families were recorded as "Accidental" species while their members ranged between "Dominant", "Subdominant" and "Recedent". Members of family Lycosidae: *Pardosa* sp. which was "Subdominant" in severinia and feijoa and *Trochosa urbana* which was "Subdominant" in feijoa. Members of family Salticidae: *Plexippus paykulli* which was subdominant in severinia and feijoa but its "Dominant" in dombeya tree. *H. adansoni* family Salticidae was "Dominant" in severinia and dombeya and "Subdominant" in Feijoa. Family Philodromidae, Occobiidae and Filistatidae were disappeared from severinia tree. But family Philodromidae, Occobiidae, Dysderidae and Eutichuridae disappeared from dombeya tree. In feijoa tree only Gnaphosidae family and Filistatidae family was disappeared.

This result indicated that, type of vegetation acts as a filter for spider families and this was also reported by Buchholz (2016) studied spider families in peat areas with different flower composition. He found that the occurrence of larger spiders in correlated with denser vegetation and of smaller spiders with areas where the

predominant vegetation was formed by mosses.

Table (4) showed that the frequency and abundance values of the most abundant spiders in evergreen herbs "Pelargonium" and flowering annuals crinum. According to Weis Fogh system family Lycosidae was considered "Constant" 84.44% in pelargonium and "Accessory" 32.43% in crinum. Also, family Salticidae was considered "Accessory" 48.65% in crinum. The same results obtained by Abo-Zaed *et al.* (2019) who recorded eighteen species of spiders belong to nine families and one order (Araneae) was recorded, from Zoheria garden. The dominant spider families recorded with largest number of species. These are: Philodromidae and Theridiidae on jasmine flower, lavender and night-blooming jasmine at Zoheria garden whereas, the same families were dominant on rose, rose geranium and chamomile at Orman garden.

3.2. Spider leaves:

Table (5) showed that the frequency and abundance values of the most abundant leaves spiders in tree, according "Weis Fogh system" family Theridiidae and Philodromidae were considered accessory (40.00% and 26.67%), respectively in Severinia. Also, Family Salticidae and Thomisidae were considered "Accessory" (50.0% and 25.0%) respectively in dombeya. Members of family Theridiidae: *Theridion* sp. and *Kochiuraaulica* were "Dominant" and family Philodromidae: *Philodromus* sp. was "Dominant" on leaves of severinia. Also, members of family Salticidae: *Plexippus* sp. was "Dominant" and all anther species were "subdominant". Members of family Thomisidae: *Thomis* sp. was "Dominant". Also, the frequency and abundance values of the most abundant spiders in evergreen herbs and flowering annuals. According to Weis Fogh system. Family

Philodromidae and Thrediidae were considered "Accessory" (34.15% and 26.83%), respectively in pelargonium (Evergreen herbs). But family Salticidae was considered "Constant" in Crinum (Flowering annua ls). Members of family Salticidae: *H. adansoni* and *Plexippus* sp. were considered "Dominant" on leaves of Crinum. Abo-Zaed *et al.* (2019) found that the dominant spider families recorded with largest number of species, these are: Philodromidae and Theridiidae on jasmine flower, lavender and night-blooming jasmine at Zoheria garden.

4. Monthly fluctuation of spider population "Catch Size" :

From Table (6), the total monthly count of spider collected in summer during their activity density in May for spiders of trees (33 individuals). While collected from leaves were recorded in June and August (8 individuals). The lowest numbers of individuals were recorded in winter. Table (7), showed that the highest abundance of spiders was found in June and August recorded 15 individuals. These results were recorded in ground spiders under pelargonium herbs and the annual Crinum flower. Spiders were disappeared in November and February and reappeared in few numbers in December and January. Respective numbers of leaves spiders were of highest activity in August (15 individuals), decreased in September to 10 individuals. The lowest numbers of spiders were recorded in November and December 2 and 1 individual ,respectively and disappear in January and February then began to increase in March.

5. Spider diversity:

Table (8) compared the biodiversity of collected spiders in different vegetation between spiders

associated with ground or foliage leaves by using Shannon-Wiener "H", Simpson "S" indices and species evenness of diversity. These results revealed that the highest "H" value recorded on spiders of ground in feijoa 2.32 decreased to 2.21 in severinia. But the lowest "H" value recorded 1.44 in pelargonium (Evergreen herbs). But leaves spiders, revealed that the highest "H" value recorded in pelargonium 2.43, decreased to 2.02 in Crinum. Consequently, these values demonstrated that spider collected from pitfall trap "ground spiders" a greater number of spider than spider associated with foliage and diverse also. According to Simpson "S" index, which reflect the measure of dominance, it was found the highest value recorded in ground spider under pelargonium (Evergreen herbs) 0.31 decreased to 0.14 under feijoa. This result indicated that the, shady and humid conditions at soil incurs to increase number of spiders more than foliage. Also, results revealed that the highest species evenness value recorded on spiders of ground in Pelargonium 2.37 while the lowest value in severinia 1.68. But leaves spiders, revealed that the highest value recorded in severinia 1.96, decreased to 1.74 in Pelargonium. Košulič *et al.* (2016) found that some spiders species of conservation concern dependent on shady and more humid conditions. These results are in accord with findings by Muff *et al.* (2009) that showed importance of habitat variability for spiders even in small spatial scales in forest plantations and alpine timberlines.

Table (2): Species richness of the collected leaves spiders inhabiting tree, evergreen herbs and flowering annuals.

Families and taxa names	Spider name	Tree						Evergreen herbs						Flowering annuals					
		Severina		Total	%	Dombeya		Total	%	Pelargonium		Total	%	Crinum		Total	%		
		♂	♀	J		♂	♀	J		♂	♀	J		♂	♀	J			
Aranidae	<i>Neoscona</i> sp.			1					6.67										
	Unidentified species			1															
Cheiracanthidae	<i>Cheiracanthium</i> sp.																		
Dictynidae	Unidentified species							1											
Gnaphosidae	Unidentified species			1					3.33										
Lycosidae	<i>Pardosa</i> sp.																		
Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus</i> sp.	1	1	4				1											
	<i>Philodromus</i> sp.1			1															
	<i>Philodromus</i> sp.2			1					26.67										
	<i>Pulchellodromus glaucinus</i>																		
	<i>Thanatus</i> sp.									8.33									
	<i>Thyene imperialis</i>			2															
Salticidae	<i>Thyene</i> sp.			1															
	<i>Plexippus</i> sp.							2											
	<i>Plexippus paykulli</i>							1											
	<i>Bianor</i> sp.							1											
	<i>Heliophanus</i> sp.																		
	<i>Hasarius adansonii</i>																		
	<i>Hasarius</i> sp.																		
	<i>Spiderling</i>							1											
	Unidentified species																		
	<i>Theridion</i> sp.			3	2	2													
Theridiidae	<i>Kochiura aulica</i>			1	3														
	<i>Euryopis episinoides</i>								40.00										
	<i>Theridion spinirase</i>			1															
	<i>Theridion melanostictum</i>																		
Thomisidae	<i>Steatoda erigoniformis</i>							1											
	<i>Thomisus</i> sp.							2											
	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i>																		
Uloboridae	<i>Uloborus</i> sp.			1					10.00										
	<i>Uloborus walckenaerius</i>			1	1	2													
Total		7	7	16	30	30	12	12		9	6	26	41	41	41	11	11		

* Fejjoa leaves were unavailable

Table (3): Rank abundance of spider families occurred in ground and leaves inhabiting tree, evergreen herbs and flowering annuals.

Families	Number of collected ground spiders						Total	%	Number of collected leaves spiders						Total	%						
	Trees			Evergreen herbs					Flowering annuals			Trees					Rvergreen herbs			Flowering annuals		
	Severinia	Dombeya	Feijoa	Pelargonium	Pelargonium	Crinum			Severinia	Dombeya	Pelargonium	Severinia	Dombeya	Pelargonium			Severinia	Dombeya	Pelargonium	Severinia	Dombeya	Pelargonium
Araneidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00	2	0	3	0	0	0	0	5	5.32					
Cheiracanthiidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	2	2.13					
Lycosidae	13	21	22	38	12	106	106	53.27	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1.06					
Gnaphosidae	1	1	0	2	3	7	7	3.52	1	0	2	0	0	0	3	3	3.19					
Linyphiidae	3	3	5	1	1	13	13	6.53	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00					
Salticidae	10	14	7	1	18	50	50	25.13	4	6	7	7	24	24	24	25.53						
Theridiidae	3	2	1	3	0	9	9	4.52	12	1	11	0	24	24	24	25.53						
Philodromidae	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0.50	8	1	14	2	25	25	25	26.60						
Oecobiidae	0	0	1	0	1	2	2	1.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00					
Dysderidae	1	0	2	0	0	3	3	1.51	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00					
Eutichuridae	1	0	2	0	0	3	3	1.51	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00					
Filistatidae	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0.50	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00					
Thomisidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		0	3	2	0	5	5	5	5.32						
Uloboridae	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.50	3	0	0	1	4	4	4	4.26						
Pholcidae	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.50	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00					
Dictynidae	1	0	1	0	0	2	2	1.01	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1.06					
Total	33	42	42	45	37	199	199		30	12	41	11	94	94	94							
		117		82					42		52											

Leaves of feijoa were unavailable

Table (4): The dominance-frequency relationship of ground spider communities inhabiting trees, evergreen herbs and flowering annuals.

Families and taxa names	Tree												Evergreen herbs						Flowering annuals							
	Severinia			Dombeya			Feijoa			Pelargonium			Crinum			F. %			F. %							
	No.	sp. %	Dom.	F. %	Freq.	No.	sp. %	Dom.	F. %	Freq.	No.	sp. %	Dom.	F. %	Freq.	No.	sp. %	Dom.	F. %	Freq.	No.	sp. %	Dom.	F. %	Freq.	
Lycosidae	1	3.03	R	39.39	Ac	1	2.38	R	50	Ac	4	2.38	R	52.38	C	3	6.67	sd	84.44	C	1	2.70	R	32.43	ac	
<i>Wadecosa fidelis</i>		9.09	sd			4	9.52	E			16	35.56	E			11	29.73	D								
<i>Paradosa</i> sp.	3	27.27	D			13	30.95	E			4	9.52	sd													
<i>Hogna ferax</i>	9					7	16.67	D																		
<i>Trochosa urbana</i>																										
Gnaphosidae	1	3.03	R	3.03	A	1	2.38	R	2.38	A						2	4.44	R	4.44	A	2	5.41	Sd	8.11	A	
<i>Micaria dives</i>																1	2.70	R								
<i>Zelotes</i> sp.																										
Linyphiidae																										
<i>Primerigone vagans</i>	1	3.03	R			1	2.38	R			1	2.38	R													
<i>Sengletus extricatus</i>	1	3.03	R	9.09	A	1	2.38	R	7.14	A	1	2.38	R	11.90	A				2.22	A					2.70	A
<i>Gnathonarium dentatum</i>	1	3.03	R								3	7.14	sd			1	2.22	R			1	2.70	R			
<i>Mermessus denticulatus</i>																										
Salticidae	2	6.06	sd	30.30	Ac	8	19.05	D	33.33	ac	3	7.14	sd	16.67	A	1	2.22	R	2.22	A	6	16.22	D	48.65	ac	
<i>Plexippus paykulli</i>	8	24.24	D			6	14.29	D			4	9.52	sd			12	32.43	E								
<i>Hasarius adansoni</i>																										
Theridiidae																										
<i>Steatoda erigoniformis</i>	2	6.06	sd	9.09	A	1	2.38	R	4.76	A	1	2.38	R	2.38	A	2	4.44	R	6.67	A						
<i>Kochira aulica</i>	1	3.03	R			1	2.38	R								1	2.22	R								
Philodromidae																										
<i>Philodromus cespitum</i>																										
Oecobiidae																										
<i>Oecobius navius</i>																										
Dysderidae	1	3.03	R	3.03	A						1	2.38	R	2.38	A						1	2.70	R	2.70	A	
<i>Dysdera crocata</i>																										
Eutichuridae	1	3.03	R	3.03	A						2	4.76	R	4.76	A											
<i>Cheiracanthium</i> sp.											2	4.76	R	4.76	A											
Filistatidae																										
<i>Filistata</i> sp.						1	2.38	R	3.03	A																
Uloboridae																										
<i>Uloborus</i> sp.																										
Pholcidae																										
<i>Pholcus</i> sp.																										
Dicynidae	1	3.03	R	3.03	A						1	2.38	R	2.38	A											
Total	33					42					42					45					37					

Dominance, by Weigmann
 >30 % = Eudominant (E) 1 - 5 % Recedent (R)
 10 - 30 % = Dominant (D) > 1 % = Subprecedent (Sr)
 5 - 10 % = Subdominant (sd)

Dominance, by Weis Fog
 >50 % = Constant (C)
 25 - 50 % = Accessory (ac)
 > 25 % = Accidental (A)

Table (5): The dominance-frequency relationship of leaves spider communities inhabiting tree, evergreen herbs and flowering annuals.

Families and taxa names	spider name	Tree						Evergreen herbs						Flowering annuals									
		Severina			Dombeya			Pelargonium			Crotium			Freq.			F.%						
		No.	Sp.%	Dom.	F.%	Freq.	No.	Sp.%	Dom.	F.%	Freq.	No.	Sp.%	Dom.	F.%	Freq.	No.	Sp.%	Dom.	F.%	Freq.		
Araneidae	<i>Neoscona</i> sp.	1	3.33	R	6.67	A																	
	unidentified species	1	3.33	R																			
Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium</i> sp.																						
Dictynidae	unidentified species																						
Gnaphosidae	unidentified species	1	3.33	R	3.33	A																	
Lycosidae	<i>Pardosa</i> sp.																						
Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus</i> sp.	6	20.00	D																			
	<i>Philodromus</i> sp.1	1	3.33	R																			
	<i>Philodromus</i> sp.2	1	3.33	R	26.67	Ac																	
	<i>Pulchellodromus glaucinus</i>																						
	<i>Thianatus</i> sp.																						
Salticidae	<i>Thyene imperialis</i>	3	10.00	Sd																			
	<i>Thyene</i> sp.	1	3.33	R																			
	<i>Plexippus</i> sp.																						
	<i>Plexippus paykulli</i>																						
	<i>Bianor</i> sp.																						
	<i>Heliophanus</i> sp.																						
	<i>Hasarius adansonii</i>																						
	<i>Hasarius</i> sp.																						
	<i>Spiderling</i>																						
	unidentified species																						
Therididae	<i>Theridion</i> sp.	7	23.33	D																			
	<i>Kochiura atilica</i>	4	13.33	D																			
	<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i>																						
	<i>Theridion spinirase</i>	1	3.33	R	40.00	Ac																	
	<i>Theridion melanostictum</i>																						
Thomisidae	<i>Steatoda erigoniformis</i>																						
	<i>Thomisus</i> sp.																						
	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i>																						
Uloboridae	<i>Uloborus</i> sp.	1	3.33	R	10.00	A																	
	<i>Uloborus walckenaerius</i>	2	6.67	Sd																			
Total		30																					

Frequency (abundance), by Weis Fog
 > 50 % = Constant (C)
 25 - 50 % = Accessory (ac)
 > 25 % = Accidental (A)
 * Fejfoa leaves were unavailable

Dominance, by Weigmann
 > 30 % = Endominant (E)
 10 - 30 % = Dominant (D)
 5 - 10 % = Subdominant (sd)
 1 - 5 % = Recedent (R)
 > 1 % = Subrecedent (Sr)

Table (6): Monthly fluctuation of ground spider population "Catch size" in trees.

Month	Ground spiders			Total	Leaves spiders			Total
	Severina	Dombeya	Feijoa		Severina monophyla	Dombeya	Feijoa	
Jan-18	1	2	1	4	0	1	-	1
Feb-18	1	3	0	4	2	0	-	2
Mar-18	1	1	2	4	0	0	-	0
Apr-18	1	0	1	2	0	1	-	1
May-18	5	8	20	33	2	1	-	3
Jun-18	6	3	4	13	6	2	-	8
Jul-18	7	9	5	21	3	3	-	6
Aug-18	4	9	1	14	8	0	-	8
Sep-18	2	3	2	7	3	1	-	4
Oct-18	2	1	4	7	4	2	-	6
Nov-18	2	1	1	4	2	0	-	2
Dec-18	1	2	1	4	0	1	-	1
Total	33	42	42	117	30	12	-	42

Table (7): Monthly fluctuation of leaves spider population "Catch size" in flowering annuals and evergreen herbs

Month	Ground spiders			Total	Leaves spiders			Total
	Pelargonia	Crinum	Crinum		Pelargonia	Crinum	Crinum	
Jan-17	1	1	1	2	0	0	0	0
Feb-17	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Mar-17	5	1	6	6	2	0	0	2
Apr-17	1	0	1	1	3	0	0	3
May-17	2	6	8	8	3	0	0	3
Jun-17	5	10	15	15	2	0	0	2
Jul-17	1	8	9	9	5	0	0	5
Aug-17	9	6	15	15	11	4	4	15
Sep-17	12	1	13	13	9	1	1	10
Oct-17	6	3	9	9	3	6	6	9
Nov-17	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
Dec-17	2	1	3	3	1	0	0	1
Total	45	37	82	82	41	11	-	52

Table (8) Estimation of shannon-wiener (H), simpson indices (S) and species evenness of spider diversity

	Ground spider					Leaves spider			
	Severinia	Dombeya	Feijoa	Pelargonium	Crinum	Severinia	Dombeya	Pelargonium	Crinum
Shannon-Wiener Index (H)	2.21	1.89	2.32	1.44	1.76	2.13	2.09	2.43	2.02
Simpson Index (S)	0.16	0.19	0.14	0.31	0.23	0.14	0.14	0.12	0.14
Species Evenness	1.68	2.15	1.76	2.37	1.93	1.96	1.79	1.74	1.89

Leaves of feijoa were unavailable

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Reduction of desert locust *Schistocerca gregaria* (Orthoptera: Acrididae) fecundity after pyriproxyfen treatment

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Abstract :

Desert locust *Schistocerca gregaria* Forskål (Orthoptera: Acrididae) 5th nymphal instar, were feed on Egyptian clover treated with five pyriproxyfen concentrations (1000, 500, 250, 125 and 62.5 ppm). Such treatments caused mortality ranged between 36.67 and 93.33 % after 7 days, while the mortality in control treatment was 3.33%. Also, the treatments caused different degrees of molting failure. The percentages of adult emergence ranged between 6.67 and 63.33%. The maturation period of treated adult significantly prolonged in compare with untreated ones. Moreover, pyriproxyfen caused significant reduction in the egg production, also different degrees of destruction into oocytes of treated females when examined under light microscope.

Introduction

Desert locusts *Schistocerca gregaria* Forskål (Orthoptera: Acrididae) can increase their population rapidly when suitable conditions are available e.g., rainfall, and vegetation (Showler, 2002). Such increase in population could lead to swarms formation which migrate to another area carried by wind, causing damage to pasture and crops (Magor *et al.*, 2008). The most successful control strategy for desert locust is preventive control method which mean early intervening, by controlling hopper bands before reaching adult stage and forming swarms (Uvarov, 1937). Pyriproxyfen is JH mimics which showed strong activity against many pests include hormonal imbalance and suppress embryogenesis, metamorphosis, and adult formation, while it considered

harmless to non-target organisms (Dorn *et al.*, 1981).

Hence the aim of the present study is to investigate the effect of pyriproxfen on the mortality of 5th nymphal instars under laboratory condition as well as it is influence on the reproduction of resulted adults, moreover it's histopathological effect on the adult female ovary.

Martials and methods

1. Tested *Schistocerca gregaria* nymphs:

Newly molted 5th nymphal instar (1day after molting) of *S. gregaria* were used in the present study, these nymphs were obtained from the stock colony of Locust and Grasshoppers Research Dep., which conserved under crowded conditions as described by Hunter-Jones (1961) for several years.

2. Pyriproxyfen:

The insecticide pyriproxyfen, 2-[1-methyl-2-(4-phenoxyphenoxy)ethoxy]pyridine under the trade name Admiral 10% WE, were used in the present study.

3. Bioassay and treatments:

Five concentrations of pyriproxyfen (1000, 500, 250, 125 and 62.5 ppm) were prepared, about 75 g of fresh clover (Berseem) *Trifolium alexandrinum* were dipped in 100 ml of each concentration for 5 minutes, left for air dry under room temperature, then each treated clover introduced to 30 newly molted 5th instar nymphs (1-2 days after molting) of *S. gregaria*, each treated group were left with treated clover under rearing room conditions to feed for 24 hours then separated into 3 replicates 10 nymphs each. Another 30 nymphs were feed same way on clover dipped in 100 ml of tape water as control treatment and separated into 3 replicates. Mortality and malformation were observed, and clean food were introduced, daily. The days before final molt, before adult maturation, and each egg pod laid by mature adult female were recorded. Survived mature adults were paired and provided with cups filled with clean moistened sand for egg deposition. Sand cups were changed daily and tested for presence of egg pods.

4. Histological studies:

Samples of treated and untreated survived mature adult females, were dissected in saline solution, ovaries were removed and fixed in Bouin's solution for 24 hours, washed several times with 70% alcohol, dehydrated in ascending series of ethyl alcohol, cleared in xylene, then embedded in three changes of pure paraffin wax (Drury and Wallington, 1980). Serial section of 6 micron thick were cut, mounted on glass slides, and stained with haematoxylin and eosin. The slides were photographed using light microscope.

5. Statistical analysis:

Mortality data were subjected to correction according to Schneider-Orelli's formula (Püntener, 1981). For each used concentration the LT₂₅, LT₅₀, and LT₉₀ were calculated using Ldp Line software (<http://www.ehabsoft.com/ldpline>) according to Finney (1971). Data of 5th nymphal instar longevity, adult maturation period and period between each egg pod laying were subjected to analyses of variance.

Results and discussion

1. Bioassay experiment :

In the present study accumulative mortality were recorded daily for 7 days post treatment due to pyriproxyfen mode of action which act by the time of molting. Table (1) demonstrate the LT₂₅, LT₅₀, and LT₉₀ values as well as the slopes of days-mortality relationship for each treatment, also data illustrated in Figure (1) show the actual daily accumulative mortality of *S. gregaria* 5th nymphal instar feed on deferent concentrations of pyriproxyfen after 7days post treatment, it's clear that mortality was dose and time dependent, the LT₅₀ values were 4.46, 4.95, 6.11, 7.36 and 9.83 day after treatment with 1000, 500, 250, 125 and 62.5 ppm of pyriproxyfen, respectively. On LT₅₀ basis there were no significant differences between lethal time of the higher two concentrations, where both of those values were significantly lower than other concentrations, also lethal time of 250 ppm concentration was significantly lower than of 62.5 ppm. The actual mortality percentages were 93.33, 80.00, 63.33, 53.33 and 36.67 % in treated nymphs with concentrations 1000, 500, 250, 125 and 62.5 ppm, respectively after 7 days post treatment. While in control treatment the mortality was 3.33 % in the same period (Figure 1).

Table (1): Lethal time required for 25, 50 and 90 % of treated *Schistocerca gregaria* 5th nymphal instar to died and the slope of days- mortality regression.

Concentrations	LT ₂₅	LT ₅₀ *	LT ₉₀	Slope
1000 ppm	3.00	4.46 a	9.47	3.92
500 ppm	3.42	4.95 a	9.98	4.21
250 ppm	4.07	6.11 b	13.20	3.83
125 ppm	4.75	7.36 bc	16.88	3.55
62.5 ppm	5.97	9.83 c	25.32	3.12

*Values with same letter did not significantly differ.

Figure (1): Daily accumulative mortality percentages of 5th nymphal instar of *Schistocerca gregaria* after 7 days post treatments.

On other hand all died treated nymphs by the 5th day to the end of experiment showed molting disruption, the degree of such molting failure varied according to pyriproxyfen concentration, this molting failure illustrated in Figure (2), where the two higher concentrations showed sever damage which caused total molting failure (Figure 2 D and E), while emerged adults from treated nymphs with concentrations 125 and 250 ppm (Figure 2 B and C, respectively) were live malformed adults, where 250 ppm treatment caused emerged adults with old cuticle remained attached to different positions or body appendages. While emerged adults from treated nymphs with 62.5 ppm (Not shown in Figure 2), showed little curled wings.

Furthermore, percentages of emerged adults from treated and untreated nymphs were negatively corresponded with used concentrations, it could be noticed that control treatment showed 96.67% emerged adults, while 62.5, 125, 250, 500 and 1000 ppm concentrations resulted in 63.33, 46.67, 36.66, 20.00 and 6.67 % of emerged adults, respectively (Figure 3). It was notable that all emerged adults from the two-high concentration (1000 and 500 ppm) died within few days after molting before maturation. While in case of untreated and treated nymphs with 250, 125 and 62.5 ppm the percentages of survived immature adults to maturation stage were 69.66, 27.27, 35.71 and 47.37 %, respectively (Figure 4).

Figure (2): Molting failure of treated *Schistocerca gregaria* 5th nymphal instars with Several concentrations of pyriproxyfen (dash= 1Cm., A and F untreated emerged adult and 5th nymphal instar, respectively, and B, C, D and E emerged adults from 125, 250, 500 and 1000 ppm treatments, respectively).

Figure (3): Percent of emerged adults from treated and untreated 5th nymphal instar of *Schistocerca gregaria*.

Figure (4): Percent of survived immature adults to maturation stage from treated and untreated 5th nymphal instar of *Schistocerca gregaria* .

2. Longevity of adult maturation:

Maturation in *S. gregaria* is distinguished by transforming to bright yellow color in males, while the females hind wing turned into lite yellow color. Table 2 demonstrates the maturation period in days for emerged adults from treated and untreated nymphs with different concentration of pyriproxyfen, the treatments caused significant prolongation when compared with untreated immature adults. There were no significant differences between the maturation period of the subjected males and females in the present study. The mean of maturation period of normal males and females were 13.67 and 13.21 day, respectively. While in case of emerged adults from treated nymphs with 63.5, 125 and 250 that period were 19.20 and 19.50, 21.00 and 23.00 and 24.00 and 22.50, respectively.

3. Female's fecundity:

In the present study the effect of pyriproxyfen on the female's fecundity was determined on base of number of egg pod deposited per female and the period between each egg pod deposition. Number of egg pods per female were significantly reduced in

case of treated females when compared with untreated ones, where the mean number of deposited egg pods per normal female was 3.29 and those for treated females with 62.5, 125 and 250 ppm were 1.80, 1.60 and 1.50 egg pod/female, respectively as shown in Table (3). On other hand the treatment caused significant prolongation in the period between each egg pod deposition when compared with untreated females, also the higher concentration (250 ppm) caused significant prolongation than the other two concentration (125 and 62.5 ppm). It should be noticed that in case of treated females with 250 ppm there were only 2 females survived till maturation one of them deposited only one egg pod the other one deposited two egg pods so it resulted in only one value for calculation the period between each egg pod, same in case of treated female with 125 ppm 3 females survived but two of them deposited 2 egg pods and one female deposited one egg pod. The mean value of the period between each egg pod in case of untreated females was 3.34 day and those for treated females with 63.5, 125 and 250 ppm were 7.25, 7.50, 9.00 day, respectively (Table 3).

Table (2): Duration of maturation period in days of *Schistocerca gregaria* emerged adults from untreated and treated nymphs with different concentrations of pyriproxyfen.

Treatment	Sex	Females		Males	
	N	Mean ± Sd *	n	Mean ± Sd *	
Control	14	13.21 ± 1.85 c	12	13.67 ± 1.61 c	
62.5 ppm	4	19.50 ± 1.29 b	5	19.20 ± 2.28 b	
125 ppm	2	23.00 ± 1.42 a	3	21.00 ± 2.00 ab	
250 ppm	2	22.50 ± 0.71 ab	2	24.00 ± 1.42 a	
L.S.D.	3.57				

Table (3): The effect of pyriproxyfen treatment on the number of egg pods per female and the period between each egg pod in days of *Schistocerca gregaria*.

Treatment	No of Egg pod/ female		Period between each egg pod in days	
	N	Mean ± Sd *	N	Mean ± Sd *
Control	14	3.29 ± 0.08 a	32	3.34 ± 0.07 c
62.5 ppm	5	1.80 ± 0.04 b	4	7.25 ± 0.03 b
125 ppm	3	1.60 ± 0.06 b	2	7.50 ± 0.02 b
250 ppm	2	1.50 ± 0.01 b	1	9.00 ± 0.00 a
L.S.D.	1.53		1.41	

*Values with same letter did not significantly differ.

4. Histopathological effects of pyriproxyfen on the females ovary:

No survived adult mature females from treated *S. gregaria* 5th nymphal instars with 1000 and 500 ppm of pyriproxyfen were used for histopathological studies, since all treated nymphs with those two concentrations were died before maturation. Figure 5 shows different deterioration effects in immature oocyte of treated females, in compare to control (Figure 5 A), the normal oocyte is surrounded by regular follicular epithelium cells. While in case of oocytes from treated females with 62.5 ppm (Figure 5 B) there was slight destruction where there was disengagement between the cytoplasm and the irregular follicular epithelium cells which showed disintegration. The destruction increased in oocytes of treated females with 125 ppm (Figure 5 C), it showed cytoplasm disappear and follicular epithelium cells disintegrated. Much more most of oocytes from treated females with 250 ppm (Figure 5 D) were destroyed where the follicular epithelium cells were deteriorated and crashed allowing the oocytes contents to leak out.

In the present study pyriproxyfen caused reduction in the fecundity of desert locust adults emerged from treated nymphs in several ways such as: molting failure, produce malformed adults which soon die after molting, prolongation of maturation period, decrease number of deposited egg pod, prolongation of the period between deposition of each egg pod and destruction of oocytes in the ovary of treated females. The treatments with high concentrations of pyriproxyfen caused high mortality while the lower doses caused high survival percentages, but survived adults of all treatment were suffering from malformation damage that affect it is movements and flaying and reproduction ability. Pyriproxyfen is JH mimic, it is principal action is that nymphs retained in nymphal stage by the time they molting to adults, which lead to the nymphs were unable to molt successfully to adults (Pener *et al.*, 1997; Vennard *et al.*, 1998 and Bi-Zhen *et al.*, 2012). Maturation of treated adults were prolonged significantly in conjunction with reduction of egg production, such effect may be due to the mimic effect of pyriproxyfen to JH, which cause hormonal disturbance

therefore inhibiting the egg production finally leading to egg reduction, also maturation prolongation (Ishaaya *et al.*, 1994; Schneider *et al.*, 2008 and Sullivan and Goh 2008). On the other hand, malformed adults may be suffering from hunger due to the inability of movements and malformation of mouth parts such suggestion may need further examination. The oocytes of treated females were corrupted, similar finding

was reported by many authors in different insects (E.g. Fathpour *et al.* (2007) in *Blattella germanica*, Tay and Lee (2014) in *Monomorium pharaonis*, Xu *et al.* (2015) in *Spodoptera litura* and Qian *et al.* (2020) in *Bombyx mori*) such corruption may be due to reduction in vitellin synthesis, leading to the decrease of nutrients and energy in the development of ovarian oocytes.

Figure (5): Light micrograph of cross section of treated and untreated *Schistocerca gregaria* femal's ovary showing immature oocytes (A normal adult and B, C and D adults from treated nymphs with 62.5, 125 and 250 ppm pyriproxyfen. FE follicular epithelial cells, N nucleus, Oc oocyte).

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Survey and population dynamics of scale insects (Hemiptera :Coccoidea) infesting apple trees and thier natural enemies in Egypt

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Abstract :

Apple (*Malus domestica* Borkhis) one of the most important deciduous fruit trees in Egypt. Scale insects (Hemiptera : Coccoidea) are the most important pests infested orchard trees including apple . The present work dealt with the survey of scale insects infested apple trees and their natural enemies in different locations in Egypt as well as population dynamics of the dominant species infested apple of these pests. The results indicated that 21 species of scale insects were recorded infested apple trees in Egypt. The dominant species were *Hemiberlesia lataniae* (Signoret), *Lepidosaphes beckii* (Newman) , *Lepidosaphes pallidula* (Williams), *Parlatoria oleae* (Colvée) ((Hemiptera :Coccoidea: Diaspididae) , *Planococcus citri* (Risso), *Planococcus ficus* (Signoret) (Hemiptera :Coccoidea: Pseudococcidae) and *Russellaspis pustulans pustulans* (Cockerell) (Hemiptera :Coccoidea: Asterolecaniidae). Also, in the present work 19 parasitoids and 2 hyperparasitoids and 33 predators were recorded associated with scale insects infesting apple trees. The dominant species were, the parasitoids *Aphytis chrysomphali* (Mercet), *Aphytis maculicornis* (Masi), *Aphytis lepidosaphes* Compere, *Encarsia citrina* (Craw) (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae), *Leptomastidea abnormis* (Girault) , *Metaphycus asterolecanii* (Mercet) and *Zaplatycerus kempticus* (Trjapitzin and Triapitsyn) (Hymenoptera : Encyrtidae) and the predators *Chilocorus bipustulatus* L. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), *Chrysopa vulgaris* L., *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) , *Dicrodiplosis manihoti* Harris (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) , *Exochomus flavipes* Thunb. and *Scymnus syriacus* Mars. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae). Also, during the present work the populations dynamics of scale insects infested apple trees and their natural enemies were provided as well as the effect of whether factors on scale insects.

Introduction :

Apple is one of the most important fruit in Egypt as far as its acreage, production and exportation potentials are concerned. Apple trees are at damage of sustaining by scale insects infestations. Scale insects

(Hemiptera : Coccoidea) are comprising about 7,500 species in 45 families while in Egypt, are 209 valid species names in 12 families: Aclerdidae (Grass scales), Asterolecaniidae (Pit scales), Coccidae (Soft scales), Dactylopiidae (Cochineal

scales), Diaspididae (Armored scale insects), Eriococcidae (Felt scales), Halimococcidae, Lecanodiaspididae (False pit scales), Monophlebidae (true mealybug), Ortheziidae (Ensign scales), Phoenicococcidae (Date scales), Pseudococcidae (Pseudomealybug) (Abd-Rabou and Evans, 2020).

Scale insects are the major pests infesting different horticulture crops including apple in Egypt (Abd-Rabou, 2003, Wawrzynski and Ascerno, 2009 and Moustafa and Abd-Rabou, 2010). The damage of scale insects caused sucking the juices from the plants sap. Scale feeding slowly reduces plant vigor, heavily infested plants grow poorly and suffer dieback of twigs and branches. Some of scales often secrete a sticky honeydew which supports the growth of black sooty molds, interfering with photosynthesis and makes the plants unattractive. Hammad and Moussa (1973) reported 62 host plants attacked by scale insects including, apple trees. *Parlatoria oleae* (Colvee) (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) and *Russellaspis pustulans pustulans* (Cockerell) (Hemiptera:Asterolecanidae) recorded infested apple by El-Minshawy *et al.* (1974).The parasitoids and predators associated with scale insects in Egypt studied by Priesner and Hosny (1940), Hafez (1988), Abd-Rabou (1997, a, b, 1999, 2000, 2001, 2001a), Awadallah *et al.*(1999), Morsi (1999) and Evans and Abd-Rabou (2005).

The aim of the present work is to study, a survey of scale insects infesting apple trees and their natural enemies in Egypt as well as the population dynamics of them and the effect of weather factors.

Materials and methods:

1. Survey of scale insects infesting apple trees in Egypt:

A survey of scale insects infested apple trees and their natural

enemies were carried out all over Egypt from July 2018 to July 2020. Infested plants with scale insects were examined in the field, using a pocket lens. Leaves, stems and twigs were collected and placed separately in paper bags for further examination in the laboratory. Identification of scale insects was made by examining its adult in Canada Balsam. Thereafter, the leaves and twigs were kept in a closed paper bag and transferred to the laboratory for further examination and counting. Each leaf was stored in a well-ventilated emergence glass tube and monitored daily for parasitoid emergence. Predators were also, collected and identified.

2. Population dynamics of scale insects infesting apple trees and their natural enemies :

Population dynamics of scale insects and their natural enemies infested apple trees were carried out on apple during 2018-2019 and 2019-2020 in Alexandria, Behira, Demyaat, Gharbiya , Ismailia , Qalyubya and Sharqiya Governorates. The plant areas selected for these investigations received no chemical control measures for several years. Thirty trees of apple almost similar in age, size, shape and growth condition were randomly chosen for sampling at a month interval for each location. On each sampling, 30 leaves and 15 twigs of apple were chosen at random. Thereafter, the leaves and twigs were kept in a closed paper bag and transferred to the laboratory for further examination and counting. Each leaf was stored in a well-ventilated emergence glass tube and monitored daily for parasitoid emergence. Predators were counted in filed and transferred to the laboratory for further examination. The meteorological data (MxT, MnT and RH) over 2018, 2019 and 2020 was obtained from the Meteorological Central Laboratory, Agricultural

Research Center, and Ministry of Agriculture. Simple correlation and regression values were calculated to obtain information about the relationships between the three tested weather factors and the population of the pest and its natural enemies.

3. Statistical analysis:

All the data obtained during the trials over the tested seasons were subjected to analysis by using SAS (SAS Institute Inc., 1988) program.

Results and discussion

1. Survey of scale insects infesting apple trees in Egypt:

As shown in Table (1) the apple trees were infested by 25 scale insect species: 15 species belonging to Family Diaspididae, four species belonging to family Pseudococcidae, three species belonging to family Monophlebidae, two species of family Coccidae and one species of family Asterolecanidae. Also, in the present work 19 parasitoids and 2 hyperparasitoids and 33 predators were recorded associated with scale insects infesting apple trees. Eleven armored scale insect species attacking 62 host plant species including apple (Hammad and Moussa, 1973). The host plant crop of *P. oleae* and *R. pustulans* was apple (El-Minshawy *et al.*, 1974). Hafez (1988) recorded *Aphytis lingnanensis* (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) as the most common species of *A. aurantii* on apple. *Encarsia citrina* (Craw) (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) was recorded for the first time in Egypt by Priesner and Hosny (1940). *Pteroptrix aegyptica* Evans and Abd-Rabou (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) was recorded for the first time in Egypt by Evans and Abd-Rabou (2005). *Leptomastidea abnormis* (Girault) (Hymenoptera: Encyrtidae) was recorded for the first time in Egypt by Abd-Rabou and its reared from *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* (Green) with maximum parasitism rate was 21%

(Abd-Rabou, 2000). *Coccophagus scutellaris* (Dalman) (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) collected for the first time in Egypt by Priesner and Hosny (1940). The range of host plants of the monophlebid, *Icerya seychellarum* (Westwood) includes 44 host plant species (Assem, 1991). Abd-Rabou (1997) studied the parasitoids attacking some species of scale insects. He mentioned that total parasitism of *A. aurantii* by *A. chrysomphali*, *A. lingnanensis*, *E. citrina* and *Encarsia lounsburyi* (Berlese and Paoli) (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) reached a maximum during September at South Sinai and Qalyubiya.

Tawfik *et al.* (1970) recorded the insect predators associated with the black scale, in Egypt. These predators are *Chilocorns bipustulatus* L. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), *Scymnus syriacus* Muls., *Pharoscyms varius* Kirsch., *Rodalia cardinalis* Muls. and the larvae of *Chrysopa carnea* Steph., *C. bipustulatus* L. seem to be the most important predator of this scale infesting apple orchard. The coleopterous insect predators feeding on soft scale infesting different crops in Mansoura region were *Cydonia vicina* isis Cr., *Coccinella septempunctata* L., *C. undecimpunctata* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), *Scymnus interruptus* Goez, *S. cyriacus*, *Exochomus flavipes* Thunb., *Rodalia cardinalis* Muls. and *Paederus alfieri* Koch. He added two neuropterous predators, *Chrysopa carnea* Steph. (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) and *C. septempunctata* Wesm.; two hemipterous predators, *Orius laevigatus* Fieb. and *O. albidipennis* (Reuter) (Hemiptera: Anthocoridae) and two dipterous predators, *Metasyrphus corollae* Fab. and *Paragus compeaitus* Wied. (Abd Allah, 1988). *C. bipustulatus*, *S. syriacus*, *C. carnea*, *C. septempunctata* and *O. laevigatus*, recorded associated with different species of soft scale

insects in Kafr El-Sheikh (El-Agamy *et al.*, 1994). The predator *R. cardinalis* recorded associated with *Icerya* spp. Later, Abd-Rabou *et al.* (2012)

reviewed the predator species of scale insects in Egypt.

Table (1) : List of scale insects infesting apple trees and their natural enemies in Egypt .

No.	Scale insects		Natural enemies	
	Family	Species	Parasitoids	Predators
1	Asterolecaniidae	<i>Russellaspis pustulans pustulans</i> (Cockerell)	<i>Metaphycus asterolecanii</i> (Mercet)	<i>Chilocornus bipustulatus</i> L.
2	Coccidae	<i>Ceroplastes floridensis</i> Comstock		<i>Scymnus syriacus</i> Muls., <i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i> L and <i>Cydonia vicina nilotica</i> Muls.
3		<i>Kilifia acuminata</i> (Signoret)	<i>Coccophagus scutellaris</i> (Dalman)	<i>Clitostethus arcuatus</i> Rossi <i>Coccinella septempunctata</i> L. <i>Rhyzobius littura</i> Fab.
4	Diaspididae	<i>Aonidiella aurantii</i> (Maskell)	<i>Aphytis linganensis</i> Comper, <i>A. chrysomphali</i> (Mercet), <i>A. coheni</i> DeBach, <i>A. diaspidis</i> (Howad), <i>Encarsia citrina</i> (Craw), and <i>E. aurantii</i> (Howard) and the secondary parasitoids, <i>Marietta javensis</i>	<i>Scymnus syriacus</i> Mars. . <i>Stethorus</i> sp. <i>Chrysoperlla carnae</i> Steph. and <i>Chrysopa vulgaris</i> L.
5		<i>Aspidiotus nerii</i> Bouche	<i>Aphytis chrysomphali</i> (Mercet)	<i>Pharoscymnus various</i> Kirsch. and <i>Orius laevigatus</i> Fieb.
6		<i>Dynaspidiotus britannicus</i> (Newstead)	<i>Aphytis lingnanensis</i> Comepre	<i>Chilocorus bipustulatus</i> L., <i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i> L., <i>Exochomus flavipes</i> Thunb. and <i>Pharoscymnus various</i> Kirsch.
7		<i>Hemiberlesia lataniae</i> (Signoret)	<i>Encarsia citrina</i> (Craw)	<i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i> L., <i>Exochomus flavipes</i> Thunb. and <i>Pharoscymnus various</i> Kirsch.
8		<i>Hemiberlesia rapax</i> (Comstock)	<i>Encarsia citrina</i> (Craw)	<i>Chrysopa carnea</i> Steph., <i>Rhyzobius lophanthae</i> (Blaisdell), <i>Scymnus syriacus</i> Mars. and <i>Stethorus</i> sp.
9		<i>Lepidosaphes beckii</i> (Newman)	<i>Aphytis lepidosaphes</i> Compere , <i>Encarsia citrina</i> (Craw.) and <i>Aphytis lingnanensis</i> Comepre	<i>Chilocorus bipustulatus</i> L. , <i>Chrysoperlla carnae</i> Steph., <i>Chrysopa vulgaris</i> L and <i>Typhlodromus</i> sp.
10		<i>Lepidosaphes gloverii</i> (Packard)	<i>Aphytis mytilaspidis</i> (Le Baron)	<i>Typhlodromus</i> sp. and <i>Rhyzobius lophanthae</i> (Blaisdell)
11		<i>Lepidosaphes pallidula</i> (Williams)	<i>Aphytis chrysomphali</i> (Mercet)	<i>Chilocorus bipustulatus</i> L., <i>Exochomus flavipes</i> Thunb., <i>Scymnus syriacus</i> Mars. and <i>Stethorus</i> sp.
12		<i>Lepidosaphes tapleyi</i> Williams	<i>Aphytis lingnanensis</i> Comepre	<i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i> L., <i>Pharoscymnus various</i> Kirsch., <i>Rhyzobius lophanthae</i> (Blaisdell) and <i>Stethorus</i> sp.
13		<i>Lepidosaphes ulmi</i> (Linnaeus)	<i>Encarsia citrina</i> (Craw)	<i>Chilocorus bipustulatus</i> L., <i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i> L., <i>Exochomus flavipes</i> Thunb. and <i>Scymnus syriacus</i> Mars. <i>Stethorus</i> sp.

Table (1) : Continued

No.	Scale insects		Natural enemies	
	Family	Species	Parasitoids	Predators
14	Diaspididae	<i>Melanaspis inopinata</i> (Leonardi)	<i>Pteroptrix aegyptica</i> Evans and Abd-Rabou	<i>Chilocorus bipustulatus</i> L., <i>Typhlodromus</i> sp., <i>Exochomus flavipes</i> Thunb., <i>Pharoscymnus varius</i> Kirsch., <i>Rhyzobius lophanthae</i> (Blaisdell) and <i>Stethorus</i> sp.
15		<i>Mycetaspis personata</i> (Comstock)	<i>Encarsia citrina</i> (Craw)	<i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i> L., <i>Exochomus flavipes</i> Thunb. and <i>Rhyzobius lophanthae</i> (Blaisdell)
16		<i>Parlatoria oleae</i> (Colvée)	<i>Aphytis chrysomphali</i> , <i>A. diaspidis</i> , <i>A. maculicornis</i> , <i>Coccophagoides</i> sp., <i>E. aurantii</i> , <i>M. leopardina</i> and <i>Aphytis maculicornis</i> (Mercet)	<i>Pharoscymnus varius</i> Kirsch., <i>Chrysopa vulgaris</i> L. and <i>Rhyzobius lophanthae</i> (Blaisdell)
17		<i>Parlatoria pergandii</i> Comstock	<i>Aphytis lingnanensis</i> Comepre	<i>Rhyzobius lophanthae</i> (Blaisdell) <i>Exochomus flavipes</i> Thunb. <i>Pharoscymnus varius</i> Kirsch.
18		<i>Quadraspidiotus perniciosus</i> (Comstock)	<i>Aphytis proclia</i> (Walker)	<i>Stethorus</i> sp. <i>Orius laevigatus</i> Fieb.
19	Monophlebidae	<i>Icerya aegyptiaca</i> (Douglas)	None	<i>Rodalia cardinalis</i> Muls.
20		<i>Icerya purchasi</i> Maskell	None	<i>Rodalia cardinalis</i> Muls.
21		<i>Icerya seychellarum</i> (Westwood)	None	<i>Rodalia cardinalis</i> Muls.
22	Pseudococcidae	<i>Ferrisia virgata</i> (Cockerell)	<i>Gyranusoidea indica</i> Shafee, Alam and Agarwalb and <i>Leptomastix dactylopii</i> Howard	<i>Chrysoperla carnea</i> (Stephens) (Chrysopidae), <i>Orius albidipennis</i> (Reuter), <i>Scymnus syriacus</i> Mars. and <i>Homalotylus vicinus</i> Silvestri
23		<i>Maconellicoccus hirsutus</i> (Green)	<i>Leptomastix flava</i> Mercet	<i>Hyperaspis vinciguerrae</i> Capra, <i>Nephus</i> (Sidis) <i>hieki</i> Fursch, <i>Scymnus interruptus</i> Goeze and <i>Scymnus seriatus</i> Mars.
24		<i>Planococcus citri</i> (Risso)	<i>Leptomastixidea abnormis</i> (Girault)	<i>Scymnus syriacus</i> Mars., Navas and <i>Chrysoperla carnea</i> (Stephens)
25		<i>Planococcus ficus</i> (Signoret)	<i>Neoplatycerus kemticus</i> Trjapitzin and Triapitsyn	<i>Dicrodiplosis manihoti</i> Harris, <i>Chrysoperla carnea</i> (Stephens) and <i>Chrysopa vulgaris aegyptica</i> (Schneider).

2. Population dynamics of scale insects infesting apple trees and their natural enemies :

2.1. *Hemiberlesia latania* and its natural enemies :

The seasonal abundance of *Hemiberlesia latania* (Signort) (Hemiptera : Diaspididae) was studied for two successive years from 2018-2019 and 2019-2020 on apple trees in Gharbiya Governorate. The obtained results in Figures (1 and 2) showed that, the insect population reached maximum

during October 2018 (1111 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) and May 2019 (1320 /30 leaves and 15 twigs) in the first year and in the second year the maximum population was during October 2019 (658 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) and May 2020 (1466 /30 leaves and 15 twigs) respectively. Numbers by the parasitoid , *Encarsia citrina* (Craw) (Hymenoptera : Aphelinidae) reached maximum (32 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during July and (40 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during May of the first year.

While in the second year reached maximum (23/ 30 /15 twigs) during February and during May (41/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs). In case of the predator, numbers by the predators , *Exochomus flavipes* Thunb. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) reached maximum (65 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during October and (87/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during May of the first year. While in the second year reached maximum (45/ 30

/15 twigs) during October and during May (66/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs).

Data in Tables (2 and 3), showed that the simple correlation between the population of parasitoids *Encarsia citrina*, *Exochomus flavipes*, maximum, minimum temperatures and % of relative humidity and the mean number of pests during the first and second years.

Figure (1): Population dynamics of *Hemiberlesia latania* and its natural enemies on apple trees in Gharbiya Governorate during 2018-2019 season.

Figure (2): Population dynamics of *Hemiberlesia latania* and its natural enemies on apple trees in Gharbiya Governorate during 2019-2020 season.

Table (2): Statistical analysis based on correlation coefficient indicating the effects of some weather factors and natural enemies on *Hemiberlesia latania* on apple trees in Gharbiya Governorate during 2018-2019 season.

Variable	Simple correlation "r"	Probability "P"
<i>Encarsia citrina</i>	0.66337	*
<i>Exochomus flavipes</i>	0.79859	**
Max. Temp. °C	0.11737	-
Min. Temp. °C	-0.10983	-
RH%	-0.36288	-

Table (3): Statistical analysis based on correlation coefficient indicating the effects of some weather factors and natural enemies on *Hemiberlesia latania* on apple trees in Gharbiya Governorate during 2019-2020 season.

Variable	Simple correlation "r"	Probability "P"
<i>Encarsia citrina</i>	0.79808	**
<i>Exochomus flavipes</i>	0.58084	*
Max. Temp. °C	0.16657	-
Min. Temp. °C	-0.04541	-
RH%	-0.28207	-

In Egypt, there are three generations per year for this pest (El-Minshawy *et al.*, 1974). Abd-Rabou (1999) recorded 2 parasitoid species associated with latania scale. These are *Aphytis mytilaspidis* (LeBaron) (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) and *Haprolepis aspidioti* Compere and Annecke (Hymenoptera: Encyrtidae). Later the same author (2006) stated that *Aphytis lingnanensis* Compere (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) is one of the most important parasitoids associated with armored scale insects including *H. lataniae*. Moustafa and Abd-Rabou (2011) mentioned that, the latania scale *H. lataniae* is a dangerous pest in different locations in Egypt. They recorded 17 species of natural enemies from samples of *H. lataniae*. Abundance of the latania scale *H. lataniae* natural enemies were evaluated in different locations in Egypt, representing various bioclimatic regions during two successive years 2009-2010. The results indicated that the parasitoid *H. aspidioti* the most abundant species associated with *H. lataniae* infested mango trees in Giza. The maximum rate of parasitism reached 9.1 and 7.3% in October, 2009 and 2010, respectively. The percentage

of parasitism ranged from 0.1 to 9.1% in the first year and from 0.3 to 7.3% in the second year. The predator *C. carnae* was the most abundant species and occurred all over the years under investigation on *H. lataniae* on olive trees in Alexandria and the maximum number was 25 individuals /60 leaves and 15 twigs in July in the first year and 17 individuals/60 leaves and 15 twigs in June in the second year.

2.2. *Lepidosaphes beckii* and its natural enemies :

The seasonal abundance of *Lepidosaphes beckii* (Newman) (Hemiptera : Diaspididae) was studied for two successive years from 2018-2019 and 2019-2020 on apple trees in Alexandria. The obtained results in Figures (3 and 4) showed that, the insect population reached maximum during October 2018 (1203 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) and May 2019 (1550 /30 leaves and 15 twigs) in the first year and in the second year the maximum population was during October 2019 (987 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) and May 2020 (2100 /30 leaves and 15 twigs) respectively. Numbers by the parasitoid , *Aphytis lepidosaphes* Compere (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) reached maximum (28 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs)

during October and (41 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during May of the first year. While in the second year reached maximum (43/ 30 /15 twigs) during November and during May (46/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs). In case of the predator, numbers by the predators , *Chilocorus bipustulatus* L. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) , reached maximum (21 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during July and (9/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during June of the first year. While in the

second year reached maximum (31/ 30 /15 twigs) during August and during May (9/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs).

Data in Tables (4 and 5), showed that the simple correlation between the population of *A. lepidosaphes*, *C. bipustulatus*, maximum, minimum temperatures. % of relative humidity and the mean number of pests during the first and second years.

Figure (3): Population dynamics of *Lepidosaphes beckii* and its natural enemies on apple trees in Gharbiya Governorate during 2018-2019 season.

Figure (4): Population dynamics of *Lepidosaphes beckii* and its natural enemies on apple trees in Gharbiya Governorate during 2019-2020 season.

Table (4): Statistical analysis based on correlation coefficient indicating the effects of some weather factors and natural enemies on *Lepidosaphes beckii* on apple trees in Alexandria Governorate (Nobaria) during 2018-2019 season.

Variable	Simple correlation "r"	Probability "P"
<i>Aphytis lepidosaphes</i>	0.77468	*
<i>Chilocorus bipustulatus</i>	-0.61970	*
Max. Temp. °C	-0.56645	*
Min. Temp. °C	-0.45870	-
RH%	0.02324	-

Table (5): Statistical analysis based on correlation coefficient indicating the effects of some weather factors and natural enemies on *Lepidosaphes beckii* on apple trees in Alexandria Governorate (Nobaria) during 2019-2020 season.

Variable	Simple correlation "r"	Probability "P"
<i>Aphytis lepidosaphes</i>	0.70819	*
<i>Chilocorus bipustulatus</i>	-0.62850	*
Max. Temp. °C	-0.27024	-
Min. Temp. °C	-0.47377	-
RH%	-0.40368	-

During the present work the results indicated that the purple scale, *L. beckii* has two peaks on apple trees in Alexandria. Also, one parasitoid *A. lepidosaphes* and one predator *C. bipustulatus* were recorded. Karam (1979) studied the armored scale insects and their hymenopterous parasitoids on the grapefruit trees. Who found two parasitoids from purple scale, *L. beckii*, namely, *A. lepidosaphes* and *Encarsia* sp. In Kafr El-Sheikh, El-Agamy (1981) recorded *A. lepidosaphes* associated with *L. beckii*. The abundance of the various stages of ectoparasitoid, *Aphytis* sp. on *L. beckii* in an orange orchard of apple. The highest percentage of parasitism was 19.5-30% by immature stages of *Aphytis* during the winter season (November-February), with lower levels present during the rest of the year. The rate of adult emergence of *Aphytis* was in March through August (26.5- 58.6%) and lower during the remainder of the year (Hafez *et al.*,1987). Abd-Rabou (1997c) recorded total parasitism of *L. beckii* by different aphelinid species reached a maximum during August in Behira.

2.3. *Lepidosaphes pallidula* and its natural enemies:

The seasonal abundance of *Lepidosaphes pallidula* (Williams) (Hemiptera : Diaspididae) was studied for two successive years from 2018-2019 and 2019-2020 on apple trees in Behira. The obtained results in Figures (5 and 6) showed that, the insect population reached maximum during November 2018 (988/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs) and May 2019 (966/30 leaves and 15 twigs) in the first year and in the second year the maximum population was during November 2019 (52 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) and May 2020 (78 /30 leaves and 15 twigs) respectively. Numbers by the parasitoid, *Aphytis chrysomphali* (Mercet) (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) reached maximum (16 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during November and (19/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during May of the first year. While in the second year reached maximum (9/ 30 /15 twigs) during October and during June (14/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs). In case of the predator, numbers by the predators, *Scymnus syriacus* Mars. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) reached maximum (9 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during October and (15/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during May of the first year. While in the second year reached maximum (11/ 30

/15 twigs) during October and during April (13/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs).

Data in Tables (6 and7), showed that the simple correlation between the population of parasitoids , A.

chrysomphali, *S. syriacus*, maximum, minimum temperatures, % of relative humidity and the mean number of pest during the first and second years.

Figure (5): Population dynamics of *Lepidosaphes pallidula* and its natural enemies on apple trees in Behira Governorate during 2018-2019 season.

Figure (6): Population dynamics of *Lepidosaphes pallidula* and its natural enemies on apple trees in Behira Governorate during 2019-2020 season.

Table (6): Statistical analysis based on correlation coefficient indicating the effects of some weather factors and natural enemies on *Lepidosaphes pallidula* on apple trees in Behira Governorate during 2018-2019 season.

Variable	Simple correlation "r"	Probability "P"
<i>Aphytis chrysomphali</i>	0.46857	-
<i>Scymnus syriacus</i>	-0.10763	-
Max. Temp. °C	-0.27567	-
Min. Temp. °C	-0.49271	-
RH%	-0.35847	-

Table (7): Statistical analysis based on correlation coefficient indicating the effects of some weather factors and natural enemies on *Lepidosaphes pallidula* on apple trees in Behira Governorate during 2019-2020 season.

Variable	Simple correlation "r"	Probability "P"
<i>Aphytis chrysomphali</i>	0.82268	**
<i>Scymnus syriacus</i>	0.51702	-
Max. Temp. °C	0.07807	-
Min. Temp. °C	-0.08665	-
RH%	0.16397	-

The main host plant crops of *L. pallidula* were mango, guava, citrus and apple trees. It has 3-4 annual generations in Egypt. Abd-Rabou, S. and Evans (2005 and 2019) recorded the parasitoid *Encarsia perniciosi* (Tower) associated with *L. pallidula*.

The aphelinid parasitoids *Aphytis* attack the pest and several Phytoseiidae developed when feeding on the eggs of *L. pallidula*. The mean percentages of parasitism in the field were 13% on *L. pallidula* (Shalaby *et al.*, 2000). The maximum parasitism rates of *Aphytis hispanicus* (Mercet) on *L. pallidula* on mango in Ismailia was 9.4% during Oct., with an average rate of 3.7% (Abd-Rabou, 2006).

2.4. *Parlatoria oleae* and its natural enemies:

The seasonal abundance of *Parlatoria oleae* (Colvée) (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) was studied for two successive years from 2018-2019 and 2019-2020 on apple trees in Demyaat. The obtained results in Figures (7 and 8) showed that, the insect population reached maximum during November 2018 (112/30 leaves and 15 twigs) and May 2019 (121/30 leaves and 15 twigs)

in the first year and in the second year the maximum population was during October 2019 (658/30 leaves and 15 twigs) and May 2020 (1466/30 leaves and 15 twigs) respectively. Numbers by the parasitoid, *Aphytis maculicornis* (Masi) (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) reached maximum (32/30 leaves and 15 twigs) during July and (40/30 leaves and 15 twigs) during May of the first year. While in the second year reached maximum (13/30/15 twigs) during November and during May (17/30 leaves and 15 twigs). In case of the predator, numbers by the predators, *Chrysopa vulgaris* L. (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) reached maximum (65/30 leaves and 15 twigs) during October and (87/30 leaves and 15 twigs) during May of the first year. While in the second year reached maximum (15/30/15 twigs) during December and during May (23/30 leaves and 15 twigs).

Data in Tables (8 and 9), showed that the simple correlation between the population of *Aphytis maculicornis*, *Chrysopa vulgaris*, maximum, minimum temperatures, % of relative humidity and the mean number of pests during the first and second years.

Figure (7): Population dynamics of *Parlatoria oleae* and its natural enemies on apple trees in Demyaat Governorate during 2018-2019 season.

Figure (8): Population dynamics of *Parlatoria oleae* and its natural enemies on apple trees in Demyaat Governorate during 2019-2020 season.

Table (8): Statistical analysis based on correlation coefficient indicating the effects of some weather factors and natural enemies on *Parlatoria oleae* on apple trees in Demyaat Governorate during 2018-2019 season.

Variable	Simple correlation "r"	Probability "P"
<i>Aphytis maculicornis</i>	0.62216	*
<i>Chrysopa vulgaris</i>	0.82310	**
Max. Temp. °C	-0.14095	-
Min. Temp. °C	-0.34663	-
RH%	-0.22930	-

Table (9): Statistical analysis based on correlation coefficient indicating the effects of some weather factors and natural enemies on *Parlatoria oleae* on apple trees in Demyaat Governorate during 2019-2020 season.

Variable	Simple correlation "r"	Probability "P"
<i>Aphytis maculicornis</i>	0.86554	***
<i>Chrysopa vulgaris</i>	0.82383	**
Max. Temp. °C	-0.48012	-
Min. Temp. °C	-0.61807	*
RH%	-0.34139	-

El-Hakim and Helmy (1982) and Kasim (1995) studied the population dynamics of in *P. oleae* n different crops including apple trees. They recorded two peaks in Alexandria on olive trees and two generations of on plum and peach in Beheira, respectively . While Asfoor (1997), reported two generations on plum, pear and apple trees.

2.5. *Planococcus citri* and its natural enemies:

The seasonal abundance of *Planococcus citri* (Risso) (Hemiptera : Pseudococcidae) was studied for two successive years from 2018-2019 and 2019-2020 on apple trees in Qalyubya. The obtained results in Figures (9 and 10) showed that, the insect population reached maximum during November 2018 (1036 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) and May 2019 (1745 /30 leaves and 15 twigs) in the first year and in the second year the maximum population was during November 2019 (810 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) and May 2020 (925 /30 leaves and 15 twigs) respectively. Numbers by the parasitoid , *Leptomastidea abnormis* (Girault) (Hymenoptera :Encyrtidae) reached

maximum (45 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during November and (67 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during May of the first year. While in the second year reached maximum (29/ 30 /15 twigs) November and during May (29/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs). In case of the predator, numbers by the predators , *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuroptera : Chrysopidae) reached maximum (35 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during November and (55/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during May of the first year. While in the second year reached maximum (24/ 30 /15 twigs) during November and during May (22/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs).

Data in Tables (10 and 11), showed that the simple correlation between the population of *Leptomastidea abnormis*, *Chrysoperla carnea*, maximum, minimum temperatures. % of relative humidity and the mean number of pests during the first and second years.

Figure (9): Population dynamics of *Planococcus citri* and its natural enemies on apple trees in Qalyubia Governorate during 2018-2019 season.

Figure (10): Population dynamics of *Planococcus citri* and its natural enemies on apple trees in Qalyubia Governorate during 2019-2020 season.

Ahmed and Abd-Rabou (2010) studied in details the bionomics of the citrus mealy bug, *P. citri*. Their results indicated that the citrus mealy bug infested 65 plant species belonging to 56 genera in 36 families and distributed in 20 Governorates. Twelve species of parasitoids were collected and the dominant one was *L. abnormis*. Also collected nine species of predators attacked *P. citri* and the dominant one is *Chrysopa vulgaris aegyptica* (Schneider) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae). The results also observed the host plants and temperatures greatly influenced on the development of *P. citri*. The lowering of the temperature increased the dimension of the mealy bug and lengthened the developmental period.

2.6. *Planococcus ficus* and its natural enemies :

The seasonal abundance of *Planococcus ficus* (Signoret) (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) was studied for two successive years from 2018-2019 and 2019-2020 on apple trees in Ismailia. The obtained results in Figures (11 and 12) showed that, the insect population reached maximum during December 2018 (127 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) and June 2019 (155 /30 leaves and 15 twigs) in the first year

and in the second year the maximum population was during November 2019 (128 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) and May 2020 (124 /30 leaves and 15 twigs) respectively. Numbers by the parasitoid , *Zaplatycerus kemticus* (Trjapitzin and Triapitsyn) (Hymenoptera :Encyrtidae) reached maximum (12 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during January and (34 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during June of the first year. While in the second year reached maximum (14/ 30 /15 twigs) during December and during June (23/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs). In case of the predator, numbers by the predator, *Dicrodiplosis manihoti* Harris (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) reached maximum (18 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during December and (24/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during May of the first year. While in the second year reached maximum (15/ 30 /15 twigs) during December and during May (19/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs).

Data in Tables (12 and 13), showed that the simple correlation between the population of *Zaplatycerus kemticus*, *Dicrodiplosis manihoti* , maximum, minimum temperatures. % of relative humidity and the mean number of pests during the first and second years.

Figure (11): Population dynamics of *Planococcus ficus* and its natural enemies on trees in Ismailia Governorate during 2018-2019 season.

Figure (12): Population dynamics of *Planococcus ficus* and its natural enemies on trees in Ismailia Governorate during 2019-2020 season.

Table (12): Statistical analysis based on correlation coefficient indicating the effects of some weather factors and natural enemies on *Planococcus ficus* enemies on apple trees in Ismailia Governorate during 2018-2019 season.

Variable	Simple correlation "r"	Probability "P"
<i>Zaplatycerus kenticus</i>	0.76599	**
<i>Dicrodiplosis manihoti</i>	0.79791	**
Max. Temp. °C	-0.22474	-
Min. Temp. °C	-0.15851	-
RH%	-0.21792	-

Table (13): Statistical analysis based on correlation coefficient indicating the effects of some weather factors and natural enemies on *Planococcus ficus* enemies on apple trees in Ismailia Governorate during 2019-2020 season.

Variable	Simple correlation "r"	Probability "P"
<i>Zaplatycerus kenticus</i>	0.87191	***
<i>Dicrodiplosis manihoti</i>	0.69989	*
Max. Temp. °C	-0.13158	-
Min. Temp. °C	-0.10861	-
RH%	-0.16424	-

P. ficus recorded infesting apple trees by Granara *et al.*(1997) . The individuals of mealybugs were found throughout the year beneath the bark and infestation with *P. ficus* began in mid April and appeared in mid June. The most active period covered from mid August to October 1st showing the highest peak. The population of mealybugs on root showed in February 1st. The decrease of mealybug individuals after this date referred to the movement of individuals from roots to trunks (Hassan *et al.*, 2012). Trjapitzin and Trjapitsyn (2002) and Tawfik *et al.* (2005) reported *Neoplatycerus* spp. parasitized *P.ficus*. Later Fallahzadeh *et al.* (2011) studied **natural enemies of *P. ficus* in Iran. They recorded** seven primary, two primary/secondary, three secondary parasitoid species, two coccinellids, primary parasitoids, and four predator species were associated

with *P. ficus*. The eulophids *Aprostocetus trjapitzini* and *Baryscapus sugonjaevi* are new records for Iran.

2.7. *Russellaspis pustulans pustulans* and its natural enemies:

The seasonal abundance of *Russellaspis pustulans pustulans* (Cockerell) (Hemiptera: Asterolecaniidae) was studied for two successive years from 2018-2019 and 2019-2020 on apple trees in Sharqiya. The obtained results in Figures (13 and 14) showed that, the insect population reached maximum during October 2018 (1204 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) and June 2019 (892/30 leaves and 15 twigs) in the first year and in the second year the maximum population was during October 2019 (1128 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) and June 2020 (788 /30 leaves and 15 twigs) respectively. Numbers by the parasitoid , *Metaphycus*

asterolecanii (Mercet) (Hymenoptera :Encyrtidae) reached maximum (47 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during October and (26 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during June of the first year. While in the second year reached maximum (45/ 30 /15 twigs) during October and during June (18/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs). In case of the predator, numbers by the predators *Chilocorns bipustulatus* L. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) reached maximum (46 / 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during October and (38/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs) during June of the first year.

While in the second year reached maximum (40/ 30 /15 twigs) during October and during June (31/ 30 leaves and 15 twigs).

Data in Tables (14 and 15), showed that the simple correlation between the population of *Metaphycus asterolecanii*, *Chilocorns bipustulatus*, maximum, minimum temperatures. % of relative humidity and the mean number of pests during the first and second years.

Figure (13): Population dynamics of *Russelaspis pustulans* and its natural enemies on apple trees in Sharqiya Governorate during 2018-2019 season.

Figure (14): Population dynamics of *Russelaspis pustulans* and its natural enemies on apple trees in Sharqiya Governorate during 2019-2020 season.

Table (14): Statistical analysis based on correlation coefficient indicating the effects of some weather factors and natural enemies on *Russelaspis pustulans* on apple trees in Sharqiya Governorate during 2018-2019 season.

Variable	Simple correlation "r"	Probability "P"
<i>Metaphycus asterolecanii</i>	0.88467	***
<i>Chilocorns bipustulatus</i>	0.90103	***
Max. Temp. °C	0.78930	**
Min. Temp. °C	.49858	-
RH%	0.84762-	***

Table (15): Statistical analysis based on correlation coefficient indicating the effects of some weather factors and natural enemies on *Russelaspis pustulans* on apple trees in Sharqiya Governorate during 2019-2020 season

Variable	Simple correlation "r"	Probability "P"
<i>Metaphycus asterolecanii</i>	0.89368	***
<i>Chilocorns bipustulatus</i>	0.95222	***
Max. Temp. °C	0.80119	**
Min. Temp. °C	0.52811	-
RH%	-0.80129	**

R. pustulans pustulans is a major pest of different orchard trees including apple (Habib, 1943 and El-Minshawy *et al.* , 1972) . The former species had two generations, the first about four months from January till the end of April, while the second generation took about 3 months from the beginning of October till the end of December (Eraki, 1991). Later Darwish (2007) reported four peaks of the total population recorded in the two seasons; November 11th, May 5th, July 14th and August 25th throughout the first season from October 21st 2004 till October 20th 2005. In the consecutive season (2005/2006) the four peaks were recorded in November 17th, April 6th, July 13th and October 19th. Abd-Rabou and Evans (2010) recorded *M. asterolecanii* associated with *R. pustulans pustulans* in Alexandria.

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Usage of some botanical oils to control the land snail *Monacha* sp.
(Gastropoda : Helicidae)

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Abstract:

The land snail *Monacha* sp. (Müller) (Gastropoda : Helicidae) is a serious pest of a wide range of field and vegetable crops. Nowadays using natural molluscicides for snail control is considered to be the most pragmatic approach. The aim of this study was to assess the molluscicidal potential of three essential botanical natural oils, clove oil, *Syzygium aromaticum* (*S. aromaticum*); black cumin oil or black seed oil, *Nigella sativa* L. (*N. sativa*) and mustard oil, *Brassica alba* (*B. alba*) comparing with non-specific molluscicide (neomyl) as a standard chemical pesticide against *Monacha* snail. The tested oils as well as neomyl were applied as sprays to *Monacha* adults under laboratory and field conditions. All tested compounds gave satisfactory control against *Monacha* snail . Neomyl exerted highest molluscicidal potential followed by *S. aromaticum* oil, *N. sativa* oil and *B. alba* oil under laboratory conditions where the mean value of mortality percentage reached 90, 79, 66 and 60 respectively after 21 days of treatment. The tested compounds revealed the same trend of action against the target snail under field conditions i.e., the reduction % of population after 21 days of treatment was 93.28%, 76.76%, 64.16% and 50.75% for neomyl, *S. aromaticum*, *N. sativa* and *B. alba* respectively with high significant difference in between (L.S.D0.05 = 2.89). Bioassay toxicity test showed that *S. aromaticum* oil was the most effective and *B. alba* was the least effective after all time intervals i.e., value of LC₅₀ was 4.17%, 9.29% and 15.29% after 24hrs; were 3.24%, 7.86% and 12.42% after 48 hrs; were 2.90%, 7.31% and 11.73% after 72 hrs and were 2.81%, 7.31% and 11.73% after 96 hrs for *S. aromaticum*, *N. sativa* and *B. alba* respectively. Toxicity index proved that *S. aromaticum* oil was the superior one gave the arbitrary index value 100 unites. and Relative potency established that *B. alba* exerted the least toxic effect (1fold) against *Monacha* snail. In the light of these results, clove oil, black cumin oil and mustard oil as botanical natural oils safe on the environment, can be used to control this pest as an attempt to dispense the usage of chemical pesticides.

Introduction

Land snails are considered one of the most serious pests of many crops and vegetables causing heavy economic damages as a result of feeding the plant's leaves, roots, and fruits (Hussein and Sabry, 2019) and contamination agricultural products with their bodies, feces or slime, leading to deterioration of their qualities and financial loss (Ali, 2017). The glassy clove snail, *Monacha* sp. (Müller) (Gastropoda : Helicidae) is considered the most predominant land snail in all localities at Sharkia Governorate attacking all plants (Mahrous *et al.*, 2002).

Nonspecific molluscicides have been described over a century (Parvate and Thayil (2017) and still one of the most effective methods (Radwan *et al.*, 2008) must be used only in integrated pest management for controlling pests when their numbers cannot be reduced by employing non-chemical methods (Edyta *et al.*, 2018). Now, the use of these chemicals is not being encouraged due to about 25 million of agricultural workers in developing countries are poisoned every year by pesticides (Frag, 2017). They cause disruption of natural biological control systems, undesirable effects on non-target organisms, harmful for most of the living organisms, and development pests' resistance to synthetic insecticides which are applied to reduce their populations (Ismail *et al.*, 2015). So, scientists attention has been directed toward monitoring the molluscicidal activity of different plants (Abdel-Rahman, 2017; Mortada *et al.*, 2012 and Mourad, 2014). The natural plant derivatives known as botanical pesticides constitute an alternative way of reducing chemical insecticide usage and could extend the list of friendly agents applied in pest control (Edyta *et al.*, 2018) particularly essential oils

(Eos). Eos are excellent natural botanical products due to their high bioactive potential constituting a rich source of bioactive compounds that are biodegradable into nontoxic products, easy availability, economic viability (Lahlou, 2004). They potentially suitable for use in integrated management programs, may be applied to food crops shortly before harvest without leaving excessive residues, environmentally safe, with low cost, can be used by individuals and communities in specific situations (Redwane *et al.*, 2002). Also, they have repellent, antifeedant and insecticidal effects (Khater, 2012), can be inhaled, ingested or skin absorbed by insects (Edyta *et al.*, 2018).

For these reasons, much effort has been focused on plant Eos and their constituents as potential sources of pest control agents (Bakkali *et al.*, 2008; Minjas and Sarda, 1986; WHO, 2005 and Koul *et al.*, 2008). Of these oils, clove oil, *Syzygium aromaticum* (*S. aromaticum*); black cumin oil or black seed oil, *Nigella sativa* L (*N. sativa*) and mustard oil, *Brassica alba* (*B. alba*). Clove oil has exhibited biological activity on a wide range of organisms ranging from microorganisms to humans (Kumar *et al.*, 2011). A finding by Ismail and Abd El-Kader (2011) evaluated the potential of the flower-bud powder and commercially available eugenol of clove; *Syzygium aromaticum* against juveniles and adults of *M. cartusiana* using baiting technique. Hollingsworth *et al.* (2012) revealed potent ovicidal activity of clove oil against the eggs of *Cantareus apersus* and *Succinea* sp. Parvate and Thayil (2017) assessed the molluscicidal activity of clove oil against the adult snails of *A. fulica* and evaluate its toxic effect on various tissues of the snail.

Black cumin oil has antihistaminic, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, antimicrobial, antitumor,

antihypertensive and insect repellent effects (Gulçin and Zehra, 2018). Ismail *et al.* (2015) evaluated the relative efficacy of the essential oil black cumin (*Nigella sativa* L.) against *Ceroplastes rusci* L. and *Asterolcanium pustolans* Cock. on fig trees. No data are available about the toxicity of black cumin oil for land snails using spray application.

Mustard oil is a natural preparation, active against insects (Edyta *et al.*, 2018), causing growth inhibition effects via topical application to the dorsum of *Trichoplusia ni* (Akhar *et al.*, 2014). The effect of mustard oil applied in the diet of insects has been evaluated against *Bradysia impatiens* from the order Diptera (Main *et al.*, 2014) and *Bruchidius incarnatus* from the order Coleoptera (Sabbour and E-Abd-El-Aziz 2010). Ismail *et al.* (2015) evaluated the relative efficacy of the essential mustard oil (*Brassica nigra* Koch.) There are no available data on the toxicity of this plant product applied on the land snails. Lot of natural compounds have been explored and found to be effective in snails like *Lymnaea acuminata* (Chauhan *et al.*, 2011), *Subulina octona* (Silva *et al.*, 2012), *Indoplanorbis exustus* (Pandey and Singh, 2009), *Eobania vermiculata*, *Monacha cartusiana* (Aal and Hamed, 2010 and Abdel-Rahman, 2017).

The aim of this study was to estimate the potential usefulness of clove, black cumin and mustard oils in plant protection from *Monacha* snail. The present research provides new results concerning the molluscicidal activity of the tested oils as specific natural plant alternatives applied to the target snail *Monacha* sp. via spray application of the oils.

Materials and methods

1. Tested animal:

Adults of *Monacha* sp. were collected from infested Egyptian clover (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) field at Soofea

village, Awlad-Sakr district, Sharkia Governorate and transferred to the laboratory in porous plastic bag. In the laboratory the snails were kept in ventilated glass jar under laboratory conditions and were fed a diet of fresh clover plant for acclimatization one week before bioassay. Dead snails were removed immediately (Eshra, 2014).

2. Tested materials:

2.1. Nonspecific molluscicide:

Neomyl (Lannate ® 90% SP):

Trade name: Neomyl 90% WP

Common name: methomyl

Chemical group: Carbamates

Chemical name: S-methyl N (methylcarbamoyloxy) thioacetimidate.

The chemical structure: (C₅H₁₀N₂O₂S).

2.2. Specific molluscicides: Botanical essential oils (ESO):

2.2.1. Clove oil:

Scientific name: Clove

Biological name: *Syzygium aromaticum* / *Caryophyllus aromaticus* / *Eugenia caryophyllata*.

Other names: Clove, cloves, caryophyllus.

Family: *Myrtaceae*.

Active compounds: The major compounds are eugenol (88, 58%), which is a member of the phenyl propanoids class of chemicals compounds (Chaieb *et al.*, 2007a).

chemical structure: (C₁₀H₁₂O₂).

Active compounds

IUPAC name: 4- Allyl-2-methoxyphenol

2.2.2. Black seed oil:

Scientific name: Black cumin

Biological name: *Nigella sativa* L.

Other names: In different languages the plant is known by various names, e.g., black cumin, black seed, black

caraway (English), Habbah Al-Sauda, seed of blessing (Arabic), chernushka (Russian), çörek out (Turkish), and Cyah-daneh in Persian.

Family: Ranunculaceae

Active compounds: Thymoquinone, α -thujene and p-cymene are the major ones, especially thymoquinone. The chemical structure of main ingredients of *N. sativa* oil including thymoquinone, dithymoquinone, thymohydroquinone, p-cymene, and thymol (Amin and Hosseinzadeh, 2015).

Chemical structure of the active ingredients of *N. sativa* L. seeds.

2.2.3. Mustard oil:

Scientific name: mustard

Biological name: *Brassica alba* /*Brassica nigra* Koch. /*Brassica juncea* (L.) Coss. /*Brassica carinata*.

Other names: white mustard /black mustard /brown or Indian mustard/ Ethiopian mustard.

Family: Cruciferae

Active compounds: Allyl isothiocyanate in *Brassica juncea* (L.) Coss (Jimmy *et al.*, 2003). Butyl isothiocyanate in *Brassica alba* (Edyta *et al.*, 2018).

Clove oil, black cumin oil and mustard oil as pure oils (100%) were obtained by El-Captain Company for extracting natural oils and were procured from perfumery and Tween 80 from pharmacy. 1% tween 80 solution was used as a vehicle for oils (Klopell

et al., 2007). The required concentrations of oils dissolved in 1% tween 80 solution (v/v) were always prepared fresh before use.

Chemical structure: C₄H₅NS or CH₂=CHCH₂N=C=S

3. Laboratory evaluation:

Laboratory experiments were performed according to the method of Parvate and Thayil (2017). In order to determine the LC₅₀ values of the tested materials, the acclimatized animals were divided into three groups viz., control, vehicle treated group and tested oils treated group in plastic cups. Tested oils' treated animals were sprayed with varying concentrations (2%, 5%, 8%, 14%, 20% and 26%) of each oil that were prepared in 1% tween 80 solution (V/V). Neomyl concentrations (0.125%, 0.25%, 0.5%, and 1%) were prepared in tap water (W/V). The tested oils, the vehicle and neomyl were applied as sprays to the animals. Each concentration was replicated three times with ten healthy adults of each replicate in plastic cup. Cups were covered with muslin clothes and secured with rubber band to prevent snails from escaping (Hilmy and Hegab, 2010). The mortality of animals was observed at a regular interval of 24 hrs. of treatment as per the WHO (1965) by touching it with a stainless-steel needle. Loss of response was considered as death of animal. The dead snails were counted and immediately removed. Mortality percentages were recorded after 1,2,3,4,7,15 and 21 days of treatment. Values of LC₅₀ after 24, 48, 72 and 96 hrs. of treatment were computed using costat statistical software, Costat (2005) Version 6.311. The relative efficiency as Toxicity index (T.I) and Relative potency (R.P.)

(Fold) were determined by using Sun's equation (1950) as follows:

$$\text{Toxicity index} = \frac{\text{LC50 or of LC90 of the highest efficient compound}}{\text{LC50 or of LC90 of the other compound}} \times 100$$

Relative potency (R.P.) values were measured according to the method described by Zidan and Abdel-Maged (1988).

$$\text{Relative potency (Fold)} = \frac{\text{LC50 or of LC90 of the lowest efficient compound}}{\text{LC50 or of LC90 of the other compound}}$$

Analysis of variances was conducted to test significance between treatments at different compounds using F. test and L.S.D_{0.05} values according to Snedecor (1957).

4. Field evaluation:

Field experiment was carried out in Egyptian clover (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) field infested with land snail *Monacha* sp. at Soofea village, Awlad-Sakr district, Sharkiah Governorate. (1% tween 80) solution was prepared by incorporating the calculated volume with water (v/v). The tested oils were applied as solution sprays concentration (30%) that was prepared freshly in (1% tween 80) solution (v/v). Neomyl solution concentration (2%) was prepared by incorporating the calculated weight with water (w/v). Each treatment had three replicates as plots. Each plot 3x3.5m= 10.5m². All spray applications were made once on March, 2020 using knapsack sprayer. Alive snails inside each plot were counted before just treatment and after 1, 3,7,15 and 21 days of spray application. Reduction percentages were statistically calculated according to the formula of Henderson and Tillton (1955) as mentioned by Abdel-Rahman *et al.* (2019). Analysis of variances in field trials were compared by F. test and L.S.D_{0.05} according to Little and Hills (1978). Statistical analyses were

designed using Costat (2005) Version 6.311.

Results and discussion

1. Laboratory results:

Table (1) illustrated that the tested plant oils exerted considerable toxic effect comparing with neomyl against *Monacha* adults. Neomyl was the most toxic compound followed by *S. aromaticum* oil, *N. sativa* oil and *B.alba* oil where the general mean value of mortality percentage was 87.5, 64.8, 50 and 40; was 88.3, 69, 55 and 48; was 89, 73, 60 and 50; was 90, 76, 64 and 54 and was 90, 79, 66 and 60 after 1,3,7,15 and 21 days consecutively. Analysis of variances revealed significant differences between these values at different tested compounds where L.S.D_{0.05} values were 32.56, 28.41, 29.45, 29.84 and 29.89 after 1,3,7,15 and 21 days respectively. Results in Table (2) showed the potency of the tested botanical ESO against *Monacha* adults as LC50, toxicity index and Relative potency after 24, 48, 72 and 96 hrs of treatment under laboratory conditions. Considering the LC50 value, *S. aromaticum* oil revealed the most toxic potency recording the lowest values of LC50 whereas that of *B.alba* oil was the least in this concern, recording the highest LC50 and *N. sativa* oil located in between i.e., values of LC50 were 4.17, 9.29 and 15.29 after 24 hrs.; were 3.24, 7.86 and 12.42 after 48hrs; were 2.90, 7.31 and 11.73 after 72hrs and were 2.81, 7.31 and 11.73 after 96hrs of treatment with *S. aromaticum* oil, *N. sativa* oil and *B.alba* oil, respectively. Toxicity of the three tested oils was found to be time and concentration dependent up to three days of exposure period. LC 50 values (%) decreased from 4.17, 9.29 and 15.29 (24 hrs) to 3.24, 7.86 and 12.42 (48 hrs) to 2.90, 7.31 and 11.73 (72 hrs) and remained nearly the same i.e., 2.81, 7.31, and 11.73 (96hrs.) as that of the third day.

As seen in Table (2), Toxicity index proved that *S. aromaticum* oil was taken as the standard molluscicide and gave the arbitrary index value 100 unites. Toxicity index was 100, 44.88 and 27.27; was 100, 41.22 and 26.08; was 100, 39.67 and 24.72 and was 100, 38.44 and 23.95 for *S. aromaticum*, *N. sativa* oil and *B.alba* oil after 24 hrs, 48hrs, 72 hrs and 96 hrs successively against *Monacha* snails. The corresponding values of the relative potency were (3.67, 1.60 and 1); (3.83, 1.60 and 1); (4.04, 1.60 and 1) and (4.17, 1.60 and 1). Respecting the relative potency, *S. aromaticum* oil was

the standard, recording the highest toxic potency (3.67, 3.83, 4.04 and 4.17) after 24, 48, 72 and 96 hrs. respectively, followed by *N. sativa* oil (1.60, 1.60 and 1.60) and *B.alba* oil was the lowest (1, 1, 1 and 1) after the same time intervals. An excessive mucous secretion and complete withdrawal of the whole body inside the shell was observed due to direct effect of the tested oils's sprays on the epithelial cells of *Monacha* snail's foot.

Table (1): The general means of mortality percentages of *Monacha* snails treated with different concentrations of the tested compounds as sprays under laboratory conditions for 21 days.

Toxicant	Conc. (%)	Mortality % after indicated time (Days)						
		1	2	3	4	7	15	21
Neomyl	1	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	0.5	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	0.25	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	0.125	0	52	53	55	55	60	60
	Mean	87.5a	88a	88.3a	89a	89a	90a	90a
<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> oil	26	90	90	90	90	90	100	100
	20	80	80	80	80	90	90	100
	14	70	70	76	80	80	86	92
	8	60	60	68	70	70	70	70
	5	49	50	50	50	60	60	60
	2	40	50	50	50	50	50	50
	Mean	64.8ab	66.7ab	69ab	70ab	73ab	76ab	79ab
<i>Nigella sativa</i> oil	26	80	80	80	80	90	90	90
	20	70	70	70	80	80	90	90
	14	60	60	70	70	70	70	70
	8	40	40	40	44	46	50	55
	5	30	38	38	40	40	44	46
	2	20	30	34	34	34	40	45
	Mean	50b	53b	55b	58b	60b	64ab	66b
<i>Brassica alba</i> oil	26	70	70	70	70	70	80	90
	20	60	60	67	67	70	70	70
	14	40	50	50	50	55	55	60
	8	30	40	40	40	40	45	50
	5	20	30	30	30	35	44	50
	2	20	30	30	30	30	30	40
	Mean	40b	47b	48b	48b	50b	54b	60b
F.test		0.0198*	0.0168*	0.0221*	0.0242*	0.0365*	0.0618*	0.1254*
L.S.D 0.05		32.56	27.98	28.41	28.63	29.45	29.84	29.89

Table (2): Comparative toxicity of the tested essential oils (%) to *Monacha* snails.

Toxicant	LC ₅₀ % after				*Toxicity index after				**Relative potency after			
	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.
<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> Oil	4.17	3.24	2.90	2.81	100	100	100	100	3.67	3.83	4.04	4.17
<i>Nigella sativa</i> oil	9.29	7.86	7.31	7.31	44.88	41.22	39.67	38.44	1.60	1.60	1.60	1.60
<i>Brassica alba</i> oil	15.29	12.42	11.73	11.73	27.27	26.08	24.72	23.95	1	1	1	1

*= Toxicity index compared with *S. aromaticum* oil.

**= Relative potency compared with Mustard oil.

Data presented in Table (3) indicated the mean numbers of alive *Monacha* snails that were counted in treated plots under field conditions. The applied concentration was 2% neomyl, 30% *S. aromaticum* oil, 30% *N. sativa* oil and 30% *B.alba* oil sprays. A significant negative correlation was observed between the toxic efficiency of the tested compound and the mean number of alive *monacha* adults in treated plots i.e., neomyl had highest toxic efficiency exhibited (48d) followed by *S. aromaticum* oil (166c) *N. sativa* oil (256b) and *B.alba* oil (339a) after 21 days of treatment. A converse relationship between mean number of alive snail and time of treatment where mean values were (90, 76, 69, 62 and 48) for neomyl; were (256, 228, 214, 180 and 166) for *S. aromaticum* oil; were (360, 339, 311, 270 and 256) for *N. sativa* oil and were (450, 436, 415, 367 and 339) for *B.alba* oil after 1, 3, 5, 7, 15 and 21 days respectively

Table (4) revealed the general means of reduction percentages of *Monacha* snails after treatment with one concentration of the tested compounds as sprays under field conditions. *Monacha* snails revealed the same trend of reaction against the tested compounds under laboratory conditions i.e., neomyl exhibited highest reduction percentages over 21 days of treatment followed by *S. aromaticum* oil , *N. sativa* oil and *B.alba* oil where the corresponding values were 87.41, 64.16, 49.60 and 37.00 ; were 89.33, 68.08, 52.54 and 38.96 ; were 90.33, 70.23, 56.41 and 41.9 ; were 91.32, 74.80, 62.20 and 48.62 and were 93.28, 76.76, , 64.16 and 50.75 after 1,3,7,15 and 21 days respectively. F. test showed significant differences between values of the reduction percentages at the four tested compounds.

Table (3): The mean numbers of alive *Monacha* snails after treatment with the tested compounds as sprays under field conditions.

Toxicant	The mean numbers of alive snails in replicates after treatment under field conditions					
	Replicate	1 day	3 days	7 days	15 days	21 days
Neomyl 2%	r 1	85	74	71	59	47
	r2	93	78	68	63	49
	r3	92	76	68	64	48
	Mean	90 d	76 d	69 d	62 d	48 d
<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> oil	r 1	258	230	210	180	163
	r2	250	224	214	183	169
	r3	260	230	218	177	166
	Mean	256c	228c	214c	180c	166c
<i>Nigella sativa</i> oil	r 1	365	336	310	264	252
	r2	355	339	311	270	260
	r3	360	342	313	276	256
	Mean	360b	339b	311b	270b	256b
<i>Brassica alba</i> oil	r 1	443	431	411	362	338
	r2	451	433	413	370	337
	r3	456	444	421	369	342
	Mean	450a	436a	415a	367a	339a
F. test		0.00 ***	0.00 ***	0.00 ***	0.00 ***	0.00 ***
L.S.D 0.05		10.09	8.09	6.61	7.93	5.41

Table (4): The general mean values of population reduction percentages of *Monacha* snails treated with one concentration of the tested compounds as sprays under field conditions.

Toxicant	The general means of population reduction percentages of snails after indicated days				
	1 day	3 days	7 days	15 days	21 days
Neomyl	87.41a	89.33a	90.33a	91.32a	93.28a
<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> Oil	64.16b	68.08b	70.23b	74.8b	76.76b
<i>Nigella sativa</i> oil	49.60c	52.54c	56.41c	62.2c	64.16c
<i>Brassica alba</i> oil	37.00d	38.96d	41.9d	48.62d	50.75d
F. test	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 **	0.000 ***	0.000 **
L.S.D 0.05	1.41	1.13	0.97	1.11	2.89

In the present work, the results cleared that the tested oils *S. aromaticum*, *N. saliva* and *B. alba* as well as neomyl have substantial molluscicidal effective against adults of *Monacha* sp. with concentration and time dependent. Neomyl exerted the

highest toxicity agree with the finding of Hussein *et al.*, 1999; Abdel-Rahman, 2010 and Abdel-Rahman *et al.*, 2019 who revealed that neomyl exerted highly toxic effect against *Monacha* snail but Ali *et al.*, 2012; Salama *et al.*, 2005 and Abdelgaleil, 2005 found that

methomyl was moderately toxic and was the least effective test material against land snails. Hussein *et al.* (1999) attributed its highly toxic effect to the use of commercial methomyl (Lannate 90%) with its additives and/or the higher sensitivity of the tested population.

The present results concerned with clove oil, *S. aromaticum* are in agreement with Parvate&Thayil, 2017 who indicated that clove oil is highly effective against land snail *A. fulica* and can be used to control its population. They found that the LD 50 values (%) by applying topical administration to the snails decreased from 7.965 (24 hrs.) to 5.157 (48 hrs.) to 3.916 at (72 hrs.) and remained the same i.e. 3.916 at (96 hrs.) thus, its toxicity was found to be time and concentration dependent up to three days of exposure exhibiting a significant negative correlation. Hollingsworth *et al.* (2012) revealed that clove oil exhibited ovicidal properties against eggs of several varieties of snails including *A. fulica* and said that clove oil being eco-friendly and also being exempted from pesticide registration requirement and pesticide residue tolerance requirements. Ismail *et al.* (2015) found that the reduction of infestation values under the effect of clove oil, varied greatly with the time elapsed after spraying and according to the nature of each tested compound. Ismail and Abdel Kader (2011) revealed that the reduction percentages for *M. cartusiana* adult snails were 39.6, 57.2 and 62.4 % for (1, 2 and 4 %) concentrations of essential oil *S. aromaticum*, using baiting technique under field conditions after 21 days and elucidated that the eugenol compound is responsible for most of the characteristic aroma of cloves and indicated that the flower bud powder and the clove oil eugenol of *S. aromaticum* are important sources of

botanical molluscicides. The molluscicidal activity of *S. aromaticum* may be attributed to the presence of several constituents, mainly eugenol (Kumar and Singh, 2006), eugenol acetate beta-caryophyllene, 2-heptanone (Chaieb *et al.*, 2007 b). Acetyl- eugenol, alpha-humulene, methyl salicylate, iso-eugenol, methyl-eugenol (Yang *et al.*, 2003), phenylpropanoides, dehydrodieugenol, trans-confireryl aldehyde, biflorin, kaempferol, rhamnocitrin, myricetin, gallic acid, ellagic acid and oleanolic acid (Cai and Wu 1996). Rani *et al.*, 2012 indicated that 60% - 90% of clove oil is constituted by eugenol which is regarded to be the source of its antifungal, anaesthetic and antiseptic properties. Bauer *et al.* (2001) revealed that eugenol is the major compound in the essential oil extracted from *S. aromaticum*, comprising 75 to 85% of the total. Eugenol consists of a member of the phenyl-propanoides class of chemical compounds (Chaieb *et al.* 2007a). Juven *et al.* (1994), indicated that the toxicity of clove oil (Eugenol) was primarily due to phenolic compounds, because these compounds sensitize the phospholipid bilayer of the microbial cytoplasm membrane causing increase permeability, unavailability of vital intracellular constituents and/ or impairment of bacterial enzymes systems (Farag *et al.*, 1989).

The results respect to mustard oil *Brassica alba* agree with Edyta *et al.* (2018) who said that the mustard oil had a strong insecticidal activity against lepidopteran pests and it seems to be a promising candidate for protecting crops from insect infestation. He showed that, the application of 2% of the oil caused 100% mortality of *C. pomonella* and *D. pini*. Ismail *et al.* (2015) cleared that black mustard oil (*Brassica nigra*) treatment caused higher pronounced toxic effect than black cumin oil (*Nigella sativa*) against

Ceroplastes rusci L. and *Asterolecanium pustolans* Cock. infesting fig trees where the number of insects *Ceroplastes rusci* L. dropped from 26.9 to 17.3 and from 28 to 22.1 for *Brassica nigra* and *Nigella sativa* respectively after the first post – treatment count. The same trend was observed against *Asterolecanium pustolans* Cock where the number dropped from 52.3 to 41.3 and from 42.3 to 34.3 for *Brassica nigra* and *Nigella sativa* respectively. They also showed that *Brassica nigra* oil among other essential oils, presented moderate activity; giving an average of 56.4% reduction followed by *Nigella sativa* oil 51.3 % reduction , throughout the whole experimental interval and decided that black mustard oil could be used successfully for controlling *Ceroplastes rusci* L. and *Asterolecanium pustolans* Cock on fig trees. Edyta *et al.* (2018), concluded that, mustard oil (*B. alba*) exhibited high insecticidal activity against pests from the order Lepidoptera and seems to be an effective biopesticide. Amin and Hosseinzadeh (2015) reported that *N. sativa* seeds contain a complex of more than 100 compounds, some of which have not yet been studied or even identified. Unsaturated fatty acids in fixed oil and essential oil components, especially thymoquinone, dithymoquinone, thymohydroquinone, thymol, alkaloids, saponins, and vitamins as well as trace elements. They have shown the antinociceptive and anti-inflammatory potential of *N. sativa* seeds active ingredients, in particular, thymoquinone, the main active constituent. (Isman, 1999) reported that plant essential oils are potential candidates for snail control, due to their selective action, and little or no harmful effects on the non target organisms and the environment.

The attempt was made to test the potential of the plant oils, *S.*

aromaticum, *N. sativa* and *B. alba* against the adult stage of *Monacha* snail. It can be concluded from the result of our study that the potential of *S. aromaticum*, *B. alba* and *N. sativa* oils may be used as a potent molluscicides for controlling *Monacha* snail. However, further studies are necessary to elucidate the mechanism of action in snail body.

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Histopathological alterations in the foot and digestive gland of the land snail, *Monacha* sp. (Gastropoda: Helicidae) treated with some plant oils and neomyl

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to test if the essential plant oils: Clove oil, *Syzygium aromaticum* (*S. aromaticum*); black cummin oil or black seed oil, *Nigella sativa* L (*N. sativa*) and mustard oil, *Brassica alba* (*B. alba*) have a molluscicidal potential that induced histological alterations against the land snail *Monacha* sp. (Muller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) comparing with neomyl as a slandered chemical molluscicide. The tested oils were applied separately as a spray with sublethal concentration (60% of LC50 /24 hrs.) to the snails and their food. The estimated value of LC50 was 0. 125%, 4.17%, 9.29 % and 15.29 % of neomyl, clove oil, black cummin oil and mustard oil respectively, and the values of (60% of LC50) were 0.075, 2.502, 5.574 and 9.174% respectively. The effect was observed on the histological structure of the foot and hepatopancreas after four days of treatment. Snails in both control group and the vehicle (1% tween 80) treated group exhibited nearly the same normal histological structures of the examined tissues, whereas those treated with sublethal concentrations of the tested compounds exhibited substantial damages almost proportional to the potency of the applied compounds. Neomyl was the most effective one followed by clove oil, black cummin oil and mustard oil which is the least effective one. Thus, it can be concluded that these tested oils obtained from plants are toxic to the snail *Monacha* sp. and can introduce economic control of its population without causing environmental pollution.

Introduction

Terrestrial gastropods from the most important threats of sustainable agriculture in many parts of the world (Barker, 2002). Moreover, they play an important role in transmitting and spreading diseases to cultivated plants (Kandil *et al.*, 2020). Land snails are considered one of an economic importance among pest attacks different types of plants (Ismail and Abdel Kader, 2011). *Monacha cartusiana* (Muller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) is a

well-known species in this category for its great damage to many vegetable crops in the Egyptian coastal areas (El-Okda, 1983). Growers and farmers have often had trouble in controlling land gastropods with conventional molluscicides and need to use non-conventional methods (Schuder *et al.*, 2003). Synthetic chemical molluscicides had a toxic effect on non-target organisms, where they contaminate soil and water and may consequently affect local populations of

humans and other animals (Thiengo *et al.*, 2005). In contrast, the molluscicidal plants have many advantages as: low toxicity effect to non-target organisms, biodegradable, not expensive and more safely to the environment (Abdel-Haleem and EI-Kassas, 2013). Essential oils from plants serve as excellent products of botanical origin due to their high bioactive potential, easy availability and economic viability (Lahlou, 2004). Essential clove oil is one such example, which has exhibited biological activity on a wide range of organisms ranging from microorganisms to humans (Kumar *et al.*, 2011). It is constituted by eugenol, which is regarded to be the source of its antifungal, anaesthetic and antiseptic properties (Rani *et al.*, 2012) and also its cytotoxicity (Watcharee *et al.*, 2012). The essential oil of black cumin seed, which has valuable phytomedicinal features contains a variety of active compounds, especially thymoquinone is one which is the most attractive component in phytomedicinal studies. Genotypes, cultural practices and environmental conditions affect the essential oil composition (Burits and Bucar, 2000). The essential mustard oil has very high application value and can be used to suppress the growth of microorganism in seafood, such as *Helicobacter pylori* and *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*. It also shows inhibitory effects on the growth of bacteria that cause food poisoning and fungi (Olivier *et al.*, 1999; Nielsen and Rios, 2000 and Shin and Kang, 2001). The oil exhibits significant inhibitory activities against *Aspergillus niger*, *A. Flavus*, *Trichoderma viride*, *Candida albicans*, *C. utilis*, *C. tropicalis*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Trichosporon mucoides*, *Trichophyton tonsurans* and *Geotrichum capitatum*

(Musk and Johnson, 1993; Jiao *et al.*, 1994; Hashim *et al.*, 1998 and Hou *et al.*, 2000). The main component of mustard oil is allyl isothiocyanate (Kirk *et al.*, 1964 and Kharchenko, 1964).

The present studies aim to examine the histological effects of these essential oils, clove oil, *Syzygium aromaticum* (*S. aromaticum*); black cumin oil or black seed oil, *Nigella sativa* L. (*N. sativa*) and mustard oil, *Brassica alba* (*B. alba*) in the digestive gland and foot of *Monaca* snails before and after treatment with 60% of LC50 / 24 hrs. that applied as a spray under laboratory conditions.

Materials and methods

1. The tested land snail:

Monacha sp. (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Pulmonata: Stylommatophora: Helicidae). Adults of nearly equal shell diameter (16-18 mm) were collected during March (2020) from infested clover field at Soofea village, Awlad-Sakr district, Sharkia Governorate, Egypt. The collected snails were transferred to the laboratory in ventilated plastic container. In the laboratory, the healthy individuals were selected and kept for acclimatization in a glass aquarium containing moist clay soil to a depth of about 10 cm and were provided daily with fresh cabbage leaves for two weeks before any tests (Hemmaid *et al.*, 2017). The aquarium was covered with muslin cloth on the top. The water were added to provide suitable humidity for snail activity and the continuous cleaning of the aquarium achieved (Ustina *et al.*, 2018) by removing left-over food when the new food was introduced and the soil was adjusted at 75 ± 5 % relative humidity (Hemmaid *et al.*, 2017).

2. The tested compounds:

Table (1) included the compounds were tested in the present study.

Table (1): Showed neomyl and the three botanic essential oils.

The compound		Group or Family	Specialization	Name	Formula	Structure
1	Neomyl (Lannate @ 90% SP)	Chemical group: Carbamates	Non-specific molluscicide	Trade name: Neomyl 90% WP Common name: methomyl Chemical name: S-methyl N (methylcarbamoyloxy) thioacetimidate I)C5H10N2O2S(
2	Clove oil	Family: Myrtaceae.	Specific molluscicides: Botanical essential oils (ESO)	Scientific name: Clove Biological name: <i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> / <i>Caryophyllus aromaticus</i> / <i>Eugenia caryophyllata</i> Other names: Clove, clovos, caryophyllus)C10H12O2(
3	Black seed oil	Ranunculaceae	Specific molluscicides: Botanical essential oils (ESO)	Scientific name: Black cumin Biological name: <i>Nigella sativa L</i> Other names: black cumin, black seed, black caraway		
4	Mustard oil	<i>Cruciferae</i>	Specific molluscicides: Botanical essential oils (ESO)	Scientific name: mustard Biological name: <i>Brassica alba</i> / <i>Brassica nigra</i> Koch. / <i>Brassica juncea</i> (L.) Coss. / <i>Brassica carinata</i> Other names: white mustard / black mustard / brown or Indian mustard / Ethiopian mustard		C4H5NS Or CH2=CHCH2N=C=S

3. Experimental design:

Only healthy adult snails from the aquarium were selected for the experiment and distributed at the plastic boxes (Ten snails in each box). The snails were divided into three groups viz., control, vehicle treated group and clove oil, black cumin oil and mustard oil treated group with three replicates for each. The snails in control group were maintained at optimum conditions without any treatment, those in the vehicle treated group sprayed with 1% tween 80 solution, and those in the oils treated group were sprayed with 60% value of (LC 50 / 24 hrs.) of the tested

oils prepared in 1% tween 80 solution (v/v) as shown in Table (2).), but neomyl concentration was prepared in water (W/V). Values of LC 50/24 hrs. were determined using the spraying technique based on the % percentage. The snails were starved for 24 hours then introducing considerable amount of lettuce leaves. The spraying technique for the tested compounds as well as the vehicle was applied on the snails during their foraging their food, to contact their food and foots. During the four days post- spraying, no removing left-over food and no new food was introduced.

Table (2) : Concentrations of the tested compounds.

The compound	LC 50 / 24 hrs. %	60% of (LC 50 / 24 hrs.) %
Neomly	0.125	0.075
Clove oil	4.17	2.502
Black cumin oil	9.29	5.574
Mustard oil	15.29	9.174

4. Histological studies:

Four days post- spraying application , snails from each group (control group, vehicle control treated group and essential oils (clove oil, black cumin oil and mustard oil) treated group, were processed for analysis of histological changes by hematoxylin and eosin staining, The whole mount of soft tissues of *Monacha* sp. were carefully taken out of their shells and dropped immediately into the Bouin's solution as a fixative for 24 hours, dehydrated in ascending grades (70% to 100%) of ethyl alcohol in subsequent steps and cleared in xylene. The fixed tissues were embedded in paraffin wax and sectioned to obtain 4µm sections that mounted on glass slides then stained with hematoxylin and eosin method according to (Cowie, 1984). They were examined on light microscope and photographed by using a microscopic camera.

Results and discussion

1. The foot :

1.1. The normal foot:

The snails in control group exhibited normal histology of foot (Figure 1) with very muscular foot usually forms a typical creeping sole, occupying the whole of the ventral surface and generally not delimited from the body sides (Abdel-Rahman *et al.*, 2012).The foot tissues contain mucocytes, protein cells, columnar muscle fibers and pigment cells. Pigment cells are the most abundant in the foot (Birgül *et al.*, 2004). A single outermost cuticular layer of epithelial cells (Epithelial covering) mostly

ciliated covers the foot for protective . Inner to this lining there is a layer of tall columnar epithelium with unicellular glands which secrete mucous. Embedded in between are transversely inter woven muscle fibers, called as longitudinal muscle fibers. Major part of the foot muscles is represented by thickly arranged oblique muscle fibers (Nagare, 2013).

1.2. The treated foot:

The snails in vehicle treated group (Figure 2) exhibited normal histology as control group barring slight shrinkage and rupture of muscular tissue, migration and accumulation of the pigment cells and slight distortion of epithelial covering . *Monacha* snails exposed to neomyl (Figure 3) exhibited destruction of the epithelial covering and the muscular tissue. In snails treated with clove oil (Figure 4), toxic precipitation nearby the margin, destruction of the epithelial covering, complete destruction and lyses of the muscular tissue. Snails exposed to black cumin oil (Figure 5) observed toxic precipitation) towards the epithelial covering, distortion and destruction of the muscular tissue and the epithelial covering. The foot of *Monacha* sp. treated with mustard oil (Figure 6) revealed shrinkage of the muscular tissues, slight toxic precipitation in-between. An excessive mucous secretion and complete withdrawal of the whole body inside the shell was observed due to direct effect of the tested oils's sprays on the epithelial cells of *Monacha* snail's foot.

Figure (1): Photomicrograph of a section through normal foot of *Monacha* sp. control. H. & E. stain. (200X) showing muscular tissue (mt), pigment cells (c) and epithelial covering (ec).

Figure (2): Photomicrograph of a section through foot of *Monacha* sp. treated with vehicle control H. & E. stain. (200X) showing slight shrinkage and rupture of muscular tissue (mt), migration and accumulation of the pigment cells (c) and slight distortion of epithelial covering (ec).

Figure (3): Photomicrograph of a section through foot of *Monacha* sp. treated with neomyl H. & E. stain. (200X) showing neomyl precipitation (arrows), destruction of the epithelial covering (ec) and the muscular tissue (mt).

Figure (4): Photomicrograph of a section through foot of *Monacha* sp. treated with clove oil H. & E. stain. (200X) showing toxic precipitation nearby the margin (arrows), destruction of the epithelial covering (ec) , complete destruction and lysis of the muscular tissue (mt).

Figure (5): Photomicrograph of a section through foot of *Monacha* sp. treated with black cumin oil H. & E. stain. (200X) showing toxic precipitation (arrows) towards the epithelial covering (ec) , distortion and destruction of the muscular tissue (mt) and the epithelial covering (ec).

Figure (6): Photomicrograph of a section through foot of *Monacha* sp. treated with mustard oil H. & E. stain. (200X) showing shrinkage of the muscular tissues, slight toxic precipitation in-between (arrows) and distortion of the epithelial covering (ec).

2. The hepatopancreas:

2.1. Normal hepatopancreas (Control group):

Hepatopancreas of molluscs involved in extracellular and intracellular digestion of food material; absorption of nutrients; storage of lipids, glycogen and minerals and it plays also a major role in detoxification (Beeby and Richmond, 1988 and Henry *et al.*, 1991). The morphology and histology of the hepatopancreas of the land snail *Monacha* sp. has been described in several studies (Aioub *et al.*, 2000; Abdel-Rahman *et al.*, 2012; Parvate and Thayil, 2017; Hemmaid *et al.*, 2017 and Ustina *et al.*, 2018). The hepatopancreas of *Monacha* snail Figure 7 (a,b) is a bilobed tubuloacinar gland located in the dorsal portion of the animal. The gland is covered by the general covering integument of the visceral mass which consists of a single layer of epithelial cells rest on a delicate basement membrane. The tissue of the hepatopancreas comprises numerous, compressed small blind-ending tubules. Between the tubules, loose connective tissues and hemolymphatic spaces were present. The tubules lined by columnar epithelial cells of unequal heights and containing basal nuclei (Yonge, 1983). These cells rest on a thin basement membrane known as basal lamina. The epithelium lining the digestive tubules consists of four different cellular populations, digestive cells, excretory cells, calcium cells and thin cells (Sherifa *et al.*, 2007). The two main cell types are the digestive and excretory cells (Figure 7b). Digestive cell is by far the most numerous elements in the wall of the digestive gland tubules. They are long columnar with domed distal apices and flat bases by which they rest on very thin basement membrane. They vary greatly in length within the same tubule. The nucleus is basal, usually

oval but may be spheroidal or even irregular. They show important morphological alterations according to the digestive activity of the animal. Excretory cells are present in much smaller number than the digestive cells. They are shorter pyramidal, globular or cone-shaped, but sometimes may be columnar. They are markedly shorter than the digestive cells and therefore appear wedged in between groups of the digestive cells. They are characterized by the presence of a single large vacuole often in the form of a large brown body. The free surface of the cell possesses a well-developed brush border. The nucleus is small and pressed flat against the cell base.

2.2. Treated Hepatopancreas:

The hepatopancreas in Vehicle treated snails exhibited histology close to the normal one in the control group (Figure 7c). The tissue of the hepatopancreas of *Monacha* sp. exhibited marked histological alterations in response to treatment by neomyl, clove oil, black cumin oil and mustard oil as follows: Neomyl (Figure 8) showed cell's necrosis, degeneration of the digestive tubules and neomyl precipitation. In snails treated with clove oil (Figure 9), detachment of the integument (itg), complete distortion of digestive tubules and toxic precipitation full the digestive tubules and in between. Black cumin oil (Figure 10) showed shrinkage and collapse of the digestive tubules and slight toxic precipitation (arrows). The hepatopancreas of *Monacha* sp. treated with mustard oil revealed negligible toxic precipitation, collapse and shrinkage of the digestive tubules and detachment of the covering membrane (itg) (Figure 11).

Figure (7a)

Figure (7 b)

Figure (7c)

Figure (7): Photomicrograph of a section through normal hepatopancreas of *Monacha* sp. control (a,b) ; Vehicle control (c) : H. & E. stain. (200X) showing (a): digestive gland tubule (dgt), lumen of digestive gland tubule (L), (b): digestive cell (dgc), excretory cell (exc), secretion (S), (c): digestive ducts (dd), secretion (S) and the epithelial covering (integument) (itg).

Figure (8): Photomicrograph of a section through hepatopancreas of *Monacha* sp. treated with neomyl H. & E. stain. (200X) showing severe toxic precipitation cell's necrosis, degeneration of the digestive tubules and neomyl precipitation (arrows).

Figure (9): Photomicrograph of a section through hepatopancreas of *Monacha* sp. treated with clove oil H. & E. stain. (200X) showing detachment of the integument (itg), complete distortion of digestive tubules and toxic precipitation full the digestive tubules and in between.

Figure (10): Photomicrograph of a section through hepatopancreas of *Monacha* sp. treated with black cumin oil H. & E. stain. (200X) showing shrinkage and collapse of the digestive tubules and slight toxic precipitation (arrows).

Figure (11): Photomicrograph of a section through hepatopancreas of *Monacha* sp. treated with mustard oil H. & E. stain. (200X) showing negligible toxic precipitation (arrow), collapse and shrinkage of the digestive tubules and detachment of the covering membrane (itg).

Plant essential oils are potential candidates for snail control, due to their selective action, and little or no harmful effects on the non-target organisms and the environment (Isman, 1999). The toxic effect of any compound on an organism can be evaluated by observing the histopathological changes caused by the compound (Parvate and Thayil, 2017). The digestive glands of molluscs are known as target organs for toxicants and the changes in the cytoarchitecture of digestive gland of snails is used as a biomarker of induced toxicity (Triebkorn and Kohler, 1996). Thus any structural damage to the digestive gland affects the animals in multiple ways. The present results are in accordance with the data obtained in the studies of Zhou *et al.* (1993) on the snail *Biomphalaria glabrata* treated with niclosamide and extracts of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*, that showed irregularity and shrinkage in the digestive cells (Hepatocytes) and calcium cells of hepatopancreas along with breakage of some digestive cells and leakage of its secretory material into the lumen. Similar observations such as shrinking of lumen of

digestive tubule, degeneration and necrosis of cells along with atrophy of the connective tissue of digestive gland were noted on exposure of *Lymnaea luteola* to Paraquat (Kanapala and Arasada, 2013). Irreversible necrotic changes were noticed in the digestive gland of *Lymnaea stagnalis* following exposure to thiodan (Unlü *et al.*, 2005).

The present results also agree with the studies on the snail *Archachatina marginata* exposed to sublethal concentrations of Cu salt wherein there was clogging of hepatocytes observed along with peripheral thickening of hepatic tubules (Otitoloju *et al.*, 2009). The data obtained by Parvate and Thayil (2017) on the snail *Achatina fulica* illustrated that the land snail *Achatina fulica* in the vehicle treated group had histology close to normal but the digestive cells of the hepatopancreas were degenerated in snails exposed to both lower as well as higher concentration of clove oil roughly in proportion to the dose administered, along with peripheral thickening of hepatic tubules, and atrophy of connective

tissue in snails exposed to lower sub-acute dose.

Clustering of secretory material exuded from the damaged hepatocytes was also observed which was massive in snails treated with higher sub-acute dose of clove oil. Lahlou (2004) revealed that clove oil possesses strong bioactivity. It has also exhibited ovicidal properties against eggs of several varieties of snails including *A. fulica* (Hollingsworth *et al.*, 2012). Kamel *et al.* (2017) illustrated that the application of 1/2 LC50 of neomyl resulted in cytoplasmic degeneration in digestive cells of the land snail *Eobania vermiculata* and LC50 of neomyl showed that the digestive cells were widely degenerated and harboring pleomorphic mitochondria. Sharaf *et al.* (2015) observed additional histological changes in the digestive gland of treated land snail *H. vestalis* with methiocarb and chlorpyrifos-pesticides included severe tubular disruption, nuclear pyknosis and necrosis of tubules.

Moreover, Mustafa (2018) reinforced the present results in another gland, salivary gland, where he found vacuolated cytoplasm and degenerated nuclei after treated with LC90 of thymol against *L. maximus*. Ustina *et al.*, (2018) revealed that the effect of LC90/48 hrs. on the digestive gland of the Egyptian giant garden slug, *Limax maximus* caused severe histological changes and ultrastructural abnormalities; as: cytoplasmic vacuolation, scattered toxic agents, degeneration of some nuclei and cells, rupture of microvilli, increasing of calcium spherules inside secretory cells and wide-fused vacuoles. Heiba *et al.* (2002) revealed that the pathological alterations in the digestive gland of the land snails *E. vermiculata* and *M. contiana* exposed to lannate are probably due to accumulation of the insecticide in the cells of the digestive

gland. This damage could be correlated with the disturbed enzyme activities in the different species.

Comparable results were obtained in the current investigation wherein the land snail *Monacha* sp. in the vehicle treated group had histology close to the normal. Neomyl caused necrosis, degeneration of the digestive tubules and toxic precipitation. Clove oil exhibited detachment of the integument, complete distortion of digestive tubules and toxic precipitation full the digestive tubules and in between. Black cumin oil showed shrinkage and collapse of the digestive tubules and slight toxic precipitation. The hepatopancreas of *Monacha* sp. treated with mustard oil revealed negligible toxic precipitation, collapse and shrinkage of the digestive tubules and detachment of the covering membrane. The foot of snails treated with vehicle showed histological similarity to the control group barring slight shrinkage and rupture of muscular tissue, migration and precipitation of pigment cells and slight distortion of epithelial covering. Snails exposed to neomyl exhibited destruction of the epithelial covering and the muscular tissue. Clove oil resulted in toxic precipitation nearby the margin, destruction of the epithelial covering, complete destruction and lyses of the muscular tissue of the foot. Black cumin oil observed toxic precipitation towards the epithelial covering, distortion and destruction of the muscular tissue and the epithelial covering.

The foot of *Monacha* sp. treated with mustard oil revealed shrinkage of the muscular tissues and slight toxic precipitation in-between. These observations are in congruence with the results of the earlier and recent study using crude extracts of camellia seed and mangosteen pericarp, which affected cells in the foot by relaxing

muscle fibers and creating gaps between epithelial cells and connective tissue, resulting in the dearangement of the cilia in the snail *Bithynia siamensis* (Aukkanimart *et al.*, 2013). Degenerative changes in the muscle fiber, protein and pigment cells of the foot were noticed in the snail *Lymnaea stagnalis* exposed to thiodan in pesticide-free freshwater (Unlü *et al.*, 2005). The results here also agree with the recent study of Parvate and Thayil (2017) who found that the foot of snail *A. fulica* treated with both lower as well as higher subacute dose of clove oil showed increase in the size of empty spaces within the mesoepithelial cells and muscle fibers, which was more pronounced in higher subacute dose. Further at higher subacute dose the empty spaces within the muscle fibers were also infiltrated with inflamed cells. An excessive mucous secretion and complete withdrawal of the whole body inside the shell was observed in the present study, due to direct effect of the tested oils's sprays on the epithelial cells of *Monacha* snail's foot. This observation agrees with Triebkorn *et al.* (1998) who said that the topical application of the molluscicides on snails primarily target the epithelial cells of skin including the mucus cells.

In fact, one of the first responses of molluscs to stress is increased mucus production and secretion (Triebkorn and Ebert, 1989). Profuse mucus production was observed in snails exposed to both lower (20% of LD 50/24 hrs.) as well as higher dose (60% of LD 50/24 hrs.) of clove oil. This is in accordance to the observations of Desai *et al.* (2015) who had exposed the snail *A. fulica* to various synthetic molluscicides. The mucus forms a protective barrier between the toxin and the surface of epithelial cells and helps in diluting the toxin (Triebkorn and Ebert, 1989).

In conclusion, these results indicated that the tested essential oils, clove oil, black cumin oil and mustard oil are highly effective against *Monacha* snail and the histopathological alterations caused were proportionate to the potential of the tested oil. Thus, these oils may be of great value in the field to control the population of the target herbivorous land snail *Monacha* sp., being eco-friendly as safe and economic molluscicide, which no harm upon ecosystems instead of using chemical pesticides that could pollute the environment.

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Evans and Abd-Rabou (2005): Two new species and additional records of Egyptian Aphelinidae. Zootaxa, 833:1-7.

Simmons, A. and Abd-Rabou, S. (2006): Whitefly populations in vegetables crops with different fertilizers. 52nd Annual meeting of the South Carolina Entomological Society, Mc Cormick, Sc., October 19-20.

Abd-Rabou, S. and Simmons, A. M. (2012): *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) whitefly as a pest in Egypt. Advances In Agricultural Research In Egypt, 10 (1): 1-82.

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